

Network for phytosanitary
research coordination and funding

Deliverable D2.1

Report of the stakeholders' consultations to
develop a strategic research agenda

EUPHRESKO III

Strengthening phytosanitary research programming and collaboration: from European to global phytosanitary research coordination.

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2. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CSA: Coordination and Support Action

ENO: EUPHRESKO III Network Office

EPPO: European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization

ERA: European Research Area

ERA-LEARN: European Research Area Learning and Networking Platform

ERA-NET: European Research Area Network

IPM: Integrated Pest Management

M: month

SR(I)A: Strategic Research (and Innovation) Agenda

WP: Work Package

3. PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Key factors for successful alignment of national research programmes include: the combination of (i) bottom-up alignment actions that involve research stakeholders and (ii) top-down alignment actions that involve decision makers (research funders and policymakers) and building mutual trust and consensus at all levels through regular consultations and dialogue¹.

In line with these recommendations, consultations of stakeholders that operate in plant health at national and regional level such as research funders, policy makers, research organizations, industry, farmers and foresters, were organized in the framework of the EUPHRESKO III project.

The work was led by the EUPHRESKO III regional and discipline champions and the EUPHRESKO III project partners, the Advisory Board members and the network of Satellite Organizations were involved at different degrees, in identifying and selecting relevant stakeholders and collecting their needs and views *via* consultations.

A mapping of stakeholders in the countries (Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Italy, Latvia, the Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Türkiye, Uzbekistan, and the United States of America), regions (Africa, Australia, Latin America, Northern Europe, Southern Europe and Mediterranean, North America, Pacific islands, Central Asia and South-East Asia) and disciplines (biotech industry, diagnostic industry, seed industry and forest and tree health) covered by the project partners was undertaken. The stakeholders were interviewed via e-mail exchange, *ad-hoc* meetings, online surveys, conferences, *etc.*

The regional champions consolidated the information collected at national level into a regional position, which was further prioritized with the help of decision makers in the countries/regions.

The consultations have allowed to identify plant health needs that have been used to identify the research priorities for the annual calls for transnational collaboration and for the strategic research agenda.

¹ ERA-LEARN2020 (2015). Deliverable 4.1-Report on the definition and typology of alignment. https://www.era-learn.eu/support-for-partnerships/additional-activities/copy_of_alignment/financial-alignment-case-studies (accessed on 2023-03-06).

4. INTRODUCTION

4.1 European Research Area Networks

The ERA-NET scheme was launched in 2002 under the 6th Framework Programme (FP6) to support the coordination and collaboration of national research programmes. It aimed at facilitating the exchange of good practices, the strategic planning and the design of joint research programmes as well as the implementation of joint activities, in particular joint calls².

4.2 Joint Programming activities within ERA-NETs

Core to the activities of the ERA-NET consortia are Strategic Research (and Innovation) Agenda (SRIAs), which serve as instruments to align research funding, policy objectives and societal challenges. Within the European Research Area (ERA) context, SRIA have increasingly evolved from technical documents outlining thematic priorities to participatory and political tools that shape governance dynamics and institutional behaviour (Green ERA-Hub, 2025³). This evolution has been reflected in the methodologies used for the development of SRIAs by the various coordination and support actions (CSAs) over the years.

The SRIAs are also at the foundation of the process of identification of research topics for the calls for funding organized by the ERA-NET consortia. The commissioning of research projects has also evolved over the years, and project consortia have moved from being composed exclusively of research organizations to multi-actor groups.

4.3 Prioritization process within EUPHRESKO ERA-NET (2006-2013)

In the plant health field, a first Strategic Phytosanitary Research Agenda was developed in the framework of the EUPHRESKO ERA-NET in 2010. The development process consisted of: i) the mapping and analysis of national phytosanitary research programmes, ii) consortium meetings to review the report of the mapping and analysis and discuss and agree on the research agenda, iii) national workshops were also organized to engage with the plant health communities within the countries covered by the consortium, iv) endorsement of the agenda by the Euphresco Governing Board and publication. More information is available in deliverable D5.1 Common Strategic Phytosanitary Research Agenda⁴.

The overall process for tackling emergencies topics in the framework of the EUPHRESKO project consortium consisted of: i) expressions of an emerging problem are submitted by research funders, National Plant Protection Organizations (NPPOs), scientists and private companies, ii) funders evaluate and prioritize the topics, iii) information and opinions of the NPPOs is collected to further prioritize the topics, iv) research topics are developed on the basis of information collected, v) consortia of experts are established and VI) research projects are initiated.

² <https://www.era-learn.eu/documents/ec-publications/the-era-net-scheme-from-fp6-to-horizon-2020.pdf>

³ Report on the 2nd Green ERA-Hub Masterclass 'Designing Strategic Research Agendas for Impact'.

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/1127678>

4.4 Prioritization process within Euphresco self-sustained network (2014-2023)

The SRA of the Euphresco self-sustained network was developed taking into account national research agendas of Euphresco members and suggestions gathered from plant health experts who participated in various EPPO Panels meetings. This approach allowed field and research experience to be combined with national guidance. Stakeholders of the Euphresco Network were also consulted and their views were taken into account. More information is available in the 2017-2022 Strategic Research Agenda⁵.

The identification of the research topics was driven by network members, responsible for proposing national priorities that would be prioritized based on a number of criteria, including the interest that the topic would raise within the Euphresco network and outside.

4.5 Prioritization process within EUPHRESCO III (2024-2026)

A new methodology was developed and tested in the framework of the EUPHRESCO III project, based on recommendations from ERA-LEARN⁶. According to these recommendations, 'key factors for successful alignment of national research programmes include: the combination of (i) bottom-up alignment actions that involve research stakeholders and (ii) top-down alignment actions that involve research funding organizations and building mutual trust and consensus at all levels through regular consultations and dialogue'. Consultations of stakeholders that operate in plant health were organized in the framework of the EUPHRESCO III project. The consultations are considered as an essential part of the project and they are aimed: i) to inform plant health decision makers and funders about the possibilities and benefits for transnational collaboration, ii) to identify common needs and priorities to feed the transnational calls for collaboration and to shape the Strategic Research Agenda, iii) to explore the needs and possibilities for future collaboration, within a region or discipline and/or worldwide, iv) to build trust in future collaborations, v) to inquire plant health decision makers and funders to engage in the future network.

⁵ <https://drop.euphresco.net/data/d5de4f71-5941-45b1-80e2-2b85fe47d139>

⁶ [https://www.era-learn.eu/documents/d4-](https://www.era-learn.eu/documents/d4-1-reportonthedefinitionandtypologyofalignment_inra_final_nov2015.pdf)

[1-reportonthedefinitionandtypologyofalignment_inra_final_nov2015.pdf](https://www.era-learn.eu/documents/d4-1-reportonthedefinitionandtypologyofalignment_inra_final_nov2015.pdf)

5. EUPHRESKO III OVERALL PRIORITIZATION MECHANISM

A mechanism for the identification of needs and prioritization of plant health research topics was developed and tested in the first period (M1-M18) of the EUPHRESKO III project. This mechanism took into account: i) the recommendations from ERA-LEARN (see above) for a combination of bottom-up and top-down alignment⁷, ii) previous work performed in the framework of the Euphresco self-sustained network for the identification of research priorities for the Mediterranean region^{8,9}, iii) the need to develop a mechanism that would allow to identify national, regional and global research priorities, iv) the need to develop a mechanism that would allow to delegate responsibilities to countries and regions, while allowing communication and consolidation at global level, v) the need for a flexible mechanism to cope with the responsibilities and specificities in place in the different countries/regions and disciplines. The various steps are illustrated in the image below (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Overall prioritization mechanism developed and tested in EUPHRESKO III.

A video that describes the process used for the identification of common plant health research priorities (for Northern Europe) is available from the EUPHRESKO III [YouTube channel](#).

A consultation package was developed to support the project partners in their activities. The package is available upon request to anyone interested in applying the methodology. In the sections 5.1 to 5.6 the various steps of the prioritization mechanism are described. The reports of the regional and discipline consultations are provided in the sections 6 to 18.

⁷ [https://www.era-learn.eu/documents/d4-](https://www.era-learn.eu/documents/d4-1_reportonthedefinitionandtypologyofalignment_inra_final_nov2015.pdf)

[1_reportonthedefinitionandtypologyofalignment_inra_final_nov2015.pdf](https://www.era-learn.eu/documents/d4-1_reportonthedefinitionandtypologyofalignment_inra_final_nov2015.pdf)

⁸ <https://drop.euphresco.net/data/4e15edb6-a523-4d4c-8311-be7c0fa70020>

⁹ <https://drop.euphresco.net/data/0d651050-3e0b-467b-bf15-d1061110677f>

5.1 Inform: identification of stakeholders

Stakeholders were identified by the EUPHRESKO III partners in their respective countries, regions or discipline of responsibility. The regions considered in the framework of the EUPHRESKO III projects are: Africa, Australia, Latin America, Northern Europe, Southern Europe and Mediterranean, North America, Pacific islands, Central Asia and South-East Asia. The disciplines considered in the framework of the EUPHRESKO III projects are: biotech industry, diagnostic industry, seed industry and forest and tree health.

Stakeholders were classified in categories, as follows:

Role	Category	What for?
Initiator	Policy makers	They provide the policy needs around which research activities are developed
	Research funders Industry	They define the national programmes and provide the resources for the research activities to be undertaken
Research implementer	Research organisations Industry Farmers and foresters Others	They provide the expertise that allow research activities to be implemented, from the laboratory to the field
End-users of research	Farmers and foresters Industry Policy makers Research funders Others	They use the outputs of the research activities

The number of stakeholders identified by the champions are presented below (Figure 2).

Figure 2.

Some issues were identified during the process: i) the coverage of the different stakeholder categories may not be complete. This may be linked to the structure of the plant health system within the country (structural) or to incomplete mapping (operational), ii) the level of coverage (number of stakeholders) within countries and regions differs. This may be linked to the structure of the plant health system within the country (structural), to incomplete mapping (operational), or to existence of mechanisms for the identification of stakeholder needs and

research priorities that made the use of the methodology developed within EUPHRESKO III superfluous. Differences in the ‘maturity’ of countries and regions for what concerns research coordination activities also explain the observed differences, iii) the same stakeholders may have been identified by partners or champions. This is particularly true for the regional champions that focused on geographic coverage (all disciplines confounded) and the discipline champions that focused on activity domains (all countries confounded).

5.2 Inform: national surveys

Two surveys have been conducted: i) a survey for the identification of the stakeholder needs and research priorities and ii) a survey to collect information on the processes used by the organizations that fund research.

The survey on the needs and priorities allowed to collect information on: i) a maximum of five practical priorities that the stakeholder would like to work on in the next 5-10 years, ii) a maximum of five priorities to be addressed at country / region / global level in the next 5-10 years to face plant health issues or related practical problems. Indicate the scale of each priority (country, region or worldwide), iii) agricultural crops that are important to study from the stakeholder point of view, iv) needs in terms of capacity building, v) pests that are considered a regional priority, vi) pests that are considered a global priority, vii) research areas to be addressed / developed to support future work on plant health issues or related practical problems¹⁰, viii) one concrete research need to be addressed in the next three years. Feedback was received from stakeholders as follows (Figure 3).

Figure 3.

¹⁰ Examples of research areas related to plant health are: Emergency preparedness, Horizon scanning to identify the next big plant health issue, Risk assessment, Pest management (sustainable), Diagnostics, Surveillance & inspection, Epidemiology, Minimising spread of diseases through trade of plant material and travel, Innovation, Artificial intelligence, Climate change impact, Pesticide reduction and alternatives, Data and information sharing, Research infrastructures and collections, Phytosanitary research collaboration (national, regional, continental) and cooperation (e.g. skill and knowledge transfer)

The survey on the processes of research funders allowed to i) collect information on the processes used by the organizations that fund research for the identification of research priorities/topics, the prioritization of research activities and for the allocation of funds, ii) collect suggestions that will help the shaping of processes to increase synergies between the research funding processes of partners of the future network and improve the abovementioned processes for EUPHRESKO III (and the future global network) to identify, prioritize and implement research activities that are more impactful for policymaking and innovation.

The surveys were conducted using different modalities to adapt to the local specificities. The use of languages other than English was considered important for certain regions, like Africa and Latin America. Surveys were distributed by e-mail, as online forms, or conducted during face-to-face events such as workshops and conferences.

Some issues were identified during the process: i) slow response was observed, ii) difficulty to engage with stakeholders, but the organization of bilateral meetings helped to increase the understanding by the stakeholder and its commitment, iii) a low response rate, associated to 'stakeholder fatigue', but the rate of response for this survey is average, i.e. 15% of the stakeholders contacted provided feedback, iv) time issues, no incentives, v) privacy concerns.

5.3 Analyse and discuss: survey's input analysis

The information collected through the survey on plant health needs and research priorities was analysed by each champion using methodologies of their choice. Analysis was needed to: i) review the quality of the inputs received, ii) harmonise the information collected, iii) identify commonalities and differences within the needs, priorities and research areas identified by the different groups of stakeholders, iii) identify what are, within the same group of stakeholders, the commonalities and differences in needs, priorities and research areas, iv) have an understanding of what are the crops and pests that are considered a priority or not. This analysis allows to identify patterns and preliminary priorities at regional and discipline level which was used for the top-down consultations. The methodologies used for the survey's analysis are described in detail in the consultation reports provided in the sections 6 to 18.

5.4 Analyse and discuss: regional and discipline consultations

During the regional/discipline consultations, top-down (by the decision makers i.e. policy makers and funders) and bottom-up (by stakeholders, e.g. research implementers, end-users) information on needs and priorities is confronted, and a 'common denominator' of needs in the region or within the discipline is found.

The people involved in the consultations are the high-level decision makers in countries and regions, as they have the responsibility to decide on the funds to invest in research or to shape the research policies and research operations. If bottom-up surveys aimed at collecting the largest number of feedback possible, the consultations aimed at involving a reduced number of participants, taking care of securing that all countries in a region are represented. Consultations were organized in different formats (face-to-face, online, hybrid) and whenever possible alongside existing events, in order to facilitate participation and increase visibility and institutionalization of the mechanism.

5.5 Analyze and formalize: surveys input enriched, champions' review and research priorities agreed

5.5.1 2025 call

The champions used consultations with the decision makers in their region to identify a number of research priorities in their region or disciplines. The number varied. Four topics were proposed by Australia, four by Latin America, seven by Northern Europe, eight by Southern Europe and Mediterranean (based on consultations organized in previous years), nine by North America, six by the Pacific islands, four by Central Asia, four by South-East Asia, three by the diagnostic industry, and five by the tree and forest health. Africa and the seed industry did not provide priorities for the 2025 as their consultations were not organized yet at the time of the champions' review. The biotech industry did not identify plant health priorities. The full list of priorities by region/discipline is available upon request.

The 53 topics identified by the champions were reviewed in order to identify commonalities on topics and pests or complementarities. The matching has to be considered as a first approach to coagulate collaboration at transregional level. Fourteen topics were discussed by the champions, as follows:

Topics	Regions and Disciplines
On site diagnostics	Australia, Northern Europe, Diag industry
Build capacity and expertise	Australia, Latin America
Potato diseases and vectors	Northern Europe, North America
Sustainable management, IPM	Australia, Latin America, Mediterranean, North America, Pacific, Northern Europe, South-East Asia, Forest, Central Asia
Traps testing and validation	Northern Europe, North America, Forest
Modelling	North America, Mediterranean, Latin America
Community engagement, raising awareness	Pacific, Northern Europe, Forest
Epidemiology	Mediterranean
Climate change	Pacific, Australia, Latin America, Forest
Fruit flies	Pacific, Central Asia, South-East Asia, North America
<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	Mediterranean, South-East Asia, Pacific
whiteflies	Central Asia, Latin America
Risk assessment and measures for wood material	Northern Europe, North America
Sharing Knowledge	Northern Europe, Forest

The need to use criteria to prioritise the topics and avoid dilution of resources was discussed by the champions, who eventually agreed not to use them. The champions discussed the need to submit a generic research topic or a detailed research topic for the 2025 call. There was a general agreement that a detailed research topic should be prepared, as it will facilitate the commitment of research partners and of funders.

5.5.2 2026 call

The EUPHRESKO III champions will meet in early September 2025 to identify the modalities for the identification of the research topics for the 2026 call. Preliminary agreement on the 2026 call indicates that: i) topics that were discarded in 2025 call because no topic coordinator was identified can be reconsidered for the 2026 call, ii) champions will develop topics from the priorities left from the 2024 prioritization process, iii) champions may further analyse the consultation reports or use different approaches to identify new priorities for 2026.

5.5.3 Strategic Research Agenda

The development of the SRA will take inputs from various sources, including the funding survey, the survey on the research priorities and following consultation process, and the existing agendas of relevant organizations. Discussions are ongoing on the actual coverage of the SRA, if it should cover only statutory plant health, or if it should expand to topics such as food safety, which are related to plant health.

5.6 Agree and implement: research agenda and projects implemented

5.6.1 2025 call

The 2024 champion review led to the following priorities submitted by the regional champions for the 2025 call for transnational collaboration:

On-site diagnostics: how to make it happen

The project aims to define the scope of on-site testing within the plant health system and to develop and validate on-site diagnostic tests for prioritized pests.

Testing and validation of innovative tools for generic surveillance of wood-boring beetles

The project aims to test and validate a number of tools for the generic surveillance of *Scolytinae*, *Buprestidae* and *Cerambycidae*, including: multi-coloured and multi-lured baited traps, smart traps, and entomoscope.

Risk assessment and mitigation in wood chip and fuelwood international trade

The project will focus on assessing non-commodities destructive technologies for pest detection, evaluating phytosanitary measures to overall assess and mitigate the risk of wood chip and fuelwood trade.

Integrative approach to streamline trade compliances of fruits and vegetables from Asia with respect to fruit flies

The project will identify, document, and promote sustainable fruit fly management practices, such as the use of biologicals and attractants. Phytosanitary treatments will be evaluated.

Risk assessment of anthracnose of tree and chili plants

The project will investigate the genetic, environmental, and biological factors influencing susceptibility of fruit trees and chili plants to *Colletotrichum* spp. Diagnostics tests and phytosanitary measures (e.g. synthetic fungicides and biopesticides) will be assessed.

Bio-rational management of invasive rugose spiralling whitefly in coconut and banana

The project aims to develop and validate sustainable pest management approaches against *Aleurodicus rugioperculatus*, based on biological control agents, cultural practices and natural pesticides.

Identification and characterization of host plant resistance in maize against fall army worm

The project will evaluate and characterize the resistance levels of maize genotypes against *Spodoptera frugiperda*. The project will also promote sustainable pest management practices, by combining host plant resistance with integrated pest management (IPM) approaches.

Eco-friendly mitigation of *Phytophthora* root rot in vegetables using biostimulants and biopesticides

The project will assess the efficacy of commercial biopesticides against *Phytophthora* and biostimulants to improve productivity of selected vegetable crops. The efficacy of the treatments will be evaluated in pot and field trials.

Potato Diseases and Vectors

The project will develop integrated, comprehensive strategies for managing potato diseases and their vectors, with a strong emphasis on advancing biological understanding, improving diagnostic techniques, and creating effective control measures to ensure the long-term sustainability of potato production.

Using a modeling approach to improve detection, eradication and management of Asian long-horned beetle

The project aims to mine data to identify correlations between Asian long-horned beetle host choice, landscape factors and characteristics of infested trees and to create prediction models.

Development of genetic and ecological approaches for managing the spread of *Ambrosia artemisiifolia*

The project aims to analyse *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* genetic traits, ecological tolerances, and dispersal patterns and to develop sustainable control strategies.

6. REPORT OF THE CONSULTATIONS FOR AFRICA

1. Introduction

1.1 A description of the region

Africa is located south of Europe and Southwest of Middle East. It is divided into five major regions each with distinct geography and agricultural characteristics. They include East Africa (Kenya, Ethiopia, Uganda, Tanzania, Rwanda, Somalia, etc); North Africa (Egypt, Libya, Tunisia, Algeria, Morocco, Western Sahara, Sudan); West Africa (Nigeria, Ghana, Senegal, Ivory Coast, Mali, Burkina Faso, Niger); Central Africa (Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), Cameroon, Gabon, Central African Republic); Southern Africa (South Africa, Zambia, Zimbabwe, Botswana, Namibia, Angola, Mozambique). Africa's climatic conditions are highly diverse due to its varying altitudes, vast size, location along the equator and proximity to oceans. It has different agroecological zones that encourage a variety of agricultural practices. The climatic conditions and cropping systems generally favor the development of most tropical pests.

1.2 A description of the regional champion

The EUPHRESKO III Network Office (ENO) is the champion for Northern Europe. Euphresco is a collaborative network of organizations responsible for funding and coordinating national research in the field of Plant Health. The overall goal of Euphresco is to foster coordination and collaboration in phytosanitary research, and to maintain itself as a strong, long-term network of research stakeholders. The objectives of Euphresco are:

- To coordinate transnational research programmes, by developing a common strategic research agenda
- To fund collaborative research projects in the phytosanitary area, through annual rounds of calls
- To support and complement other Plant Health initiatives
- To provide scientific evidence to support national and international policy
- To optimise and make best use of limited national Plant Health research resources by avoiding duplication and overlap of research activities
- To facilitate the dissemination of research outputs

1.3 The reasons underlying the interest for regional and global research coordination

Plant health is increasingly under threat, due to climate change, inadequate institutional capacities in different countries, and pest pressure. Global movement of plant material has led to the spread of pests from one region to the other where in some cases, they have become invasive with devastating consequences. Addressing these challenges requires collaboration between countries. Phytosanitary research coordination at national, regional and global levels can provide opportunities for prudent resource utilization, mentorship and training, information sharing and efficiency in response mechanisms to emerging/existing plant health challenges. Euphresco III (<https://www.phrescoglobal.net/>) is a global network of organizations involved in plant health research funding, research implementation and policy making that seek to develop, coordinate, fund and conduct phytosanitary research to inform policy. The network aims to strengthen the coordination of national and regional phytosanitary research programs primarily focusing on statutory plant health (emerging and regulated pests). Globally, phytosanitary research coordination has been identified as a key strategic activity within the

IPPC Strategic Plan 2030 (Agenda 7) and within the AU-IAPSC Plant Health Strategy for Africa (2022-2036).

1.4A summary of the EUPHRESCO III project, the aims of the consultation, and the process used for the consultation

The aim of the EUPHRESCO III project is to enhance national and regional phytosanitary research coordination and to set the foundations for global phytosanitary research coordination. This will be achieved by building on the foundations developed by the Euphresco self-sustained network and explore fit-for-purpose activities. The objectives of the project are:

- Develop a global strategic agenda on medium-term (5-10 years) phytosanitary research priorities. The agenda will guide phytosanitary research programming activities of the project partners and support them to address national, regional and global challenges through synergies between regions/continents of the world
- Organize joint calls on common research priorities to support and enhance international collaboration through the commissioning and implementation of research projects which meet the needs of the research funders and policy makers and have significant positive outcomes for Plant Health
- Develop and test models for the governance, the structure and the operations of a global network for phytosanitary research coordination. A roadmap will be established to guide the development of a global network for phytosanitary research coordination
- Engage with stakeholders such as policy makers, research funders, academia, industry (agri-food, biotech, diagnostic, seed industry), farmers and foresters and to foster knowledge exchange, involvement in the project activities, co-development, innovation, dissemination and adoption of outputs

Fig 1: EUPHRESCO III Work Package 2 on tested global Phytosanitary research consultation mechanism

The consultation process for the Africa region began in early 2024 with the identification of the stakeholders (national plant protection organizations, research organizations (national and international), research funders, industries, farmers, forestry institutions, diagnostic service providers) across the countries in Africa.

During the preparation of the survey tools, the EUPHRESCO III project was introduced to National Plant Protection Organizations at the 17th session of the AU-IAPSC's Steering

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Committee, March 18-19, 2024, at the Hotel SAWA in Douala, Cameroon. In June 2024, a survey was launched to share their phytosanitary research needs and priorities. Seed industry stakeholder engagement was undertaken during the 1st International Seed Quality Conference held in Nairobi, Kenya, from 19th -21st August 2024. Preliminary results were also presented and feedback gathered at the African Association of Insect Scientists (AAIS) 2024 conference, held in Lusaka, Zambia, between 18th and 22nd November 2024 which was attended by experts, researchers, and stakeholders from across m 30 different countries to share research findings, explore recent emerging technologies, and discuss holistic collaborative approaches to resolving the challenges posed by insect pest pests in agriculture. A webinar on Phytosanitary Research Prioritization- Africa. It was held on 25th February 2025 to raise awareness on the EUPHRESO III, phytosanitary research and collect research needs from the participants. The webinar was attended by 120 participants from Papua New Guinea, Kenya, Myanmar, Côte d'Ivoire, Uganda, Egypt, Senegal, Ethiopia, Pakistan, Tunisia, India, Scotland, The Republic of Congo, Sierra Leone, Hungary, Madagascar, Comoros, South Africa, Zimbabwe, Zambia, Thailand, China, Burkina Faso, and Burundi.

The responses across various African countries, with a total of 59 responses recorded. The highest representation came from Burundi (17%), followed by Kenya (14%) and Uganda (10%). Ghana (8%), along with Lesotho and Sierra Leone (each at 5%), also had notable mentions. Mali, Nigeria, and Zimbabwe accounted for 3% each, while the remaining 19 countries had 2% representation each. Additionally, the dataset includes references to broader regions like Eastern Africa and Africa (each at 2%), suggesting some responses were categorized at a regional level rather than by specific country. The results were presented at the recently held Africa Phytosanitary Research Regional Consultation workshop from 19th to 22nd August 2025, Nairobi, Kenya. The consultation meeting refined the phytosanitary research topics, needs that will shape the phytosanitary research priorities for Africa and EUPHRESO III strategic Research agenda at global level.

2. The agricultural crops

2.1 The list of agricultural crops that are important for the region

Based on the survey responses, the following crops have been identified as important for Africa:

- Cereals
 - Maize, rice-Staple crops for food production and security
 - Maize is the most common crop as a key priority, appearing often in Kenya (6), Uganda (5), Ghana (4), and Zimbabwe (3), Nigeria (4)
- Root crops
 - cassava and potatoes are important for food
 - Cassava is also widely grown, especially in Nigeria (4), Ghana (3), and Burundi (3).
- Cocoa and coffee
- Legumes
 - Beans, soybean
- Oil crops
 - Groundnuts
- Fibre crops
 - Cotton
- Fruits and vegetables
 - Fresh fruits e.g avocado, mango, citrus, cucumbers ,
 - Fresh vegetables e.g fresh herbs, peppers, chilli peppers, capsicum
- Cut flowers
 - Roses, chrysanthemums,

- Bananas

3. Important pests for the region

3.1 The list of pests for which collaboration within the region is sought, including some information on this pest like geographical distribution / host range / impact

Based on the survey, the most serious pests are Fall Armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*), which devastates maize and other staple foods, and tomato leaf miner *Phthorimaea absoluta*, which has badly impacted tomato production. Fruit flies (*Bactrocera dorsalis*) are a major trade issue, triggering export prohibitions, and Fusarium Wilt TR4 (*Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *cubense*) is a banana production threat with no antidote. Cassava Brown Streak Virus (CBSV) and Maize Lethal Necrosis Disease (MLND) are major threats to food security of staple foods vital to millions. Whiteflies (*Bemisia tabaci*) act as vectors of virus, spreading destructive plant diseases, while Diamondback Moth (*Plutella xylostella*) ruins vegetable crops, reducing their market worth. Weevils, such as the maize weevil (*Sitophilus zeamais*) and sweet potato weevils (*Cylas* spp.), contribute to post-harvest losses. The pests and diseases were ranked according to economic, trade, and food security implications that call for joint regional efforts, policies, and management interventions to combat their impacts.

Nr of Mentions	Pest Names	Priority Factors
12	Fall Armyworm (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>)	High yield loss in maize, rapid spread, pesticide resistance
10	Tomato Leaf Miner - <i>Phthorimaea absoluta</i>	Severe damage to tomatoes, difficult control, pesticide resistance
9	Fruitfly- <i>Bactrocera dorsalis</i>	Major fruit losses, quarantine pest, wide host range
8	Fusarium Wilt (<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> TR4), Cassava Brown Streak Virus (CBSV)	Devastating to bananas, soil-borne, no effective chemical control
7	Maize Lethal Necrosis Disease (MLN), <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i> , <i>Bemisia tabaci</i> (Whitefly)	Maize crop failure, multiple virus complex, limited resistance
6	Banana Bunchy Top Virus (BBTV), Cassava Mosaic Virus (CMV), Cocoa Black Pod Disease (<i>Phytophthora palmivora</i>), Papaya Mealybug (<i>Paracoccus marginatus</i>)	Severe yield loss in bananas, no cure, spread by aphids
5	Rice Blast (<i>Magnaporthe oryzae</i>), Striga (<i>Striga hermonthica</i>), False Codling Moth (<i>Thaumatotibia leucotreta</i>), Citrus Greening Disease (<i>Huanglongbing</i>), Potato Cyst Nematodes (<i>Globodera</i> spp.), African Cassava Whitefly, American Fall Armyworm	Major rice yield losses, airborne spores, fungicide resistance
4	<i>Plutella xylostella</i> (Diamondback Moth), Maize Stalk Borer (<i>Busseola fusca</i>), Red Spider Mite (<i>Tetranychus urticae</i>), Groundnut Rosette Virus, Banana Thrips, Weevils (Various species), Thrips (<i>Frankliniella occidentalis</i> , <i>Thrips tabaci</i>), Phytophthora Root Rot (<i>Phytophthora cinnamomi</i>), Citrus Black Spot, Mango Bacterial Black Spot, Bruchids (<i>Callosobruchus maculatus</i> , <i>Acanthoscelides obtectus</i>), Rusts (Various cereal rust diseases), Blights (Early & Late Blight - <i>Phytophthora infestans</i>), Aphids (<i>Aphis</i> spp.)	Affects crucifers, pesticide resistance, high reproductive rate
3	Leaf Miners (<i>Liriomyza</i> spp.), Paddy Rice Snail, Quelea Birds (<i>Quelea quelea</i>), Desert Locust (<i>Schistocerca gregaria</i>), Sorghum Chaffer (<i>Pachnoda interrupta</i>), Rice Hispa Beetle, Kapra Beetle (<i>Trogoderma granarium</i>), <i>Antestiopsis orbitalis</i> (Coffee Bug), <i>Glycaspis brimblecombei</i>	Virus vectors, widespread, hard to control

	(Eucalyptus Psyllid), <i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i> (Bacterial Wilt), Sweet Potato Weevils, Cassava Witches' Broom Disease, Tomato Bacterial Wilt, Cocoa Swollen Shoot Virus, Citrus Psyllid (<i>Diaphorina citri</i>)	
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At the regional consultation, the following were highlighted as regional pests of priority:

- Fruit flies
- FCM
- Scale insects
- *Xylella fastidiosa*
- BBTV
- Fusarium TR4
- FAW
- PCN
- Goss wilt
- MLND
- Dessert locust
- CBSD
- Citrus black spot
- Ginger diseases
- CBSD
- Papaya mealybug and other mealybug
- CBSV+Vector
- Soft rot
- UG99
- Persea mite
- Carrot weeds

3.2 The list of pests for which collaboration at global level is sought, including some information on this pest like geographical distribution / host range / impact

The table below highlights the most frequently reported global priority pests and their impact on agriculture, trade, and food security.

At the regional consultation, the following were highlighted as pests of priority at global level:

- MLN
- Goss wilt
- CBS

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- *Phthorimaea absoluta*
- White flies
- Aphids
- CMV
- Fruit flies
- FCM
- Fusarium TR4
- *Xylella fastidiosa*
- PCN
- UG99
- FAW
- Wheat blast
- Khapra beetle
- Tomato brown rugose
- BBTV
- Anthracnose
- Cocoa black pod
- Papaya mealybug
- Citrus green disease

3.3 Summary of the research activities conducted in the last 5 years on the above pests

Country	Project	Institution (s)	Funding Agency	Pest	Crop (s)
Kenya	Hot Vapour Treatment	KEPHIS, ICIPE, AFA-HCD, UoN, TradeMark, FPEAK, IPPC	EU	Fruit fly	Mango
	Strategies for managing potato cyst nematode	KALRO, FAO, CIP, KEPHIS, MoA	FAO, ICIPE	Potato Cyst Nematode	Potatoes
	False codling moth Project	KEPHIS, FPEAK, Keya Flower Council (KFC)	TMA, COLEAD	False codling moth	Avocado, chillies
	Soft rot of potatoes	KEPHIS, CABI, Potato Council, KALRO, MoA, CoG, Netherlands Embassy	CABI	Soft rot of potatoes	Potatoes
	MRLs	AFA-HCD, FPEAK, TMA, CABI, PCPB, FPC (Fresh Produce Consortium), aa-Grow	TMA		Green beans
	Area of low pest prevalence of mangoes (Makueni)	KEPHIS, TMA, KALRO, ICIPE, HCD			Mangoes
	Fumigation project on flowers – testing various protocols	AFA-HCD, KEPHIS, KALRO, PCPB,			Flowers

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Country	Project	Institution (s)	Funding Agency	Pest	Crop (s)
	for fumigating flowers	Australian NPPO			
	Monitoring entry of new pests	KEPHIS			
	Banana Bunchy top Virus	KEPHIS, IITA		Banana Bunchy top virus disease	Banana
	Biological control of papaya mealybug	CABI, KALRO, KEPHIS, National Museum of Kenya		mealybug	Papaya
	MLN in maize	CYMMIT, KALRO, KEPHIS, STAK		MLN	Maize
	Scale insect	CABI, KEPHIS			
	Capacity building on boarder officers	KEPHIS, PCPB, TMA			
	Capacity building	Hamelmallo Agricultural college, FAO, NPPS	FAO		
	Bio- security risks posed by sea container pathway in Kenya	IPPC , KEPHIS	IPPC/KEPHIS		
Eritrea	Fruit flies project	Hamelmallo Agricultural college, FAO, NPPS	FAO	Fruit flies	Mango, guava, oranges
	Locust invasion	Hamelmallo Agricultural college, FAO, NPPS	FAO	Locust	
	Controlling Mango mealy bug using parasitoids	ISABU, NPPO, Extension services, IITA		mealybug	Mango
Burundi	Scale insect	NPPO, CABI, KEPHIS			
	Rapid risk assessment to prioritize potentially non-native plant pests to protect agriculture and facilitate trade	ISABU, NPPO, Extension services, Universities and CABI			
	Phytosanitary capacity evaluation	FAO, Ethiopian Agricultural Authority (EAA), MoA	FAO		
Ethiopia (FAO)	System development for FCM in roses	FAO, EAA, Ethiopian Horticultural	FAO		

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Country	Project	Institution (s)	Funding Agency	Pest	Crop (s)
		producers and exporters Association			
Ghana	Surveillance (early detection) to inform policy	NPPO (PPRSD, Ghana) and BNARI	CABI	BBTV	Banana
Cameroon	Surveillance	NPPO (Cameroon), University and IITA	IAEA	<i>Bactrocera</i> spp.	Mango
Comoros	Surveillance	NPPO (Comoros) and University	KAFACI and FAO	Fall armyworm <i>Spodoptera</i> spp	Maize
Several countries	Surveillance	ICIPE, KEPHIS, CIMMYT, IITA, SLARI, CABI, AU-IAPSC, RECs, CILSS, academia, private sectors-CSR	CABI, FAO, IITA, USAID, USA land grant university, NGOs	Fall Army worm	Maize
Several countries	Surveillance	ICIPE, KEPHIS, CIMMYT, IITA, SLARI, CABI, AU-IAPSC, RECs, CILSS, academia, private sectors-CSR	CABI, FAO, IITA, USAID, USA land grant university, NGOs	Fruit Fly	Several fruits
Several countries	Surveillance	ICIPE, KEPHIS, CIMMYT, IITA, SLARI, CABI, AU-IAPSC, RECs, CILSS, academia, private sectors-CSR	CABI, FAO, IITA, USAID, USA land grant university, NGOs	TR4 Fusarium	Banana
Several countries	Surveillance	ICIPE, KEPHIS, CIMMYT, IITA, SLARI, CABI, AU-IAPSC, RECs, CILSS, academia, private sectors-CSR	CABI, FAO, IITA, USAID, USA land grant university, NGOs	FCM	Several fruits and vegetables
Several countries	Surveillance	ICIPE, KEPHIS, CIMMYT, IITA, SLARI, CABI, AU-IAPSC, RECs, WAVE, CILSS, academia, private sectors-CSR	CABI, FAO, IITA, USAID, USA land grant university, Bill and Melinda Gates	Cassava Viruses (mosaic and brown streak)	Cassava
Several countries	VIRCA Plus developed	KALRO, KEPHIS,	National Science	cassava CBSV and CMV	Cassava

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Country	Project	Institution (s)	Funding Agency	Pest	Crop (s)
	resistance varieties	Danforth Plant Science, UON, ISAAA, IITA, also includes RAB	Foundation USA, Gates Foundation		
Kenya	Tracking the evolution changes on whiteflies and begomoviruses	ILRI and North Carolina Uni	Foundation USA, Gates Foundation	Whiteflies and Begomoviruses	Several hosts
Rwanda	Building Rwandan Capacity for Accelerated Development, and Adoption of Crops Enhanced through Modern Biotechnology	CIP, Michigan State University, Danforth Centre, IITA . Alliance for Science	Danforth Centre	Several	Several

4. Key drivers for collaboration

4.1 The main plant health issues or related practical problems of the policy makers in the region

Pests Affecting Crops:

- Common pests include Fall Armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*), Fruit Flies, Whiteflies, and Mealybugs.
- Tuta absoluta* (Tomato Leaf Miner) damages tomatoes, while False Codling Moth (FCM) affects fruits.
- Cassava and sweet potatoes suffer from whiteflies and weevils.
- Other pests mentioned: Aphids, Sorghum chaffer, sesame seed bugs, diamondback moths, Thrips on cotton and vegetables, and Locust swarms (*Locusta migratoria*, *Nomadacris septemfasciata*)

Major Crop Diseases

- Cassava Brown Streak Disease and Maize Lethal Necrosis are major threats.
- Banana Bunchy Top Virus and Fusarium Wilt (*Fusarium oxysporum*, including TR4 in bananas) are spreading.
- Bacterial and fungal diseases affect potatoes, rice, and vegetables. Bacterial Wilt in bananas (BXW), Banana Bunchy Top Virus (BBTV), *Pyricularia oryzae* (Rice Blast)
- Other diseases mentioned: Sweet potato virus Disease, *Xylella fastidiosa*, Potato Cyst Nematodes, *Phytophthora* Root Rot, Anthracnose, Citrus Greening Disease, Cocoa Swollen Shoot Virus,

Climate and Environmental Challenges

- Rising temperatures and droughts are increasing pest outbreaks.
- Weeds provide breeding grounds for pests and diseases.
- Pests are becoming resistant to pesticides.

Institutional Challenges

- Many countries lack proper pest surveillance and diagnostic labs.
- There are not enough trained experts in plant health.
- Outdated laws make pest control and quarantine difficult.

Research and Diagnostic Limitations

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- Lack of well-equipped national plant health laboratories
- Shortage of trained personnel in pest diagnostics and management
- Limited use of molecular tools for insect identification
- Inadequate seed testing and disease diagnostics
- Weak research capacity on new pathogens and invasive pests

Storage and Post-Harvest Losses

- Poor storage leads to insect infestations in grains and tubers.
- Many farmers lack knowledge of proper storage methods.

Trade and Regulation Issues

- Strict seed import rules and quarantine laws limit crop movement.
- Poor coordination between countries affects pest control efforts.

4.2 The main plant health issues or related practical problems of the research funders in the region

Pests Affecting Crops:

- Common pests include Fall Armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*), Fruit Flies, Whiteflies, and Mealybugs.
- *Tuta absoluta* (Tomato Leaf Miner) damages tomatoes, while False Codling Moth (FCM) affects fruits.
- Cassava and sweet potatoes suffer from whiteflies and weevils.
- Other pests mentioned: Aphids, Sorghum chaffer, sesame seed bugs, diamondback moths, Thrips on cotton and vegetables, and Locust swarms (*Locusta migratoria*, *Nomadacris septemfasciata*)

Major Crop Diseases

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Climate and Environmental Challenges

- Rising temperatures and droughts are increasing pest outbreaks.
- Weeds provide breeding grounds for pests and diseases.
- Pests are becoming resistant to pesticides.

4.3 The main plant health issues or related practical problems of the research organizations in the region

Institutional Challenges

- Many countries lack proper pest surveillance and diagnostic labs.
- There are not enough trained experts in plant health.
- Outdated laws make pest control and quarantine difficult.

Research and Diagnostic Limitations

- Lack of well-equipped national plant health laboratories
- Shortage of trained personnel in pest diagnostics and management
- Limited use of molecular tools for insect identification
- Inadequate seed testing and disease diagnostics
- Weak research capacity on new pathogens and invasive pests

4.4 The main plant health issues or related practical problems of the industry in the region

Trade and Regulation Issues

- Strict seed import rules and quarantine laws limit crop movement.
- Poor coordination between countries affects pest control efforts.

4.5 The main plant health issues or related practical problems of farmers and foresters in the region

Storage and Post-Harvest Losses

- Poor storage leads to insect infestations in grains and tubers.
- Many farmers lack knowledge of proper storage methods.

4.6 The needs in terms of capacity building

The key capacity-building needs across various plant health and agricultural research sectors can be grouped into the following major areas:

1. Training and Skill Development
 - Training in diagnostics, pest and disease surveillance, pest risk analysis, and integrated pest management (IPM)
 - Skill development in bioinformatics, epidemiology, and AI tools for pest and disease management
 - Professional development programs, workshops, and exchange programs for researchers, extension workers, and plant health officers
2. Resources and Infrastructure
 - Modern laboratory facilities equipped with PCR machines, ELISA kits, and sequencing technologies
 - Equipment and tools for field diagnostics, disease surveillance, and quality control
 - Funding for research, infrastructure development, and acquisition of advanced laboratory equipment
3. Technology Transfer and Advanced Methods
 - Adoption of molecular diagnostic tools, DNA fingerprinting, and biological pest control methods
 - Development of disease-resistant crop varieties and improved genetic mapping techniques
 - Use of remote sensing, AI-based pest prediction models, and digital traceability systems
4. Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing
 - Partnerships between research institutions, universities, and government agencies
 - Strengthening regional and international collaboration for data sharing and policy alignment
 - Creation of databases and digital platforms for pest surveillance, risk analysis, and information dissemination
5. Policy and Regulatory Frameworks
 - Develop plant health regulations, quarantine services, and pest surveillance protocols
 - Strengthening seed certification systems and enforcing international phytosanitary standards
 - Mobilization of resources and expertise to improve policy implementation and regulatory compliance

5. The research priorities

5.1 The medium-term (5-10 years) research priorities identified through the bottom-up approach (stakeholders' survey input from research implementers and end-users)

Priorities for the Next 5-10 Years

Organizations and institutions involved in plant health and biosecurity have outlined several key priorities for the coming decade. These priorities can be categorized into the following themes:

1. Strengthening Regulatory Frameworks & Policies
 - Updating national quarantine pest lists and invasive pest regulations.
 - Reviewing and harmonizing plant health laws, pesticide regulations, and phytosanitary certification.
 - Developing national plant health policies and legislation for better governance.
 - Aligning legal frameworks with international obligations (e.g., WTO-SPS, IPPC).
 - Strengthening enforcement mechanisms for biosecurity and border control.
2. Enhancing Surveillance, Inspection & Certification
 - Updating national pest and disease surveillance systems.
 - Strengthening pest risk analysis (PRA) and epidemiological surveillance.
 - Conducting national surveys for pest and disease identification.
 - Improving inspection and certification of consignments for import and export.
 - Implementing an electronic phytosanitary certification system (e-Phyto).
 - Ensuring effective plant health monitoring and response mechanisms.
3. Capacity Building & Training
 - Enhancing the skills of scientists, inspectors, and farmers in pest and pesticide management.
 - Training extension workers, laboratory staff, and researchers in modern diagnostic techniques.
 - Providing specialized training in areas such as toxicological evaluations, molecular diagnostics, and integrated pest management (IPM).
 - Recruiting and retaining skilled personnel in plant health and biosecurity sectors.
4. Strengthening Laboratory & Research Infrastructure
 - Establishing and equipping modern laboratories for pesticide analysis and plant diagnostics.
 - Expanding greenhouse facilities for research and experimentation.
 - Improving laboratory capacities for molecular identification of plant pathogens.
 - Researching on emerging pests and alternative pest control solutions.
 - Investing in technology such as AI for pest diagnostics and remote sensing.
5. Improving Pest & Disease Management Strategies
 - Strengthening control measures for invasive pests such as FAW, mealybugs, fruit flies, and bacterial wilt.
 - Developing sustainable pest management strategies, including biopesticides and biological control.
 - Mapping pest and disease distributions to improve risk assessment and mitigation.
 - Reducing pesticide residues in food and ensuring compliance with safety regulations.
 - Promoting good agricultural practices and integrated pest management (IPM) to reduce reliance on chemical pesticides.
6. Partnerships & Regional Cooperation
 - Enhancing collaboration with international organizations (FAO, IPPC, CABI, etc.).
 - Strengthening regional and international agreements for plant health and trade.
 - Supporting the implementation of the African Plant Health Strategy.
 - Engaging with stakeholders in adopting and enforcing plant health regulations.
 - Advocating for increased funding and investment in phytosanitary research and capacity building.

7. Seed & Crop Health Improvements

- Establishing seed health testing protocols and facilities.
- Certifying pest-resistant seed varieties (e.g., maize tolerant to FAW, banana resistant to BXW).
- Mapping and improving seed certification systems to ensure quality standards.
- Strengthening phytosanitary measures for seed import and export.
- Raising awareness of informal seed systems and their impact on plant health.

1st Priorities for Plant Health in the Next 5-10 Years

- Strengthen Regional and International Collaboration – Improve cooperation with neighbouring countries and global organizations for better pest and disease management.
- Improve Regulations and Legal Frameworks – Update and enforce phytosanitary laws, seed certification standards, and pesticide regulations.
- Enhance Surveillance and Diagnostics –
 - Set up border laboratories
 - Conduct regular pest monitoring
 - Maintain a national pest and disease database
- Capacity Building and Training –
 - Train plant health officers, farmers, and researchers
 - Improve skills in pest control, diagnostics, and crop protection methods
- Increase Funding for Plant Health Programs – allocate more resources to research, extension services, and pest management initiatives.
- Biological Control and Sustainable Pest Management –
 - Promote the use of biopesticides and nanotechnology
 - Implement natural pest control methods
- Improve Quarantine and Border Control – Establish plant quarantine stations at all entry points to prevent the spread of invasive pests and diseases.
- Invest in Research and Technology – Support research on pest-resistant crops, emerging plant diseases, and innovative pest control strategies.
- Develop a National Phytosanitary Strategy – Create a structured approach to managing plant health risks and ensuring food security.
- Improve Data Management and Decision-Making –
 - Develop an effective pesticide database
 - Conduct surveys to guide policy decisions

Top Priorities for Plant Health in the Next 5-10 Years

Priority one

- Stronger International and Regional Cooperation
 - Work with other countries to stop plant diseases and pests from spreading.
 - Make trade rules easier for importing and exporting plants and seeds.
- Better Pest and Disease Monitoring
 - Regularly check farms and borders for new plant diseases and pests.
 - Keep track of pests and diseases in neighbouring countries.
- Improve Border Protection and Plant Quarantine
 - Set up plant quarantine stations at all entry points.
 - Strengthen border security to stop dangerous pests from entering.
- Train More People in Plant Health
 - Teach farmers, plant health officers, and inspectors about pest control.
 - Train experts to diagnose plant diseases and inspect crops.
- Stronger Plant Health Laws and Regulations
 - Update laws to protect plants and make pesticide use safer.
 - Ensure the country follows international plant health rules.

- More Research and Innovation
 - Support research on natural pest control methods.
 - Use technology like AI and nanotechnology to fight plant diseases.
- Increase Funding for Plant Health Programs
 - Get more money from the government for plant protection.
 - Work with international partners to fund plant health projects.

Priority two

- Faster Pest and Disease Response
 - Provide vehicles and equipment for plant health teams to work quickly.
 - Improve quarantine and monitoring efforts.
- Use More Natural Pest Control Methods
 - Promote biopesticides and other eco-friendly pest control solutions.
 - Research safer ways to manage plant pests.
- Better Training and Awareness
 - Organize workshops to teach farmers and workers about plant health.
 - Train people to use pesticides safely.
- Stronger Pest and Disease Testing
 - Improve laboratories for testing plant diseases.
 - Increase pest monitoring to stop the spread of new diseases.
- Support Sustainable Farming
 - Create policies that help farmers use fewer harmful chemicals.
 - Reduce pesticide residues in food and soil.
- Ensure Good-Quality Seeds
 - Stop fake or low-quality seeds from being sold.
 - Improve seed certification rules to protect crops.
- Expand Research and Resources
 - Support studies on plant diseases and pests.
 - Provide better tools and staff for plant health programs.

Priority three

- Approve Plant Health Laws; Pass the Plant Health Act to improve rules and pest control.
- Better Pest Monitoring: Study and map all harmful pests in different areas and set up better systems to track pests and diseases.
 - Train More People: Teach farmers and agriculture officers how to manage pests and train experts to identify plant diseases.
 - Improve Plant Health Labs: Build a modern lab for testing plant diseases. And set up better equipment at borders for checking plants.
- Stronger Import and Export Rules
 - Make sure imported and exported plants are pest-free.
 - Check high-risk crops and pests before they spread.
- Fight New Plant Diseases
 - Control major plant diseases like cassava virus and rice blast.
 - Stop pests like armyworms from destroying crops.
- Use of Technology in Farming
 - Use digital tools to track pests and diseases.
 - Invest in modern farming methods.
- More Funding for Plant Health
 - Get more money to fight pests and diseases.
 - Support research, training, and monitoring.

Priority four

- Better Engagement and Education

- Increase farmer education on plant health issues.
- Involve all stakeholders along agricultural value chains.
- Improved Pest and Disease Management
 - Strengthen invasive plant species control.
 - Develop a national system for managing and reporting pest information.
 - Combat Fall Armyworm and False Codling Moth (FCM).
- Upgrading Facilities and Resources
 - Establish new plant health inspection facilities.
 - Improve seed storage practices to maintain seed quality.
 - Provide transportation for plant health officers to conduct fieldwork.
- Strengthening Research and Technology
 - Expand the use of AI for field pest and pathogen detection.
 - Secure funding for plant health research and diagnostic equipment.
 - Develop a sustained national plant health surveillance system.
- Policy and International Collaboration
 - Harmonize phytosanitary requirements with neighbouring countries.
 - Support the implementation of the African Plant Health Strategy.

Priority five

- Enhancing Agricultural Best Practices
 - Promote the use of biopesticides as an alternative to chemical pesticides.
 - Ensure the efficient use of pesticides through better training programs.
 - Strengthen plant clinics across all agricultural regions.
- Infrastructure and Equipment Improvement
 - Set up quarantine infrastructure at border checkpoints.
 - Acquire new inspection equipment for phytosanitary control.
 - Establish modern laboratories for plant health diagnostics.
- Advancing Research and Seed Quality
 - Conduct DNA fingerprinting and genetic purity testing for seeds.
 - Develop new pest-resistant seed varieties.
 - Perform economic impact studies on pests and diseases in the seed system.
- Technology and Digital Tools
 - Hire an ICT specialist for plant health digital platforms (IPPC, CABI, COLEAD).
- Improving Trade and Regulations
 - Streamline phytosanitary requirements to apply to species instead of individual varieties.
 - Ensure transparency and proper notification for smooth agricultural trade.

5.2 The medium-term research (5-10 years) priorities identified through the top-down approach

Regional Priorities for Plant Health (Next 5-10 Years)

1. Stronger Border Control and Trade Rules
 - Improve border checks to stop pests from spreading.
 - Build regional plant quarantine centers.
 - Make plant health rules the same across all countries.
 - Create agreements between countries on plant health standards.
2. Research and New Solutions
 - Study ways to grow pest-resistant crops.
 - Research new pests and diseases in the region.
 - Develop better ways to manage plant pests.
 - Focus on tomato leaf curl virus research.
3. Training and Education
 - Train plant health workers and inspectors.

- Teach farmers better pest and disease management.
 - Organize workshops and learning programs across countries.
 - Help the seed industry understand international plant health rules.
4. Pest and Disease Monitoring
 - Set up teams to study pest risks in the region.
 - Improve systems to detect pests early.
 - Share plant health data between countries.
 - Work together on regional pest control plans.
 5. Better Pest and Disease Control
 - Use natural methods like biopesticides.
 - Improve pest control programs (e.g., for Fall Armyworm).
 - Stop the spread of harmful invasive species.
 - Promote safer pest control alternatives.
 6. Stronger Laws and Rules
 - Make pesticide approval rules the same across all countries.
 - Create one regional list of dangerous plant pests.
 - Make trade rules fair and easy for all countries.
 7. Better Facilities and Equipment
 - Build new plant health testing labs.
 - Get better equipment for plant inspections.
 - Improve storage and transport for plant health monitoring.
 8. Climate Change and Plant Health
 - Help farmers use farming methods that resist climate change.
 - Study how climate change affects plant diseases.
 - Use new technology to fight climate-related plant health problems.

Global Priorities for Plant Health (Next 5–10 Years)

1. Controlling Pests and Diseases
 - Stop the spread of major pests like fall armyworm and citrus greening.
 - Improve pest prediction models and eco-friendly control methods.
 - Strengthen quarantine and early warning systems.
2. Sustainable and Climate-Smart Agriculture
 - Reduce chemical pesticides and adopt natural pest control.
 - Develop pest- and climate-resistant crops.
 - Support farmers with tools to combat climate-related plant issues.
3. Stronger Policies and Regulations
 - Enforce international plant health standards.
 - Ensure pesticide safety and fair-trade rules.
 - Improve cooperation between countries and private sectors.
4. Research, Innovation, and Training
 - Use AI, satellite images, and new technologies for plant health monitoring.
 - Train farmers and scientists in pest management.
 - Fund research on disease-resistant crops and cheaper pest control solutions.
5. Public Awareness and Food Security
 - Educate farmers and the public on plant health.
 - Regulate online plant sales to prevent pest spread.
 - Connect plant health to human and environmental well-being.
6. Funding and Infrastructure
 - Invest in pest control research and diagnostic labs.
 - Improve plant product tracking for safe global trade.
 - Support developing countries in maintaining strong plant health systems.

5.3 Outcome of the consultation: common research priorities for the region

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-01 under grant agreement No 101130467

The participants identified the need for upgraded pest monitoring and control systems, improved training, and better lab facilities for accelerated disease diagnosis. They emphasized the need to provide farmers with the education necessary for proper protection and storage of crops to reduce losses. Updating plant health legislation and quarantine was considered a priority to be able to contain new pests/diseases and ensure safe trade. In addition, they emphasized the importance of regional and international cooperation to avoid the dissemination of pests and diseases.

The next 5-10 years will see opinion focused on improving plant health, controlling pests, and border security. Action plans include updating pest lists, increasing inspections, and making better laboratory equipment available. Training will allow growers and experts to handle pests safely. International cooperation will allow adherence to international regulations and expand trade. These steps will allow for food safety and better farming.

In the next 5–10 years, around the world, efforts are needed to safeguard plants against pests and diseases. Key measures are enhanced monitoring systems, stricter quarantine regulations, and research into disease-resistant plants. Farmers need training as well as access to safer pest management techniques such as biopesticides and integrated pest management. They need to work together to facilitate information exchange and develop fair trade policies to counter pest infestation.

At the regional consultation workshop, the following were prioritized as key phytosanitary Research areas:

Phytosanitary Research Area	Regional topics	Global topics
Diagnostics & Detection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Egg detection of insect pests • DNA Barcoding of pests • Morphological and DNA identification • Rapid detection KIT • Pest check list • Geographical occurrence map • Sampling protocol • Diagnostic tools • Country pest list • Biology of pests • Surveillance protocols 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proficiency testing (DNA and diagnostic protocol) • Stakeholder mapping engagement and coordination (2) • Evaluation of fitness of purpose • Knowledge resources • Funding resources • Surveillance • Harmonization of diagnostic eg protocol (1) • Cost reduction of test kits • Country pest list • Skilled human resources and equipped lab (3) • Modelling • Use of Drones for surveillance
Surveillance & Monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General surveillance • Specific surveys on detection and monitoring • Research to establish pest status, pest free areas and areas of low pest prevalence • Functional coordination (1) • Modelling and forecasting (2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supportive policies and regulatory frameworks • Training in surveillance and detection (3) • Support data management systems (2) • Develop surveillance plans including contingency plans

Phytosanitary Area	Research	Regional topics	Global topics
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of digital tools to support surveillance and data repository • Host range timing • Research on surveillance tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of training on dossier for market access • Strengthen capacity for PRA, pest list development to enhance trade • Multidisciplinary teams to coordinate surveillance and monitoring (1) • Simulation exercises • Infrastructure
Management & Control		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biological control • Breeding for resistance • Identify the diversity of existing strains for pests and diseases • Pathogenicity studies • Georeferencing and mapping of high/low prevalence areas • Develop IPM approaches to pest and disease centres • Capacity building • Integration of digital technologies eg, drones • Innovative dissemination channels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of modern digital tools • Platform harmonization • Resource mobilization • Training for policy makers in IPM • Funding on IPM infrastructure • Training on existing and emerging IPM tools • Review and update of university curriculum on effective IPM • Pesticide risk reduction
Capacity & Systems		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pest surveillance • Diagnostics • Modelling risks • Biology, ecology and commodity pathway • Management options (3) • Genetic breeding • Pest Risk Reduction • Policies regulation and harmonization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human resource development- technical support and scientists • Infrastructure eg data base management system, laboratory space, equipment. • Diagnostic protocol • Policy advocacy • Funds • Coordination and collaboration • Communication and dissemination of the systems approach
Policy, Trade & Innovation		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post harvest management treatment eg policy on cold chains or fumigation • Area wide approaches • Surveillance and early warning systems • Protocol harmonization for diagnostic tools and treatments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional harmonization and mutual recognition of control and inspection systems. • Infrastructure eg well equipped standard laboratory • AI Information sharing tools

Phytosanitary Area	Research	Regional topics	Global topics
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conformed assessment to procedures to confirm compliance • PRA Pathway studies • Trade concerns eg socio economic assessment of bans , regulations • Risk based inspection protocols • MRL studies • Alternative pest control measures- Pest Risk reduction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk based inspection protocol/ testing • Capacity building for actors eg NPPOs and policy makers • Compliance programs eg certification schemes for farmers • AI for surveillance and detection of pests • Rapid diagnostics kit tools • Phytosanitary treatment protocol eg Hot water treatment for fruitflies in mangoes • Coordinated development and review of phytosanitary policies, standards per country, region or global • Improvement of regulatory frameworks, coordinated mechanisms or platforms • Free trade agreement • Regional centres of excellence • Advocacy awareness

5.4 The suggested research topics for 2025 and 2026

Climate resilience, plant breeding, and pest management are the main future priorities for East Africa. Suggested that the future focus needs to be on protecting crops from pests, developing better plant varieties, and adapting to climate change. West Africa: work on safe ways to control pests, study farming costs and profits, and improve crops. Southern Africa: Study pest risks, use technology to track pests, and find ways to deal with climate change. All regions want to improve food production by using science, new ideas, and training for farmers to ensure farming stays strong in the future.

Region	Country	Future Focus Areas
East Africa	Uganda	Studying pests, natural pest control, tracking pests, adapting to climate change
	Kenya	Improving crops, soil health, cleaning polluted soil, better plant breeding

	Tanzania	Checking risks, testing plants, understanding economic impact, educating people
	Ethiopia	Using advanced genetics, studying climate effects, researching pest-plant interactions
	Somalia	Researching pest risks, tracking pest problems, studying impact on crops
	Burundi	Better crop breeding, using natural pesticides, researching pest control
West Africa	Nigeria	Using eco-friendly solutions, improving plant breeding, using new technology
	Ghana	Studying farm economy, improving breeding, stopping harmful species, using data analysis
	Benin	Finding new ways to control pests, improving research
	Togo	Studying insects, plant diseases, and fungi that harm crops
	Mali	Studying diseases, improving crops, adapting to climate, and better farming methods
	Côte d'Ivoire	Protecting crops, managing plant diseases, controlling pests
Southern Africa	Zimbabwe	Checking pest risks, using technology to monitor pests, adapting to climate
	Malawi	Continuing farm research
	South Africa	Predicting pest problems, controlling citrus diseases, managing pests
	Lesotho	Controlling weeds, reducing food loss after harvest, adapting to climate
	Madagascar	Improving farm research and innovation

Table summarizing the research needs by region and country:

Region	Country	Research Needs
East Africa	Uganda	Infrastructure development, biopesticide research, AI-based pest surveillance, phytosanitary research
	Tanzania	Plant disease resistance, climate change effects, and integrated pest management (IPM)
	Kenya	Invasive pest management, bio-control solutions, pesticide effects, alternative pest management strategies
	Ethiopia	Invasive pest research, pest modelling, biological control
	Somalia	Pest surveillance, fruit fly impact, economic damage from Quelea birds
	Djibouti	Pest identification, biological control, phytoprotection
	Burundi	Biopesticides, pest resistance management, phytosanitary certification
Southern Africa	Madagascar	Climate change impact on pests, alternative pest control methods, pest transfer mechanisms
	Lesotho	Post-harvest management, climate change effects, weed control
	Zimbabwe	Climate change adaptation, pest risk analysis, AI-based phenotyping, novel pest management technologies
	Malawi	Bacterial wilts, Fusarium wilt in bananas, Fall Armyworm management
	South Africa	Targeted pesticide application, funding for pest research
	Eswatini	Citrus black spot research, Fall Armyworm control
	Comoros	Alternative pest management, biocontrol solutions, Fusarium disease research
West Africa	Nigeria	Biopesticide development, climate change impact on pests, reduction of synthetic inputs
	Sierra Leone	Pesticide efficacy research, pest identification, quarantine pest studies
	Ghana	Climate change impact on plant health, IPM strategies, and seed health improvement

	Liberia	Emerging pest surveillance, disease diagnostics, farmer capacity building
	Gambia	IPM strategies, pest inspection, plant extract-based pest control
	Benin	Rapid plant disease detection kits, biopesticide testing
	Togo	Biological control of invasive pests, pest distribution mapping
	Niger	Food safety, plant protection, innovative agricultural products
	Côte d'Ivoire	Quarantine regulations, plant protection
	Mali	Pest modelling, molecular biology studies, capacity building
	Cabo Verde	Biological pest control, organic agriculture

Mapping Phytosanitary Research priority topics for Africa 2025/2026

Diagnostics and Detection

1. Knowledge sharing for sampling, surveillance, diagnostics, and support for phytosanitary outreach stations for regional harmonisation.

To build satellite capacities in terms of basic equipment, and generate harmonised sampling protocols priority pests. It also aims to build technical capacities in phytosanitary technologies (professional and academic)

2. Risk modelling for False Codling Moth (*Thaumatotibia leucotreta*)

FCM is a quarantine pest with zero tolerance at the EU market and influence trade with devastating impact on key export crops (e.g. avocado, rose value chains). The topic encompasses the development of a digital system for the detection, identification and management of the phenological stages of FCM. It also enhances future climate modelling in diverse ecological zones.

3. Low cost rapid diagnostics linked with centralized molecular hub

Most regions lack modern diagnostics laboratories to detect and identify priority pests. This idea comes to build a low cost and state of the art facilities to enhance regional and international diagnostic capabilities for key pests of regional and international trade.

It enables retention of our best brains while minimizing costly diagnostic services in overseas laboratories. For example;

Foc TR4 (*Fusarium wilt*), BBTV (*Banana bunchy top virus*), *Xylella fastidiosa*, Scale insects, Cassava Brown Streak Disease

Surveillance and monitoring

1. Development and use of digital tools for surveillance and modelling of Goss's wilt in Africa

Goss's Wilt is an emerging bacterial disease, caused by *Clavibacter nebraskensis*. It has recently been reported in South Africa and it has a potential to spread across Africa. Since maize is a staple in many African countries, the spread of this pest is likely to significantly impact on food security. Coordinated regional active surveillance through use of digital tools and risk modelling is required for early detection, preparedness and response.

2. Monitoring surveys for FCM to inform management options

FCM is a major pest affecting market access for a number of commodities (Fruits, flowers and vegetables). Monitoring surveys using modern technologies including satellite imagery, drones) are required to enable establishment of Pest free places of production, pest free areas

and ALLP to inform management options (Area wide management, systems approach) to facilitate market access.

3. Detection survey and traceability system for *Xylella* in Africa

Xylella is a pest of global concern due to its devastating impact on a number of priority commodities due to its wide host range including, olive trees, citrus, coffee, avocado and various ornamentals plants. To date, it has not been reported in Africa. Coordinated detection surveys using modern tech

Management and Control

1. Ginger diseases

Georeferencing, mapping, and developing an IPM approach for ginger disease.

Prevent the spread and establishment in other countries. Devastating ginger fungal disease (*Proxipyricalaria zingiberis*) has already been reported in Nigeria, Ghana, and Madagascar.

2. Fruit Fly

Develop an area-wide coordinated management system in Africa in Mangoes.

Fruit fly is present in most countries in Africa therefore it requires a coordinated approach among the countries to manage. Effort of one country can be affected by the neighboring countries for example in South Africa. Between 2016 and 2025, 922 interceptions related to fruit flies on mangoes have been reported in Africa

3. False codling moth (FCM)

Regional approach -Enhancement of existing IPM strategies through inclusion of digital technologies, and post-harvest treatments.

FCM is present in many countries in Africa and affects various export crops Avocados, pepper, cut flowers. 2016 -2025: 977 interceptions to the EU from Africa on vegetables related to FCM with peppers recording the highest at 618. 2020-2025: 577 interceptions for flowers, the highest being roses, 434.

4. Fusarium TR4

Development of resistant varieties to the disease Fusarium TR4

This is a challenge in exchange for banana planting material globally. There is a continuous spread of diseases. Management system for diseases, but there is no effective control

Capacity & Systems

The group target pest is *Xylella Fastidiosa*

Risk modelling of the impact of *XylellaFastidiosa* in Africa

- PRA (planting materials) and mapping
- Capacity building of expertise and diagnostic protocols and tools
- Surveillance using modern smart tools and technologies

Topic 2: Smart technologies and digital tools for identification of potential vectors and natural enemies

- Surveillance using modern smart tools and technologies
- Transmission experiment for confirmation of the bacteria in the vector(s)
- Modern analytical technologies and bioinformatics

Topic 3: Eco-friendly mitigation of *Xylella Fastidiosa* and its vectors using natural enemies and biopesticides

- Assessing the efficacy and toxicity of biopesticides against the vector(s)
- Sustainable pest management approaches against the vectors (identifying natural enemies)
- Determine the management of the vector via the natural enemies

Policy, Trade & Innovation

1. Develop or review policy and strategy on PH treatments to facilitate exports eg Establish a common user facility for treatment of FCM and fruitfly. Justification; Many countries in Africa continue to face export rejection due to presence of FCM na FF in exporte commodities
2. Conduct economic impact assessment on government inactions or regulatory impacts on export of mango from Africa to EU to inform policy decisions. This will also support the case of establishing common user facilities.
3. Develop policy and harmonization of testing, inspection and diagnostic protocols for easy access to regional and international markets. Justification: Available protocols are not standardized.
4. Policy to strengthen phytosanitary coordination mechanisms or platforms within regions. Justification: There is a weak linkage between regional blocks on coordination.
5. Policy to support development of infrastructure for regional centres of diagnostic eg Centres of excellence in all regions.
6. Policy to support capacity development for phytosanitary research in Africa. Use of AI and community of experts to support trade.

6. The programmes and the funds allocated to plant health research *(optional, if already known or if Funding survey has already been conducted)*

The list of plant health research funders in the region includes:

- TradeMark Africa
- EU through the EU desks at AU Member States
- Standards and Trade Development Facility (STDF)
- Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office (FCDO)
- Netherlands Embassy desks at AU Member States
- International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD)

Amount of funding available yearly for plant health research activities:
The funding explicit survey has not been conducted yet.

7. Coordination and collaboration *(optional, if already known or if Funding survey has already been conducted)*

- Interest for transnational coordination and collaboration in the region and globally
- Barriers to transnational coordination and collaboration in the region
- Interest in joining the global network
 - African Union Inter-African Phytosanitary Council (AU IAPSC)

- Africa Seed Traders Association
- International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA)

Formal engagements have not been able to be undertaken.

8. Supplementary information or messages originated from the consultation

The report on the international workshop 'Plant Health Research Priorities for Africa held from 19th August to 22nd August 2025 is under drafting and will include participants' comments and feedback gathered during the consultation.

7. REPORT OF THE CONSULTATIONS FOR AUSTRALIA

1. Introduction

1.1 Description of the region

Australian agriculture is a significant part of the nation's economy and exports, characterised by a wide range of commodities and a diverse range of climates and farming practices. Agriculture accounts for over half of Australia's land use therefore the sustainable management of this land is an important issue for both farm businesses and the public.

The gross value of agricultural production has increased by 34% in the past 20 years in real term from \$AUD 61.5 billion in 2004–05 to \$AUD 82.4 billion in 2023–24.

Biosecurity has played a critical role in reducing risk and shaping our nation to become one of the few countries in the world to remain free from the world's most invasive pests and diseases. While its status as an island nation has been a key factor in maintaining this position several factors, including growth in trade volumes are putting pressure on the system.

The Australian biosecurity system protects agriculture, forestry and fisheries export industries worth \$AUD 51 billion; a tourism sector worth \$AUD 50 billion; environmental assets worth more than \$AUD 5.7 trillion; and more than 1.6 million jobs.

Australia has over 60 000 kilometres of coastline offering a variety of pathways for exotic pests, weeds, and diseases to enter the country. The department screens, inspects and clears millions of mail parcels, cargo containers, plants and animals, and passengers. Using x-ray machines, pre- and post-entry quarantine and surveillance programs and detector dogs, our border security is our first line of defence for protecting our environment and social amenity.

To protect Australia, biosecurity measures are applied offshore, at the border and onshore. Investing in research and new ways of understanding and detecting risks, sharing international resources and intelligence, and continually reviewing our risk settings helps prevent the introduction, establishment and spread of pests, weeds, and diseases in Australia.

The use of surveillance and monitoring of the highest risk areas is critical along with border control activities, which focus on managing potential biosecurity threats at airports, seaports, and mail centres.

Source: <https://www.agriculture.gov.au/biosecurity-trade/policy/australia>

1.2 Description of the regional champion

The Program Director for the Plant Biosecurity Research Initiative (PBRI) is the regional champion for this project. The Program Director is a full-time role, hosted by PBRI member Research and Development Corporation, Hort Innovation, and is responsible for the coordination and prioritisation for investment in plant biosecurity research in Australia.

The PBRI was formed in 2017, recognising the critical need for aligned efforts in the plant biosecurity space. The PBRI provides a platform for organisations to create and invest in plant biosecurity research, development and extension (RD&E) activities. By pooling resources and expertise, the PBRI achieves a level of efficiency and impact that transcends individual capabilities. The reasons underlying the interest for regional and global research coordination.

The PBRI is a collaboration between Australia's seven plant RDCs and the Department of Agriculture, Fisheries and Forestry. Its specific focus is coordinating plant biosecurity research. The PBRI was formed in 2017 in response to the Intergovernmental Agreement on Biosecurity (IGAB) Review, which highlighted the lack of coordination of biosecurity research and innovation, particularly in cross-sectoral biosecurity research. At that time, the Australian biosecurity research landscape was defined as fragmented with replicated investments in biosecurity research across industries.

Since 2017, a total of \$AUD 82 million worth of R&D investments have been prioritised and commissioned for delivery through the membership base.

1.3 Reasons underlying the interest for regional and global research coordination

The PBRI is interested in minimising duplication in plant health research at a national and global level. The benefit from collaboration is well regarded by its members as a central part of its strategic goals is the coordinating and leveraging of investment in plant health research and development.

1.4 A summary of the EUPHRESKO III consultation, and the process used for the consultation

A partnership forum was on May 10, 2024, held adjacent to the biannual PBRI symposium in Cairns, Queensland. A specific agenda item was to agree to the PBRI priority areas for Australia for further plant health research as part of the Euphresco project.

Representatives from PBRI membership included:

- AgriFutures Australia
- Cotton Research and Development Corporation (CRDC)
- Forest and Wood Products Australia Limited (FWPA)
- Grains Research and Development Corporation (GRDC)
- Horticulture Innovation Australia Limited
- Sugar Research Australia (SRA) Limited
- The Australian Government Department of Agriculture, Fisheries and Forestry
- Wine Australia

PBRI partner organisations present included:

- CEBRA,
- B3, New Zealand,
- ACIAR,
- The ARC Plant Biosecurity Training Centre,
- The Plant Health Committee and
- Plant Health Australia.

Previously, a strategy workshop was held in Canberra in December 2023. This workshop was attended by PBRI members who contributed and agreed to the three strategic goals and for key focus areas, to prioritise co-investment in biosecurity research. From this workshop the strategic vision was agreed to for the 2023-2028 period which was 'PBRI is a leader in collaboration, delivering innovative and impactful biosecurity research'.

The three strategic goals developed were:

1. Identify and explore novel approaches and technologies for biosecurity

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2. Coordinate and leverage high value cross-sectoral investment in plant biosecurity innovation.
3. Drive responsive collaboration for better plant biosecurity outcomes.

To build a framework for future co-investment, the PBRI members agreed to four key focus areas for plant biosecurity research. There were:

Key Focus Area 1: Early warning and risk

Pests, diseases, and weeds may be introduced into Australia through natural dispersal patterns or by regulated and unregulated pathways. Understanding how the risk of introduction may be influenced by factors such as seasonal conditions, wind patterns, people and commodity movement is central to this.

Outcome: Industry is better prepared for the arrival of a biosecurity threat.

Key Focus Area 2: Diagnostics and surveillance

The timeliness of detection and diagnosis of pests can increase the chance of containment and subsequent eradication. Cost-effective and coordinated surveillance activities will support early detection of biosecurity threats, provide evidence for market access, and assist in targeted pest and insecticide resistance management strategies. The PBRI will continue to support the development of new platforms and technologies that rapidly identify and differentiate biosecurity threats at the border, in-field and along commodity supply chains.

Outcome: Rapid, accurate and cost-effective detection of high priority pests and diseases and early and accurate diagnosis enables a rapid response, reducing impact on production and protecting access to domestic and international markets.

Key Focus Area 3: Resilient crop protection systems

The ongoing challenge of pesticide resistance and the increasing withdrawal of chemicals that have been relied on in the past, requires RD&E to support Australian plant industries' response to pest threats and to minimise their impact on the environment. Managing pests requires control options that comply with domestic and international guidelines and managing pests in proximity to natural environments requires compliance with environmental guidelines.

Outcome: Industry is ready to respond to pest, weed and disease threats with measures that meet trading partner requirements and environmental legislation.

Key Focus Area 4: Readiness and recovery

In Australia, plant industries experience many challenges to their business operations that may affect their future sustainability. These challenges include adverse seasonal conditions, rising costs of fuel and equipment, labour shortages, trade compliance and pest and disease management. A biosecurity incursion is another challenge to a sustainable business practice with several recent experiences in Australia resulting in significant economic and social costs to growers and their communities, including varroa mite of bees, fall armyworm in maize and sweetcorn, and leaf miner in vegetables. This Key Focus Area will include investments that support industry's ability to respond to biosecurity threats and to continue their business operations post incursion. To further support industry, the PBRI will play a role in contributing to Australian biosecurity expertise and capability through investments in targeted RD&E projects, training, and activities.

Outcome: Plant industries are equipped with tools, knowledge, and expertise to identify and respond to biosecurity threats on farm.

The PBRI members develop co-investment priorities under each of the four areas on an annual basis. The goals and key focus areas were presented to broader plant health organisations at the partnership forum in May 2024 in Cairns, as part of the EUPHRESKO III regional consultations. No changes were made to the priority areas.

2. The agricultural crops

2.1 List of agricultural crops that are important for the region and the reasons

The following Research and Development Corporation members of PBRI represent their levy paying agricultural industries:

- **AgriFutures Australia** services the Research, Development and Extension (RD&E) needs of Australian rural industries. They represent the research needs for 13 thriving rural industries including rice, honeybee and pollination, ginger, tea tree oil, pasture seeds and export fodder).
- **The Cotton Research and Development Corporation (CRDC)** delivers outcomes in cotton research, development and extension (RD&E) for the Australian cotton industry.
- **Forest and Wood Products Australia (FWPA)** is an industry-owned, not-for-profit [Rural Research and Development Corporation \(RDC\)](#) for the forest and wood products industry.
- **The Grains Research and Development Corporation (GRDC)** focuses on research, development, and extension (RD&E) for twenty-five leviable grain crops in Australia. These crops include various cereals, pulses, legumes, and oilseeds.
 - Cereal Crops:
 - wheat, barley, oats, millet, and rye.
 - Pulses and Legumes:
 - peas, beans, chickpeas, lentils, and soybeans.
 - Oilseeds:
 - canola, sunflower, safflower, and linseed.
- **Hort Innovation** represents a wide range of industries within the Australian horticulture sector. This includes fruits, vegetables, nuts, nursery, cut flowers, and other plant-based industries.
 - Fruits:
 - Apples, pears, bananas, avocados, citrus, berries (like blueberries and strawberries), cherries, and more.
 - Vegetables:
 - A wide range of vegetables, including potatoes, tomatoes, and others.
 - Nuts:
 - Almonds, macadamias, chestnuts, and others.
 - Nursery and cut flowers:
 - Hort Innovation also supports the nursery and cut flower industries, including potted plants and cut flowers.
 - Other plant-based industries:
 - This includes industries like mushrooms, olives, and other specialty crops.
- **Sugar Research Australia (SRA)** is the specialist research organisation for the Australian sugarcane industry.
- **Wine Australia** invests in research, innovation and adoption to enhance global competitiveness, helping grape and wine businesses meet the challenges of tomorrow, today.

3 Important pests for the region

3.1 List of pests for which collaboration at global level is sought, including some information on this pest like geographical distribution / host range / impact

The list of pests for which collaboration at global level is sought, including some information on this pest like geographical distribution / host range / impact:

- the *Xylella* genus of bacteria and the vectors (insects) that carry it
- Khapra beetle
- Spotted wing drosophila.
- BMSB
- FAW

For more information see the National Priority Plant Pests list <https://www.agriculture.gov.au/biosecurity-trade/pests-diseases-weeds/plant/national-priority-plant-pests>

3.2 Summary of the research activities conducted in the last 5 years on the above pests

A summary of the research activities conducted in the last 5 years on the above pests:

- [The National Xylella Action Plan \(2019-2029\)](#) outlines activities to strengthen preparedness for Xylella which have been conducted during the last five years.
- [Fall armyworm research - Horticulture](#)
- [Fall armyworm outreach](#)
- [Fall armyworm - Grains](#)

4. Key drivers for collaboration

4.1 Main Plant Health issues or related practical problems of the stakeholders in the region

Climate change

The globally changing climate causes an increased frequency of extreme weather events. It is also altering the habitat, range and distribution of many pests, weeds and diseases that affect plant health, as well as increasing their ability to spread and establish in new areas. This will have flow-on effects to biosecurity management, through changes to pest dispersal pathways, pest monitoring and management, and will potentially influence trade and passenger travel patterns.

Trade

Australia's supply chains, trading partners and demand for goods continuously evolve and increase in complexity. Multiple factors influence trading patterns including regulatory requirements, climate change, technological advances and geopolitics. The increased movement of people, equipment and goods increases biosecurity risks, by providing more opportunities for pests, weeds and diseases to spread. As a trading nation, safe trade is critical to Australia's plant production sector.

Risk pathways

The risk pathways for entry of a plant pest into Australia are cargo or shipping containers, air freight, mail, international travellers and dispersal of insects, seeds or pathogens on wind currents, rain droplets or the natural movement of insects and vector borne disease. Risk

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pathways are dynamic. We therefore must have a dynamic response to minimise the risk to our plant industries.

Sustainability

Sustainability status will increasingly affect consumer purchasing decisions and trading partner requirements. Plant industries operating with sustainable business practices will be an expectation. Meeting these requirements presents competitive advantage opportunities and areas for more efficient RD&E investment. There are reputational risks if expectations are not met. Additionally, regulation of chemical use has led to the withdrawal of many chemicals from the market, and increased effort to develop pesticides with specificity to the target pest.

5. The research priorities

5.1 The medium-term (5-10 years) research priorities identified through the bottom-up approach (stakeholders' survey input from research implementers and end-users)

1. Early warning and risk – understanding climate change on risk pathways
2. Cost effective plant health diagnostics and surveillance tools
3. Pest management in a chemically limited future e.g. Global withdrawal of pesticides previously relied on in the past
4. Preparedness for biosecurity threat arrival and recovery of plant industries during and post an incursion
5. Research to assist response and industries' recovery from plant health incursions
6. Sustaining plant health capability and expertise for the future

6. The programmes and the funds allocated to plant health research *(optional, if already known or if Funding survey has already been conducted)*

The PBRI has co-invested \$82 million in plant health research with partners since 2017.

7. Coordination and collaboration *(optional, if already known or if Funding survey has already been conducted)*

PBRI is a coordinating plant health research body in Australia and committed to being part of the global network through EUPHRESKO III.

8. Supplementary information or messages originated from the consultation

None.

8. REPORT OF THE CONSULTATIONS FOR CARIBBEAN, CENTRAL AMERICA AND SOUTH AMERICA

9. Introduction

Caribbean, Central and South America is a vast region, characterized by a variety of ecosystems, farming systems and biodiversity and intense trade movement. Moreover, if we count all the countries, regions and dependent territories, we are talking about more than 50. This represents an extremely challenging scenario for plant health and for coordination activities. This work has attempted to address as many countries as possible in order to obtain outcomes that are truly representative of the Latin America and Caribbean (LAC) region.

The National Institute for Agricultural and Food Research and Technology (INIA) within the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) is the Regional Champion for LAC within the EUPHRESKO III project. Due to the linguistic and cultural nexus and their traditional scientific liaisons already established with some homologous institutions in the region, INIA-CSIC is in a good position to lead this ambitious consultation. Therefore, INIA-CSIC conducted this data collection within the framework of the EUPHRESKO III project.

Plant health in the LAC region holds significant importance due to the agricultural richness of the area and the need to protect key crops against transboundary pests and diseases. There is strong justification for coordinating research efforts both regionally and globally. On one hand, many agricultural pests and diseases do not respect national borders, making regional cooperation essential for efficiently addressing common challenges, avoiding duplication of efforts, and promoting shared solutions. On the other hand, global collaboration in plant health is crucial given emerging threats exacerbated by international trade and climate change—it is estimated that invasive species (including agricultural pests) cause global economic losses exceeding 423 billion USD annually. International coordination facilitates knowledge exchange, harmonization of phytosanitary protocols, and quicker responses to phytosanitary emergencies.

This context frames EUPHRESKO III, the third phase of an international project aimed at strengthening the global plant health research network. EUPHRESKO III seeks to improve governance, prioritize needs, and enhance collaborative tools to establish a sustainable phytosanitary network in regions such as LAC. Aligned with this objective, the regional consultation aimed to identify research priorities and opportunities for collaboration by combining a bottom-up approach (input from researchers and end-users) with a top-down approach (guidance from decision-makers and funding bodies). The consultation process included a standardized online survey—which received nearly 100 responses from the region—followed by participatory workshops (for example, during the XX Meeting of the INIA System of Ibero-America held in Montevideo, November 2024). The strategic vision proposed was to "promote sustainable and resilient practices in plant health, leveraging technological and biological advances to respond to emerging challenges." This vision and the consultation results guide the priorities outlined in the following sections.

10. The agricultural crops

In LAC, **up to ten key agricultural crops** were identified as the most important for the region, considering their food, economic, and social contributions:

- **Maize (*Zea mays*):** This is the most widely planted crop in the region, serving as a staple food and forage, and is a significant export commodity. Countries such as Mexico, Brazil,

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and Argentina rank among the world's top maize producers, reflecting the strategic importance of this cereal for food security and the regional economy.

- **Beans/Legumes (*Phaseolus* spp. and others):** Common beans and other legumes are cultivated on both small and large scales and serve as a crucial source of plant protein in the Latin American diet. Their importance lies not only in basic nutrition but also in their role in biological nitrogen fixation, which improves the sustainability of farming systems.
- **Rice (*Oryza sativa*):** Rice is a staple food in many LAC countries (especially in the Caribbean, Central America, and tropical zones of South America). It provides essential calories and economic support to thousands of producers, making it fundamental to regional food security.
- **Banana and Plantain (*Musa* spp.):** These Musaceae are of high socio-economic importance in tropical regions. Central America, the Caribbean, and tropical Andean countries depend on banana as an export product and basic food. Its significance lies in supporting smallholder farmers and being one of the leading agricultural export products.
- **Cocoa (*Theobroma cacao*):** A crop native to the Amazon, cocoa is the source of chocolate. It is a high-value export crop cultivated in many countries (Ecuador, Brazil, Peru, Dominican Republic, among others) and supports rural economies. In addition to its cultural importance, cocoa is a key export product that drives income in tropical agricultural communities.
- **Coffee (*Coffea arabica*):** Although introduced from the Old World, coffee adapted excellently to the highlands of countries such as Colombia, Brazil, Peru, and Central America. Today, Latin America produces some of the highest-quality coffees in the world and is a leader in exporting the bean. Coffee represents a vital source of foreign exchange and agricultural employment, especially in Andean and Central American communities.
- **Citrus (various *Citrus* species):** Oranges, lemons, mandarins, and other citrus fruits are economically significant in the region. Brazil leads the global production of oranges and orange juice, Mexico is a leader in lemon production, and countries like Argentina, Cuba, and Costa Rica also have notable citrus industries. Citrus fruits contribute to both internal consumption and exports, although they face sanitary threats as discussed later.
- **Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*):** Native to South America, the tomato is now a universal horticultural crop. In Latin America, it is widely produced for both fresh and processed markets, with Mexico being a major exporter to North America. Its importance lies in its economic value for horticultural farmers and its role as an essential vegetable in the regional diet.
- **Soybean (*Glycine max*):** Soybean has become one of the main commercial crops in the region, driving the agricultural boom in the Southern Cone. Brazil and Argentina, in particular, are global powerhouses in soybean production and export, jointly contributing more than half of the world's trade. Soybean is crucial as a source of vegetable oil and protein for balanced animal feeds and as a key driver in regional agrarian economies.
- **Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*):** Although not native to the region, wheat is an important cereal especially in the temperate zones of South America. Argentina, Brazil, Uruguay, and Chile produce wheat for domestic consumption and export, playing a key role in food security (for baking) and regional trade. Additionally, countries such as Mexico cultivate wheat on a smaller scale to meet flour demand.

Each of these crops is highlighted for **specific reasons of importance**: whether as pillars of food security (e.g., maize, rice, beans, wheat), as generators of significant exports and income (banana, coffee, cocoa, citrus, soybean, tomato), or as livelihoods for numerous rural

populations. Their relevance justifies focusing research efforts on protecting them from phytosanitary threats and sustainably improving their productivity.

In addition to the crops already mentioned, high-value products such as avocado and berries are of increasing relevance in some subregions. Their phytosanitary protection also requires attention in collaborative efforts.

11. Important pests for the region

Regional priority pests

Based on the consultation, a set of high-priority pests that affect multiple LAC countries was identified, whose effective management requires transnational collaboration. Among the main pests identified for the region are:

- **Fall Armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*): A polyphagous pest native to the Americas known for** devastating crops such as maize, sorghum, rice, and other cereals. Widely distributed throughout Latin America and the Caribbean, it can reduce maize yields by 20–50% if uncontrolled. Its rapid spread and pesticide resistance underline the importance of regional management strategies and knowledge sharing.
- **Whitefly (*Bemisia tabaci* and related species):** A complex of whiteflies present in tropical and subtropical areas across the region, attacking vegetables and industrial crops (e.g., cotton, beans, tomato, cassava). These pests cause severe damage by vectoring economically important viruses (particularly geminiviruses in beans and tomato). Whiteflies are considered both a regional and global priority, given their cosmopolitan distribution and devastating economic impact. Regional collaboration efforts include monitoring, biological control, and integrated pest management (IPM), as well as international coordination on resistance management, development of resistant crop varieties, and standardized diagnostic tools.
- **Thrips (various species, e.g., *Thrips palmi*, *Frankliniella* spp.):** Small insects widespread in LAC, causing direct crop damage through tissue scraping and transmitting viral diseases like tomato spotted wilt virus. Thrips have broad host ranges (vegetables, fruits, ornamentals) and are challenging to control. Regional efforts focus on shared monitoring methods and effective biological control.
- **Citrus Greening (HLB, *Huanglongbing*):** A lethal bacterial citrus disease prioritized as the highest threat in citrus-producing areas. HLB is present in Mexico, Central America, the Caribbean (e.g., Cuba, Jamaica, Belize), and parts of South America (Brazil, Paraguay). Its vector, the Asian citrus psyllid (*Diaphorina citri*), is widespread. HLB has destroyed over 100 million trees globally and caused up to 75% production losses in affected areas. Coordinated regional research focuses on early detection, vector management, and development of tolerant varieties.
- **Asian Citrus Psyllid (*Diaphorina citri*):** Prioritized together with HLB, its control is essential for managing citrus greening spread. Regional collaboration focuses on chemical and biological control methods, monitoring psyllid populations, and coordinated cross-border surveillance efforts.
- **Tomato Leafminer (*Tuta absoluta*):** Native to South America, this pest affects tomatoes and other solanaceous crops, causing severe yield reductions (over 50% without control measures). Due to its invasive status globally, sustainable control strategies (rotations of insecticides, biological control) are essential. Regional efforts include experience sharing and validation of biological control methods.

- **White Grubs (*Phyllophaga* spp.):** Soil-dwelling larvae attacking roots of crops such as maize, sugarcane, pastures, and vegetables. Present across tropical and subtropical America, their control is challenging due to the subterranean nature of infestations. Collaboration focuses on biological control methods (entomopathogenic fungi, nematodes), as grubs exhibit similar behavior regionally.
- **Aphids (various species, including *Melanaphis sacchari*):** Affect cereals, legumes, citrus, and vegetables, weakening plants and transmitting important viruses (e.g., maize streak virus). Their widespread regional distribution, recent invasions (e.g., sugarcane aphid on sorghum), and emerging pesticide resistance highlight the need for coordinated regional strategies.
- **Mites (*Tetranychus urticae* and related species):** Common pests affecting vegetables, fruits, and ornamentals, especially under warm, dry climates. Their importance stems from rapid pesticide resistance development, creating opportunities for coordinated regional biological control programs and resistance management strategies.
- **Maize Leafhopper (*Dalbulus maidis*):** Present throughout maize-producing regions in Mesoamerica, the Caribbean, and tropical South America, this vector transmits serious maize pathogens (e.g., maize lethal necrosis diseases). Its regional priority is due to its direct impact on maize yields, requiring coordinated vector management and resistance breeding programs.
- **Fruit Flies (*Anastrepha* spp., *Ceratitis capitata*):** Affecting the fruit sector, these pests remain significant, prompting active international monitoring and management programs. Although not leading the consultation list, their economic relevance justifies regional research and harmonized control programs.
- **Fungal Diseases (e.g., coffee rust, banana Black Sigatoka):** Although not topping the priority list, fungal pathogens like coffee rust and banana Black Sigatoka remain relevant. Active international research programs exist to address these pathogens, emphasizing collaboration on resistant varieties, IPM, and early detection systems.

Additional emerging threats highlighted during the XX INIA Iberoamérica Meeting include *rice hoja blanca virus* and its vector (*Tagosodes orizicolus*), *Moniliophthora* spp. affecting cacao, herbicide-resistant weeds in extensive cropping systems, the invasive giant African snail (*Lissachatina fulica*), and *Tecia solanivora* in potatoes. Their regional relevance suggests they should also be considered in future cooperation agendas.

Global priority pests

The consultation also highlighted pests, whose impact transcends regional boundaries, requiring global collaborative research efforts. These include:

- **Fall Armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*):** Already prioritized regionally, its recent global expansion (Africa, Asia, Oceania) emphasizes the importance of international collaboration. Lessons learned from Latin America's IPM strategies are invaluable globally.
- **Whitefly (*Bemisia tabaci*):** Its global relevance lies in its role as a universal plant-virus vector. Latin America's extensive experience with managing whiteflies provides important insights internationally, especially for regions facing similar challenges in Africa and Asia.
- **Citrus Greening (HLB):** Recognized as the most devastating citrus disease worldwide, HLB demands global research cooperation, including the exchange of tolerant citrus germplasm, biological control agents, and innovative management strategies (e.g., thermotherapy, experimental antimicrobials).

- ***Xylella fastidiosa***: Originally from the Americas, this pathogen now severely impacts agriculture globally, affecting crops such as citrus, grapes, olives, coffee, almonds, and ornamentals. Latin America's longstanding experience (particularly Brazil) is crucial in global efforts addressing resistant varieties, vector control, and early diagnosis.
- **Late Blight of Potato (*Phytophthora infestans*)**: A globally recognized pathogen affecting potato and tomato crops worldwide, causing major economic losses. Global collaboration includes resistance breeding, improved forecasting systems, and safer fungicide alternatives, with Latin America actively contributing knowledge and germplasm.
- **Cotton Bollworm (*Helicoverpa armigera*)**: Recently introduced to South America, this Old World pest attacks multiple crops including cotton, maize, and legumes. Its rapid global spread necessitates coordinated monitoring, research, and sustainable control strategies.
- **Tomato Leafminer (*Tuta absoluta*)**: Originating from Latin America, this pest has expanded to the Mediterranean, Africa, and Asia. LAC expertise on biological control, integrated pest management, and pesticide resistance management contributes significantly to global pest management initiatives.
- **Fusarium Tropical Race 4 (R4T, *Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. cubense*)**: Threatening the global banana industry, this pathogen was recently detected in Latin America. Collaborative international efforts aim at developing resistant varieties, effective containment measures, and soil disinfection strategies.
- **Potato Psyllid (*Bactericera cockerelli*)**: Native to North America and expanding southward, this pest is a significant threat due to its role in transmitting zebra chip disease. International cooperation focuses on diagnostics, vector management, and preventing its spread to key potato production zones in the Andes.
- **Migratory Locusts (*Schistocerca* spp.)**: Species such as the Central and South American locusts, historically managed regionally, have become global research priorities due to recent outbreaks and global lessons learned, emphasizing surveillance, satellite monitoring, and biological control technologies.
- **Other Emerging or Context-Specific Pests**: Additional pests such as specific fruit flies, forest insects, and fungal diseases also merit global attention through ongoing international research initiatives, although less frequently highlighted.

Summary of recent research (last 5 years):

In recent years, the LAC scientific community has actively mobilized research to address the prioritized pests, emphasizing transnational collaboration and integrated approaches:

- **Fall Armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*)**: Multiple LAC countries have led integrated pest management (IPM) trials combining biopesticides (such as specific nucleopolyhedroviruses), Bt maize varieties, and agroecological practices. Regional networks have been established for monitoring resistance to Bt maize and sharing effective biological control agents, contributing globally relevant knowledge.
- **Whitefly (*Bemisia tabaci*)**: Intensive research has focused on population dynamics under climate change, coordinated releases of parasitoids (*Encarsia* spp.) across multiple countries, and molecular characterization of different biotypes. These activities laid groundwork for regional integrated pest management and strengthened international collaborations, especially beneficial for other tropical regions globally.

- **HLB and Asian Citrus Psyllid (*Diaphorina citri*):** Countries such as Mexico, Brazil, and Cuba have been highly active, establishing a Latin American diagnostic network that standardizes early detection protocols for citrus greening. Research includes evaluating resistant rootstocks, experimental antimicrobials, and vector management. Findings have been globally disseminated, reflecting the region's significant international contribution.
- **Tomato Leafminer (*Tuta absoluta*):** Collaborative efforts have included insecticide rotation studies, use of pheromones for mating disruption, and introduction of native biological control agents (*Necremnus* spp., *Trichogramma*). Latin America has significantly contributed strains of natural enemies now utilized internationally, particularly in Europe and Africa, enhancing global pest management strategies.
- **Fusarium R4T in banana:** Following recent detections in Colombia and Peru, the region rapidly mobilized to characterize strains genetically, evaluate epidemiological dynamics, and test resistant banana varieties. National institutes partnered with global banana initiatives, demonstrating a strong regional commitment to confronting this global threat.
- **Cross-cutting technologies:** The region has actively developed and adopted innovative solutions applicable to multiple pests, such as portable diagnostic tools (real-time PCR/LAMP assays for field diagnosis of quarantine pathogens), AI-driven early warning systems (predictive models for pest outbreaks), and low-risk agrochemical alternatives (biopesticides and botanical extracts). These technologies have been shared and validated regionally, reflecting a proactive stance toward innovation.

12. Key drivers for collaboration

The consultation gathered the main **plant health issues and challenges** perceived by various stakeholders in the regional phytosanitary system, which drive the need for collaboration. Below is a synthesis of these drivers by actor type:

- **Policy makers:** Agricultural and sanitary policy makers in the region point to the growing threat of exotic and emerging pests, driven by globalization and climate change. They are concerned about the impact of these pests on food security and agricultural exports (e.g., market loss due to quarantine pests). They also face pressure to update regulatory frameworks – for example, stricter biosecurity standards at borders and bans on highly toxic pesticides – which require scientific evidence. Policy makers recognize that, individually, countries have limited capacities to tackle these challenges, so they see regional coordination as a way to strengthen phytosanitary surveillance, harmonize protocols (facilitating safe trade), and optimize resources. A frequently cited issue is the duplication of efforts: without collaboration, different countries invest in similar research independently. Therefore, policy makers are interested in driving joint R&D agendas to avoid redundancy and maximize impact. In short, they see collaboration as a means to protect national agricultural economies from devastating pest outbreaks and to meet international commitments (such as the International Plant Protection Convention), which are difficult to achieve without a multinational approach.
- **Research funders:** Agencies and funding sources (ministries of science/technology, international programs, development banks) identify insufficient financial resources and fragmented investments in plant health research as a central problem. Funders highlight that by joining forces, synergies can be harnessed and multinational projects of greater scope can be co-funded beyond the limits of a single country's budget. A practical issue mentioned is the lack of clearly defined regional priorities that guide investments; sometimes funds are dispersed over multiple topics without critical mass. Therefore, funders value consultations like this, which help prioritize common needs for investment.

They also stress the importance of building sustainable capacities: some countries have significant weaknesses (lack of infrastructure, specialized personnel) – for regional funders, addressing this requires cooperation (e.g., regional training programs, sharing reference laboratories).

- **Research organizations (institutes, universities):** From an institutional level, researchers reported several practical challenges that hinder their work in plant health, many of which could be alleviated through collaboration. A common challenge is the lack of adequate resources – limited budgets, insufficient modern equipment, and inadequate infrastructure (biosafety labs, greenhouses) – which restrict research capacity and technological response. They also mention a shortage of specialized human resources: many institutions face a lack of entomologists, phytopathologists, or biotechnologists, or have technical staff who require further training. Organizations perceive the need to update methods and skills – for example, incorporating molecular biology, bioinformatics, or climate modeling techniques to study emerging pests – but find barriers to accessing these methodologies on their own. They also highlight the fragmentation of knowledge: each institution tends to work in isolation on locally affecting pests, sometimes duplicating studies without sharing results, which delays scientific progress and practical application. Another noted challenge is the lack of long-term programs – many projects are short-term and lack follow-up, partly due to uncertain annual funding. In this context, research organizations see collaboration as a way to share burdens and benefits: for instance, developing multinational projects where each institution contributes its strengths (some cultivate pathogens for study, others perform genetic analyses) to achieve more robust results. Collaborating also enables access to international funds that require regional consortia. Finally, collaboration offers access to comparative data (e.g., the same pest in different climates), enriching research. Overall, research institutions drive coordination because it can help overcome internal resource limitations, improve scientific capacities, and accelerate technological solutions in plant health.
- **Agricultural industry (producers, companies):** From the perspective of the production sector and agrochemical companies, challenges translate into economic losses and commercial risks associated with pests and diseases. A primary issue mentioned is the high incidence of pests that reduce yields and crop quality, thereby increasing production costs (due to more frequent pesticide applications, etc.). For example, fruit producers cite difficulties in controlling quarantine pests that, if unmanaged, can shut down export markets. Pesticide resistance is another concern: the industry has observed the failure of previously effective chemical products (due to overuse), leaving them without adequate control tools. Additionally, the lack of sustainable alternatives worries the agricultural industry, given the growing scrutiny over chemical residues in food and the environment; they see the need for new technologies (biological control, resistant varieties) that are not yet locally available. There is also recognition that emerging pests can strike without warning (e.g., a new disease race), for which many producers are unprepared. In this sense, the industry sees regional collaboration as a way to better anticipate and manage phytosanitary risks through shared alert systems, joint solution development (e.g., a biocontrol company could work with several countries to introduce a beneficial parasitoid common to all), and harmonizing sanitary measures to facilitate trade. They believe that a pest outbreak in a neighboring country can quickly affect them as well, so a preventive regional approach is highly valued.
- **Farmers and Foresters (Local Producers):** At the field level, producers reported very concrete problems: on one hand, recurrent damage from endemic pests (e.g., annual outbreaks of defoliating caterpillars, foliar diseases in crops), against which farmers sometimes lack sufficient technical advice or access to appropriate inputs. On the other hand, many expressed uncertainty regarding new pests that have recently appeared in their areas – illustrating the effects of climate change and pest mobility. A farmer may face

a previously unknown pest from one year to the next, for which there is little control information available. Associated with this is the lack of training: small producers often are unaware of integrated pest management methods and depend almost entirely on chemical pesticides (which are not always effective). This leads to health and environmental problems due to improper agrochemical use. Farmers stress the need for resistant crop varieties or those more tolerant to pests, especially basic staples (maize, bean, cassava, etc.), since they currently suffer significant losses. In agroforestry or forestry systems, producers note outbreaks of forest pests (beetles, defoliators) that threaten forests and plantations and for which they have no solutions. These issues suggest that farmers and foresters need greater technical support and knowledge. Regional collaboration can indirectly benefit them by generating more effective and locally adapted technologies (instead of imported solutions that may not work as well). For example, the development of biopesticides from native pest pathogens or participatory breeding programs are driven by the desire to resolve common field problems. Moreover, the voice of the farmers emphasizes the urgency of extension and technology transfer: a problem in the region is the disconnect between research and the end-user. Addressing this requires collaboration among institutions across countries to share successful rural extension strategies in plant health.

- **Other stakeholders (civil society, international organizations):** Other groups also provided input. Consumers and environmental NGOs express concern over the intensive use of pesticides and their residues in food and ecosystems. They see the need for more ecological management methods – which drives research on biological control, agroecology, and integrated management. International organizations (FAO, IICA, etc.) note that the disparity in phytosanitary capacities among countries is an obstacle; some have robust surveillance systems while others are vulnerable. Therefore, they promote collaboration to raise the overall level of plant health in the region (e.g., through regional training programs). In the academic realm, scientists mention the lack of information exchange as a barrier – internal reports and inaccessible data hinder knowledge sharing. They recommend open knowledge networks. Finally, a cross-cutting factor is climate change – not only as a cause of new pests but also as an element of uncertainty that necessitates joint research efforts to predict and mitigate its effects on crop health.

Capacity building needs:

A recurring theme across all levels was the need to strengthen technical and human capacities to address phytosanitary challenges. Many survey participants specifically identified the following needs:

- **Specialized technical training:** More training programs in pest and disease diagnosis, inspection methods, integrated management, and biosecurity are needed. Several countries lack sufficient personnel with up-to-date training in these areas. Regional workshops, expert exchanges, and practical courses were requested.
- **Infrastructure and Equipment:** Numerous institutions indicated the need to improve or acquire laboratory equipment (biosafety cabinets, PCR machines, containment greenhouses, digital monitoring systems). The lack of reference laboratories in certain subregions is problematic – for example, few labs have the capacity to identify quarantine viruses or pests. A collaborative strategy would be to share facilities or create regional diagnostic centers.
- **Sustained financial resources:** Scarce funding was mentioned as a limiting factor for hiring personnel, maintaining surveillance programs, and carrying out applied research. There is a need for dedicated funds for plant health research and for regional mechanisms

that pool resources (e.g., international competitive grants that require partnerships). Strengthening the capacity to formulate projects and attract funding is equally important.

- **Standardized methods and processes:** Several respondents noted the need for **common protocols** and the transfer of methodologies. For example, standardizing pesticide resistance testing methods or quarantine protocols for invasive pests so that all countries can implement them properly. Technical assistance from more advanced countries in adopting such methods is considered essential.
- **Information Management and Alert Systems:** Strengthening capacities in data management, modeling, and forecasting was another area highlighted. This includes training in GIS (geographic information systems) for mapping pests, using shared digital platforms for reporting and early alerts, and risk analysis. Few countries currently have dedicated units to model pest spread or evaluate pest risks; creating these competencies regionally would help anticipate outbreaks.
- **Biological and genetic resources:** The need to have banks of biological control agents (entomopathogens, parasitoids, antagonists) and resistant germplasm was emphasized. Some countries lack *insectary facilities* for producing natural enemies or breeding programs focused on resistance. Support is required to develop these capacities, which can then be shared (e.g., a regional biocontrol production laboratory serving several countries).
- **Coordination and Communication:** Paradoxically, part of the capacity to develop is how to collaborate effectively. Several participants expressed the need to improve in managing international projects, mastering technical English for global communication, and using scientific communication tools. This meta-capacity indicates that before effective collaboration, institutions must strengthen their interaction and coordination skills.

In summary, the key drivers for regional collaboration span from shared phytosanitary threats that no country can solve alone to structural weaknesses (in resources and training) that could be more easily addressed together. All stakeholders – from authorities to farmers – recognize challenges that transcend national borders, creating fertile ground for collaborative research and management initiatives. The identification of common capacity building needs reinforces the logic of collaboration: by joining forces, the region can elevate its technical and scientific readiness to protect plant health more effectively and equitably.

13. The research priorities

The regional consultation used two complementary approaches to identify mid-term (5–10 years) research priorities in plant health: a bottom-up approach, gathering insights from researchers and end-users (technicians, producers), and a top-down approach, with inputs from decision makers and funders. Below are the priorities resulting from each approach, followed by the agreed common research priorities and some suggested research topics for 2025 and 2026.

Bottom-up research priorities (5–10 years):

Through the survey, plant health researchers and professionals in the region indicated the thematic areas they consider most relevant for mid-term research. Among the most frequently mentioned priorities are:

- **Biological control and bioinputs:** The development and implementation of **biological control methods** was the most recurrent priority among respondents. There is an emphasis on researching native natural enemies (predators, parasitoids, entomopathogenic fungi) and bioinputs derived from microorganisms or plant extracts to

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manage the main pests. This preference reflects an interest in reducing dependency on chemical pesticides, aligned with more sustainable practices. Concrete examples include mass production of parasitoids for whitefly control, formulation of virus-based bioinsecticides for fall armyworm, and biofungicides against soil pathogens.

- **Integrated Pest Management (IPM) and agroecological approaches:** Integrating multiple tactics in production systems was another key priority. Many participants proposed deepening **IPM strategies** adapted to different crops, combining biological control, cultural practices (crop rotation, living barriers), resistant varieties, and the rational use of chemicals. Agroecological pest management, highlighting polycultures, trap crops, and beneficial associations, was also noted. This priority shows a trend toward holistic and preventive approaches in plant health.
- **Impact of climate change on pests and diseases:** Concerns about how **climate change** will alter pest epidemiology in LAC were frequently mentioned. Investigating predictive models and distribution studies of pests under future climate scenarios is prioritized. Identifying new threats emerging due to climate change (e.g., pests expanding their range into previously cooler areas, altered life cycles) is critical. This priority also includes exploring adaptation practices (e.g., more stress-tolerant crop varieties).
- **Emerging/exotic pests and pathogens:** There was strong consensus to allocate research toward emerging pests – whether newly introduced species or new pathogen strains detected locally – as well as exotic pests with a high risk of entry. The scientific community wants to proactively study emerging threats by understanding their biology to contain their spread. This bottom-up priority reflects the need for proactive monitoring and research of new pests.
- **Diagnosis and early detection:** Many responses highlighted the need to improve diagnostic techniques for pests and pathogens – developing faster, more sensitive, and field-adapted methods. This includes research on portable molecular detection kits (real-time PCR, LAMP), remote sensors for crop stress, and smart trap systems connected to networks. Several participants explicitly mentioned “strengthening early diagnosis and monitoring” as a priority, underscoring the need to identify pests early and facilitate control measures. Creating early warning systems supported by data science is linked to this priority.
- **Genetic improvement and resistance:** The development of crop varieties resistant or tolerant to pests and diseases was noted as a key priority, especially for critical crops (bananas resistant to *Fusarium R4T*, citrus tolerant to HLB, maize resistant to multiple insects, beans resistant to viruses, etc.). There is an emphasis on combining conventional breeding and biotechnology (including modern biotechnological methods such as CRISPR/Cas gene editing) for resistance. Research in this area is vital for providing long-lasting, broadly effective solutions against biotic threats.
- **Advanced technologies (digital, ai, automation):** Some respondents highlighted the importance of incorporating cutting-edge technologies in plant health research. This covers the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning for pest recognition (e.g., mobile applications that identify pests from images), sensors and IoT for continuous field monitoring (such as insect counts in traps and environmental conditions predisposing diseases), drones for aerial surveillance, and targeted application. The priority is to adapt and develop these technologies in local contexts to improve phytosanitary management.
- **Epidemiological and population dynamics studies:** To underpin better management strategies, deepening research into the biology and ecology of priority pests was proposed. Understanding life cycles, refuges, dispersal, genetic variability, and interactions with natural enemies in various LAC environments is essential. For example, studying the population genetics of migratory pests (locusts) or identifying different biotypes of whitefly

that may require tailored tactics is prioritized. This line of research provides essential knowledge to support control measures.

- **Integrated resistance management for pesticides and transgenic technologies:** Given the growing concern over loss of efficacy of chemical and transgenic tools, this research line should explore resistance mechanisms in pest populations, design rotation strategies, and develop integrated management approaches to prolong the durability of current technologies while minimizing harm to beneficial organisms and pollinators.
- **Plant health in sustainable agricultural systems:** Finally, there emerged a vision to integrate plant health into a broader sustainability context. Researching the interaction between agricultural practices and pest incidence (for instance, how crop diversification, soil health, or surrounding landscapes affect pest pressure) aligns with holistic “One Health” or integrated landscape management approaches. It is also suggested to investigate the socio-economic impact of pests and control measures to guide public policies and technology adoption by farmers.

Overall, the bottom-up priorities reflect a strong emphasis on sustainable innovation, anticipation of threats, and strengthening technical capacities. Topics such as biological control, IPM, early diagnosis, climate change adaptation, and genetic improvement are highlighted as areas where the regional technical community sees the most need for research in the next decade.

Top-Down Research Priorities (5–10 years):

In parallel, priorities were considered from the perspective of regional authorities and funding entities to complement the bottom-up approach. Although direct participation from decision makers was limited in the current consultation, inputs from national policies and regional strategic plans in plant health were incorporated. Among the top-down priorities are:

- **Food security against cross-border pests:** Decision makers prioritize research that safeguards staple crops against emerging threats. In this line, the need for regional surveillance systems and risk analysis studies for quarantine pests affecting essential food production is highlighted. For example, developing detection and contingency methods for pests like wheat rust race UG99 or high-impact pests in stored grains is considered strategically critical.
- **Scientific support for international trade in plant health:** A priority for governmental agencies is to support research that underpins compliance with international phytosanitary standards and facilitates market access. This includes studies on pest status (distribution, confirmed absence) and the efficacy of quarantine treatments (cold, irradiation, alternative fumigants) to demonstrate the phytosanitary safety of products. Research on more efficient port inspection methods and measures to prevent pest dissemination through trade is promoted.
- **Strengthening national capacities (scientific and regulatory):** Funders and authorities prioritize meta-research that evaluates and strengthens national capacities in plant health. This involves creating laboratory networks and standardizing diagnostic protocols, as well as studies to identify gaps in human resources and propose training plans. Essentially, top-down research is aimed at public policy – for example, cost-benefit analyses of implementing large-scale biological control programs or modeling invasion scenarios and their economic impacts to support investment decisions.
- **Innovation in biosecurity and regulatory biotechnology:** With evolving technologies (gene editing, RNA interference, etc.), decision makers consider it important to research their applicability and regulation in plant health. Priorities here include trials of

biotechnologically improved varieties for pest resistance under local conditions and the development of safe bioinsecticides, evaluating both efficacy and environmental aspects. Preparing for the incorporation of innovations requires research in biosecurity, which is being promoted at the strategic level.

- **Pests impacting forest and environmental economies:** Unlike the bottom-up focus on agricultural crops, decision makers also prioritize pests affecting natural resources and forest economies. Examples include research into controlling the Central American locust, which periodically affects large agricultural and pastoral regions, or the bark borer in pine forests in Mesoamerica. These pests, though not food-related, have serious socio-economic implications (loss of jobs, environmental degradation), prompting governments to support research for management and restoration plans.
- **Climate change and plant health in public policy:** While the bottom-up approach highlighted scientific aspects, top-down priorities emphasize integrating plant health into the climate change agenda. This implies research on ecosystem-based adaptation, such as restoring landscapes to reduce pest outbreaks (e.g., the black palm weevil affecting coconuts under climate stress) or implementing climate-based alert systems. Studies on emissions and the carbon footprint of various plant health strategies (e.g., reduced chemical applications) are also included to align plant health with climate goals.
- **Sustainability and reduction of hazardous pesticides:** In line with international policies (such as the Stockholm Convention or FAO guidelines), top-down research prioritizes R&D aimed at alternatives to highly hazardous pesticides (HHPs). Projects that develop and validate IPM practices that reduce chemical usage are supported by public funds and regional banks. The political focus is on addressing growing environmental and food safety demands, so research that yields concrete recommendations for replacing toxic molecules and managing resistance is considered crucial.
- **Economics and sociology of plant health:** Another strategic priority is to understand the economic and social factors that facilitate or hinder the adoption of plant health innovations by farmers. Research on extension systems, economic incentives for preventive practices, and the social impact of pest outbreaks (employment, rural migration) is valued at a macro level. This drives integrated policies – emphasizing not only available technology but also ensuring that it reaches the producer and is used correctly. Funders advocate for interdisciplinary studies combining plant health with social sciences to design effective interventions.
- **Sustainability and extension in plant health:** Although not a “classic research” area, both groups emphasized that without effective technology transfer, innovation cannot reach the field. Thus, projects that integrate a research-action component with training and extension for technicians and farmers, participatory validation of technologies, and scaling of successful practices are prioritized. The effectiveness of any innovation will depend on this aspect, and it is recognized as critical by both approaches.

Overall, the top-down priorities tend to focus on ensuring large-scale phytosanitary stability and supporting national and regional development goals. They emphasize risk prevention (exotic pests, safe trade), regulated and secure innovation, and building robust phytosanitary systems. These priorities complement the bottom-up approach by adding economic, public policy, and institutional capacity considerations.

Common agreed priorities:

When harmonizing both approaches, there is significant convergence on several themes, which emerge as the common research priorities for the region:

- **Sustainable management of key pests via IPM and biological control:** Both the grassroots scientific community and higher-level decision makers agree on promoting research that reduces chemical dependency and provides sustainable solutions. The shared priority is to develop integrated management packages (including biological, cultural, genetic, and rational chemical use) for the pests with the greatest regional impact (e.g., fall armyworm, whitefly, HLB, Fusarium in banana, etc.). This theme reconciles the bottom-up emphasis on technical innovation with the top-down focus on sustainability and environmental standards.
- **Strengthening surveillance and early diagnosis of emerging pests:** There is unanimous agreement on the need for improved diagnostic methods and efficient monitoring systems. The common priority is to research and establish rapid detection tools, regional monitoring networks, and harmonized protocols for emerging pests. This covers both the technical aspect (developing kits, predictive models) and the institutional aspect (alert networks). The threat of cross-border pests requires a unified scientific response recognized by both approaches.
- **Climate change and plant health:** This issue figures in both approaches – scientists want to understand it, and decision makers want to incorporate it into policy. Therefore, jointly, research on *the impacts of climate change on pests* and adaptation strategies in the region’s agricultural systems is prioritized. Collaborative studies (e.g., observation networks across countries) are proposed to monitor how climate variability alters pest phenology and to test adaptive practices.
- **Genetic improvement for pest resistance:** All agree that developing resistant cultivars is a cost-effective and high-impact solution. Thus, a common priority is research in genetic improvement (both conventional and biotechnological) focused on resistance/tolerance to the main pests and diseases. This involves exploring native resistant germplasm and gene editing approaches, with the bottom-up technical expertise and top-down regulatory support converging.
- **Safe use and reduction of hazardous pesticides:** Both groups concur on the need to mitigate problems associated with pesticides (resistance, residues, health issues). Consequently, it is a common priority to research rotations and mixtures that prevent resistance, evaluate biopesticides as substitutes for highly dangerous chemicals, and develop integrated resistance management strategies. This aligns with international frameworks and is seen as essential by both approaches.
- **Training and extension in plant health:** Although it may not sound like “classic research,” both sides emphasized that without effective technology transfer, innovation does not reach the field. Therefore, it is agreed to prioritize projects that integrate a research-action component with training for technicians and farmers, participatory validation of technologies, and scaling of successful practices. This aspect is vital for ensuring that any innovation has a tangible impact.

Overall, there were no major contradictions between the bottom-up and top-down approaches, only differences in emphasis. The areas where one group focused more (e.g., social aspects in top-down vs. entomological details in bottom-up) complement each other. The process of harmonization enriched the initial priorities, resulting in a balanced list addressing both new technology generation and its practical application in policy. These common priorities will guide the regional research agenda in plant health and serve as the basis for collaborative, multinational initiatives in the coming years.

Proposed research topics for 2025–2026

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Based on the outcomes of the regional consultation, integrating inputs from researchers, technical experts, producers, and decision-makers, four key research topics have been identified for collaborative actions in LAC:

1. Integrated Pest Management (IPM) for emerging agricultural threats

- **Pests:** New invasive pests in the region, notably *Tuta absoluta* and *Spodoptera frugiperda*.
- **Commodities:** Economically critical crops, particularly maize, soybean, tomatoes, and coffee.
- **Activities:** Developing biocontrol agents, pest monitoring tools, insecticide resistance management strategies, and promoting sustainable IPM and agroecological practices.
- **Expected outcomes:** Decreased dependence on chemical pesticides, improved crop resilience, reduction in pest-related economic losses, and strengthened regional IPM frameworks.

Research Topic 2: Strengthening resilience against climate-driven pest risks

- **Pests:** Climate-sensitive pests like aphids, whiteflies, mites, and migratory locusts, whose impact is intensified by climate variability.
- **Commodities:** Key food security crops such as fruits, vegetables (e.g., tomatoes, bananas), and staple cereals.
- **Activities:** Establishing pest-monitoring and early-warning networks, predictive modeling using climate data, and regional capacity-building workshops.
- **Expected outcomes:** Improved forecasting and preparedness for climate-driven pest threats, enhanced regional cooperation, and adaptive management strategies for resilience against climate risks.

Research topic 3: Enhancing biological control in sustainable agriculture

- **Pests:** Pests effectively managed through biological control methods, including aphids, thrips, whiteflies, mites, and soil pests like nematodes and white grubs.
- **Commodities:** High-value crops, notably avocados, citrus fruits, bananas, tomatoes, and sugarcane.
- **Activities:** Isolation, production, and upscaling of effective biocontrol agents; expanding use of biopesticides; farmer training on biological control practices.
- **Expected outcomes:** Greater adoption of biological pest control, reduced environmental impacts, improved agricultural productivity, and strengthened regional expertise in sustainable pest management.

Research topic 4: Strengthening capacity for phytosanitary governance in LAC

- **Pests:** Transboundary invasive threats and regional priority pests, including *Helicoverpa armigera*, *Bemisia tabaci*, *Xylella fastidiosa*, Fusarium Tropical Race 4, and others requiring coordinated governance.
- **Commodities:** Essential staples and economically critical crops, such as maize, rice, beans, wheat, citrus, bananas, and vegetables.
- **Activities:** Regional training programs for policymakers, developing harmonized pest management protocols, coordinated surveillance networks, and stakeholder workshops.
- **Expected outcomes:** Improved governance frameworks for phytosanitary management, harmonized regional pest control measures, strengthened emergency response capabilities, and enhanced collaboration across LAC countries.

During the consultation event, the directors of participating institutes signed the European Soil Mission Manifesto, aligning their institutions with the vision that healthy soils are essential for sustainable plant health, food production, and ecosystem services.

14. The programmes and the funds allocated to plant health research

To implement the identified research priorities, it is essential to understand the current funding landscape supporting plant health initiatives in the region.

Within the scope of the conducted consultation, a specific survey was launched regarding funding sources for plant health research in LAC. However, the survey only garnered five responses, making it impossible to draw representative conclusions about the region's financial ecosystem. Despite this limitation, a general overview of the funding landscape for plant health research in LAC is provided based on public information and analysis of key actors:

- **National Agricultural Research Institutes (“INIAs”) and Ministries of Agriculture:** In most countries, INIAs (e.g., INTA in Argentina, Embrapa in Brazil, INIFAP in Mexico, INIA in Peru/Uruguay/Chile, IDIAP in Panama, etc.) are central to agricultural research, including plant health. These institutions are primarily funded by national governments through public budgets. Although the exact figures vary greatly, typically between 5% and 15% of an INIA's total budget is allocated to plant health (pathology, entomology, weeds, etc.). For instance, Embrapa (Brazil) annually invests tens of millions of dollars in phytosanitary projects across its thematic units; INTA (Argentina) and INIFAP (Mexico) each dedicate several million dollars annually to pest and disease research in their priority crops. Ministries of Agriculture sometimes channel specific funds through national programs (e.g., National Rust Combat Program with dedicated annual budgets). Generally, most applied plant health research is supported by these national public funds, although the exact amount depends on each country's economy.
- **National Science and Technology Councils/Agencies:** Many countries have agencies such as CONACYT (Mexico), CONICET (Argentina), CNPq (Brazil), SENACYT (Panama), etc., funding research projects through competitive calls. Collectively, these agencies have supported numerous phytosanitary research projects at universities and public centres. Although there isn't an exclusive budget line for "plant health," they annually allocate considerable resources to projects in plant biotechnology, crop protection, and related fields. For example, Mexico's SAGARPA-CONACYT Sector Fund previously co-funded several phytosanitary projects worth millions of Mexican pesos. These agencies contribute primarily to basic and frontier research, complementing the applied research performed by INIAs.
- **Regional collaborative funds:** A prominent actor is FONTAGRO (Regional Fund for Agricultural Technology), a cooperative funding mechanism supported by LAC countries and the Inter-American Development Bank (IDB). FONTAGRO finances multinational agricultural innovation projects, several of which focus on plant health (e.g., regional projects on banana sigatoka management and biological pest control in rice). Typically, FONTAGRO issues annual or biannual calls with funding ranging from USD 1 to 2 million per call, distributed across various projects (each receiving approximately USD 300,000-500,000 for 2-3 years). Recently, about 20-30% of FONTAGRO projects have related to plant health. For example, in 2022-2023, it co-funded projects on citrus disease surveillance and bio pesticides for horticulture. Since its inception, FONTAGRO has invested over USD 100 million in agricultural R&D in the region, with a significant portion dedicated to plant health.

- **Multilateral banks and international programs:** The World Bank, Inter-American Development Bank (IDB), and other international financiers sometimes support plant health components within broader agricultural development loans or grants. For example, productivity enhancement projects may include pest management subcomponents with allocated budgets. The Global Food Security Fund may also direct funding toward research on pests threatening staple crops. Similarly, the Inter-American Institute for Cooperation on Agriculture (IICA) provides technical cooperation and occasionally seed funding for regional plant health initiatives (e.g., in 2018, IICA coordinated a regional HLB surveillance project with approximately USD 500,000 funded by USDA). Although these funds are not consistently annual, they represent significant one-time investments.
- **International organizations and bilateral cooperation:** The FAO and other UN organizations provide funding for technical assistance and applied research in specific cases (e.g., Integrated Pest Management projects for smallholder farmers funded through UTF). Likewise, cooperation from developed countries—through agencies like USAID (U.S.), AECID (Spanish Cooperation), German GIZ, Japanese JICA—has financed plant health research/demonstration projects in the region. For example, USAID supported moniliasis control activities in cocoa in Central America; AECID funded diagnostic laboratory networks in the Andean Community. Although variable, collectively, these sources represent millions of dollars invested over the past decade in plant health in LAC.
- **Private sector and industry:** Although lesser in research volume (since the private sector typically focuses on known commercial solutions), there are instances of agricultural companies or private foundations financing research. For example, citrus grower associations in Brazil and Mexico have co-funded university research on HLB. Large banana companies support anti-Fusarium programs. Multinational phytosanitary companies establish agreements with local institutes for testing bio-products or new molecules. While not precisely quantified, private contributions can be significant in export crops; in Costa Rica, pineapple and banana producers sometimes allocate funds to research emerging pests affecting them directly. Nevertheless, private funding usually focuses more on field trials or validations than foundational research.

15. Coordination and collaboration

Stakeholders across LAC expressed **high interest in transnational coordination and collaboration** on plant health research. In the Montevideo meeting, participants emphasized that many plant pest and disease challenges are shared across countries, requiring joint efforts to address them. This sentiment was echoed in the regional stakeholder survey, where nearly all respondents rated **international collaboration as “very important” or “essential”** for advancing plant health.

There is enthusiasm not only for **intra-regional cooperation within LAC**, but also for engaging with **global networks**, reflecting a recognition that plant health threats **do not respect borders** and must be met with cooperative research and information exchangers noted that greater collaboration would help avoid duplicated efforts, leverage diverse expertise, and improve the region’s capacity to manage emerging pests and diseases in alignment with global best practices.

The **Funding Survey was launched to assess financial priorities and challenges for phytosanitary research in LAC**, but it received **only five responses**. Due to this **low participation rate**, the survey results were **insufficient to extract meaningful conclusions** regarding funding needs and opportunities for collaboration. This limited response underscores a recurring challenge in regional coordination—namely, the difficulty in obtaining

structured feedback from funding institutions, which may reflect a **lack of centralized funding mechanisms** or **institutional barriers to engaging in regional discussions**.

Moreover, the consultation was conducted under the umbrella of the INIA Ibero-America network, a platform established in 2002 that brings together 21 national agricultural research institutes. This structure provides a strong institutional base for sustained phytosanitary collaboration in the region.

Key barriers to effective collaboration in LAC

Despite the clear interest, stakeholders identified several **barriers hindering effective collaboration** among LAC countries. Both survey responses and Montevideo discussions highlighted challenges in four main areas:

- **Financial constraints: limited funding** for joint research projects, exchange visits, and sustained networks was the most frequently cited obstacle. Many countries struggle to allocate resources for collaborative initiatives, making it difficult to maintain long-term partnerships or conduct multi-country research trials. Without dedicated funds or co-financing mechanisms, even highly motivated teams face hurdles in working together across borders.
- **Regulatory and policy differences: Inconsistent or cumbersome regulations** among countries pose a significant challenge. Participants pointed to **phytosanitary rules, material transfer agreements, and permitting processes** that vary by country. These differences can slow down or even block the exchange of germplasm, biological samples, or data. Aligning policies or establishing regional agreements was seen as crucial to facilitate smoother collaboration. Regulatory heterogeneity in the region often means researchers must navigate complex bureaucratic requirements in each country, hampering timely cooperative research.
- **Logistical challenges:** Practical issues of **distance, infrastructure, and language** create additional barriers. Travel logistics (and associated costs) for regional meetings or fieldwork can be difficult, especially for geographically distant partners or island states in the Caribbean. Limitations in connectivity and laboratory infrastructure disparities make it hard to share real-time data or research results. Language differences (Spanish, Portuguese, English, and French in the region) can also complicate communication and knowledge sharing, though stakeholders are generally willing to overcome them with translation and bilingual materials. Additionally, the **lack of a centralized platform** for communication means networking often happens ad-hoc rather than through an established channel.
- **Institutional and administrative hurdles:** Stakeholders noted that **institutional frameworks for collaboration are weak or absent** in many cases. There is no permanent regional mechanism dedicated to coordinating phytosanitary research, leading to fragmentation. **Bureaucratic procedures** (e.g. lengthy approval processes for MOUs or international agreements) delay the start of joint projects. Furthermore, differences in institutional priorities or research agendas can make alignment tricky, as not all countries prioritize the same pests or issues. Limited institutional support (in terms of staff time or recognition for international work) was also cited as a barrier, with some respondents explaining that their organizations focus on national mandates unless external programs incentivize collaboration.

These barriers underscore the **challenges LAC countries face in turning interest into action**. Notably, **funding and regulatory issues were the top concerns** across both the survey data and the Montevideo event discussions, followed by logistical and institutional challenges. Participants stressed that addressing these hurdles (for example, through dedicated regional funding, policy harmonization, improved communication infrastructure, and capacity building for network coordination) will be essential to unlock effective transnational collaboration.

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Willingness for joining a global phytosanitary research network

There is strong interest among regional stakeholders in joining a global phytosanitary research network, such as the one envisaged under EUPHRESKO III. At the Montevideo consultation, attendees voiced enthusiasm about linking LAC with international research efforts, viewing it as an opportunity to share knowledge globally and co-develop solutions to common plant health problems.

Survey findings reinforce this: a large majority of respondents indicated that their institution would likely participate in a global network for phytosanitary research coordination, if the network's activities address regional needs. They see value in mechanisms like joint transnational research calls, collaborative projects, and information exchanges that a network like EUPHRESKO could facilitate. This interest aligns with the direction of EUPHRESKO III, which aims to extend the successful European collaboration model to a broader international scale.

Many noted that it would help them stay informed of emerging threats, access knowledge or technologies not available locally, and ensure that LAC priorities are represented on the global phytosanitary agenda. Importantly, the enthusiasm is coupled with practical questions (raised during the event) about how to join and sustain involvement – for instance, whether there will be membership fees, how projects will be funded, and how regional representation will be managed within the global network's governance.

Overall, however, the consultation confirmed a broad willingness to engage with global initiatives. Stakeholders consider such participation as a strategic way to amplify LAC's research impact and to leverage global resources for local benefit, ultimately strengthening plant health outcomes in the region.

16. Supplementary information or messages originated from the consultation

In addition to the points discussed in the previous sections, the consultation yielded additional messages and considerations that complement the overall regional vision:

- **Emphasis on disseminating results:** Several participants noted that generating knowledge is not enough; it is crucial to effectively communicate it to potential users. There was a call to improve plant health scientific dissemination both at a technical level (regional bulletins, open-access databases) and for producers (user-friendly materials, mobile apps, rural radio). The idea of creating a regional plant health information platform was mentioned, where alerts, management recommendations, and research results ready for application are centralized. This would enhance the value of collaborative research by making it more accessible.
- **Plant health as a component of sustainability and human health:** Some respondents linked plant health with holistic approaches such as One Health. They stressed that improving plant health not only protects crops but also reduces the use of dangerous chemicals (benefiting human and environmental health) and prevents food crises. These messages suggest promoting the importance of plant health research within broader agendas of sustainable development, climate change, and public health. For example, it was proposed to work intersectorally to assess whether pest outbreaks might influence food availability and nutrition in vulnerable communities, reinforcing the importance of investing in plant health.
- **Recognition of existing collaboration:** Although the consultation revealed the need for further coordination, positive examples of existing collaboration in the region were also highlighted. Examples such as the COSAVE program (Phytosanitary Committee of the Southern Cone) that has united Southern Cone countries in applied research projects (e.g.,

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detection of *Brevipalpus* and viruses in citrus) or OIRSA (Regional International Organization for Plant and Animal Health) in Mesoamerica supporting biological control research in coffee borer management were cited. These experiences have generated trust among neighbouring countries. The message was to build on these initiatives, scaling them up and connecting them to the new global structure.

- **Importance of including all producer scales:** Emphasis was placed on ensuring that the research agenda addresses the needs of both large-scale commercial agriculture and family farming. At times, research has been skewed toward one or the other; the consulted vision is to strike a balance. For example, investing in solutions for export crops (banana, soybean) but also for traditional systems (cassava, quinoa, native maize) where plant health affects the subsistence of rural communities. Regional collaboration should ensure that knowledge also reaches these historically underserved sectors.
- **Monitoring and evaluation of collaboration:** There was a suggestion that any network or program implemented (regional or global) should include a component for periodic evaluation of results. The aim is to avoid collaboration that remains only as meetings without tangible impact. It was proposed to define indicators (e.g., number of jointly developed technologies, reduction in the incidence of a pest thanks to coordinated actions) and to monitor progress. This would allow strategies to be adjusted and demonstrate the value of collaboration to funding providers (governments, organizations).
- **Flexibility in emergencies:** A practical message was the need for rapid mechanisms within the collaboration to respond to phytosanitary emergencies. Beyond mid-term plans, the network should be able, in the event of an unexpected outbreak in one country, to mobilize regional experts, share materials, and provide immediate diagnosis. This requires flexibility in both the agenda and funding (perhaps a regional contingency fund). The experience with *Fusarium R4T* in banana – where the region improvised a response – suggests formalizing such emergency protocols.
- **Generational continuity in research:** Many senior researchers expressed concern about generational turnover. They noted a low influx of young specialists in plant health. An additional message is to leverage the network to attract and train young researchers through exchanges, scholarships, and attractive projects. Maintaining a critical mass of plant health experts in the region is essential for the sustainability of all planned actions.

In addition, a key message of the regional meeting was the need to formalise academic (university) training in plant health, recognising it as a specialised discipline, similar to a 'Plant Medicine' profession, that requires holistic and multidisciplinary education under a *One Health* perspective. Participants noted a general lack of public and institutional awareness of the importance of plant health. Raising visibility and political commitment is necessary to ensure phytosanitary issues are prioritised in agricultural policies.

In conclusion, the consultation not only produced priority lists but also valuable reflections on how to carry out collaboration and what considerations to address. Regional stakeholders show high commitment and have provided these ideas to ensure that collaborative efforts in plant health are inclusive, effective, and long lasting.

9. REPORT OF THE CONSULTATIONS FOR NORTHERN EUROPE

1. Introduction

1.1 Description of the region

Northern Europe is a geographically diverse and economically developed region located in the northern part of the European continent. While definitions can vary depending on context (geographical, cultural or political), the following countries are typically considered part of Northern Europe: Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, United Kingdom, and Ireland. However, for this exercise a broader coverage was considered:

- Scandinavian countries: Denmark, Finland, Norway and Sweden
- Baltic countries: Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania
- North-Western European countries: Belgium, France, Germany, Ireland, Netherlands and United Kingdom
- Central European countries: Austria, Czech Republic, Luxembourg, Poland, Slovakia and Switzerland

Agriculture in Northern Europe is shaped by its unique geography, climate and historical traditions. The region experiences a cool-temperate climate with short growing seasons, especially in areas near the Arctic Circle. Coastal areas benefit from milder conditions due to the Gulf Stream, enabling certain crops to thrive despite northern latitudes. In the Baltic states (Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania) and northern parts of the UK and Ireland, the climate is temperate, supporting diverse agricultural activities. Common crops in the region include cereals (barley, oats, rye, wheat), root crops (potatoes, turnips and swedes), oilseeds (rapeseed or canola), berries, vegetables, peas and beans, sugar beets and greenhouse crops (tomatoes, cucumbers and leafy greens) in areas with harsher climates. In Nordic countries (Norway, Sweden and Finland) forestry is intertwined with agriculture, as large portions of land are covered in forests.

Northern Europe hosts renowned research institutions dedicated to Plant Health, with a strong focus on climate adaptation, pest management, sustainability and biodiversity conservation. Collaborative efforts among these institutions, supported by EU frameworks, enhance their ability to address these challenges, ensuring agricultural productivity is sustained while protecting the region's ecosystems.

1.2 Description of the regional champion

The EUPHRESKO III Network Office (ENO) is the champion for Northern Europe. Euphresco is a collaborative network of organizations responsible for funding and coordinating national research in the field of Plant Health. The overall goal of Euphresco is to foster coordination and collaboration in phytosanitary research, and to maintain itself as a strong, long-term network of research stakeholders.

The objectives of Euphresco are:

- To coordinate transnational research programmes, by developing a common strategic research agenda
- To fund collaborative research projects in the phytosanitary area, through annual rounds of calls
- To support and complement other Plant Health initiatives
- To provide scientific evidence to support national and international policy
- To optimise and make best use of limited national Plant Health research resources by avoiding duplication and overlap of research activities
- To facilitate the dissemination of research outputs

1.3 Reasons underlying the interest for regional and global research coordination

In Europe, phytosanitary policies, regulations and technical recommendations are often determined at a regional level, while the supporting research is predominantly funded and conducted at the national level. Coordinating these national activities is essential to minimizing the impact of plant pests on the economy, the environment, and public health—both within individual countries and on a broader European and international scale.

The success of the Euphresco self-sustained network as a platform for coordinating European phytosanitary research demonstrates the value of such collaborative efforts. This success has paved the way for discussions about developing initiatives to meet the needs of other regions worldwide and to enhance global coordination of phytosanitary research.

1.4 Summary of the EUPHRESCO III project, the aims of the consultation, and the process used for the consultation

The aim of the EUPHRESCO III project is to enhance national and regional phytosanitary research coordination and to set the foundations for global phytosanitary research coordination. This will be achieved by building on the foundations developed by the Euphresco self-sustained network and explore fit-for-purpose activities. The objectives of the project are:

- Develop a global strategic agenda on medium-term (5-10 years) phytosanitary research priorities. The agenda will guide phytosanitary research programming activities of the project partners and support them to address national, regional and global challenges through synergies between regions/continents of the world
- Organize joint calls on common research priorities to support and enhance international collaboration through the commissioning and implementation of research projects which meet the needs of the research funders and policy makers and have significant positive outcomes for Plant Health
- Develop and test models for the governance, the structure and the operations of a global network for phytosanitary research coordination. A roadmap will be established to guide the development of a global network for phytosanitary research coordination
- Engage with stakeholders such as policy makers, research funders, academia, industry (agri-food, biotech, diagnostic, seed industry), farmers and foresters and to foster knowledge exchange, involvement in the project activities, co-development, innovation, dissemination and adoption of outputs

The EUPHRESCO III project is structured across 9 different world regions: Africa, Australia, Caribbean-Central America & South America, Central Asia, Europe-North, Europe-South & Mediterranean, North America, Pacific Islands and South-East Asia. The aim is to implement various activities in the countries within these regions, gradually elevating the knowledge gathered or produced at the national level to a regional scale, and ultimately to a global perspective.

In summary, the EUPHRESCO III consortium will contribute to the coordination of national, regional and global phytosanitary research programmes and will allow a better alignment of the research funding and policy making activities in the participating countries. Key factors for successful alignment of national research programmes include: the combination of (i) bottom-up alignment actions that involve research stakeholders and (ii) top-down alignment actions that involve research funding organizations and building mutual trust and consensus at all levels through regular consultations and dialogue. In line with these recommendations, consultations of stakeholders that operate in Plant Health at national and regional level have been organized in the framework of EUPHRESCO III, following the procedure below:

For Northern Europe, the consultation process began in early 2024 with the identification of stakeholders (policy makers, research funders, research organizations, industries, farmers and foresters and others) across various countries. During Spring, a stakeholder survey was distributed and ca. 600 stakeholders were invited to provide their views on the Plant Health key issues, needs and priorities (corresponding to the blue circle in the figure above). Feedback was received from ca. 100 stakeholders from Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Slovakia, Sweden and the United Kingdom.

The data collected was then analyzed by the Centre of Excellence for Biosecurity Risk Analysis (CEBRA, AU). Three vocabularies were used to classify survey responses: (1) Biosecurity Thesaurus, (2) Priority Pests vocabulary, and (3) Commodities vocabulary. Detailed information on the analysis performed by CEBRA and the generated outputs are available in Annex 1 and Annex 2 (section 1.5). The results obtained from this analysis were presented to ca. 40 high level representatives of research funders and policy makers from Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland and the United Kingdom during an online event organized on 2024-10-25. The meeting with Plant Health decision makers allowed to refine the views of the stakeholders (corresponding to the green circle in the figure above). This information, along with data from other regions and disciplines, will be used to identify research priorities and develop Euphresco call topics. By the end of the EUPHRESKO III project in 2026, the collected input will help shaping the next Strategic Research Agenda.

2 The agricultural crops

2.1 List of agricultural crops that are important for the region and the reasons

Based on the survey responses and the Commodity Concept Clusters map from the CEBRA analysis (see section 10; Annex 1), the following agricultural crops have been identified as important for Northern Europe:

- Potatoes (*Solanum tuberosum*)
 - A staple crop across Europe, integral to food security
 - High yields per hectare make it a key food source for both rural and urban populations

- Used in diverse ways, from fresh consumption to industrial processing (e.g., starch, chips, fries)
- Plays a crucial role in the economy of countries like Poland and Germany, which are major potato producers
- Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*)
 - A cornerstone of European diets, used for bread, pasta and other staples
 - Europe is a leading global exporter of wheat, supporting international trade
 - Provides feed for livestock and raw material for beer and whiskey industries
 - Adaptable to varied climates, making it a primary crop across much of Europe
- Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*)
 - Essential for European diets, fresh and processed (sauces, canned products)
 - High economic value, grown intensively in countries like Italy, Spain and the Netherlands
 - Supports greenhouse agriculture and advanced farming techniques, such as hydroponics
 - Contributes to the Mediterranean diet, recognized for health benefits
- Grapevines (*Vitis vinifera*)
 - Central to Europe's renowned wine industry, a significant economic sector
 - Grown in countries like France, Italy, Spain, and Germany, which are global leaders in wine production
 - Promotes biodiversity and sustainable agricultural practices in vineyards
- Maize (*Zea mays*)
 - Critical as a feed crop for Europe's extensive livestock industry
 - A growing bioenergy source for ethanol and biogas, supporting renewable energy goals
 - Provides food products like cornmeal and corn oil
 - Fits well into crop rotation systems, enhancing soil health
- Vegetables
 - Includes a wide array of crops (e.g., carrots, cabbage, lettuce) essential for nutrition and health
 - High-value horticultural exports, especially from the Netherlands
 - Contributes to regional economies and employment in greenhouse and open-field agriculture
 - Meets the increasing consumer demand for fresh, locally produced foods
- Berries
 - Includes crops like strawberries, raspberries and blueberries, which are popular for fresh and processed products
 - High market demand due to increasing awareness of their health benefits
 - Thrives in various European climates, from Nordic countries to temperate zones
 - Supports rural development and agri-tourism, especially in small-scale farming systems
- Legumes
 - Includes peas, beans, and lentils, which are a major source of plant-based protein
 - Improve soil fertility by fixing nitrogen, reducing the need for synthetic fertilizers
 - Important in sustainable farming and crop rotation systems
 - Increasing demand as plant-based diets gain popularity across Europe
- European ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*)
 - Valued for high-quality timber, used in construction and furniture-making
 - Supports agroforestry systems that combine agriculture and forestry
 - Provides ecosystem services, including biodiversity habitat and carbon sequestration
 - Historically and culturally significant in many European regions

- Birch (*Betula* spp.):
 - An important source of timber and pulp for the paper industry
 - Thrives on marginal lands, contributing to land use efficiency in Northern and Eastern Europe
 - Promotes biodiversity and provides habitat in forestry systems
 - Supports traditional uses, including sap harvesting for health products and beverages

3 Important pests for the region

3.1 List of pests for which collaboration within the region is sought, including some information on this pest like geographical distribution / host range / impact

Based on the survey responses and the Common Pest Priority Clusters map from the CEBRA analysis (see section 10; Annex 1), the following pests have been identified as priority for Northern Europe:

Insects

- *Anoplophora chinensis* (Asian longhorned beetle)
 - Geographical Distribution: native to East Asia; introduced to Europe and North America
 - Host Range: broad, including maples, poplars and willows
 - Impact: causes structural damage to host trees, leading to mortality and economic losses in urban and natural forests
- *Anoplophora glabripennis* (Citrus longhorned beetle)
 - Geographical Distribution: native to East Asia; introduced to Europe and North America
 - Host Range: wide, including hardwood trees like maple, birch, and elm
 - Impact: kills trees by tunneling through trunks and branches; significant forestry and ecological impact
- *Echinothrips americanus*
 - Geographical Distribution: North and Central America, Europe
 - Host Range: broad range including ornamentals and greenhouse crops
 - Impact: feeds on leaves and flowers, causing aesthetic and economic damage to ornamental plants
- *Hylobius abietis* (Large pine weevil)
 - Geographical Distribution: Europe
 - Host Range: coniferous trees, especially pines and spruces
 - Impact: damages seedlings and young trees, hindering reforestation efforts
- *Ips typographus* (European spruce bark beetle)
 - Geographical Distribution: Europe, Asia
 - Host Range: spruce trees (*Picea* spp.)
 - Impact: kills mature spruce trees; exacerbates forest decline, especially after droughts or storms
- *Popillia japonica* (Japanese beetle)
 - Geographical Distribution: native to Japan; invasive in North America and Europe
 - Host Range: over 300 plant species including roses, grapes, and turfgrass
 - Impact: defoliates plants, damages turfgrass, and reduces crop yields
- *Rhagoletis* (Fruit flies)
 - Geographical Distribution: worldwide
 - Host Range: various fruits including cherries, apples, and blueberries
 - Impact: causes fruit damage, reducing marketable yield and quality
- *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Fall armyworm)
 - Geographical Distribution: Americas, Africa, Asia
 - Host Range: over 80 plant species including maize, rice, and sorghum

- Impact: major pest in agriculture, causing significant yield losses in staple crops
- *Tuta absoluta* (Tomato leaf miner)
 - Geographical Distribution: South America, Europe, Africa, and Asia
 - Host Range: tomato and related solanaceous crops
 - Impact: causes severe losses in tomato production; difficult to control due to rapid reproduction and resistance development

Bacteria

- *Clavibacter sepedonicus*
 - Geographical Distribution: temperate regions worldwide
 - Host Range: potatoes
 - Impact: causes ring rot, leading to severe economic losses in potato production
- *Erwinia amylovora* (Fire blight)
 - Geographical Distribution: North America, Europe, the Middle East, and parts of Asia
 - Host Range: pome fruits like apples, pears, and quince
 - Impact: destroys blossoms, shoots, and branches, severely impacting orchard productivity and profitability
- *Xylella fastidiosa*
 - Geographical Distribution: Americas, Europe, and Asia
 - Host Range: wide host range including olives, grapevines, citrus, and almonds
 - Impact: causes diseases like olive quick decline and Pierce's disease in grapevines, leading to significant crop losses

Fungi

- *Annosus root and butt rot*
 - Geographical Distribution: Europe, North America, Asia, and parts of Africa
 - Host Range: conifers, particularly pine and spruce
 - Impact: causes significant economic losses in forestry by weakening and killing trees, reducing timber quality
- *Cryphonectria parasitica* (Chestnut blight)
 - Geographical Distribution: native to East Asia; introduced to North America and Europe
 - Host Range: primarily chestnut trees (*Castanea* spp.)
 - Impact: decimated chestnut populations in North America; severe ecological and economic consequences
- *Fusarium euwallaceae*
 - Geographical Distribution: North America, Central America, and parts of Asia
 - Host Range: over 200 plant species, including avocado, sycamore, and castor bean
 - Impact: causes Fusarium dieback, leading to branch dieback and tree mortality
- *Fusarium* spp.
 - Geographical Distribution: worldwide
 - Host Range: broad host range including cereals, vegetables, and ornamentals
 - Impact: causes wilt, root rot, and blight, resulting in yield and quality losses in many crops
- *Ophiostoma novo-ulmi* (Dutch elm disease)
 - Geographical Distribution: Europe, North America, Asia
 - Host Range: Elm trees (*Ulmus* spp.)
 - Impact: lethal disease causing widespread destruction of elm populations; significant ecological and urban landscape effects

Phytoplasmas

- Grapevine flavescence dorée phytoplasma
 - Geographical Distribution: Southern and Central Europe

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-01 under grant agreement No 101130467

- Host Range: Grapevines (*Vitis vinifera*)
- Impact: Reduces grape yield and quality; severely affects viticulture in affected regions

3.2 List of pests for which collaboration at global level is sought, including some information on this pest like geographical distribution / host range / impact

The table below highlights the most frequently identified global priority pests by country, as reported in the stakeholders' survey:

Country	Global priority pests
Austria	<p><i>Xylella fastidiosa</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geographical Distribution: Americas, Europe, and Asia Host Range: wide host range including olives, grapevines, citrus, and almonds Impact: causes diseases like olive quick decline and Pierce's disease in grapevines, leading to significant crop losses
	<p><i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geographical Distribution: Americas, Africa, Asia Host Range: over 80 plant species including maize, rice, and sorghum Impact: major pest in agriculture, causing significant yield losses in staple crops
	<p><i>Popillia japonica</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geographical Distribution: native to Japan; invasive in North America and Europe Host Range: over 300 plant species including roses, grapes, and turfgrass Impact: defoliates plants, damages turfgrass, and reduces crop yields
Belgium	<p><i>Xylella fastidiosa</i></p> <p><i>Drosophila</i> spp.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geographical Distribution: many species of the genus <i>Drosophila</i> are cosmopolitan and found worldwide Host Range: most <i>Drosophila</i> species are generalists, feeding on a wide variety of decaying organic matter, particularly overripe and fermenting fruits. Some species are specialists, restricted to specific plants or fruits. Impact: fermenting fruit infested by <i>Drosophila</i> can be a nuisance in homes, food markets, and storage facilities, leading to quality degradation. Invasive species like <i>D. suzukii</i> outcompete native fruit fly species, disrupting local ecosystems. Economic losses can be in the billions annually, especially in temperate fruit-growing regions.
	<p><i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i></p>
Estonia	<p><i>Xylella fastidiosa</i></p>
France	<p><i>Candidatus Liberibacter</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geographical Distribution: the distribution of <i>Candidatus Liberibacter</i> species varies by host and vector availability Host Range: specific to the bacterial species and associated vectors Impact: significant yield reductions and shortened lifespan of trees, Solanaceous crops suffer reduced yields and quality
	<p><i>Xylella fastidiosa</i></p> <p><i>Myzus persicae</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geographical Distribution: likely originated in East Asia, now distributed worldwide in temperate, subtropical, and tropical regions Host Range: highly polyphagous pest, feeding on over 400 plant species across more than 40 families. Primary host: Peach and other stone fruits (<i>Prunus</i> spp.) Impact: Heavy infestations can kill young plants and reduce crop yields
Germany	<p><i>Xylella fastidiosa</i></p>
	<p><i>Popillia japonica</i></p>
	<p><i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i></p>
Lithuania	<p><i>Aphidae</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geographical Distribution: virtually all terrestrial ecosystems, primarily due to their adaptability and association with a wide variety of host plants Host Range: many aphids have a primary host where they overwinter (e.g., trees or shrubs like peach or plum) Impact: reduced plant vigor and stunted growth, leaf curling, yellowing, and wilting, Premature fruit and flower drop. Aphids transmit over 200 economically important plant viruses

Netherlands	<p><i>Xylella fastidiosa</i></p> <p>Tomato Brown Rugose Fruit Virus (ToBRFV)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geographical Distribution: highly infectious virus that has rapidly spread across the globe since its identification in 2014 in Israel Host Range: primary hosts are tomato and pepper Impact: significant yield reductions in tomato and pepper crops. Reduces marketability due to visual damage and deformities in fruits.
	<p><i>Meloidiogyne spp.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geographical Distribution: global distribution and are found in various regions worldwide Host Range: highly polyphagous, with the ability to infect a broad range of plant species Impact: yield losses can range from 10% to 80%, depending on the crop and environmental conditions. Decline in soil health. Long-term infestations can lead to changes in ecosystem structure
Norway	<p>Bark beetles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geographical Distribution: distributed globally, with different species thriving in specific climatic and ecological zones Host Range: primarily target woody plants but have varying levels of host specificity Impact: during outbreaks, they can kill vast tracts of healthy forest, altering ecosystems and reducing biodiversity
	<p><i>Ips typographus</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geographical Distribution: Europe, Asia Host Range: spruce trees (<i>Picea</i> spp.) Impact: kills mature spruce trees; exacerbates forest decline, especially after droughts or storms
	<p><i>Phytophthora spp.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geographical Distribution: widespread global distribution Host Range: highly polyphagous and can infect a wide variety of plants (agricultural crops, fruit crops, forestry, ornamental and nursery crops, tropical crops, weeds) Impact: agricultural losses. The spread of Phytophthora in forests can cause long-term damage to native tree species and disrupt ecosystem services.
Sweden	<i>Phytophthora spp.</i>
	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>
United Kingdom	<p><i>Xylella fastidiosa</i></p> <p><i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geographical Distribution: native to East Asia; introduced to Europe and North America Host Range: wide, including hardwood trees like maple, birch, and elm Impact: kills trees by tunneling through trunks and branches; significant forestry and ecological impact
	<p><i>Agrilus planipennis</i> (emerald ash borer)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geographical Distribution: highly destructive invasive insect native to Asia. It has rapidly spread to other parts of the world, particularly North America and Europe Host Range: highly specialized, with a preference for ash trees (<i>Fraxinus</i> spp.), but it can also occasionally infest other tree species Impact: large-scale tree mortality in both urban and forest environments. Changes in forest composition and structure, with long-term implications for forest regeneration and ecosystem services

3.3 Summary of the research activities conducted in the last 5 years on the above pests

At this stage, it is premature to complete this section, as the specific pests to be addressed in the topics proposed by the Network Office after the consultation for Northern Europe will be determined later in the Euphresco call process.

4. Key drivers for collaboration

4.1 Main Plant Health issues or related practical problems of the policy makers in the region

Country	Plant Health issues or related practical problems
Austria	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Managing survey programs with less resources and good accuracy at early stage of pests ▪ Resistant ryegrass ▪ New outbreaks, upcoming new pests ▪ Grapevine flavescence dorée <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Rapid availability for test methods to detect new pathogens and pests with a high level of security ▪ Surveillance of increasing number of pests with high requirements regarding statistical confidence level ▪ <i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i> ▪ <i>Tephritidae</i> <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increasingly better conditions for new pests due to change of climate ▪ Limited availability of plant protection products ▪ Grapevine flavescence dorée ▪ <i>Popillia japonica</i> <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increasingly better conditions to introduce new pests due to global trade with large quantities of plant products ▪ Changing behavior of pests in relation to climate change ▪ Esca (<i>Phaeoconiella chlamydospora</i>, <i>Phaeoacremonium minimum</i>, <i>Fomitiporia mediterranea</i>) <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of measures for eradication, especially concerning virus diseases in closed conditions ▪ <i>Nezara viridula</i>
Belgium	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Having not enough information to identify a quarantine organism ▪ Detecting harmful organisms during plant health checks at import ▪ Phytosanitary import checks slow down the logistics process (e.g. when consignments are held pending the result of a lab analysis) and operators respond by moving trade flows very quickly ▪ Limited number of research institutes and experts specifically focusing on Plant Health and Q organisms ▪ Dealing with emerging plant pathogens and pests ▪ Spruce bark beetle <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Having not enough people to follow the phytosanitary issues ▪ New emerging risks and their pathways ▪ Checks on postal packages and courier shipments because of the high number of shipments and the speed at which they are moved ▪ Visibility of Plant Health research and experts (compared to other domains as human health, animal health) ▪ Striving towards fast and sensitive diagnostics ▪ Oak dieback <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Having no speed and cheap tests to confirm a diagnosis ▪ Availability of detailed data on the location of risk sites for each quarantine pest ▪ Access to and sharing of information on ongoing projects or end results of research projects (national, European framework, global) ▪ Developing prediction models or tools ▪ Ash dieback <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The difference between the legislation and the application ▪ Horizon scanning has improved in past years, the bottleneck remains that for many new organisms no data/expertise is available ▪ Regulated Q and NQ in plant reproductive material ▪ Contarinia (<i>Cecidomyiidae</i>) on Douglas fir (<i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i>) <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ "Institutional lasagna": the coordination on a common topic, the process harmonization with the others institutions, availability and transfer of data ▪ Mismatch/lack of interaction between research programs and policy as well as stakeholder needs

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Drought
Estonia	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Plant pest surveillance and inspections <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Minimizing the spread of pests through trade of plant material and international travelling <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ EU-wide pesticide reduction and lack of alternatives <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strengthening phytosanitary research programming and collaboration <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Innovation: diagnostic protocols and control measures
Germany	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lacking staff ▪ Uneven application of EU regulations for import controls at different points of entry into the EU ▪ Request for studies from the EU surveys with no or only vague information on the methods required/to be used ▪ <i>Saperda candida</i> outbreak <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Establishing a quality management system parallel during daily work ▪ Not all tasks can be fully completed with the available personnel and equipment ▪ Wood packing material ▪ Due to increasing number of relevant SE-establishment of the corresponding number of methods in the laboratory (capacities) <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Monitoring program: lack of knowledge about biology of the organisms, diagnosis, sampling, damage images ▪ Excessive density of EU regulations ▪ Increasing number of relevant SEs-financial and human resources ▪ Potato diseases <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Regulations often lead to a high level of bureaucracy, so that there is no time for essential tasks (physical inspection of plant products, plants, wood, etc.) ▪ Interception and tracing back <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The existing system does not guarantee complete registration of all respective businesses, only those that register voluntarily or attract negative attention in a certain way ▪ Nematodes in nurseries
Lithuania	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of diagnostics protocols, procedures for official testing of EU regulated non-quarantine pests, quarantine pests in implementation of official control and other official activity <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of biological reference material and trainings for production and maintenance of it for official testing of pests in implementation of official control and other official activity <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of proficiency testing for diagnostics of EU regulated non-quarantine pests, quarantine pests which are actual for Northern EU countries <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Unified sampling methodologies of growing crop and consignments for QP as well as RNQP <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Share of experience on the applicable phytosanitary control measures among the experts of the same climatic zone (creation of Network)
Netherlands	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Emergency preparedness <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Managements and elimination of new outbreaks <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Surveys and diagnostics <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Phytosanitary guarantees
Norway	<p>Issue 1</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Decay in Sitka spruce forests in the coast ▪ Moth species causing defoliation on broadleaved trees (such as <i>Epirrita autumnata</i>, <i>Operophtera brumata</i>, <i>Agriopis aurantiaria</i>) ▪ <i>Hylobius abietis</i> ▪ Updating regulations, including background information/knowledge (surveillance, epidemiology, effects of management) ▪ All priorities are given in the strategy of 2023-2027 and the published calls (Norwegian Research Council) <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Large pine beetle (<i>Hylobius abietis</i>) ▪ Root rot on first generation Norway spruce forests ▪ Deer ▪ Manage outbreaks of pests or other incidents (plans, correct management, effective pest control, information) <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mouse eating the bark of Norway spruce and Sitka spruce plants ▪ Dieback of trembling aspen (causative agent unknown) ▪ Surveillance and early detection: Giving priority to one pest as compared to others, choice of method, effective use of resources, specific/general surveillance <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Deer browsing on Norway spruce and Sitka spruce plants ▪ Decay caused by <i>Phellinus pini</i> in old Scots pine forests ▪ Effective control of imported plants; risk-classification, diagnostic tools, digitization <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Some <i>Ips typographus</i> damages ▪ Management of quarantine pests present in Norway, e.g. Potato Cyst Nematode (PCN), pear decline, <i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>. How contain infections.
Poland	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Changing scope of plant diseases and shifts in the range of plant pest hosts. <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Progressive soil and water pollution. <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Climate change <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Decline in biodiversity and soil depletion <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of awareness and education regarding the need to preserve plant health and manage crops properly
Sweden	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Better access to reliable and faster diagnostic services responding to various needs for risk managers. For example, testing of samples taken from import/trade consignments must be able to show whether live pests (and not DNA only) <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Access to high capacity for diagnostic services in the case of a pest outbreak(s) leading to crisis situation and contingency management where a high amount of samples need to be analyzed in a relatively short amount of time <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sufficient financial resources as well as personnel with sufficient level of plant health skills in risk management and in plant health related inspections <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Access to effective methods for detection surveys targeting a wide range of different plant pests causing harm to wide range of plant production systems (forestry, agriculture, horticulture, green and other natural environments) for early detection of pests. In particular, there is a need for data on the distribution of plant hosts as well as estimations on the efficacy of various pest survey detection methods
United Kingdom	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Risk and horizon scanning for new plant health risks ▪ Control of ongoing incursions of pests dispersed via windblow e.g. <i>Ips typographus</i> ▪ Globalisation of trade ▪ Availability of fumigants effective (and approved) as PPPs

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Maintaining skills and knowledge particularly for the certification of material entering propagation schemes
Issue 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Detection and diagnosis for pests and diseases at border and inland ▪ Increasing management costs of non-native, significantly damaging pests and diseases ▪ Climate change ▪ Funding ▪ Being able to provide rapid diagnostic results to quickly release held consignments at the border ie < 48 h
Issue 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Effectively managing pests and diseases outbreaks while minimizing environmental impact and cost ▪ Climate change impacts on pests and diseases ▪ Being able to detect cryptic infect in large consignments
Issue 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Developing landscapes resilient to future pests and diseases ▪ Being able to predict what will be and where will be the next big incursion within the territory to make appropriate preparations
Issue 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Reducing the impact of destructive testing on high value imports such as requiring 10,000 tomato seed to detect numerous pathogens of this host

4.2 Main Plant Health issues or related practical problems of the of the research funders in the region

Country	Plant Health issues or related practical problems
Austria	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ New outbreaks, upcoming new pests <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Surveillance of increasing number of pests with high requirements regarding statistical confidence level <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Limited availability of plant protection products <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Changing behavior of pests in relation to climate change
Belgium	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Detecting harmful organisms during plant health checks at import ▪ Phytosanitary import checks slow down the logistics process (e.g. when consignments are held pending the result of a lab analysis) and operators respond by moving trade flows very quickly ▪ Limited number of research institutes and experts specifically focusing on Plant Health and quarantine organisms ▪ Dealing with emerging plant pathogens and pests ▪ Spruce bark beetle <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ New emerging risks and their pathways ▪ Checks on postal packages and courier shipments because of the high number of shipments and the speed at which they are moved ▪ Visibility of PH research and experts (compared to other domains as human health, animal health) ▪ Striving towards fast and sensitive diagnostics ▪ Oak dieback <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Availability of detailed data on the location of risk sites for each quarantine pest ▪ Access to and sharing of information on ongoing projects or end results of research projects (national, European framework, global) ▪ Developing prediction models or tools ▪ Ash dieback <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Horizon scanning has improved in past years, the bottleneck remains that for many new organisms no data/expertise is available ▪ Regulated Q and NQ in plant reproductive material ▪ <i>Contarinia</i> on Douglas fir (<i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i>) <p>Issue 5</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mismatch/lack of interaction between research programs and policy as well as stakeholder needs (with the main objective being science-based and timely measures) ▪ Drought
Estonia	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Plant pest surveillance and inspections <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Minimizing the spread of pests through trade of plant material and international travelling <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ EU-wide pesticide reduction and lack of alternatives <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strengthening phytosanitary research programming and collaboration <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Innovation: diagnostic protocols and control measures
France	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ban of numerous pesticides, notably insecticides, resulting in increased pressure of pests, and in the need for innovative and sustainable pests management ▪ Climate change impact ▪ Insects control due to loss of active substances and taking account consequences of climate changes and new insects occurring in Europe (e.g. <i>Drosophila suzukii</i>) <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Management of a wide diversity of diseases, requiring integrated crop management and to enhance global plant health ▪ Biological invasions and new hazards ▪ Weeds control due to loss of active substance, loss of mode of action and lack of alternatives <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Consequences of global and climatic change on pests (faster cycles, shifts in epidemiological risks and geographical distribution, etc.): many insects including virus vectors, wireworms, etc. ▪ Develop efficient biocontrol methods ▪ Disease control due to loss of mode of action and taking account consequences of climate changes. Increase of mycotoxins frequency on some crops and strengthening of quality standards <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Risks associated with movement and trade of plant material, or if lower regulation (e.g. on farm-saved seeds): higher risk of dissemination of emerging diseases, nematodes, viruses, etc. <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Pressure of soil pathogens, and their detection in complex matrices, resulting from fewer protection solutions and new cropping systems (e.g. <i>Pythium</i>, <i>Rhizoctonia</i>; etc.)
Poland	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dynamic development of populations of harmful insects resulting in damage to stands as a result of drought and climate change <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Difficulties and constraints in aerial application of plant protection products <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dieback of spruce stands due to drought and secondary insect pests <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Pine dieback due to infestation by mistletoe in association with drought <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Damage to forest caused by game
United Kingdom	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Risk/ assessment from new and spreading Plant Health issues ▪ Availability of fumigants effective (and approved) as PPPs <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Climate change ▪ Funding <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Specific species/ group including Honey fungus <i>Armillaria media</i>

4.3 Main Plant Health issues or related practical problems of the of the research organizations in the region

Country	Plant Health issues or related practical problems
Austria	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Adaptation to climate change – resilience to drought ▪ Coordination and management of outbreaks and spread of new plant pests ▪ Increasing number of regulated pests (e.g. listing of specific non-European species) <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Reduction of biodiversity ▪ Rapid increase in number of new pests ▪ Missing identification tests and standards for regulated and emerging pests <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Soil pollution (microplastic, antimicrobials, radioactive contamination) ▪ Lack of available practical management options ▪ Lack of resources (e.g. reference material, human and financial resources, expertise and experts) <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of resources (human and financial resources) and ensuring sufficient expertise for the future ▪ Unknown future risks associated with e.g. new pests, climate change, pest management-IPM, decreasing number of active ingredients, change of agricultural practices, influence on environmental biodiversity <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Difficulty of adapting to rapidly changing conditions (climate change, new pests, biodiversity, environment) quickly enough and building up interdisciplinary expertise broadly enough for the future
Belgium	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Rise of crop pathogens, combined with a decrease of chemical crop protection and slow rise of biocontrol products ▪ Emerging new pests and diseases ▪ Marginal soil ▪ Soil diseases in <i>Rubus</i> varieties ▪ Fungal disease management ▪ Invasive species ▪ Bridging farmer and researcher knowledge ▪ New thrips species on ornamental plants ▪ Dipteran fruit pests (in particular <i>Tephritidae</i>) <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Translating abstract sustainability concepts to practical applications ▪ Slow increase and uptake of allowed new genomic techniques in Europe ▪ Aggravating general pests and diseases due to lack of efficient crop protection products ▪ Environmental pollution ▪ Extreme weather ▪ Emergence of pesticide resistance ▪ Soil health ▪ Dipteran and hymenopteran pollinators ▪ Control of vine weevil (<i>Otiorynchus sulcatus</i>) <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Long regulatory path for new biocontrol products ▪ Quarantine status for diseases that are already widely spread (e.g. ToBRFV) ▪ Study of soil microbiota and biocontrol agents ▪ Healthy plant material ▪ Lack of products against <i>Fusarium</i> and <i>Verticillium</i> in ornamental plants ▪ Participatory advisory services ▪ Pests: aphids, beetles, <i>D. suzukii</i> <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ High energy price ▪ Disproportionate or ineffective yet very costly measures for Q-organisms (e.g. steaming substrate before disposal) ▪ Low use of new disease-resistant varieties ▪ Disappearing of crop protection means ▪ Lack of usable herbicides for different ornamental crops <p>Issue 5</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Risks of disease introduction via seeds and/or nurseries and few tools to effectively screen seeds/plants ▪ Lack of products against root diseases (<i>Phytophthora</i> species, and others) ▪ Viruses and phytoplasmas
Estonia	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Plant pest surveillance and inspections ▪ New viruses in cereals <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Minimizing the spread of pests through trade of plant material and international travelling ▪ Climate change and biotic stress <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ EU-wide pesticide reduction and lack of alternatives ▪ Climate change and abiotic stress <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strengthening phytosanitary research programming and collaboration <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Innovation: diagnostic protocols and control measures
France	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Withdrawal active substances ▪ ISO17025 accreditation and maintenance of accreditation for a wide range of different quarantine pathogens ▪ Research for alternatives to plant protection products for the management of pests ▪ Country phytosanitary requests for import: not always relevant (e.g., detection of the pathogen on a non-host plant species) ▪ Climate change impact ▪ Vine downy mildew ▪ Yellowing virus ▪ <i>Curculio nucum</i> <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Access to reference specimens from third countries due to the associated administrative constraints (Nagoya) ▪ Climate change and its impact on the biology or spread of pests ▪ Detection method efficacy: molecular methods vs bioassays ("biological relevance": presence of a sequence vs. viability/pathogenicity); impact of seed treatment on the capacity of a method to detect a pathogen ▪ <i>Halyomorpha halys</i> ▪ Apple Scab ▪ Cercosporiosis <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Impact of climate change on post-quarantine flow & emergence of new pests/pathogens ▪ Evolution of strains and populations of pests in relation to resistance to plant protection products and the sustainable management of varietal resistances ▪ Reference material: availability of characterized pest isolates and infected seed samples may be difficult ▪ Bacterial diseases ▪ Weevils ▪ <i>Pentatomidae</i> <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Efficiency of surveillance ▪ Means to stimulate plant immunity ▪ Grasses ▪ Pests (aphids) ▪ Seedborne and seed-transmitted pathogens: knowledge on the capacity of a pathogen to be transmitted through seeds may be lacking / not conclusive ▪ <i>Fomitiporia</i> <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Withdrawal of conventional phytosanitary products without any available alternative ▪ Assistance in choosing the combination of methods (multicriteria analyses) ▪ Weeds ▪ Identification of pests (pathogens, insects, invasive plants) at the species level: in some cases, cannot be achieved with current methods, but asked at country borders

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Moths (<i>Lepidoptera</i>) ▪ <i>Phytoptus avellanae</i>
Germany	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of human resources ▪ Missing references or methods for diagnoses/diagnosis not possible <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Growing complexity vs. specialization of experts (e.g. legislation globalization) ▪ Missing information and images of pests/visual inspection not possible <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Safeguarding Plant Health in the expanding e-commerce sector ▪ No assistance/compensation for affected companies <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Too many "unknown/irrelevant" regulated pests <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Too little time/too few staff/insufficient relevant training
Lithuania	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Reduction of plant protection products ▪ Septoria leaf blotch (<i>Zymoseptoria tritici</i>) in winter wheat crop <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of biological plant protection products-alternative plant protection measures/insufficient effectiveness and use in practice ▪ Sclerotinia stem rot (<i>Sclerotinia sclerotiorum</i>) in oilseed rape <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Spread of new pathogens ▪ Potato leaf blight (<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>) <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Pathogen resistance to plant protection products ▪ Fusarium head blight (<i>Fusarium graminearum</i>) <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Insufficient cooperation between institutions, researchers and growers/farmers ▪ Chocolate Spot (<i>Botrytis fabae</i> and <i>B. cinerea</i>)
Netherlands	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Spread of pests and diseases (effect of climate change) ▪ Quality of Antisera ▪ Lack of information on biology, taxonomy and epidemiology to enable proper risk assessment <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Introduction of new pests/diseases ▪ Acceptance of PCR ▪ Lack of capacity and material (plant and pathogen) to develop and validate diagnostic methods for all quarantine pests, including early detection <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Breakdown of host plant resistance genes and evolution of pathogen virulence traits ▪ Cut off ToBRFv ▪ Effects of globalization, cultivation of exotic crops and climate changes on plant pathogens: this creates extremely favorable conditions for the movement and establishment of emerging pests in new areas <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Pesticide resistance and registration of plant protection products ▪ Variation in export requests ▪ Impact of more generic methods like HTS, that increases the number of QP found which prompt to subsequent actions <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Requests Bio-assays ▪ The list of quarantine species is not suited good enough to the Dutch (local situation): many species are listed that cannot occur here or only limited data/recordings are known
Norway	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Plant protection in organic fruit and berry production ▪ Evaluate the risk of damage caused by alien species, plant and tree pathogens and pest included. Knowledge about spread pathways, potential primary and alternative hosts is important in our work ▪ Difficult to find cost-effective biological means to protect plants against diseases ▪ Cost-effectively and ecologically prevent or reduce damage by weevils in conifer plantations

	<p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Pests and fungal damage ▪ Import of plants containing damage agents has created great problems. Current phytosanitary inspections and quarantine routines are not sufficient. Large volumes of garden plants are imported with soil ▪ Cost-effectively and ecologically prevent or reduce ungulate browsing in plantation fields <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Reduced plant communities important for pollinators ▪ Lack of nurseries that can provide high-quality plants with an affordable price. Seed as a potential source for diseases is not sufficiently understood, and regulative rules for seed import and export among European countries are too strict. Seed is likely seldom the source of diseases and there should be better routines in place for exchange of non-commercial plants ▪ Drought and warmer summers coupled with the risk of bark beetle attacks on Norway spruce - identification of site conditions and regions where other tree species than Norway spruce should be planted <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Measures (precision forestry) to mitigate decay in Norway spruce forests <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ spread and control of invasive alien pathogens and pests, such as the ash dieback pathogen <i>Hymenoscyphus fraxineus</i>
Slovakia	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Climate change (drought and heat stress) which support the spread of new and invasive pests ▪ <i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i> <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of effective ecological preparations ▪ <i>Lema melnopus</i> <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Soil acidification which limits nutrient availability and crop production ▪ <i>Ceutorhynchus napi</i> <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Soil erosion and land degradation/ soil compaction ▪ <i>Thrips tabaci</i> <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Non chemical pest management ▪ <i>Cydia pomonella</i>
Sweden	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of certain data important for performing detailed analysis in PRA, e.g. distributions of hosts ▪ Accurate and sensitive early detection tools and protocols for pests and pathogens of concern <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Improved surveillance tools for Buprestid, woodboring insects <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Biological control programs to protect trees from forest pests
United Kingdom	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Risk/ assessment from new and spreading Plant Health issues ▪ Climate change <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Climate change ▪ Forestry species choice <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Specific species/ group including Honey fungus <i>Armillaria media</i> ▪ Emergence of new pests and pathogens

4.4 Main Plant Health issues or related practical problems of the industry in the region

Country	Plant Health issues or related practical problems
Belgium	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ (Re-)export issues due to increasing complexity to move seed internationally. There is an increase in non-harmonized and progressively more specific phytosanitary requirements for seeds

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Quality of seed potatoes ▪ Emerging new pests and diseases due to changing environment (climate, globalization) ▪ <i>Nezara viridula</i> <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Regulatory policy determining pest classification, e.g. emergency measures ▪ Possibilities to destroy soil insects ▪ Decreasing efficiency of IPM due to non-adjusted to changing environment ▪ Exotic thrips <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Import requirements for pests for which there is no scientific evidence for seed transmission under seed production practices ▪ Potato varieties with late blight resistance ▪ Decreasing intervention/treatment alternatives due to European policy on plant protection products ▪ Aphids <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Seed tests that are very sensitive and do not discriminate between environmental background or true risk of possible seed transmission ▪ Seed Transmission risks are not examined well, no data around ▪ Minimal infective dose of viral diseases / relation between the virus titer and seed transmission ▪ Possibilities to use NGT to adapt the genome of the varieties ▪ Slow renewal of (biological) crop protection toolkit ▪ Powdery mildew <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Less seed treatment options available in the future, this can cause a concern for diseases that have not been a problem for the last decade(s) ▪ Official monitoring not adjusted to import requirements of third countries ▪ <i>Fusarium</i>
Estonia	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Environmental conditions and plant stress <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Diseases and pests <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Biological diversity <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Soil quality <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Economic consequences of plant health problems
France	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Beetles (all crops), such as <i>Lixus juncii</i> (beets), Flea beetle (mainly crucifers), Pea weevil, broad-bean weevil (legumes), <i>Tychius</i> (alfalfas), Clover seed weevil, <i>Apion</i> sp. (red clover) <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ In-row weeding for a wide range of crops <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fungal diseases, such as downy mildew (beet, forage legumes, vegetables, PPAM flowers), late blight, rust, leaf spots, phoma (vegetables), rusts (grasses, forage legumes), <i>Alternaria</i>, phoma (crucifers). Plus bacterial diseases. High needs in seed treatments and foliar applications <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Biting insects - new alternatives are needed at short term level, because of the lack of effective solutions against aphids (all crops), shield bugs (lygus beet, alfalfa, orthops carrot, etc.) <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Against maggots (vegetables) and other soil pests, the current solutions are based on active substances that may not be reapproved in the coming years without alternatives, including wireworms (all crops)
Netherlands	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Insufficient knowledge of spreading mechanisms of pathogens/disease (e.g. mechanically, seeds/propagating material etc.) ▪ <i>Popillia japonica</i>, distribution within Europe; risks; solutions to mitigate risks and epidemiology in the northern regions of the EU: which measures are effective in these regions? ▪ Lack of monitoring in other countries. Countries deny having (quality) organisms

	<p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IPM <i>vis-a-vis</i> phytosanitary requirements by third-countries <i>Knolcyperus</i> (nutgrass): Few control options are known. Meanwhile, this weed is spreading rapidly throughout the Netherlands. Jimson weed is also becoming increasingly common Tendency of third countries to require tests for all organisms, while these are not important from a phytosanitary point of view, because they are quality organisms <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insufficient knowledge of resistance genes to (upcoming) pathogens/disease Wart disease: findings of a new physio (38) in the Netherlands. The potato sector has concerns about the development of this fungi, because of the new findings Lack of international coordination on the use of homogeneous testing methods in third countries. This leads to wrong interpretations <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requests for seed test on pests that are not seed borne nor proven to be seed transmitted <i>Ralstonia pseudosolanacearum</i>: since 2021 the are finding of this organism in surface water. The wide range of host plants is a concern Some third countries blame problems on imported starting material, whilst local cultivation methods need to be improved <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of results from very sensitive seed health tests that do not provide information on presence of living or dead pathogens <i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>, <i>M. fallax</i>, <i>M.hapla</i> and <i>M. naasi</i>
Norway	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Virus diseases <i>Phytophthora infestans</i> resistant clones Pests in imported plants of fruit and berries <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Growth media Fungicide resistance Pests in imported fruits and berries (<i>Drosophila</i>, <i>Cydia pomonella</i>, <i>Plutella xylostella</i>) <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to environment friendly and sustainable varieties Insecticide resistance Pests/diseases against which there are no effective pesticides available <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge in market regarding plant health and import Seed borne diseases

4.5 Main Plant Health issues or related practical problems of the farmers and foresters in the region

Country	Plant Health issues or related practical problems
Belgium	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organisms that are QP or RNQP and therefore have major consequences if found on the farm <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organisms problematic for export to third countries <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Xylella</i>, <i>Phytophthora ramorum</i>, <i>Erwinia amylovora</i>, <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>, (Asian) longhorn beetle, etc.
Denmark	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Export restrictions
Estonia	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental conditions and plant stress <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diseases and pests <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biological diversity <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil quality <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Economic consequences of plant health problems

France	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ More exogenous pests (lacking predators) and diseases with no known/efficient treatment clue ▪ <i>Cobweb disease (Cladobotryum dendroïdes)</i> ▪ <i>Cydia pomonella</i> ▪ <i>Curculio nucum</i> <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sciarid flies (<i>Lycoriella auripila</i>) ▪ <i>Rhagoletis completa</i> ▪ <i>Halyomorpha halys</i> ▪ Pests (insects and diseases) being less manageable due to climatic changes <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Less chemicals allowed, very few are still authorized for citrus in France at the moment ▪ Dry bubble (<i>Lecanicillium fungicola</i>) disease ▪ <i>Gnomonia leptostyla</i> ▪ <i>Pentatomidae</i> <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weed killer resistance ▪ Cost of sustainable solutions such as beneficial/auxiliary insects, traps, pheromone/keromone for mating disruption, etc. ▪ <i>Fomitiporia</i> <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fungal attacks on wood ▪ Lack of methods, process, and resources in Corsica for citrus crops as it is the only tiny part of France producing citrus ▪ <i>Phytoptus avellanae</i>
Netherlands	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Plant disease management <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weed management <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Control of quarantine organisms <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prevention of new introductions
Norway	<p>Issue 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Access to approved pesticides ▪ Overwintering fungi in feed and fodder. Robustness and tolerance of different varieties ▪ Bark beetles ▪ Root and butt rot ▪ Measures to control root and butt rot in Norway spruce and Scots pine forests ▪ Fungi <p>Issue 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Reason for failing crops ▪ Weevils ▪ Wounding related wood decay ▪ Knowledge about the resilience of continuous cover forests to climatic factors ▪ Weevils <p>Issue 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Root and butt rot ▪ Weevils ▪ New damage agents in plantation fields (<i>Herpotrichia juniperi</i>, <i>Hylastes cunicularius</i>, weevils in family <i>Entiminae</i>) ▪ Abiotic stressors <p>Issue 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Drought (Norway spruce) ▪ Wind damages ▪ Alternative tree species to Norway spruce, Scots pine and birch to meet the challenges posed by climate change and new damage agents on the conventional forest tree species <p>Issue 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The challenge of long periods of drought to forestry

4.6 Main Plant Health issues or related practical problems of others

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-01 under grant agreement No 101130467

Country	Plant Health issues or related practical problems
Netherlands	Issue 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To be able to guarantee the phytosanitary safety of growing media (substrates) for professional horticulture <i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i>, <i>Clavibacter sepedonicus</i> ISPM 15 compliance in transport value chains
	Issue 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Meloidogyne chitwoodi</i>, <i>M. fallax</i>, <i>M.hapla</i> and <i>M. naasi</i> ISPM 15 harmonization in the EU (on trade and repair specifically)
	Issue 3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Globodera rostochiensis</i> and <i>G. pallida</i>
	Issue 4 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i>
	Issue 5 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Cyperus esculentus</i>

4.7 The needs in terms of capacity building

Country	Needs in terms of capacity building
Austria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased resources Methods Processes Biological control & resistance breeding Comparable guidelines for the use of PPPs
Belgium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased resources People, formation, resumed information in the mother tongue, photos and information on the spread stat of new pathogens Independent advisory services, inclusion of non-chemical solutions in the curriculum of farming schools Centralization of knowledge in the sector that can also be deployed in a guided manner Resources that allow field work Fast determination & detection methods Increase in potato production to meet need for the potato industry Talent Knowledge (competences) Sufficient employees (labor) Specific funding for research projects and the possibility of hiring researchers in these areas Expansion of resources and personnel to implement and expand the monitoring programme, training and equipment (in particular appropriate IT tools) Increased standardization of methods certifying plant reproductive material Training for researchers on how to search for practical applications of research results
Estonia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased resources Raising awareness of travelling and international trade Sharing experience between member states regarding pests that are not yet present in Estonia Ensuring sustainable resources for research Better rooms for growing plants and stability in the acquisition of funds for researchers and technicians Stay up to date with the latest research, methods and solutions in plant health. Collaboration with other experts and practitioners to share knowledge and experience and best practices in solving problems
France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased resources Bioinformatics skills, data science and artificial intelligence Access to biological reference material Maintaining skills in traditional taxonomy over the long term Access to quick barcoding methods How to manage the epidemiology (including vectorization) of a new emerging or reemerging pest Experimentation, evaluation of alternative phytosanitary products, phytodiagnostic, supporting innovation, supporting competitiveness of agricultural branches Exchanges with other countries on technical issues

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ High needs for research and development of alternatives plus regulatory harmonization of PPP uses ▪ Improve EU and worldwide collaborations ▪ Information and data sharing to develop alternatives faster in minor crops ▪ Information and shared knowledge on major and emerging pests ▪ Data science and modelling for risk assessment and impacts of climatic change ▪ Innovative detection tools, including metagenomics and characterization of microbial diversity ▪ Indicators for plant health and soil fertility ▪ Transfer of processes, methods, and resources from abroad ▪ Harmonization on definition and naming of uses ▪ Promote public & private research projects ▪ Review relevance of requirements related to residues trials repartition in France (France characterized by 2 zones : North and South) ▪ Funding to perform research with other research institutes in the world ▪ Collaboration with research institutes to test protocols/methods with growers
Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increased resources (staff, laboratories) ▪ Competences (new technologies) ▪ Primarily qualified specialized employees ▪ Workshops on (new) methods ▪ Clear specifications for methods to be used
Lithuania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increased funding for research ▪ Irrigation systems ▪ Facilities for field vegetation trials ▪ Deeper knowledge about pests' resistance ▪ Facilities for sample storage
Netherlands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Input knowledge, communication and explanation of regulations, methods, support with export problems due to phytosanitary regulations or lack of knowledge in the receiving country ▪ Knowledge exchange on which eradication methods are effective ▪ For <i>Popillia japonica</i>: research on limiting the dispersal ▪ Research, regulatory control, monitoring ▪ Capacity building in third countries on reliable testing methods and cultivation practices ▪ Infrastructure to share data on identification methods and reference material; ▪ Exchange taxonomic knowledge / research /expertise ▪ Expertise in recognition of symptoms in the field for diseases that are currently absent in the region ▪ Regular twinning with third countries on field inspection and international legislation
Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ High quality research and knowledge on plant health ▪ Increased funding to forest health research ▪ Increased capacity for cryo-storage ▪ Improved both methods and expertise for cleaning viruses. ▪ Better and cheaper test methods ▪ Recruitment and knowledge update ▪ Build-up of knowledge across the country and organizations about plant damage agents such as <i>Phytophthora</i> ▪ Good availability of courses for employees on plant/forest health ▪ Better integration of various tools (diagnostics and remote sensing) in forest health monitoring ▪ Disease protection methods for small plants ▪ Knowledge about spread of decay fungi, climate change and potential damage agents, and general forest health ▪ Knowledge about planting, choice of plant type, tree species and planting technique ▪ Competence in assessment of forest health based on visual evaluation and realistic estimates/calculations about loss of revenue in stressed forests ▪ Competence and methods concerning regeneration ▪ Great need to develop politically correct methods for soil scarification that fulfill the basic requirements for such a treatment ▪ Updating knowledge on plant health, capacity on digitizing processes, innovation and implementing new technologies for surveillance and <i>in situ</i> diagnosis as well as precision farming ▪ Increased knowledge on new threats to be able to implement regulatory measures

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National capacity/competence on soil health in general
Poland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intersectoral information exchange and collaboration Facilitating the transfer of technology and innovation from the scientific sector to agricultural practice Development of new methods, tools, and technologies supporting agricultural production and plant protection Ensuring access to financial resources and infrastructure supporting scientific research, technological development, and agricultural practice Developing forecasting models to identify risks
Slovakia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase in staffing capacities Updated infrastructure Better software equipment Free access to the latest scientific knowledge and information Assessment and preservation of plant genetic resources in collections Financial stability to systematically monitor major pathogens Increased investment in research and development Collaboration between institutions dealing with plant diseases Cooperation with farmers and civil associations Fair evaluation of projects Salaries for restriction of additional activities of scientists employed at university
Sweden	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Methods: Epidemiological modelling and development of different applications using R Resources: Data on climatic variables and host distribution Funding to support continued research into developing novel methods of detection and monitoring of pest/pathogens and studies of the biology, epidemiology and control of forest pathogens and pests of concern Development of best practices and protocols for diagnostic field surveying that can lead to more rapid detection and efficient monitoring of pest populations Resources to develop new analytical tools for sub- commercial diseases and pests Establishing a national reference laboratory for diagnosis of pests
United Kingdom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased resources More skilled researchers at all levels PhDs fellowship and internships for Early Career researchers Data sharing (within country and worldwide) Resources to carry out outbreak preparedness and response Taxonomic/ diagnostic skills Diagnostics (field), process improvement, use of technology Artificial intelligence, bioinformatics, remote surveillance Finding time and experience to provide training Retaining corporate knowledge regarding how historic outbreaks were handled Gaining experience on new pests to better manage them

5 The research priorities

5.1 The medium-term (5-10 years) research priorities identified through the bottom-up approach

Country	Medium-term (5-10 years) research priorities
Austria	Institutional priorities
	Priority 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil and plant health Implementation of contingency plans and organization of regular simulation exercises to be better prepared for possible outbreaks Development, establishment and validation of identification methods and protocols
	Priority 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil contamination Raising awareness on plant health issues; Citizen Science Further development of forecasting methods and models for pests to better predict their occurrence
	Priority 3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate change adaptation and mitigation Ensuring sufficient resources and expertise for the future

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ IPM research: development and application of biotechnological and biological control methods to reduce pests as alternative to insecticides <p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Evaluation of new plant pests (listing of new species and delisting of non-relevant species) and the significance for its own federal territory (risk-based assessments) ▪ New detection and monitoring tools (e.g. e-DNA studies, electronic traps, drones and apps, citizen science, scent detection dogs) <p>Priority 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increase and improve networking in the plant health sector ▪ Support and increase of knowledge transfer (dissemination of information, publications, workshops)
Belgium	<p>Institutional priorities</p> <p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Early detection ▪ Increase knowledge among growers and traders about the priority pests (monitoring, visual recognition, risks) ▪ Research for control (monitoring, IPM tools, chemical products) of new thrips species in ornamental plants ▪ Genetic/genomic profiling invasive species ▪ One science-based, internationally recognized list of seed pests that are considered to be a risk for introduction and transmission by seed ▪ Mitigation alternatives for new / emerging pests and diseases ▪ Practical IPM solutions for recently emerged pests and diseases in vegetables ▪ Research for control (monitoring, IPM tools, chemical products) of new thrips species in ornamental plants ▪ Potato varieties resistant against late blight ▪ Development of new platforms for plant vaccine development and fermentation technologies ▪ Sustainable crop production ▪ New growing systems ▪ Study of soil microbiota <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Decision support systems ▪ Collaboration with Euphresco network on Plant health research, including on using plant breeding as a tool ▪ Development pest free areas ▪ Potato varieties resistance against abiotic stress ▪ New detection methods for pathogen detection ▪ Solutions to mitigate the fast decline in effective crop protection products ▪ Valorization of organic residual streams ▪ Plant varieties ▪ Use/monitoring of biocontrol agents ▪ Diagnostics ▪ Alternative mitigation measures for several diseases and pests that become more important due to withdrawal of plant protection products ▪ Research for control (monitoring, IPM tools, chemical products) of soil insects (grubs, leatherjackets, vine weevils) in ornamental plants and landscaping <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Augmentative biocontrol ▪ Potentiate the participation or setting up an International Consortium doing research on Biological Relevance of the results from virus detection methods ▪ Interaction natural habitats versus agricultural fields with regard to pollinators ▪ Clean energy sources to reduce carbon footprint ▪ Resistant varieties ▪ Improved plant tolerance through bio-stimulants, priming, etc. ▪ Study of emerging pathogens or the evolution of current pathogens ▪ Pest and disease models ▪ Withdrawal of Q-status for specific diseases and pests that have become widespread by now - e.g. ToBRFV ▪ Efficacy and phytotoxicity trials for obtaining new authorized products against <i>Fusarium</i> <p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Conservation biocontrol ▪ Setting up an International Consortium doing research on alternative methods for seed treatment

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Pollinator diversity ▪ Reducing abiotic stress to reduce disease severity: climate control, bio-stimulants, cultivation techniques ▪ IPM ▪ Efficacy and phytotoxicity trials for obtaining new authorized products against root phytophthora <p>Priority 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ IPM ▪ Healthy or protected seed/planting material ▪ Reduction of chemical residues ▪ Preventive use of biopesticides against root and vascular diseases in different ornamental crops
Denmark	Institutional priorities
	<p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Export restrictions
Estonia	Institutional priorities
	<p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Climate change and biotic stress ▪ Conservation and restoration of biological diversity <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Climate change and abiotic stress ▪ Promotion of integrated pest management <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Innovation: gene editing for gaining tolerance (biotic and abiotic stresses) ▪ Supporting research and innovation on preventing diseases and pests, developing new control techniques, and improving plant resistance and plant variety <p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Training and raising awareness <p>Priority 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ International cooperation and use of synergy opportunities
	Institutional priorities
	<p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weed management for field crops, horticulture, aromatic herbs ▪ Regulated virus and bacteria of tropical crops (roots and tubers, rice, banana, citrus, sugarcane, etc.) ▪ Search for alternatives: resistant or tolerant genetics ▪ Combination of alternative tools (biocontrol, bio-stimulants, genetic, technology, agronomy, etc.) ▪ Fungal attacks on wood ▪ All alternatives that make sense at technical level (efficacy), economical level, environmental level, societal level for all priority needs, in a context of climate change and global warming ▪ Developing/improving detection methods (bioassays; HTS, multiplexing) ▪ Climate change impact ▪ Face current and upcoming plant health issues in the most sustainable way, regarding climate changes and the lack of authorized chemicals ▪ Yellowing virus ▪ Cobweb disease (<i>Cladobotryum dendroïdes</i>) ▪ <i>Curculio nucum</i> <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Management of downy mildew and black rot in vineyards ▪ Ability to detect emergences (technical & technological issues) ▪ Research on alternatives: biocontrol and means to enhance immunity ▪ Supporting innovation - biocontrol products ▪ Validation of detection methods on treated seeds (at least the more frequent type of treatments) ▪ Get in touch with other European or worldwide region that produce citrus ▪ Developing biocontrol ▪ Sciarid flies (<i>Lycoriella auripila</i>) ▪ <i>Gnomonia leptostyla</i> ▪ Cercosporiosis ▪ <i>Halyomorpha halys</i> <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Management of coleoptera for seeds and plants ▪ Improve morphological identification tools (e.g. matrix keys)
	Institutional priorities
	<p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weed management for field crops, horticulture, aromatic herbs ▪ Regulated virus and bacteria of tropical crops (roots and tubers, rice, banana, citrus, sugarcane, etc.) ▪ Search for alternatives: resistant or tolerant genetics ▪ Combination of alternative tools (biocontrol, bio-stimulants, genetic, technology, agronomy, etc.) ▪ Fungal attacks on wood ▪ All alternatives that make sense at technical level (efficacy), economical level, environmental level, societal level for all priority needs, in a context of climate change and global warming ▪ Developing/improving detection methods (bioassays; HTS, multiplexing) ▪ Climate change impact ▪ Face current and upcoming plant health issues in the most sustainable way, regarding climate changes and the lack of authorized chemicals ▪ Yellowing virus ▪ Cobweb disease (<i>Cladobotryum dendroïdes</i>) ▪ <i>Curculio nucum</i> <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Management of downy mildew and black rot in vineyards ▪ Ability to detect emergences (technical & technological issues) ▪ Research on alternatives: biocontrol and means to enhance immunity ▪ Supporting innovation - biocontrol products ▪ Validation of detection methods on treated seeds (at least the more frequent type of treatments) ▪ Get in touch with other European or worldwide region that produce citrus ▪ Developing biocontrol ▪ Sciarid flies (<i>Lycoriella auripila</i>) ▪ <i>Gnomonia leptostyla</i> ▪ Cercosporiosis ▪ <i>Halyomorpha halys</i> <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Management of coleoptera for seeds and plants ▪ Improve morphological identification tools (e.g. matrix keys)
France	Institutional priorities
	<p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Weed management for field crops, horticulture, aromatic herbs ▪ Regulated virus and bacteria of tropical crops (roots and tubers, rice, banana, citrus, sugarcane, etc.) ▪ Search for alternatives: resistant or tolerant genetics ▪ Combination of alternative tools (biocontrol, bio-stimulants, genetic, technology, agronomy, etc.) ▪ Fungal attacks on wood ▪ All alternatives that make sense at technical level (efficacy), economical level, environmental level, societal level for all priority needs, in a context of climate change and global warming ▪ Developing/improving detection methods (bioassays; HTS, multiplexing) ▪ Climate change impact ▪ Face current and upcoming plant health issues in the most sustainable way, regarding climate changes and the lack of authorized chemicals ▪ Yellowing virus ▪ Cobweb disease (<i>Cladobotryum dendroïdes</i>) ▪ <i>Curculio nucum</i> <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Management of downy mildew and black rot in vineyards ▪ Ability to detect emergences (technical & technological issues) ▪ Research on alternatives: biocontrol and means to enhance immunity ▪ Supporting innovation - biocontrol products ▪ Validation of detection methods on treated seeds (at least the more frequent type of treatments) ▪ Get in touch with other European or worldwide region that produce citrus ▪ Developing biocontrol ▪ Sciarid flies (<i>Lycoriella auripila</i>) ▪ <i>Gnomonia leptostyla</i> ▪ Cercosporiosis ▪ <i>Halyomorpha halys</i> <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Management of coleoptera for seeds and plants ▪ Improve morphological identification tools (e.g. matrix keys)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Exploration of alternatives: physical methods (mechanical, electrical, UV, light) ▪ To facilitate knowledge and deployment of alternative tools for farmers ▪ Improving availability of reference material (strain collection characterization; e.g. by sequencing) ▪ Using/managing plant immunity ▪ Find which diseases are affecting pomelo crops, as a large proportion of the fruits end up with multiple unidentified kind of stains ▪ Weevils ▪ Dry bubble (<i>Lecanicillium fungicola</i>) disease ▪ <i>Cydia pomonella</i> ▪ <i>Pentatomidae</i> <p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Management of <i>D. suzukii</i>, flies, aphids and lepidoptera for fruit trees ▪ Explore new techniques for routine identification (automatic triage, AI, etc.) ▪ Risk characterization: epidemiological surveillance and forecasting models ▪ To facilitate transfer of laboratory results to field conditions ▪ Weed killer resistance ▪ Develop agroecology ▪ Grasses ▪ <i>Fomitiporia</i> <p>Priority 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Management of <i>Alternaria</i> and downy mildew in organic farming ▪ Vectorization, epidemiology, ecology ▪ Precision spraying ▪ To help new actors to emerge in plant health issues ▪ Develop risk analysis in plant health management ▪ <i>Rhagoletis complete</i> ▪ Moths (<i>Lepidoptera</i>) ▪ <i>Phytoptus avellanae</i>
Germany	<p>Institutional priorities</p> <p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Improvement of diagnosis <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research on biology of quarantine pests <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ New technologies for surveys <p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Modeling the effect of climate change on the spread and impact of pests
Lithuania	<p>Institutional priorities</p> <p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research with biological/ alternative plant protection measures and their application in practice ▪ Verticillium stem stripe (<i>Verticillium longisporum</i>) <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Participate in international plant health research programmes ▪ <i>Meligethes aeneus</i> (rape beetle) <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Aphids in cereals as virus vectors <p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Control of pests (insects) in legume crops (peas and beans mainly) <p>Priority 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Control of fungal diseases in legume crops (peas and beans mainly)
Netherlands	<p>Institutional priorities</p> <p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Biological relevance of protein or nucleic-acid based seed/plant health test results ▪ New detection methods for pests and diseases ▪ Development of analysis techniques for organic substrates ▪ Management and control of <i>Phytophthora infestans</i> ▪ <i>nolcyperus</i> (nutgrass); exchange international knowlegde about mitigation of risks and which measures are effective ▪ <i>Meloidogyne chitwoodii</i> and <i>M. fallax</i> ▪ ELISA – PCR ▪ Lack of monitoring in other countries. Countries deny having (quality) organisms ▪ ISPM 15 harmonization in the EU ▪ Initiating and participating in research on biology, taxonomy and epidemiology

	<p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Improved alignment between IPM and phytosanitary requirements third-countries ▪ Optimal use of NGS platforms and pipelines (databases) for detection/identification of Q organisms ▪ Development of sanitation techniques for substrates ▪ Resistance breeding in arable crops ▪ <i>Popillia japonica</i>; exchange international knowledge about mitigation of risks and which measures are effective ▪ <i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i> ▪ Export test ▪ Tendency of third countries to require tests for all organisms, while these are not important from a phytosanitary point of view, because they are quality organisms ▪ Closer collaboration with custom authorities on import of goods combined with wood packaging material (WPM) ▪ Innovative methods in diagnostics (classic and molecular) and early detection approaches <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Enhance information exchange between institutes and industry on determination of phytosanitary risks ▪ Identifying insect vectors and host plant range for spread of plant diseases ▪ management of <i>Erwinia/Dickeya</i> in cultivation of potato ▪ <i>Ralstonia pseudosolanacearum</i>: which crops are host plants, how it manifests and measures ▪ <i>Cyperus esculentus</i> ▪ Unify methods ▪ Lack of international coordination on the use of homogeneous testing methods in third countries. This leads to wrong interpretations ▪ Creating more (public) awareness on the phytosanitary risks connected to WPM in logistics ▪ Collection management, especially developing vouchered molecular reference collection (i.e. Q-bank) <p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Development of sequencing techniques for seed /plant health testing: research on use and interpretation of results - harmonized approach to data generation and interpretation, validation of methods, biological relevance of results ▪ Development of resistant cultivars and new crop protection tools (e.g., RNAi & bio-fungicides) ▪ Research on vectors of virus diseases ▪ Wart disease ▪ <i>Globodera rostochiensis</i> and <i>G. pallida</i> ▪ Robotization ▪ Some Third Countries blame problems on imported starting material, whilst local cultivation methods need to be improved ▪ Capacity building, data sharing and training (education, PhDs, field collection trips, etc.) <p>Priority 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ New sampling strategies and methods ▪ <i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i>, <i>Clavibacter sepedonicus</i> ▪ Data enrichment ▪ Validating diagnostic methods for all EU Q pests
Norway	<p>Institutional priorities</p> <p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Detection and management of viruses and other pests ▪ Pesticides or biopesticides against pests in fruits and berries ▪ Overwintering fungi, management and knowledge ▪ Development and implementation of solutions for sustainable use of resources ▪ Pests (<i>Anthonomus rubi</i>) in organic strawberry production ▪ Biological control of damage agents ▪ How does diversification of forest tree species composition and structure at site and landscape level affect forest resilience against different abiotic and biotic disturbances ▪ Bark beetles ▪ Root and butt rot ▪ Novel regeneration methods ▪ Fungi

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Development of varieties with higher resistance to diseases <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Preservation of genetic material ▪ Fungi in grasses and clover ▪ Pests (<i>Lygus rugulipennis</i>) in organic vegetable production ▪ Peat-free growing substrates for cultivating different plant species ▪ Diagnostic tools and procedures to prevent introduction and establishment of alien pests and pathogens ▪ Weevils ▪ Rationalization in establishment of mixed tree species forests ▪ Identification of resistance genes with CRISPR <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Marketing of Norwegian plant material adapted to Norwegian climate ▪ Pollinators in organic fruit and berry production ▪ Bio-secure seed delivery ▪ Use of remote sensing to monitor forest health condition, also that of individual tree species in mixed tree species forests ▪ Root and butt rot ▪ Preventative methods against pathogenic wood decay fungi ▪ Reduction of abiotic stressors ▪ Research on production that promotes soil health and plant health <p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Develop better and more consistent plant material ▪ Increased understanding of the basis of genetic variation in tree resistance against specific abiotic and biotic disorders ▪ Drought (Norway spruce) ▪ Research on use of beneficial organisms, especially in the field <p>Priority 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Identification tree species compositions that are beneficial to prevent specific damage agents or abiotic disorders on specific site conditions
Slovakia	<p>Institutional priorities</p> <p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Conservation of genetic diversity of economically important plant species for food and agriculture ▪ Invasive pests <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ecological cultivation of genetic resources ▪ Nonchemical and biocontrol control of pests <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Biopesticides as a promising alternative to synthetic pesticides ▪ Essential oils <p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Use multifunctionality of forage crops for pests reduction ▪ Entomogenous fungi <p>Priority 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Soil health and diversity as part of non-chemical pest management ▪ biocontrol of soil pathogens
Sweden	<p>Institutional priorities</p> <p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The work with risk ranking of quarantine pests will be continued. FinnPRIO (https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-016-1123-4) is used to determine the risk different pests constitute to Sweden ▪ Plant resistance (i.e. ash trees with ash dieback and emerald ash borer). Studies of bronze birch borer would also be possible via key collaborations with colleagues in Canada and USA ▪ Analytical tools for "new" potato diseases <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Improve our ability of incorporating climate change in PRAs that is fit for purpose ▪ Trap design and lure improvement for Buprestid beetles (key collaborations within bronze borer infestation range in Canada and key collaborations within Baltic countries and Ukraine who are monitor for emerald ash borer) ▪ Molecular markers for distinguish between different clubroot pathotypes <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Improve the assessments of environmental impact in PRAs ▪ Rapid, portable detection and monitoring tools for both targeted pests/pathogen diagnostics and untargeted approaches that can be used for high throughput

	<p>screening of plants or other suspect plant products at ports of entry or in nursery surveys. This also includes RNA-based approaches that would allow identification of alive/viable propagules on tested substrates as opposed to DNA-based approaches which cannot distinguish between that which is alive/dead</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantification of fungal infections in cereal crop species
United Kingdom	Institutional priorities
	Priority 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase surveillance and monitoring of plant health in Gardens Climate change adaptation
	Priority 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Box problems research: management of box tree moth (<i>Cydalima perspectalis</i>) and box blight fungi (<i>Calonectria</i> spp.) Identification of alternative forestry species
	Priority 3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring and mitigating spread of <i>Phytophthora</i> species Preparedness for and response to new pests and pathogens
	Priority 4 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identification of new and changes in established plant health problems in a changing climate

5.2 The medium-term research (5-10 years) priorities identified through the top-down approach

Country	Medium-term (5-10 years) research priorities
Austria	Institutional priorities
	Priority 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordination on main issues Soil protection Healthy propagating material for plant production in professional horticulture Grapevine flavescence dorée
	Priority 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of appropriate legal framework Autonomous plant protection systems Safe testing methods for scions and rootstocks in nurseries and other propagating material in plant production
	Priority 3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Funding of research activities Resistance management Information for inspectors and professional operators about pests and possible confusion with other causes
	Priority 4 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Detecting diseases, pests and competitors through AI Combination of traps for different pests on the same locations to optimize working hours
	Priority 5 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information about good practice for eradication and containment of pests
Belgium	Institutional priorities
	Priority 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sensitization to phytosanitary risks, more training to new diseases recognition Avoiding introduction of pests by efficient plant health checks Climate soil water relationship Biodiversity and climate Development of the One Health concept (biodiversity part) Development of European infrastructures such as MIRRI (access to microbial resources, including those relevant to agri-food) Availability of detailed data on the location of risk sites for each quarantine pest Awareness-visibility Plant Health (e.g. within one health framework) Diagnostics
	Priority 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> More communication to the operators Survey of plant health on the territory Monitoring of forest trees pathogens, pests and bacteria Data collection and reach out to research on QP and potential QP QP and RNQP
	Priority 3

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Testing more the phytosanitary knowledge's operators to the phytosanitary issues (they doesn't always understand their responsibilities and obligations) ▪ Fast detection and identification methods for pests ▪ Methodology for estimating the health status of tree crowns ▪ Criteria/ decision making on regulation (output horizon scan, risk assessment) ▪ Plant health (emerging) problems in support of the sector <p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Obtain faster results of analyses ▪ Integration of new technologies and artificial intelligence ▪ IPM: reducing pesticide impact
Estonia	Institutional priorities
	Priority 1
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Maintaining high level of surveillance in the face of reduced co-financing
	Priority 2
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strengthening phytosanitary border control methods and processes; raising awareness of travelling and international trade
	Priority 3
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increasing the effectiveness of integrated pest management, especially for cereals, potato and rapeseed; better control measures for clubroot disease
	Priority 4
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Carrying out research and exchange experience and practices on certain pests between EU Member States
	Priority 5
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Innovation: development of new diagnostic tools and control measures for certain pests
France	Institutional priorities
	Priority 1
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sustainable management of major pests (wireworms, viruses, blackleg, etc.) ▪ Climate change impact ▪ Combination strategy for plant protection instead of only relying on chemical products. This strategy is based on four pillars : Bio-solutions (Biopesticides + bio-stimulants) - Biotechnologies - Digital agriculture and plant protection products
	Priority 2
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Surveillance and prevention of harmful pests to preserve the health status of seed lots and farms, including innovative monitoring ▪ Developing biocontrol
	Priority 3
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Epidemiology and risk assessment (conditions for the development of pathogens, identification of reservoirs, DSS, etc.) for major pests (wireworms, diseases vectored by insects, blackleg, etc.) ▪ Using/managing plant immunity
	Priority 4
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Innovative, reliable and cost-effective tools for the diagnostics, detection or quantification of pests, notably for certification (viruses, bacteria, nematodes, etc.) ▪ Develop agroecology
	Priority 5
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Indicators and means to improve biological soil fertility and global plant health ▪ develop risk analysis in plant health management
Germany	Institutional priorities
	Priority 1
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Establishing a quality management system ▪ Prioritization according to urgency and priority in order to organize the completion of tasks with the given personnel and technical resources ▪ Detection of (Q)SE ▪ <i>Saperda candida</i> detection with sniffer dogs
	Priority 2
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Simulation exercises ▪ Knowledge transfer and ensuring that all employees have access to and use relevant information ▪ Wood packing material surveys in the vicinity of tree nurseries
	Priority 3
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Monitoring program: establishing of knowledge about flows of goods, risk locations, settlement conditions ▪ Complete digitalization of controls and administration

	<p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Improvement of public relation: internet, social media, events ▪ Introduction of a QM system in the area of import controls ▪ Industrial hygiene during processing, disposal <p>Priority 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Introduction of a QM system in the entire area of plant health and review of implementation ▪ Use of fermentation residues from the biogas plant, analyses
Lithuania	<p>Institutional priorities</p> <p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Implementation of official laboratory functions and national reference laboratory functions <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Phytosanitary research and diagnostics collaboration in Northern EU, continental and cooperation (e.g. skill and knowledge transfer). <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Effectiveness of composting as a phytosanitary measure to be used for eradication of outbreaks of bacterial potato diseases (e.g. <i>Clavibacter sepedonicus</i>, <i>Ralsotnia solanacearum</i>) <p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Database of possible purchase of pheromones/traps for implementation of surveillance programmes, especially for priority pests and taking into account other QP as well
	<p>Institutional priorities</p> <p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Climate change impact <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Keeping control of international trade and transport (including postal packages) <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Impact of new diagnostic tools and taxonomic developments on the regulation of organisms <p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ International collaboration and homogenization of methods used in plant quarantine
Netherlands	<p>Institutional priorities</p> <p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Decay in Sitka spruce forests in the coast ▪ Moth species causing defoliation on broadleaved trees (such as <i>Epirrita autumnata</i>, <i>Operophtera brumata</i>, <i>Agriopis aurantiaria</i>) ▪ Urban agriculture ▪ Digitization of the plant import process <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Large pine beetle (<i>Hylobius abietis</i>) ▪ Root rot on first generation Norway spruce forests ▪ Urban biodiversity ▪ Guidance and information <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mouse eating the bark of Norway spruce and Sitka spruce plants ▪ Dieback of trembling aspen (causative agent unknown) ▪ Green roofs ▪ Surveillance programs <p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Deer browsing on Norway spruce and Sitka spruce plants ▪ Decay caused by <i>Phellinus pini</i> in old Scots pine forests ▪ Contingency plans <p>Priority 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Identification and risk assessments of new threats ▪ Some <i>Ips typographus</i> damages
	<p>Institutional priorities</p> <p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Development of biological methods ▪ Registration of new chemicals for insect pests treatment <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Integrated plant protection and sustainable pesticide use ▪ Ways to effectively control mistletoe on pine trees <p>Priority 3</p>
Poland	<p>Institutional priorities</p> <p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Development of biological methods ▪ Registration of new chemicals for insect pests treatment <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Integrated plant protection and sustainable pesticide use ▪ Ways to effectively control mistletoe on pine trees <p>Priority 3</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Monitoring and early detection of crop diseases ▪ Large protected animals and cervids and their impact on the forest environment <p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research on plant resistance ▪ Strengthening biodiversity and the resilience of forests against pests <p>Priority 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Education and awareness
Sweden	<p>Institutional priorities</p> <p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Continue working and influencing higher political level on the need for the establishment of a national reference laboratory in Sweden for diagnosis of plant pests. Today these services are purchased by tender from another country <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Risk ranking of pests of interest for the Swedish (Northern Europe) ecoclimatic conditions to facilitate awareness raising and prioritization of limited resources <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Practical exercising of established contingency plans together with external stakeholders who may be affected by future large scale outbreak of pests. This would also contribute to improve the contingency plans, and to raise awareness about plant health area
United Kingdom	<p>Institutional priorities</p> <p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Risk and horizon scanning for new plant health risks ▪ Identification and implementation of nature-based solutions ▪ Outbreak preparedness ▪ Use of new technology (AI, advances in Remote Sensing, Earth Observation etc.) ▪ Find ways to reduce the human resource input into certification schemes <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Detection and diagnosis for pests and diseases at border and inland ▪ Increased treescape resilience to new pest and disease introductions ▪ International engagement ▪ Identification/Analysis of novel pathways for pests and diseases introduction ▪ Improve ways to better detect pests and diseases at the border <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Effectively managing pests and diseases outbreaks while minimizing environmental impact and cost ▪ Changes in pest and disease prevalence/presence as a result of climate change ▪ Raising awareness of plant health across society ▪ Influence of a changing climate on the severity of pests and diseases impacts ▪ Find ways to better detect cryptic diseases in imported samples <p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Developing landscapes resilient to future pests and diseases ▪ Improving biosecurity across the plant supply chain ▪ Cumulative impact of pests and diseases, i.e. multiple pests or diseases attacking same host tree/species at the same time ▪ Examine ways to better use data we and other inspection bodies collect <p>Priority 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Building plant health science capability ▪ Find ways to better exchange information and experience with outer NPPOs / inspectorates

5.3 Outcome of the consultation: common research priorities for the region

The report on the international workshop 'Plant Health Research Priorities for Northern Europe' (Annex 2) contains the minutes from the three working group discussions held during the event. These discussions led to the identification of the following common research priorities for the region:

Advancing diagnostics for phytosanitary import controls

With the increasing globalization of trade and the rise of e-commerce, effective diagnostic methods at entry points are critical for preventing the introduction of quarantine pests through plant material and passenger-carried items. This research priority focuses on developing,

validating and implementing rapid, cost-effective and easy-to-use diagnostic tools to enhance phytosanitary inspections at borders.

Key areas of focus include:

- Improved diagnostic methods for identifying bacterial and viral pathogens in plant materials during import controls
- Enhancing capabilities for border inspections and monitoring e-commerce shipments and passenger-carried items
- Validation of innovative diagnostic technologies such as next-generation sequencing (NGS), environmental DNA (eDNA), lateral flow assays (LFA), loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP), recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA), rolling circle amplification (RCA) and Oxford Nanopore Sequencing
- Ensuring these methods are reliable, fast and practical for use by National Plant Protection Organizations (NPPOs) both at entry points and in field monitoring
- Developing alternative diagnostic tools that minimize the time required for import controls
- Reducing reliance on traditional laboratory-based testing by implementing portable and field-ready systems
- Training border inspection personnel and NPPO staff in the application of new diagnostic methods
- Promoting knowledge exchange and developing fast recognition systems to identify quarantine pests efficiently

Strengthening phytosanitary measures for trade in wood and related commodities

The global trade of wood and wood-derived materials, such as woodchips and bark, presents significant phytosanitary risks due to the potential for pest and pathogen introduction. This research priority focuses on improving risk assessment, treatment efficiency, and safety protocols for these high-risk commodities.

Key objectives include:

- Gather detailed data on trade characteristics, including the types and quality of wood materials (e.g., bark-free wood, woodchips, bark) and their associated risks
- Evaluate current phytosanitary measures and their effectiveness in mitigating risks for these materials
- Assess the efficiency of sterilization methods for large volumes of wood-derived materials, such as woodchip piles
- Investigate the type and quality of wood used to produce these materials and analyze how treatments affect pest and pathogen eradication
- Conduct studies on imported woodchips to evaluate their condition before and after treatment, ensuring compliance with phytosanitary standards
- Develop protocols for assessing entire shipments of wood and wood-derived commodities rather than relying on sample subsets, to ensure they are fully safe for trade
- Examine the safety of sea containers and the packaging materials used in transporting these commodities to identify additional risks
- Identify and test innovative technologies and methods to improve the reliability and efficiency of phytosanitary treatments for large-scale materials
- Explore alternative approaches to ensure consistent sterilization of entire shipments

Addressing potato diseases and vector management

Potato production faces significant challenges from a wide range of diseases and pests, many of which pose threats to both yield and trade. Key issues include managing diseases such as potato wart, mop-top virus (PMTV), *Ralstonia solanacearum*, phytoplasmas, and emerging threats like *Harsenphonus* and zebra chip. With limited knowledge about certain pathogens,

such as phytoplasmas, and their vectors, focused research is essential to protect potato crops globally.

Key objectives:

- Investigate insect vectors like leafhoppers, which are known to transmit viruses and phytoplasmas
- Study the biology, lifecycle and transmission mechanisms of these vectors to develop targeted management strategies
- Focus on regulated quarantine organisms, including the vector of *Liberibacter solanacearum* haplotype Solanaceae, to prevent their spread within Europe and beyond
- Develop and refine high-throughput sequencing (HTS) and other advanced diagnostic tools to rapidly and accurately detect potato diseases
- Strengthen epidemiological surveillance to track the spread of diseases and their vectors, especially under the pressures of climate change and reduced chemical control options
- Promote the sharing and standardization of testing methods for seed potatoes across countries to ensure consistency and reliability
- Address trade-related issues by improving phytosanitary protocols for the import and export of potatoes and seed potatoes
- Assess how global trade and the movement of potatoes and seed potatoes contribute to the spread of diseases and pests
- Consider climate change as a driving factor that increases the prevalence and impact of pests and pathogens in potato production

Advancing pest monitoring and detection systems

Effective pest monitoring and early detection are critical components in Plant Health protection, especially for high-risk pests in both agronomic and forestry contexts. This research priority focuses on the development and validation of innovative tools and techniques for monitoring and trapping pests, with an emphasis on improving the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of inspection processes.

Key objectives:

- Explore new approaches to pest surveillance, such as remote sensing technologies and digital platforms for real-time data collection and analysis
- Investigate the use of smart traps for detecting pests, including those targeting Scolytinae and Cerambycidae—two significant insect groups of quarantine concern
- Develop and test novel trapping systems, such as the newly developed fan trap in Belgium, assessing their cost efficiency compared to existing methods
- Enhance pest detection capabilities using automatic image recognition technologies, enabling rapid and accurate identification of pests, such as *Anoplophora glabripennis* (Asian longhorned beetle)
- Improve trapping techniques for pests like *Agrilus* and *Epitrix* (on potatoes), focusing on trap color, shape, placement and lure effectiveness
- Incorporate citizen science to expand monitoring efforts and enhance data collection, particularly in areas where traditional surveillance might be limited
- Test and validate alternative pest monitoring techniques, including sentinel plants and vectors, for a broader understanding of pest presence and movement
- Establish an international network for validating trapping systems and methodologies, allowing participating countries to test and compare different trapping systems
- Support the validation of pest detection techniques and traps across multiple countries, ensuring that methods are universally applicable and effective in different regions

Advancing Integrated Pest Management (IPM) and sustainable plant protection

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-01 under grant agreement No 101130467

The future of Plant Health relies on reducing dependency on chemical pesticides and exploring alternative, sustainable methods for pest control. This research priority focuses on advancing IPM strategies, with an emphasis on biological control, resistance breeding, and ecological alternatives to chemical treatments.

Key Objectives:

- Explore the use of biological pesticides and biocontrol agents (BCAs) to target quarantine pests, with a focus on developing environmentally friendly and sustainable plant protection products
- Investigate the role of natural predators and beneficial organisms in managing pest populations, reducing reliance on chemical control
- Continue projects focused on breeding potatoes with resistance to key pests and diseases, aiming to reduce the need for chemical interventions
- Foster collaboration between countries to share knowledge about natural biological pest control methods that have been successful in other regions, enabling the transfer of effective strategies across borders
- Build on previous Euphresco projects to expand research on IPM and biocontrol, learning from international experiences and adapting them to local contexts
- Research alternatives to peat in nursery production, moving towards more sustainable growth substrates
- Investigate the ecological implications of different growth substrates and their potential to support healthy plant growth while maintaining pest control efficacy
- Explore specific strategies for controlling pests like *Anoplophora glabripennis* through ecological methods, emphasizing sustainable, long-term solutions for pest management

Raising awareness and engaging public participation in Plant Health

Raising awareness about Plant Health is critical, especially for key crops like potatoes, which are vital to global food security. As one of the most important crops worldwide, potatoes play a central role in food systems and offer a unique opportunity to engage the public in Plant Health initiatives.

Key Objectives:

- Use the importance of potatoes as a central theme to raise awareness about Plant Health and its impact on global food systems. By emphasizing their role in food security, this initiative aims to engage a broad audience in understanding the need for plant protection
- Promote the concept of "One World, One Health," highlighting the interconnectedness between Plant Health, human health and environmental health, reinforcing the idea that protecting crops is essential for the well-being of all living systems
- Encourage public participation in Plant Health research through citizen science initiatives, such as pest monitoring, data collection, and reporting of plant diseases. This approach can increase the scale of monitoring efforts and contribute valuable data to research
- Identify and implement effective communication strategies to inform and engage the public on Plant Health issues. Use diverse channels such as social media, educational campaigns and community outreach to reach different audiences, from farmers to consumers

Enhancing knowledge exchange on *Xylella* research

Xylella fastidiosa is a significant plant pathogen that poses a major threat to agriculture and natural ecosystems worldwide. Given the complexity and urgency of managing *Xylella* outbreaks, there is an ongoing body of research aimed at understanding its biology, spread, and impact. However, despite the substantial progress in research, the key challenge remains

the effective exchange of knowledge and coordination among research efforts to accelerate progress and implement effective control measures.

Key Objectives:

- Establish platforms and networks that facilitate the sharing of research findings, methodologies, and best practices among scientists, regulatory bodies and stakeholders involved in *Xylella* research
- Encourage international collaboration and information exchange to avoid duplication of efforts, identify gaps in research and promote the development of coordinated strategies to combat the spread of *Xylella*

5.4 The suggested research topics for 2025 and 2026

Research topic 1 – Trade: diagnosis at entry point

- Various pests
- Various commodities
- Validation of lateral flow assay (LFA), loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP), recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA), rolling circle amplification (RCA), oxford nanopore sequencing for use at inspection points
- Enhanced protection at border, reduce testing in the laboratory, faster controls

This research topic is being developed by a dedicated working group comprising experts from the following regions and disciplines: Australia, Northern Europe and the Diagnostics industry. It will be proposed for the upcoming 2025 call.

Research topic 2 – Network for trap testing and validation

- Various commodities
- Various pests relevant for the agronomic and forest sector
- Validation of trapping systems in the participating countries. Validation will cover: i) Trapping techniques, i.e. colour and shape of the traps, type of lure, position ii) Detection methodologies, i.e. automatic recognition through photographs
- Reciprocal testing for countries that cannot validate traps because they do not have the pest, better monitoring

This research topic is being developed by a dedicated working group comprising experts from the following regions and disciplines: Northern Europe, North America, forestry and the Mediterranean region. It will be proposed for the upcoming 2025 call.

Research topic 3 – Trade: Risk assessment and measures for wood material

- Various pests
- Bark free wood, woodchip, bark
- Validate phytosanitary methods for large volumes, collect data on trade (type of wood, quality before and after treatment)
- Better knowledge on trade, safer trade

Research topic 4 – potato diseases and vectors

- Wart disease, *Ralstonia solanacearum*, mop-top virus, phytoplasmas
- Pest management, diagnostics of seed potatoes, vectors
- Protect potato production

Research topic 5 – Raising awareness on Plant Health issues

- Various pests
- Various commodities, potato could be used as a paradigm
- Use case studies to communicate on Plant Health, raising awareness, engaging with the public (citizen science)
- Engagement with communities

Research topic 6 – Sharing knowledge on *Xylella fastidiosa*

- *Xylella fastidiosa*
- Various commodities
- Knowledge exchange on past and ongoing research activities on the bacterium
- Capacity and synergies building

Research topic 7 – Integrated pest management

- Various pests
- Various commodities
- Test and validate alternative methods: BCAs, resistant plants
- New solutions for pest management

6 The programmes and the funds allocated to Plant Health research *(optional, if already known or if Funding survey has already been conducted)*

The funding survey has not been conducted yet.

7 Coordination and collaboration *(optional, if already known or if Funding survey has already been conducted)*

The funding survey has not been conducted yet.

8 Supplementary information or messages originated from the consultation

The report on the international workshop 'Plant Health Research Priorities for Northern Europe' (Annex 2) includes participants' comments and feedback gathered during the consultation.

ANNEX 1: Survey analysis by the Centre of Excellence for Biosecurity Risk Analysis (CEBRA)

Summary

Centre of Excellent for Biosecurity Risk Analysis (CEBRA) has conducted analysis of survey results for the European Phytosanitary Research Coordination (EUPHRESCO). The *EUPHRESCO III* survey elicits responses from over 100 organisations across northern Europe involved in phytosanitary research, research funding, policy making, and associated industries. The survey asks these organisations about priorities for phytosanitary issues such as capability building, commodities, priority pests and research needs. Analysis suggests that the spatial context of responses is significant, and that common interests between respondents is noticeable in clustered analysis of extracted concepts. Common interests are clustered in map representations and along multiple conceptual dimensions. Improvements to the survey instrument are recommended ahead of future survey work.

This report adjusts some of the reporting criteria in response to feedback from EUPHRESCO on 24 September 2024.

Introduction

CEBREA has conducted analysis of the EUPHRESCO III survey results relating to research priorities for phytosanitary research in Northern Europe. As an outcome of the analysis, CEBRA delivers:

- This **report**, including methods, results and discussion and recommendations
- Attached files used to process survey responses
- A **presentation** of this Report (delivered 24 September 2024)

The report structure is as follows:

- **Recommendations**, given the Results and Discussion
- **Methodology**, including a System view diagram and references to reuseable code and vocabularies
- **Results**, including a number of charts (including references to charts in the Appendix)
- **Discussion**, including common interests between survey responses, and notes towards improving the survey instrument
- **Reference** list
- **Appendix**, including tables and figures

Recommendations

Given the Results and issues arising in the Discussion, CEBRA recommends that:

- the spatial proximity of extracted concepts be noted, aside from other insights
- common interests between parties be noted. Common interests are clustered in map representations and along multiple conceptual dimensions
- the survey instrument be improved to better handle responses. Improved validation will ensure processing is scalable (less dependent on manual work) and more straightforward interpretation of results. Areas for survey design improvement in the **Discussion**.

Methodology

The survey responses were codified using machine-automated indexing. Indexes were based on controlled vocabularies designed to capture concepts in biosecurity research, an output of the Biosecurity Portal project (Kneebone, 2022).

The method steps include:

- **Data cleaning** – manual fix of data formatting issues
- **Data transformation** – converting tabular data to machine-readable format compatible with graph database storage
- **Ontology design** – define properties for question and responses, and interrelate within the database
- **Vocabularies** – classify responses with vocabulary terms; iteratively update vocabularies where needed based on gap analysis
- **Aggregation** – use broader vocabulary concepts to aggregate common interests (capability needs, commodity concerns, priority pests, research priorities)
- **Clustering** – report weighted commonality between respondents based on interests, geolocated

System view

The diagram below gives a system view (applications, databases and code) of the methods used.

Figure 1. System view

Data cleaning

We point out some of the pre-processing cleaning we conducted. See also Survey design feedback for discussion on fixing some data validation and consistency issues in future survey work.

Null responses

While only one question is stated as ‘optional’, there are other questions with no response. These include blank cells or text indicating no response (“none”, “n/a” etc). We blacklisted responses such as these (that is, we treated these as null responses) in our processing.

Multiple responses

Many responses included multiple, distinct statements. These were delimited in different ways including line breaks, semi-colons and bullet points. We removed any rich text elements in our processing.

Spatial entities

Spatial entities were elicited for organisation country and for the ‘scales’. There were some consistency issues for responses. We applied the following changes before processing:

- Country names harmonised, to conform with GeoNames (GeoNames, n.d.) official name (en)
- Sub-units removed, e.g. Austria/Burgenland → Austria; BE (Région Wallonne) → Belgium
- Broadest value taken for mixed answer results, e.g. “country, EU” → Region

Data transformation

Respondent data was transformed into Resource Description Format (RDF) (W3C, 2004) using R scripts, and loaded into a GraphDB database (Ontotext, 2023). Sample transformation scripts are available: [Figshare address?].

Transformations tasks include:

- Mapping column headings to the custom ontology, e.g. “Which pests do you consider a global priority?” → <https://ontology.cebra.unimelb.edu.au/globalPestPriority>
- Concept extraction for response text. Matching terms from Biosecurity Thesaurus; Priority Pests; Commodities with response text, e.g. <cebra:globalPestPriority> <https://umelb-pp.poolparty.biz/Pests/1245>

Transformed survey response data is loaded into a GraphDB database. CEBRA hosts an Ontotext GraphDB Free license edition on Linux 5.15.0-113-generic operating system / Ubuntu 11.0.23. We use the GraphDB SPARQL Endpoint to query the database. SPARQL queries are executed from within R scripts. Sample queries are provided with this report.

Ontology design

Each survey question was codified as a property so that statements about the questions could be made in a standard database format. The properties together are documented within a custom ontology, which is basically a set of properties with information about how the properties relate to each other and to associated standards such as data types and vocabularies.

We developed properties that would address conceptual elements in the survey questions, but might be reused in future survey iterations or other project work. For example, the property `cebra:shortTermResearchNeed` broadly captures the intent of the question that mentions a

three-year timeframe – we have captured this as ‘short term’ so that the property can be reused for a similar question with different timeframe (1, 2, 4 years etc).

The following example shows how embedded questions are formalised within the ontology:

Which pests do you consider a regional priority? (provide a maximum of 5 pests with Latin name and the main factor that drives the priority (economy, trade, strategy, policy...))

... included two sub-units:

Pest n; Factor of priority n

We developed the following properties:

```
<https://ontology.cebra.unimelb.edu.au/regionalPestPriority> a owl:ObjectProperty;  
  rdfs:comment "Pest priorities as defined for a given region such as ‘northern Europe’"@en,
```

```
  "Priorités des ravageurs telles que définies pour une région donnée telle que  
  \\'l'Europe du Nord\'"@fr;
```

```
  rdfs:label "Regional pest priority"@en .
```

```
<https://ontology.cebra.unimelb.edu.au/pestPriorityFactor> a owl:ObjectProperty;
```

```
  rdfs:subPropertyOf <https://ontology.cebra.unimelb.edu.au/regionalPestPriority>;
```

```
  rdfs:comment "Contexte de priorisation des ravageurs."@fr, "Context for pest  
  prioritization."@en;
```

```
  rdfs:label "Pest priority factor"@en .
```

Note that `cebra:pestPriorityFactor` is a ‘sub property’ of `cebra:regionalPestPriority`.

The full set of custom properties, together with other metadata elements used in this project, are tabled in the Appendix.

Vocabularies

Question responses were classified using controlled vocabularies. As for other systems of coding qualitative data, vocabularies provide a system for describing and identifying concepts within unstructured text. We used three vocabularies to classify responses:

- Biosecurity Thesaurus (ARDCa n.d.)
- Priority Pests (ARDCb n.d.)
- Commodities (ARDCc n.d.)

We used all three of these vocabularies to classify some questions (such as “Identify a maximum of 5 key plant health issues...”), and for others a single vocabulary was used (e.g. Commodities vocabulary was used to classify “Which agricultural crops are important...”).

The three vocabularies are developed in conformance with the Simple Knowledge Organisation System (SKOS) standard (Miles & Bechhofe, 2009), and therefore include the following key features:

- *Equivalence*: all concepts have a preferred label in English, and most have additionally an alternative label for a synonym, quasi-synonym or antonym.

- *Hierarchy*: we follow the qSKOS guideline (Mader, n.d.) with respect to broader-narrower relationships between concepts. That is, all concepts are members of a hierarchy (or taxonomy) of other concepts. There are no 'orphan' concepts.

Together, the equivalence and hierarchical relationships are used to improve the reach and precision of response classification. An example that has great value in biosecurity and the life sciences generally is establishing equivalence between common and scientific names as preferred and alternative labels. This allows an automated classification system to classify a response text that contains "Phytophthora infestans" with a concept that has preferred label "Potato late blight" but also alternative label "Phytophthora infestans".

Aggregation

The hierarchical relationship allows aggregation of concepts to some broader level that may be more useful to analysis. For example, respondents may separately report research issues "Fungicide", "Herbicide" and "Pesticide" – we can report that these respondents collectively report "Active substances" as an issue. Similarly, "Plums", "Cherries" and "Apricots" can be aggregated to "Stone fruit" in the Commodities vocabulary. For pests, we can aggregate species to intermediate or non-taxonomic groups such as "exotic fruit fly", or establish broader matches with frameworks that are common in biosecurity (terrestrial invertebrates; weeds; plant diseases; pathogenic fungus etc).

Clustering

We used extracted concepts with high occurrence counts as the basis for concept clustering. This approach was used to generate 'common interest' maps, where organisations that reported common research interests can be seen in the context of their geospatial context. The Common interest maps are referred to in the **Discussion**.

Results

Pest priorities

We analysed responses for pest occurrences, using the Priority Pests vocabulary. *Pest responses per organisation* is tabled in the Appendix.

Percentage of Pests Broad Concepts Across All Countries

Figure 2. Percentage of regional pest priority broad concepts across all countries

Insects account for just over half (53.6%) of all pest occurrences across all responses, with Plant diseases accounting for about 38%, Nematodes 8% and Weeds 1%.

We break down regional pest broad classifications by organisation country below.

Figure 3. Regional Pest Priority Broad Concept Per Country

Commodities

We analysed responses for commodity occurrences, using the Commodities vocabulary. *Commodity responses per organisation* is tabled in the Appendix.

Percentage of Commodities Broad Concepts Across All Countries

Figure 4. Percentage of Commodities Broad Concepts Across All Countries

We found across all responses a near even breakdown of commodity classes with Vegetable crops a leading concern (37.2%), followed by Fruit crops (18.8%), Cereals (17.5%), Wood commodities (15.2%) and Seeds (6.3%).

We break down regional Commodity broad classifications by organisation country below.

Figure 5. Commodities Broad Concept Counts Per Country

Plant health activities

We analysed responses from a range of questions relating to research priorities and capability building using the *Biosecurity Thesaurus*.

Percentage of Plant Health Activities Broad Concepts Across All Countries

Figure 6. Percentage of Biosecurity Thesaurus Broad Concepts Across All Countries

The broad classifications used combine top concepts from the [Biosecurity Thesaurus](#) as such:

- *Risk assessment* = Pest risk + Risk analysis
- *Diagnostics and surveillance* = Screening + Surveillance
- *Management* = Control measures + Treatment
- *Knowledge exchange, capacity and infrastructure* = Biosecurity capability

We break down Plant health activities by organisation country below.

Figure 7. Biosecurity Thesaurus Broad Concept Counts Per Country

Discussion

The results suggest that there are some common research areas between organisations.

We assumed that common interests will be, in part, the product of spatial proximity between organisations – that is, interests (especially with respect to priority pests and commodities) will be partly determined by geographical location, given the prevalence of those concepts within given climatic and geographical conditions. The results reflect this assumption somewhat and unevenly across the themes.

Common commodity interests

Cluster analysis for the most commonly reported priority pest concepts per organisation are plotted using spatial coordinates. In *Commodity concept clusters map* (Figure 8, Appendix), some geographical trends can be seen. Cluster 4 (Potatoes; Grains; Ornamental plants; Nursery crops; Berries) are found in the northern central map region. Cluster 3 (Crops; Birch; European Ash) do not occur in Eastern central region.

Common pest interests

Cluster analysis for the most commonly reported priority pest concepts per organisation are plotted using spatial coordinates. In *Commodity priority pest clusters map* (Figure 9, Appendix), there is a similar geographical trend as that seen for commodities. Cluster 4 (Spotted Wing Drosophila; BMSB; Phytoplasmas; Plenodumas lingam; Plum pox virus) are found in the northern central map region. Cluster 3 (Tomato brown rugose fruit virus; Parasitic nematodes) do not occur in Eastern central region.

Common Biosecurity Thesaurus interests

Cluster analysis for the most commonly reported concepts per organisation drawn from the Biosecurity Thesaurus are plotted using spatial coordinates. In *Common Biosecurity Thesaurus interests map* (Figure 10, Appendix), there is again a trend around cluster 4 but otherwise geographical spread seems more even over northern Europe compared to commodity-specific and pest-specific concerns.

Combined Common interests

Cluster analysis combining scores for concepts across commodities, pests and Biosecurity Thesaurus is plotted using spatial coordinates; see *Combined Common Interests map* (Figure 11, Appendix).

Vocabulary issues

The project was a net gain for the three existing vocabulary projects – much of the extracted respondent text was retained either as new concepts or alternative labels for existing concepts. In some cases, new reference structures were developed so that concept classes could be captured and reported. The vocabularies can be accessed at Research Vocabularies Australia:

- Biosecurity Thesaurus
<https://vocabs.ardc.edu.au/viewById/646>
- Commodities
<https://demo.vocabs.ardc.edu.au/viewById/1096>
- Priority Pests
<https://vocabs.ardc.edu.au/viewById/645>

Synonyms

We ran a no-match report against the three vocabularies. In many cases we added labels to our vocabularies where labels (including synonyms) were lacking in our vocabularies, for example:

- “Soybean” added as skos:hiddenLabel for “Soya beans”
- “Biosecurity legislation” added as skos:altLabel for “Biosecurity policy”

New concepts

New concepts were added to all vocabularies in response to the no-match report.

For impacted commodities, forest species were lacking in the Commodities vocabulary and subsequently added (European Ash; Sitka Spruce; Oaks; Beeches; Chestnut trees; Birch; Pinus sylvestris; Norway Spruce).

New reference structures – new mid-level concepts

The Priority Pests vocabulary performed well in concept extraction, probably because the EPPO codes database has been used consistently as a reference (and EPPO codes are store for all Pests where available). However, there were many cases where respondents referred to differing taxonomic levels with respect to pests or commodities. This necessitated the addition of ‘mid-level’ concepts to these vocabularies. Examples include:

- Tree species – new concept with skos:narrower Birch, Norway Spruce etc
- Tephritidae – new concept with skos:broader Exotic fruit fly and skos:narrower Anastrepha ludens; Bactrocera aquilonis etc
- Scolytinae - new concept with skos:broader Exotic invasive beetles and skos:narrower Ips typographus; Tomicus piniperda
- Fusarium - new top concept with Fusarium euwallaceae; Panama disease tropical race 4 etc

For Biosecurity Thesaurus there were some structural changes also, such as:

- Active substances – new concept with skos:broader Control measures and skos:narrower Antimicrobial; Fungicide; Herbicide; Pesticide. Also skos:altLabel added: Active constituents (a term used in Australia); Biocides
- Pest management - new concept with skos:broader Control measures and skos:narrower Containment; Integrated pest management; Minimizing spread; Suppression

Survey design feedback

We draw attention to a number of issues in the survey design. Some improvements to the survey instrument will make processing (transformation, indexing) more scale-able and improve clarity around the intent of responses.

Most questions are open-ended and elicit unstructured responses – this approach does well to capture diverse and novel data but the survey instrument needs to enforce certain validation rules to support this. We needed to perform manual task to address some data quality issues. Manual fixes were achievable for approximately 100 records, however as this approach does not scale well for a larger survey we point out the following issues.

Validation

For some survey questions, responses could be validated on collection. Examples:

- Priority / Scale → enforce choice of “country”; “region”; “worldwide”. Note that respondents used different wording (e.g. “global”), or combined values (“e.g. “country/regional”), or gave specific or named information (e.g. “France”).
- A standard “non-applicable” option would support response consistency. This data may be needed as to distinguish n/a from a null value.

Delimiting values

Some questions elicited responses that featured multiple objects or concepts, for example “Which agricultural crops are important to study for your organization / institution?”. For these questions, respondents used inconsistent delimiting – that is, use of commas, semi-colons and spaces to separate terms. E.g. “Vegetables; cereals; oil and fibre; potato; maize and sorghum”; “Fruit production, grape cultivation.

Ambiguous responses

Some responses were, perhaps out of some context, difficult to interpret. For example, for the question “Which agricultural crops are important...”, for the response:

- “High value vegetable crops”, both open field and under protection” was given. We were able to extract the concept “vegetable crops” but not “high value” – we were unable to determine the meaning of ‘high value’ (we assumed ‘both’ means ‘all’ and so ignored the trailing elaboration).
- “New agricultural and horticultural crops (quinoa, chickpeas, lentils, soya, sweet potatoes, ...)” – examples of ‘new’ crops were extracted, but the intended scope remains unclear, i.e. we were unable to determine what other crops might be new in the context
- “staple crops across a wide range of agroecological zones worldwide” – we were unable to determine the scope or definition of “staple crops”
- “...vegetables that are biologically fruits” – we were unable to determine the scope or definition of these

Conditionality

We were unsure whether the last question (“Optional: mention 1 concrete research need...”) should be interpreted as a subclass of the previous question (“Which research areas do you think...”). In many cases, there was no response to the optional question. There were also many responses that indicated a research need that was not mentioned in the previous general question about research needs. It was therefore difficult to apply processing rules to the optional responses, as it was not clear whether these were an extension, an elaboration or clarification of the previously stated research needs.

For example, *AVBS, sierteelt- en groenfederatie* reported “Fire blights” as

We suggest redrafting these questions so that the second question is dependent on the first response:

- Retain “Which research areas do you think...”
- Supplementary question: “For the research areas that you have identified, which of these is most pressing” / “... rank the research areas in order of urgency” / “which of these need to be done in the next 3 years”.

Whether the supplementary question involves single, multiple or ranked responses, use markers based on the previous responses (that is, do not ask respondents to re-write their previous answers – ask them to tick boxes, radio buttons etc.

Pick lists and examples

For the question “Identify a maximum of 5 priorities you think that should be addressed in your country / region / worldwide...”, three valid answers are implied. We suggest validating and controlling these in the survey instrument.

We noticed that many responses included a mix, such as “country / region”. We suggest enforcing a maximum of one scale only for each priority.

For other questions, examples were suggested in the question:

- “Which research areas do you think need to be addressed / developed to support future work on plant health issues or related practical problems (**examples in annex**).”
- Which pests do you consider a regional priority? (provide a maximum of 5 pests with Latin name and the main factor that drives the priority (**economy, trade, strategy, policy...**))

The responses are a mix of text aligned and non-aligned with the examples. We suggest one of two approaches to these questions:

- a) Treat the examples as a controlled list which can be selected (ranked, top three, tick any boxes etc). This approach provides cleaner data for processing. An “other” free text field could be appended to the controlled list.
- b) Remove examples altogether. This approach promotes greater diversity and novelty of responses.

With ‘other’ option, a) is perhaps the better approach for eliciting responses as this will promote better validation while still supporting novel responses.

Language

Survey responses were in all by three cases in English – Euphresco supplied translations for these on request. Response language was not discussed as part of project planning and should be clarified in any future work.

For English language responses, there were occasional non-English spelling variations, for example:

- “Mildiou”, which we added as an English (en) skos:altLabel for “Downy mildew”. A loan word, this label could alternatively (or additionally) be stored as a French (fr) language skos:prefLabel for the same concept in the Priority Pests vocabulary.

Respondent representation

There were, in some cases, multiple response records from the same organisation. We see no problem with this approach *per se*, but flag that this seems to be an exceptional practice. The analysis in this report is conducted using either organisation or country groupings. It should be noted that as responses from the same organisation were treated as distinct entities, the analysis will contain slight overrepresentation of interests communicated by those organisations, which were noticeably similar in some cases. We did think a cancellation routine was justified in our concept counts, but we suggest reviewing how organisations are represented in future survey work with respect to alignment of response counts.

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Appendix

Cluster maps

The common interest maps show clusters for concepts with five highest occurrence counts. Maps are given for Commodities, Priority Pets, Biosecurity Thesaurus and Combined three vocabularies. HTML versions are delivered separately.

Commodities Concepts - 5 Clusters

Figure 8. Commodity Concept Clusters Map

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Pest Priority Concepts - 5 Clusters

Figure 9. Common Pest Priority Clusters Map

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Biosecurity Thesaurus Concepts - 5 Clusters

Figure 10. Common Biosecurity Thesaurus interests map

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Figure 11. Combined Common Interests map

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Pest responses per organisation

Table reports regional and global pest priorities per organisation. Where available, EPPO codes are appended to pest names. Pest broad classification count is given for both regional and global priority.

Organisation	Country	Regional pest priority	Global pest priority
Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES)	Austria	Scaphoideus titanus [SCAPLI], Saperda candida [SAPECN], Longhorn beetles, Epitrix [1EPIXG], Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Potato cyst nematodes, Flavescence doree [PHYP64], Rhagoletis [1RHAGG]	Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Fusarium [1FUSAG], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Tephritidae, Lycorma delicatula [LYCMDE]
Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES)	Austria	Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Flavescence doree [PHYP64], Rhagoletis [1RHAGG]	Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Root-knot nematodes, Bactrocera dorsalis [DACUDO], Ceratitis capitata [CERTCA], Rhagoletis [1RHAGG]
Landwirtschaftskammer Burgenland	Austria	Annual ragweed [AMBEL], Esca, Potato late blight [PHYTIN]	Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA]
Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Regions and Water Management	Austria	Scolytinae, Rhagoletis [1RHAGG]	Spodoptera [1SPODG], Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Potato cyst nematodes
NPPO federal state Styria	Austria	Flavescence doree [PHYP64]	Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Flavescence doree [PHYP64]
Agricultural Chamber of Lower Austria, Official plant protection service	Austria	Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL], Anoplophora chinensis [ANOLCN], Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Flavescence doree [PHYP64]	Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL], Anoplophora chinensis [ANOLCN], Tomato brown rugose fruit virus [TOBRFV], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Meloidogyne enterolobii [MELGMY]
Soil and Water Management and Crop Nutrition Laboratory of the Joint FAO/IAEA Centre of Nuclear Techniques in Food and Agriculture	Austria	Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Flavescence doree [PHYP64], Rhagoletis [1RHAGG], Longhorn beetles, Clavibacter michiganensis [CORBMI], Ralstonia solanacearum,	Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Fusarium [1FUSAG], Lycorma delicatula [LYCMDE], Tephritidae [1TEPHF]

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SPW [Département du Développement, de la Ruralité et des Cours d'Eau et du Bien-être Animal (Direction de la Qualité et du Bien-être animal)]	Belgium	Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Fire blight [ERWIAM], Bactrocera dorsalis [DACUDO], Ralstonia solanacearum	Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA]
BiobestGroup	Belgium	Nezara viridula [NEZAVI], Echinothrips americanus [ECHTAM], Silverleaf whitefly [BEMITA]	Spotted wing drosophila [DROSSU], Asian citrus psyllid [DIAACI]
Euroseeds	Belgium	Tomato brown rugose fruit virus [TOBRFV]	Tomato brown rugose fruit virus [TOBRFV]
AVBS, sierteelt-en groenfederatie	Belgium	Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL]	
Royal Museum for Central Africa	Belgium	Exotic fruit fly	Exotic fruit fly
Federal Agency for the Safety of the Food Chain	Belgium		
LUTOSA	Belgium	Fusarium [1FUSAG], Alternaria [1ALTEG], Elaterinae, Parasitic nematodes, Potato late blight [PHYTIN]	Potato late blight [PHYTIN]
Scientia Terrae VZW	Belgium	Tomato brown rugose fruit virus [TOBRFV], Parasitic nematodes	Tomato brown rugose fruit virus [TOBRFV]
Service public de Wallonie	Belgium	Ips typographus [IPSXTY], Sudden oak death [PHYTRA]	Ips typographus [IPSXTY], Bursaphelenchus xylophilus [BURSXY], Sudden oak death [PHYTRA]
Agentschap Landbouw en Zeevisserij	Belgium		
Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt (Research Station for Vegetable Production)	Belgium	Brevicoryne brassicae [BRVCBR], Tuta absoluta [GNORAB], Fusarium euwallaceae [FUSAEW], Cabbage whitefly [ALEUPR], Tomato brown rugose fruit virus [TOBRFV]	
Hasselt University	Belgium		
Proefcentrum Pamel	Belgium		Spotted wing drosophila [DROSSU]

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HEPH-Condorcet (and CARAH asbl)	Belgium	Downy mildew, Soft rot Pectobacteriaceae, Alternaria [1ALTEG], Potato cyst nematodes, Potato late blight [PHYTIN]	Soft rot Pectobacteriaceae, Alternaria [1ALTEG], Potato cyst nematodes, Potato late blight [PHYTIN]
Research Station for Fruit	Belgium	Phytoplasmas, Fire blight [ERWIAM], Brown marmorated stink bug [HALYHA], Spotted wing drosophila [DROSSU]	Brown marmorated stink bug [HALYHA], Spotted wing drosophila [DROSSU]
BELSPO	Belgium		
VBT (Association of Belgian Horticultural Cooperatives)	Belgium	Tomato brown rugose fruit virus [TOBRFV], Fire blight [ERWIAM]	
Federal Agency for the Safety of the Food Chain	Belgium	Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL], Anoplophora chinensis [ANOLCN], Epitrix [1EPIXG], Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Flavescence doree [PHYP64]	Phyllosticta citricarpa [GUIGCI], Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Popillia japonica [POPIJA]
FASFC	Belgium	Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL], Anoplophora chinensis [ANOLCN], Epitrix [1EPIXG], Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Flavescence doree [PHYP64]	Phyllosticta citricarpa [GUIGCI], Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Popillia japonica [POPIJA]
Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment - DG Animals, Plants and Foodstuffs - Service Sanitary Policy Animals and Plants - Division Plant Protection (NPPO BE)	Belgium	Emerald ash borer [AGRLPL], Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Tomato brown rugose fruit virus [TOBRFV], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Rhagoletis [1RHAGG]	Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Fusarium euwallaceae [FUSAEW], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA]
Viaverda	Belgium	Thrips parvispinus [THRIPV], Thrips setosus [THRISE], Echinothrips americanus [ECHTAM], Otiorynchus sulcatus [OTIOSU], Fusarium euwallaceae [FUSAEW]	Thrips parvispinus [THRIPV], Thrips setosus [THRISE], Echinothrips americanus [ECHTAM], Fusarium euwallaceae [FUSAEW]
ILVO	Belgium	Longhorn beetles	

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ILVO	Belgium		
Danske Juletræer	Denmark		
Aarhus University	Denmark		
Ministry of Regional Affairs and Agriculture; Agriculture and Food Board; Centre of Estonian Rural Research and Knowledge (consolidated information)	Estonia	Clavibacter sepedonicus [CORBSE], Emerald ash borer [AGRLPL], Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL], Fire blight [ERWIAM]	Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Fire blight [ERWIAM]
Tallinn University of Technology	Estonia	Clavibacter sepedonicus [CORBSE], Emerald ash borer [AGRLPL], Fire blight [ERWIAM]	Hymenoscyphus fraxineus [CHAAFR], Ips typographus [IPSXTY], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA]
The Estonian Chamber of Agriculture and Commerce (gathered the information from entrepreneurs)	Estonia	Bruchus pisorum	Leptinotarsa decemlineata [LPTNDE], Rhagoletis [1RHAGG]
FNAMS	France		
ANICC	France	Lecanicillium fungicola [VERTFU], Cladobotryum dendroides [DACYDE]	Lecanicillium fungicola [VERTFU], Cladobotryum dendroides [DACYDE]
COOPENOIX	France	Rhagoletis [1RHAGG]	Rhagoletis [1RHAGG]
FN3PT/inoV3PT (and the 3 regional Organisations of Seed Potato Producers: Bretagne-Plants, Comité Nord and	France	Soft rot Pectobacteriaceae, Fusarium [1FUSAG], Dickeya dianthicola [ERWICD], Elaterinae, PVY, Phytoplasmas, Potato late blight [PHYTIN]	Soft rot Pectobacteriaceae, Fusarium [1FUSAG], Dickeya dianthicola [ERWICD], Elaterinae, Epitrix [1EPIXG], PVY, Phytoplasmas, Potato late blight [PHYTIN]

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Comité Centre-et-Sud)			
ACTA	France		
ARVALIS	France	Elaterinae	
Organisation des Producteurs d'Agrumes de Corse	France	Whitefly	Bactrocera dorsalis [DACUDO], Ceratitis capitata [CERTCA]
INRAE	France	Emerald ash borer [AGRLPL], Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Lycorma delicatula [LYCMDE]	Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Lycorma delicatula [LYCMDE]
ITB	France		
GEVES	France	Sclerotinia sclerotiorum [SCLESC], Tomato fruit blotch virus [TOFBV0], Root-knot nematodes, Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus	
Plant Health Laboratory - ANSES	France	Bacterial wilt [RALSSO], Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Bursaphelenchus xylophilus [BURSXY], Tephritidae, Ralstonia solanacearum	Karnal bunt, Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Candidatus Liberibacter species [LIBEPS], Root-knot nematodes
Association Nationale des Producteurs de Noisettes	France	Brown marmorated stink bug [HALYHA]	Brown marmorated stink bug [HALYHA]
SCA UNICOQUE	France	Brown marmorated stink bug [HALYHA]	Brown marmorated stink bug [HALYHA]
Phyteis	France	Spotted wing drosophila [DROSSU]	
CENTRE R&D VEGEPOLYS VALLEY	France	Plenodomus lingam, Phytoplasmas, Fire blight [ERWIAM], Spotted wing drosophila [DROSSU]	Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Phytoplasmas, Brown marmorated stink bug [HALYHA]
LTZ Augustenberg	Germany		
Julius Kühn-Institute, Institute for national and international Plant Health	Germany	Emerald ash borer [AGRLPL], Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Bursaphelenchus xylophilus [BURSXY]	Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Exotic fruit fly

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SAXON STATE COMPANY FOR ENVIRONMENT AND AGRICULTURE	Germany	Pale potato cyst nematode [HETDPA], Root-knot nematodes, Phytoplasmas	Popillia japonica [POPIJA]
Landwirtschaftskammer Schleswig-Holstein	Germany	Saperda candida [SAPECN], Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL]	Clavibacter sepedonicus [CORBSE], Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Tomato brown rugose fruit virus [TOBRFV], Ralstonia solanacearum
Plant Protection Service Hesse	Germany	Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL], Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA]	Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Bursaphelenchus xylophilus [BURSXY]
Bayerische Landesanstalt für Landwirtschaft	Germany	Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL], Aromia bungii [AROMBU], Anoplophora chinensis [ANOLCN], Popillia japonica [POPIJA], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA]	Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA]
Lithuanian Research Centre for Agriculture and Forestry, Institute of Horticulture, Laboratory of Plant Protection	Lithuania	Tuta absoluta [GNORAB], Sclerotinia sclerotiorum [SCLESC], Rhagoletis [1RHAGG]	Neonectria ditissima [NECTGA]
The State Plant Service under the Ministry*	Lithuania	Clavibacter sepedonicus [CORBSE], Parasitic nematodes, PVY, Fire blight [ERWIAM], Plum pox virus [PPV000]	Weed seeds, Parasitic nematodes
Lithuanian Research Center for Agriculture and Forestry (LAMMC)	Lithuania	Fusarium [1FUSAG]	Fusarium [1FUSAG]
Plantum	Netherlands		

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Wageningen University & Research	Netherlands	Bacterial wilt [RALSSO], Tomato brown rugose fruit virus [TOBRFV], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Meloidogyne enterolobii [MELGMY], Potato late blight [PHYTIN]	Fusarium euwallaceae [FUSAEW], Emerald ash borer [AGRLPL], Anoplophora chinensis [ANOLCN], Popillia japonica [POPIJA]
RHP (Kenniscentrum en certificering voor substraten (teeltmedia))	Netherlands		
Nederlandse Akkerbouwvakbond	Netherlands	Golden potato cyst nematode [HETDRO], Potato late blight [PHYTIN]	
LTO Akkerbouw, Vollegrondsgroente, Bomen, Vaste planten en Zomerbloemen	Netherlands	Cyperus esculentus, Popillia japonica [POPIJA]	
BO Akkerbouw	Netherlands	Cyperus esculentus	
Naktuinbouw	Netherlands	Tomato brown rugose fruit virus [TOBRFV]	Tomato brown rugose fruit virus [TOBRFV]
Nederlandse Aardappel Organisatie	Netherlands	Clavibacter sepedonicus [CORBSE], Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum [LIBEPS], Ralstonia solanacearum	
Stichting Markering Houten Verpakkingen (SMHV)	Netherlands		Longhorn beetles, Bursaphelenchus xylophilus [BURSXY]
NIVIP	Netherlands	False codling moth [ARGPLE], Bacterial wilt [RALSSO], Pale potato cyst nematode [HETDPA], Ralstonia solanacearum	Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA]
NVWA	Netherlands	Meloidogyne chitwoodi [MELGCH]	Tomato brown rugose fruit virus [TOBRFV], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA]
Sagaplant	Norway		
Extension services. Region south	Norway	Raspberry beetle [BYTUTO]	

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Extension services SA	Norway		
Innovation Norway/Bionoca	Norway		
Norsøk	Norway		Spotted wing drosophila [DROSSU]
County governor (Rogaland county)	Norway	Scolytinae	Scolytinae
Artsdatabanken (Norwegian Biodiversity Information Centre)	Norway		
Bergen University Museum	Norway	Hymenoscyphus fraxineus [CHAAFR], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA]	Sudden oak death [PHYTRA]
Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research	Norway	Hymenoscyphus fraxineus [CHAAFR], Ips typographus [IPSXTY], Hylobius abietis [HYLOAB], Dutch elm disease [OPHSNU]	Hymenoscyphus fraxineus [CHAAFR], Scolytinae, Parasitic nematodes, Dutch elm disease [OPHSNU], Chestnut blight
County governor (Troms and Finnmark county)	Norway	Scolytinae	Scolytinae
County governor (Møre and Romsdal county)	Norway	Ips typographus [IPSXTY], Hylobius abietis [HYLOAB], Annosus root and butt rot	Ips typographus [IPSXTY], Hylobius abietis [HYLOAB]
Oslo County	Norway		
Syngenta	Norway		
Norskog	Norway	Ips typographus [IPSXTY], Hylobius abietis [HYLOAB], Annosus root and butt rot	Scolytinae
Allskog	Norway	Ips typographus [IPSXTY], Hylobius abietis [HYLOAB], Annosus root and butt rot	Ips typographus [IPSXTY]
Glommen Mjøsen Skog	Norway	Ips typographus [IPSXTY], Hylobius abietis [HYLOAB]	
Alstadhaug forest nursery	Norway	Ips typographus [IPSXTY], Hylobius abietis [HYLOAB]	
Norwegian Food Auhtorities	Norway		

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Landbruksdirektoratet	Norway		
Gartnerhallen	Norway	Spotted wing drosophila [DROSSU], Potato late blight [PHYTIN]	Parasitic nematodes, Potato late blight [PHYTIN]
Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development	Poland	Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Tuta absoluta [GNORAB], Silverleaf whitefly [BEMITA], Parasitic nematodes, Western corn rootworm	
General Directorate of State Forests	Poland	Spongy moths [LYMADI], Lymantria monacha [LYMAMO], Ips typographus [IPSXTY]	Viscum album [VISAL], Bursaphelenchus xylophilus [BURSXY]
National Agricultural and Food Centre	Slovakia	Fusarium [1FUSAG]	Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR]
Slovak Agricultural University	Slovakia	Western corn rootworm	
Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), SLU Risk assessment of plant pests	Sweden	Dendrolimus sibiricus, Emerald ash borer [AGRLPL], Agrilus anxius [AGRLAX], Meloidogyne chitwoodi [MELGCH], Bursaphelenchus xylophilus [BURSXY]	Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Emerald ash borer [AGRLPL], Bursaphelenchus xylophilus [BURSXY], Potato late blight [PHYTIN]
Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), Southern Swedish Forest Research Centre (SLU Alnarp)	Sweden	Emerald ash borer [AGRLPL], Agrilus anxius [AGRLAX], Sudden oak death [PHYTRA], Lecanosticta acicola [SCIRAC]	Emerald ash borer [AGRLPL], Agrilus anxius [AGRLAX], Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL], Sudden oak death [PHYTRA], Lycorma delicatula [LYCMDE]
Intertek ScanBi Diagnostics AB	Sweden		
Swedish Board of Agriculture (Swedish National	Sweden	Emerald ash borer [AGRLPL], Agrilus anxius [AGRLAX], Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL], Bursaphelenchus xylophilus [BURSXY], Sudden oak death [PHYTRA]	Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Bursaphelenchus xylophilus [BURSXY]

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Plant Protection Organisation)			
Defra Plant Health Evidence	United Kingdom		
Defra Tree Health Policy	United Kingdom	Ips typographus [IPSXTY], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Sudden oak death [PHYTRA]	
Defra Plants Risk and Horizon Scanning	United Kingdom	Emerald ash borer [AGRLPL], Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL], Leptinotarsa decemlineata [LPTNDE], Tomato brown rugose fruit virus [TOBRFV], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA]	Emerald ash borer [AGRLPL], Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL], Leptinotarsa decemlineata [LPTNDE], Tomato brown rugose fruit virus [TOBRFV], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA]
Royal Horticultural Society	United Kingdom	Exotic invasive moths	Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA]
Forestry Commission	United Kingdom	Emerald ash borer [AGRLPL], Ips typographus [IPSXTY], Agrilus anxius [AGRLAX], Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL], Anoplophora chinensis [ANOLCN], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA]	Emerald ash borer [AGRLPL], Ips typographus [IPSXTY], Agrilus anxius [AGRLAX], Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL], Anoplophora chinensis [ANOLCN], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA]
Forest Research	United Kingdom	Thaumetopoea pityocampa [THAUPI], Emerald ash borer [AGRLPL], Ips typographus [IPSXTY], Anoplophora glabripennis [ANOLGL], Anoplophora chinensis [ANOLCN], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA]	Ips typographus [IPSXTY], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Sudden oak death [PHYTRA]
APHA (Plant Health & Seeds Inspectorate within Defra's Animal and Plant Health Agency).	United Kingdom	Clavibacter sepedonicus [CORBSE], Karnal bunt, Emerald ash borer [AGRLPL], Xylella fastidiosa [XYLEFA], Ralstonia solanacearum	Karnal bunt, Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR], Leptinotarsa decemlineata [LPTNDE], Wheat stem rust [PUCGGR]
Fera Science Ltd	United Kingdom	Tomato brown rugose fruit virus [TOBRFV]	

Commodity responses per organisation

Table reports regional and global pest priorities per organisation.

Organisation	country	Commodities
Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES)	Austria	Stone fruit, Grapes, Potatoes
Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES)	Austria	Grapes, Vegetables, Ornamental plants

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Landwirtschaftskammer Burgenland	Austria	Forestry, Sugar, Stone fruit, Grapes, Sugar beet, Hazelnuts, Walnuts, Olives, Potatoes, Pumpkins, Onions, Field peas, Soya beans, Sunflower, Barley, Spelt, Millet
Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Regions and Water Management	Austria	Fruit, Soya beans, Buckwheat
NPPO federal state Styria	Austria	Forestry, Wine, Fruit
Agricultural Chamber of Lower Austria, Official plant protection service	Austria	Stone fruit, Grapes, Potatoes, Tomatoes
Soil and Water Management and Crop Nutrition Laboratory of the Joint FAO/IAEA Centre of Nuclear Techniques in Food and Agriculture	Austria	Crops
SPW [Département du Développement, de la Ruralité et des Cours d'Eau et du Bien-être Animal (Direction de la Qualité et du Bien-être animal)]	Belgium	Potatoes, Wheat
BiobestGroup	Belgium	Berries, Cucumbers, Tomatoes, Ornamental plants
Euroseeds	Belgium	Potatoes, Maize
AVBS, sierteelt- en groenfederatie	Belgium	Ornamental plants
Royal Museum for Central Africa	Belgium	Fruit, Vegetables
Federal Agency for the Safety of the Food Chain	Belgium	Crops
LUTOSA	Belgium	Potatoes
Scientia Terrae VZW	Belgium	
Service public de Wallonie	Belgium	
Agentschap Landbouw en Zeevisserij	Belgium	Potatoes, Sweet potatoes, Chickpeas, Soya beans
Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt (Research Station for Vegetable Production)	Belgium	Vegetables
Hasselt University	Belgium	Grapes
Proefcentrum Pamel	Belgium	Strawberries
HEPH-Condorcet (and CARAH asbl)	Belgium	Potatoes, Grains
Research Station for Fruit	Belgium	Grapes, Berries
BELSPO	Belgium	

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VBT (Association of Belgian Horticultural Cooperatives)	Belgium	Apples, Pears, Strawberries, Chicory, Cucumbers, Lettuce, Leeks, Tomatoes, Capsicums
Federal Agency for the Safety of the Food Chain	Belgium	Sugar, Sugar beet, Tomatoes, Maize
FASFC	Belgium	Sugar, Sugar beet, Tomatoes, Maize
Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment - DG Animals, Plants and Foodstuffs - Service Sanitary Policy Animals and Plants - Division Plant Protection (NPPO BE)	Belgium	Forestry, Apples, Pears, Strawberries, Sugar beet, Leeks, Potatoes, Cabbages, Tomatoes, Ornamental plants, Maize
Viaverda	Belgium	Potatoes, Ornamental plants
ILVO	Belgium	Potatoes, Ornamental plants, Grains
ILVO	Belgium	
Danske Juletræer	Denmark	Norway spruce
Aarhus University	Denmark	Potatoes, Grass seeds, Grains
Ministry of Regional Affairs and Agriculture; Agriculture and Food Board; Centre of Estonian Rural Research and Knowledge (consolidated information)	Estonia	Potatoes, Barley, Oats, Rye, Wheat
Tallinn University of Technology	Estonia	Potatoes, Oats, Wheat
The Estonian Chamber of Agriculture and Commerce (gathered the information from entrepreneurs)	Estonia	Wheat
FNAMS	France	Vegetables, Grains
ANICC	France	Mushrooms
COOPENOIX	France	Walnuts
FN3PT/inoV3PT (and the 3 regional Organisations of Seed Potato Producers: Bretagne-Plants, Comité Nord and Comité Centre-et-Sud)	France	Potatoes, Grains
ACTA	France	
ARVALIS	France	Potatoes, Grains
Organisation des Producteurs d'Agrumes de Corse	France	Clementines, Limes, Lemons, Avocados
INRAE	France	Crops
ITB	France	Sugar, Sugar beet

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GEVES	France	Vegetables, Grains
Plant Health Laboratory - ANSES	France	Ornamental plants
Association Nationale des Producteurs de Noisettes	France	Hazelnuts
SCA UNICOQUE	France	Hazelnuts
Phyteis	France	Wine, Fruit, Vegetables
CENTRE R&D VEGEPOLYS VALLEY	France	Apples, Vegetables, Canola, Wheat
LTZ Augustenberg	Germany	
Julius Kühn-Institute, Institute for national and international Plant Health	Germany	Fruit, Potatoes, Tomatoes, Ornamental plants
SAXON STATE COMPANY FOR ENVIRONMENT AND AGRICULTURE	Germany	Crops
Landwirtschaftskammer Schleswig-Holstein	Germany	Potatoes, Nursery
Plant Protection Service Hesse	Germany	
Bayerische Landesanstalt für Landwirtschaft	Germany	
Lithuanian Centre and of Horticulture, Laboratory of Plant Protection for Forestry, Research Agriculture Institute	Lithuania	Berries, Vegetables
The State Plant Service under the Ministry*	Lithuania	Peat, Rye, Wheat
Lithuanian Research Center for Agriculture and Forestry (LAMMC)	Lithuania	Sugar, Potatoes, Oilseeds, Wheat
Plantum	Netherlands	
Wageningen University & Research	Netherlands	Cucumbers, Potatoes, Tomatoes, Carrots, Onions, Roses, Gerbera, Grains
RHP (Kenniscentrum en certificering voor substraten (teeltmedia))	Netherlands	Crops
Nederlandse Akkerbouwvakbond	Netherlands	Sugar, Sugar beet, Potatoes, Cabbages, Carrots, Grains
LTO Akkerbouw, Vollegroondsgroente, Bomen, Vaste planten en Zomerbloemen	Netherlands	Potatoes, Nursery
BO Akkerbouw	Netherlands	Potatoes, Onions, Grains
Naktuinbouw	Netherlands	

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Nederlandse Aardappel Organisatie	Netherlands	Potatoes
Stichting Markering Houten Verpakkingen (SMHV)	Netherlands	
NIVIP	Netherlands	Berries, Ginger, Cucumbers, Potatoes, Tomatoes, Solanum macrocarpon, Sweet potatoes, Ornamental plants, Turmeric, Black-eyed pea, Mung beans
NVWA	Netherlands	
Sagaplant	Norway	Raspberries, Strawberries
Extension services. Region south	Norway	Horticulture
Extension services SA	Norway	Fodder
Innovation Norway/Bionoca	Norway	
Norsøk	Norway	Berries, Vegetables, Grains
County governor (Rogaland county)	Norway	European ash, Norway spruce, Pinus sylvestris, Oaks, Sitka spruce
Artsdatabanken (Norwegian Biodiversity Information Centre)	Norway	Agriculture
Bergen University Museum	Norway	
Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research	Norway	Birch, Norway spruce, Pinus sylvestris, Oaks, Sitka spruce
County governor (Troms and Finnmark county)	Norway	Birch, Norway spruce, Pinus sylvestris
County governor (Møre and Romsdal county)	Norway	Norway spruce
Oslo County	Norway	
Syngenta	Norway	Potatoes, Grains
Norskog	Norway	Birch, Norway spruce, Pinus sylvestris
Allskog	Norway	Birch, Norway spruce, Pinus sylvestris
Glommen Mjøsen Skog	Norway	Birch, Norway spruce, Pinus sylvestris, Beeches, Oaks
Alstadhaug forest nursery	Norway	Norway spruce, Pinus sylvestris
Norwegian Food Authorities	Norway	Berries, Potatoes, Grains
Landbruksdirektoratet	Norway	
Gartnerhallen	Norway	Fruit, Vegetables
Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development	Poland	Grain products, Maize, Wheat

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General Directorate of State Forests	Poland	
National Agricultural and Food Centre	Slovakia	Fodder, Fruit, Potatoes, Soya beans, Sunflower, Triticale, Barley, Oats, Maize, Wheat, Whitings
Slovak Agricultural University	Slovakia	Grapes, Vegetables, Sunflower, Wheat
Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), SLU Risk assessment of plant pests	Sweden	Pinus sylvestris, Potatoes
Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), Southern Swedish Forest Research Centre (SLU Alnarp)	Sweden	Birch, European ash, Horticulture
Intertek ScanBi Diagnostics AB	Sweden	Potatoes, Oilseeds, Grains
Swedish Board of Agriculture (Swedish National Plant Protection Organisation)	Sweden	Birch, Norway spruce, Pinus sylvestris
Defra Plant Health Evidence	United Kingdom	
Defra Tree Health Policy	United Kingdom	
Defra Plants Risk and Horizon Scanning	United Kingdom	Potatoes
Royal Horticultural Society	United Kingdom	Ornamental plants
Forestry Commission	United Kingdom	
Forest Research	United Kingdom	Tree species
APHA (Plant Health & Seeds Inspectorate within Defra's Animal and Plant Health Agency).	United Kingdom	Potatoes, Ornamental plants, Grains
Fera Science Ltd	United Kingdom	

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Research issues per organisation

Table reports research interests per organisation.

Organisation	Country	Research issues
Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES)	Austria	Early warning systems, Offshore surveillance, Skill and knowledge transfer, Phytosanitary research collaboration, Biosecurity funding, Evaluation, Pest management, Detection, Regulated pests, Climate, Emerging pests, Outbreaks, Plant diseases, Biodiversity, Ecosystems
Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES)	Austria	Smart traps, Early warning systems, Intelligence sharing, Information sharing, Biosecurity emergency, Biosecurity research, Sterile insect technique, Pesticide reduction, Insecticide, Integrated pest management, Biological control, Taxonomic identification, Diagnostic tests, Biosecurity detection dogs, Regulated pests, Climate, Emerging pests, Established populations, Biodiversity, Agriculture
Landwirtschaftskammer Burgenland	Austria	Autonomous plant protection, Crop rotation, Herbicide, Pesticides, Pest management, Detection, Biocidal resistance, Soil, Soil protection, Annual ragweed, Esca, Nezara viridula, Flavescence doree, Crops
Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Regions and Water Management	Austria	Surveillance, Biosecurity research, Eradication, Organic farming, Pest management, Climate, Emerging pests, Outbreaks, Emerald ash borer, Popillia japonica
NPPO federal state Styria	Austria	Popillia japonica, Flavescence doree, Tephritidae
Agricultural Chamber of Lower Austria, Official plant protection service	Austria	Traps, Eradication, Insecticide, Containment, Biological control, Detection, Plant products, Climate, Emerging pests, Pathogenicity, Containers, Host plants, Invasive diseases, Nurseries, Trade, Popillia japonica, Nursery
Soil and Water Management and Crop Nutrition Laboratory of the Joint FAO/IAEA Centre of Nuclear Techniques in Food and Agriculture	Austria	Biosecurity emergency, Antimicrobial, Contamination, Climate, Soil, Biodiversity, Soil protection
SPW [Département du Développement, de la Ruralité et des Cours d'Eau et du Bien-être Animal (Direction de la Qualité et du Bien-être animal)]	Belgium	Biosecurity strategy, Evaluation, Quarantine, Climate, Pathogenicity, Passengers, Invasive diseases, Dissolved oxygen

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BiobestGroup	Belgium	Early warning systems, Pesticides, Prevention, Integrated pest management, Classical biological control, Detection, Susceptible areas, Established populations, Invasiveness, Pathogenicity, Invasive diseases, Landscape, Powdery mildew, Nezara viridula, Fusarium
Euroseeds	Belgium	Biosecurity policy, Seed treatment, Eradication, Detection, Seeds, Treatment certificate, Virus titer, Pathogenicity, Seed dispersal, Invasive diseases, Dissolved oxygen
AVBS, sierteelt- en groenfederatie	Belgium	Border, Non-quarantine pests, Silverleaf whitefly, Anoplophora glabripennis, Fire blight, Ornamental plants
Royal Museum for Central Africa	Belgium	Area freedom, Diagnostic tests, Climate, Susceptible areas, Invasiveness, Exotic invasive species, Pollination, Agriculture, Tephritidae, Fruit
Federal Agency for the Safety of the Food Chain	Belgium	Offshore surveillance, Minimizing spread, Taxonomic identification, Diagnostic tests, Plant products, Climate, Emerging pests, Passengers, Trade
LUTOSA	Belgium	Pesticides, Seeds, Climate, Soil, Soil protection, Agriculture, Potato late blight, Potatoes
Scientia Terrae VZW	Belgium	Intelligence sharing, Information sharing, Biosecurity policy, Research infrastructures and collections, Cleaning, Vaccination, Pesticide reduction, Pesticides, Minimizing spread, Biological control, Border, Detection, Plant products, Pathogenicity, Passengers, Invasive diseases, Trade, Crops
Service public de Wallonie	Belgium	Minimizing spread, Plant products, Climate, Pathogenicity, Passengers, Soil, Invasive diseases, Soil protection, Trade, Forests, Hymenoscyphus fraxineus, Ips typographus, Oaks, Crowns
Agentschap Landbouw en Zeevisserij	Belgium	Pesticide reduction, Pesticides, Minimizing spread, Plant products, Climate, Emerging pests, Passengers, Trade, Crops
Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt (Research Station for Vegetable Production)	Belgium	Fumigation, Disinfection, Crop rotation, Integrated pest management, Biostimulants, Diagnostic tests, Quarantine, Seeds, Climate, Emerging pests, Soil, Soil protection, Greenhouses, Tomato brown rugose fruit virus, Vegetables, Nursery
Hasselt University	Belgium	Pesticide reduction, Pesticides, Biostimulants, Climate, Soil, Marginal soil, Crops
Proefcentrum Pamel	Belgium	Soil, Soil protection
HEPH-Condorcet (and CARAH asbl)	Belgium	Pesticide reduction, Organic farming, Pesticides, Pest management, Biostimulants, Climate, Biocidal resistance, Pathogenicity, Soil, Pathogenic fungus, Invasive diseases, Soil protection, Vegetables
Research Station for Fruit	Belgium	Pesticides, Minimizing spread, Integrated pest management, Diagnostic tests, Plant products, Susceptible areas, Invasiveness, Passengers, Soil, Invasive diseases, Soil protection, Trade, Phytoplasmas, Crops
BELSPO	Belgium	Prevention, Climate, Animal diseases, Biodiversity, Agriculture
VBT (Association of Belgian Horticultural Cooperatives)	Belgium	Biosecurity policy, Fumigation, Integrated pest management, Climate, Emerging pests, Soil, Soil protection, Greenhouses, Ecosystems, Tomato brown rugose fruit virus, Crops
Federal Agency for the Safety of the Food Chain	Belgium	Declared areas, Prevention, Containment, Detection, Quarantine, Packaging, Import conditions, Climate, Shipping containers, Mail articles, Plant diseases, Trade

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FASFC	Belgium	Declared areas, Prevention, Containment, Detection, Quarantine, Packaging, Import conditions, Climate, Shipping containers, Mail articles, Plant diseases, Trade
Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment - DG Animals, Plants and Foodstuffs - Service Sanitary Policy Animals and Plants - Division Plant Protection (NPPO BE)	Belgium	Offshore surveillance, Biosecurity emergency, Biosecurity policy, Biosecurity research, Quarantine, Human health
Viaverda	Belgium	Intelligence sharing, Information sharing, Phytosanitary research collaboration, Biosecurity research, Herbicide, Prevention, Integrated pest management, Biopesticide, Culturable, Soil, Invasive diseases, Soil protection, Landscape, Thrips parvispinus, Thrips setosus, Echinothrips americanus, Otiorynchus sulcatus, Fusarium, Ornamental plants
ILVO	Belgium	Intelligence sharing, Information sharing, Pesticide reduction, Pesticides, Minimizing spread, Integrated pest management, Diagnostic tests, Plant products, Non-quarantine pests, Climate, Pathogenicity, Passengers, Plant diseases, Trade
ILVO	Belgium	Biosecurity strategy, Farm biosecurity, Integrated pest management, Culturable
Danske Juletræer	Denmark	Trade
Aarhus University	Denmark	eDNA sampling, Climate, Emerging pests, Pathogenicity, Invasive diseases
Ministry of Regional Affairs and Agriculture; Agriculture and Food Board; Centre of Estonian Rural Research and Knowledge (consolidated information)	Estonia	Offshore surveillance, Biosecurity research, Pesticide reduction, Pesticides, Minimizing spread, Integrated pest management, Border, Innovative diagnostic tools, Inspection, Plant products, Climate, Passengers, Plant diseases, Trade, Potatoes, Grains
Tallinn University of Technology	Estonia	Offshore surveillance, Minimizing spread, Plant products, Climate, Emerging pests, Passengers, Trade, Grains
The Estonian Chamber of Agriculture and Commerce (gathered the information from entrepreneurs)	Estonia	Biosecurity policy, Pesticide reduction, Farm biosecurity, Pesticides, Prevention, Integrated pest management, Border, Susceptible areas, Invasiveness, Soil, Pathogenic fungus, Invasive diseases, Biodiversity, Soil protection, Crop yield, Rural areas, Fusarium, Limes, Grains
FNAMS	France	Seed treatment, Farm biosecurity, Active substances, Prevention, Seeds, Climate, Emerging pests, Pathogenicity, Soil, Seed dispersal, Pathogenic fungus, Invasive diseases, Weeds, Dissolved oxygen, Soil protection, Downy mildew, Plenodomus lingam, Alternaria, Bruchus pisorum, Elaterinae, Flea beetles, Popillia japonica, Potato late blight, Wheat stem rust, Carrots, Clover seeds, Grains

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ANICC	France	Lecanicillium fungicola, Cladobotryum dendroides
COOPENOIX	France	Biological control, Biocidal resistance, Weeds, Exotic invasive moths, Rhagoletis, Crops
FN3PT/inoV3PT (and the 3 regional Organisations of Seed Potato Producers: Bretagne-Plants, Comité Nord and Comité Centre-et-Sud)	France	Intelligence sharing, Information sharing, Phytosanitary research collaboration, Biosecurity research, Pesticide reduction, Insecticide, Prevention, Minimizing spread, Integrated pest management, Diagnostic tests, Inspection, Seeds, Climate, Emerging pests, Pathogenicity, Passengers, Soil, Invasive diseases, Soil protection, Trade, Dickeya dianthicola, Elaterinae, Parasitic nematodes, Phytoplasmas, Potatoes
ACTA	France	Organic farming, Active substances, Pest management, Seeds, Weeds, Downy mildew, Alternaria, Spotted wing drosophila, Fruit
ARVALIS	France	Pest management, Biological control, Climate, Biocidal resistance
Organisation des Producteurs d'Agrumes de Corse	France	Traps, Intelligence sharing, Information sharing, Phytosanitary research collaboration, Biosecurity research, Treatment, Minimizing spread, Plant products, Climate, Passengers, Trade, Citrus
INRAE	France	Offshore surveillance, Pest management, Biological control, Climate, Susceptible areas, Biological invasions, Invasiveness, Exotic invasive species, Risk analysis
ITB	France	Pest management
GEVES	France	Sampling, Evaluation, Seed treatment, Border, Bioassay, High throughput sequencing, Seeds, Non-quarantine pests, Susceptible areas, Invasiveness, Pathogenicity, Invasive diseases
Plant Health Laboratory - ANSES	France	Surveillance, Prevention, Pest management, Border, Biological reference material, Reference laboratory, Morphological identification, eDNA metabarcoding, High throughput sequencing, Inspection, Quarantine, Climate, Emerging pests, Established populations, Pathogenicity, Dispersal pathways, Plant diseases, Agriculture, Trade, Ecosystems, Bananas, Citrus, Tubers, Rice
Association Nationale des Producteurs de Noisettes	France	Biological control, Parasitoids, Parasitic nematodes, Brown marmorated stink bug
SCA UNICOQUE	France	Biological control, Parasitoids, Parasitic nematodes, Brown marmorated stink bug
Phyteis	France	Zoning, Biosecurity strategy, Active substances, Biostimulants, Biopesticide, Spray drift, Climate, Invasive diseases, Weeds, Agriculture, Spotted wing drosophila, Crops
CENTRE R&D VEGEPOLYS VALLEY	France	Intelligence sharing, Skill and knowledge transfer, Information sharing, Phytosanitary research collaboration, Biosecurity policy, Research infrastructures and collections, Evaluation, Pesticide reduction, Farm biosecurity, Pesticides, Pest management, Biostimulants, Diagnostic tests, Weeds, Crop yield, Downy mildew, Apples
LTZ Augustenberg	Germany	Reference laboratory, Regulated pests, Forests, Crops

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Julius Kühn-Institute, Institute for national and international Plant Health	Germany	Remote sensing, Early warning systems, Biosecurity emergency, Pest management, Diagnostic tests, Quarantine, Climate
SAXON STATE COMPANY FOR ENVIRONMENT AND AGRICULTURE	Germany	Diagnostic tests, Established populations
Landwirtschaftskammer Schleswig-Holstein	Germany	Interception, Detection, Biosecurity detection dogs, Outbreaks, Nurseries, Saperda candida, Popillia japonica, Tomato brown rugose fruit virus, Parasitic nematodes, Potatoes, Nursery
Plant Protection Service Hesse	Germany	Sampling, Molecular identification, Diagnostic tests, Inspection, Plant products, Point of entry, Plant diseases, Trade
Bayerische Landesanstalt für Landwirtschaft	Germany	Sampling, Pest management, Goods, Regulated pests, Established populations, Outbreaks
Lithuanian Research Centre for Agriculture and Forestry, Institute of Horticulture, Laboratory of Plant Protection	Lithuania	Surveillance, Pesticide reduction, Pesticides, Minimizing spread, Biological control, Inspection, Plant products, Pathogenicity, Passengers, Invasive diseases, Trade, Apples
The State Plant Service under the Ministry*	Lithuania	Sampling, Zoning, Intelligence sharing, Skill and knowledge transfer, Information sharing, Phytosanitary research collaboration, Research infrastructures and collections, Eradication, Biological reference material, Reference laboratory, Diagnostic tests, Quarantine, Non-quarantine pests, Climate, Established populations, Outbreaks, Plant diseases, Trade, Clavibacter sepedonicus, Potatoes
Lithuanian Research Center for Agriculture and Forestry (LAMMC)	Lithuania	Sampling, Vector control, Herbicide, Climate, Soil, Pathogenic fungus, Weeds, Soil protection, Sclerotinia sclerotiorum, Fusarium, Potato late blight, Potatoes, Oilseeds, Wheat
Plantum	Netherlands	Offshore surveillance, Phytosanitary research collaboration, Biosecurity policy, Biosecurity research, Seed treatment, Integrated pest management, Seeds, Treatment certificate, Biocidal resistance, Pathogenicity, Invasive diseases, Dissolved oxygen
Wageningen University & Research	Netherlands	Sampling, Offshore surveillance, Biosecurity emergency, Biosecurity strategy, Pesticide reduction, Pesticides, Minimizing spread, RNA interference, Next generation sequencing, Inspection, Plant products, Climate, Outbreaks, Biocidal resistance, Virulence, Pathogenicity, Passengers, Host plants, Plant diseases, Trade, Phytoplasmas, Crops
RHP (Kenniscentrum en certificering voor substraten (teeltmedia))	Netherlands	Cleaning, Detection, Goods, Horticulture

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Nederlandse Akkerbouwvakbond	Netherlands	Prevention, Pest management, Dispersal pathways, Pathogenic fungus, Plant diseases, Weeds, Parasitic nematodes, Potatoes
LTO Akkerbouw, Vollegrondsgroente, Bomen, Vaste planten en Zomerbloemen	Netherlands	Skill and knowledge transfer, Phytosanitary research collaboration, Biosecurity policy, Biosecurity research, Eradication, Minimizing spread, Plant products, Climate, Passengers, Host plants, Weeds, Trade, Bacterial wilt, Cyperus esculentus, Popillia japonica, Meloidogyne chitwoodi, Crops
BO Akkerbouw	Netherlands	Pest management, Seeds, Emerging pests, Downy mildew, Clavibacter sepedonicus, Cyperus esculentus, Alternaria, Golden potato cyst nematode, Root-knot nematodes, Ralstonia solanacearum, Onions
Naktuinbouw	Netherlands	Bioassay, Non-quarantine pests, Tomato brown rugose fruit virus
Nederlandse Aardappel Organisatie	Netherlands	Alternative control methods, Seeds, Potatoes
Stichting Markering Houten Verpakkingen (SMHV)	Netherlands	Wood packaging material, Goods, Trade
NIVIP	Netherlands	Sampling, Early warning systems, Biosecurity emergency, Biosecurity policy, Research infrastructures and collections, Pesticides, Pest management, Taxonomic identification, High throughput sequencing, Quarantine, Goods, Potentially harmful pests, Climate, Emerging pests, Established populations, Pathogenicity, Plant diseases, Trade, Crops
NVWA	Netherlands	Biosecurity emergency, Eradication, Pest management, High throughput sequencing, Innovative diagnostic tools, Inspection, Quarantine, Packaging, Climate, Outbreaks, Pathogenicity, Mail articles, Invasive diseases, Trade
Sagaplant	Norway	Cleaning, Pest management, Detection, Plant products, Climate, Pollination, Ecosystems, Crops
Extension services. Region south	Norway	Pesticides, Biopesticide, Dissolved oxygen, Raspberries, Strawberries
Extension services SA	Norway	Forage crops, Pesticides, Pest management, Climate, Overwintering, Crop yield, Fodder
Innovation Norway/Bionoca	Norway	Climate, Tree species
Norsøk	Norway	Pesticides, Plant products, Climate, Pathogenic fungus, Pollination, Agriculture, Lygus rugulipennis, Strawberries, Vegetables
County governor (Rogaland county)	Norway	Forests, Ips typographus, Tomicus piniperda, Hylobius abietis, Norway spruce, Sitka spruce
Artsdatabanken (Norwegian Biodiversity Information Centre)	Norway	Evaluation, Climate, Pathogenicity, Dispersal pathways, Invasive diseases, Trade, Ecosystems
Bergen University Museum	Norway	Pesticides, Prevention, Containment, Biological control, Diagnostic tests, Inspection, Seeds, Population genetics, Biocidal resistance, Pathogenicity, Containers, Soil, Invasive diseases, Biodiversity, Dissolved oxygen, Soil protection, Nurseries, Trade, Forests, Nursery

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Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research	Norway	Remote sensing, Prevention, Pest management, Diagnostic tests, Climate, Susceptible areas, Population genetics, Established populations, Outbreaks, Invasiveness, Pathogenicity, Invasive diseases, Ungulate browsing, Landscape, Forestry, Forests, Hymenoscyphus fraxineus, Scolytinae, Norway spruce
County governor (Troms and Finnmark county)	Norway	Defoliants, Climate, Logging, Epidemics, Dissolved oxygen, Forests, Exotic invasive moths, Birch, Norway spruce, Pinus sylvestris
County governor (Møre and Romsdal county)	Norway	Climate, Forestry, Forests, Hylobius abietis
Oslo County	Norway	Biodiversity, Agriculture
Syngenta	Norway	Fungicide, Insecticide, Seeds, Potato late blight
Norskog	Norway	Climate, Forests, Ips typographus, Norway spruce
Allskog	Norway	Evaluation, Goods, Climate, Forests, Tree species
Glommen Mjøsen Skog	Norway	Treatment, Prevention, Pest management, Seeds, Climate, Established populations, Pathogenicity, Soil, Seed banks, Invasive diseases, Soil scarification, Forestry, Forests, Birch, Norway spruce, Pinus sylvestris
Alstadhaug forest nursery	Norway	Biological control, Plant products, Climate, Dissolved oxygen, Ecosystems
Norwegian Food Authorities	Norway	Early warning systems, Pesticides, Containment, Diagnostic tests, Quarantine, Plant products, Climate, Outbreaks, Containers, Trade, Sudden oak death, Pears
Landbruksdirektoratet	Norway	Climate
Gartnerhallen	Norway	Early warning systems, Pesticides, Detection, Plant products, Biocidal resistance, Soil, Biodiversity, Soil protection, Berries
Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development	Poland	Remote sensing, Early warning systems, Biosecurity strategy, Farm biosecurity, Pesticides, Integrated pest management, Classical biological control, Biopesticide, Border, Diagnostic tests, Climate, Extreme weather events, Population genetics, Established populations, Pathogenicity, Soil, Pathogenic fungus, Plant diseases, Soil microbiome, Human health, Soil protection, Crop yield, Land, Parasitic nematodes, Crops
General Directorate of State Forests	Poland	Treatment, Bioherbicide, Quarantine, Climate, Susceptible areas, Invasiveness, Exotic invasive species, Biodiversity, Forests
National Agricultural and Food Centre	Slovakia	Early warning systems, Biosecurity strategy, Forage crops, Pesticides, Pest management, Biopesticide, Detection, Plant products, Climate, Susceptible areas, Population genetics, Invasiveness, Pathogenicity, Soil, Plant diseases, Biodiversity, Dissolved oxygen, Soil compaction, Soil erosion, Soil acidification, Pollination, Agriculture, Land, Fusarium, Crops
Slovak Agricultural University	Slovakia	Evaluation, Biological control, Climate, Susceptible areas, Invasiveness, Pathogenicity, Soil, Pathogenic fungus, Plant diseases, Soil protection, Western corn rootworm, Essential oils

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Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), SLU Risk assessment of plant pests	Sweden	Early warning systems, Biosecurity emergency, Eradication, Prevention, Pest management, Morphological identification, Diagnostic tests, Quarantine, Climate, Susceptible areas, Established populations, Host range, Host plants, Regulating services, Ecosystems, Agrilus anxius, Sudden oak death
Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), Southern Swedish Forest Research Centre (SLU Alnarp)	Sweden	Traps, Sampling, Early warning systems, Pesticides, Pest management, Biological control, Nanopore sequencing using MinION, Nanopore sequencing, Plant products, Potentially harmful pests, Climate, Biocidal resistance, Pathogenicity, Ports, Invasive diseases, Nurseries, Forests, Hymenoscyphus fraxineus, Emerald ash borer, Agrilus anxius, Birch, Nursery
Intertek ScanBi Diagnostics AB	Sweden	Sampling, Farm biosecurity, Potatoes, Grains
Swedish Board of Agriculture (Swedish National Plant Protection Organisation)	Sweden	Sampling, Detection surveys, Sentinal species, Early warning systems, Pest management, Reference laboratory, Morphological identification, Diagnostic tests, Inspection, Plant products, Regulated pests, Established populations, Outbreaks, Plant diseases, Forestry, Agriculture, Ecosystems, Horticulture
Defra Plant Health Evidence	United Kingdom	Intelligence sharing, Information sharing, Research infrastructures and collections, Pest management, Border, Detection, Goods, Climate, Outbreaks, Landscape, Trade
Defra Tree Health Policy	United Kingdom	Intelligence sharing, Information sharing, Prevention, Pest management, Climate, Emerging pests, Incursions, Landscape, Ips typographus
Defra Plants Risk and Horizon Scanning	United Kingdom	Offshore surveillance, Evaluation, Pest management, Inspection, Climate, Outbreaks, Trade
Royal Horticulturla Society	United Kingdom	Offshore surveillance, Phytosanitary research collaboration, Biosecurity research, Pesticide reduction, Pesticides, Pest management, Plant health diagnostics, Inspection, Climate, Established populations, Invasive diseases, Exotic invasive moths, Otiorynchus sulcatus
Forestry Commission	United Kingdom	Remote sensing, Offshore surveillance, Skill and knowledge transfer, Fumigation, Minimizing spread, Inspection, Plant products, Climate, Passengers, Trade
Forest Research	United Kingdom	Sampling, Offshore surveillance, Biosecurity strategy, Pest management, Diagnostic tests, Goods, Regulated pests, Climate, Emerging pests, Culturable, Pathogenicity, Invasive diseases, Forestry, Tree species
APHA (Plant Health & Seeds Inspectorate within Defra's Animal and Plant Health Agency).	United Kingdom	Sampling, Border, Diagnostic tests, Inspection, Seeds, Treatment certificate, Emerging pests, Incursions, Outbreaks, Pathogenicity, Plant diseases, Trade, Tomatoes
Fera Science Ltd	United Kingdom	Sampling rates, Phytosanitary research collaboration, Biosecurity research, Pesticides, Pest management, Border, High throughput sequencing, Inspection, Climate, Susceptible areas, Invasiveness, Exotic invasive species, Dissolved oxygen, Landscape, Agriculture, Trade, Candidatus Liberibacter species, Emerald ash borer, Ips typographus, Tomato brown rugose fruit virus, Oaks, Horticulture

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Metadata model

Name	Property	Expected data type	Comment
Name	foaf:Organization	xs:string	
Country	dcterms:spatial	xs:string	If harmonization is needed, use GeoNames. Example: gn:officialName (en) "Austria": https://sws.geonames.org/2782113/
Organisation plant health issue	cebra:orgPlantHealthIssue	xs:anyURI	Plant health issues for a given foaf:Organization
Organisation priority	cebra:orgPriority	xs:anyURI	Any priority for a foaf:Organization
Plant health priority	cebra:plantHealthPriority	xs:anyURI	Plant health priorities for a country, region or global context.
Plant health priority scale	cebra:plantHealthPriorityScale	xs:anyURI	The scale of a plant health priority. Use vocabulary: - country - region - worldwide
Subject	dcterms:subject	xs:anyURI	
Capacity building	cebra:capacityBuilding	xs:anyURI	Capacity building needs for a foaf:organization
Regional pest priority	cebra:regionalPestPriority	xs:anyURI	Pest priorities as defined for a given region such as 'northern Europe'
Pest priority factor	cebra:pestPriorityFactor	xs:anyURI	Context for pest prioritization.
Global pest priority	cebra:globalPestPriority	xs:anyURI	Pest priorities with no geographic boundary
Country pest priority	cebra:countryPestPriority	xs:anyURI	Pest priorities for a given country
Research need	cebra:researchNeed	xs:anyURI	Research needs for a foaf:organization
Short term research need	cebra:shortTermResearchNeed	xs:anyURI	Short term research needs for a foaf:organization

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ANNEX 2: Report of the international workshop on 'Plant Health Research Priorities for Northern Europe'

Date: 25th October 2024

Location: virtual meeting, *via* Zoom

1. Agenda and final list of participants

09:00-09:10	Welcome (Baldissera Giovani, Euphresco)
09:10-09:30	EUPHRESCO III overview (Baldissera Giovani, Euphresco) Surveys and consultations (Ria Nouwen, FPS)
09:30-10:00	Analysis of responses from Northern Europe (Les Kneebone, Cebra)
10:00-10:15	Break and walk to the virtual meeting room
10:15-12:00	Working Group discussions by country's representatives How to work together on common priorities Working Group 1, facilitated by Lena Vlaminck, FPS Working Group 2, facilitated by Anna Maria D'Onghia, CIHEAM-Bari Working Group 3, facilitated by Jasmine Burr-Hersey, Defra
12:00-13:00	Working Groups reports and discussions (by the facilitators)
13:00-13:15	Moving forward (Ria Nouwen, FPS)
13:15	End of the meeting

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2. Welcome

Mr. Giovanni (Euphresco, Int.) welcomed the workshop participants which comprised over 40 representatives from research funding organizations and policy-making bodies across Northern Europe (Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom). He also thanked the participation of EFSA and the Green-ERA Hub, which represent key organizations and initiatives that support and fund agricultural, plant and Plant Health research across Europe. Mr. Giovanni (Euphresco, Int.) concluded by emphasizing that this work is made possible through the funding of the [EUPHRESCO III project](#) by the European Union.

A [video](#) created for the workshop was presented to the participants, summarizing the work completed so far in Northern Europe and outlining the plans for the upcoming months.

The presentations made during the workshop are available from the Euphresco Digital Research Object Portal ([DROP](#)).

3. EUPHRESCO III overview

Mr. Giovanni (Euphresco, Int.) presented an overview on Euphresco and research coordination activities. He emphasized that Plant Health problems are growing due to different reasons:

- Globalization and movement of people
- Trade
- Climate change

The challenges associated with Plant Health can be addressed in two main ways: through research and regulation. Research provides the essential knowledge and tools, while regulation offers the necessary framework for action. At the EU level, there has been coordinated effort in the development of EU Plant Health policy. However, from a research standpoint, there has been a lack of coordination among national phytosanitary research programs that support these policy activities. Additionally, the agencies responsible for providing scientific expertise are increasingly facing staff shortages, limited funding and insufficient training. To overcome these challenges, solutions were sought, with research coordination and collaboration being identified as a key approach. The need to revive the scientific basis of the phytosanitary field has been a priority since the [EPPO Madeira Declaration](#). Upon a request of the EC Council Working Party of the Chief Officers of Plant Health Services (COPHS), the Euphresco network for phytosanitary research coordination and funding started in 2006 to support phytosanitary research programme owners and programme managers to develop and take advantage of synergies amongst national research programmes and activities. In Europe, many of the phytosanitary policies, regulations and underpinning technical recommendations are determined at regional level, while the research that supports them is mostly funded and carried out at the national level. Coordination of such national activities is then vital to reduce the impact of plant pests on the economy, the environment and the health of citizens at the level of each country but more generally at European and international level. Over the years, Euphresco evolved from a western European initiative into an international network comprising over 75 organizations from more than 50 countries worldwide. In the past years, Euphresco has worked to establish a Plant Health research forum, a platform where regulators, research funders, research implementers, and end-users can collaborate. It serves as a hub to retrieve the latest information on Plant Health research, a space for discussing key research topics, and a venue for conducting research activities. The success of Euphresco as a primarily European network has set the

ground for discussions on the development of initiatives to address the needs of other world regions and for global coordination of phytosanitary research.

Recently, Euphresco received funding from the European Union to explore possibilities to develop a global network for coordinating phytosanitary research under the project EUPHRESCO III. Its goal is to set the foundations for global phytosanitary research coordination and to assess how Euphresco's models can be adapted to serve a wider, international audience. To achieve this, the project aims to:

- Strengthen national coordination efforts
- Engage a broader range of stakeholders, recognizing that Plant Health is a shared global challenge
- Tailor activities to meet the diverse needs of a wider audience

The EUPHRESCO III project is structured across 9 different world regions: Africa, Australia, Caribbean-Central America & South America, Central Asia, Europe-North, Europe-South & Mediterranean, North America, Pacific Islands and South-East Asia. The aim is to implement various activities in each country within these regions, gradually elevating the knowledge gathered or produced at the national level to a regional scale, and ultimately to a global perspective.

4. Surveys and consultations

Ms. Nouwen (FPS, BE) presented an overview on the EUPHRESCO III methodology used to gather information for the identification of research needs and their prioritization.

In the framework of the EUPHRESCO III project, consultations are organized in different regions of the world with the following purposes:

- To collect information on needs & priorities based on an alignment of bottom-up (survey) and top-down (workshop/consultation) input:
 - to decide on call for topics (2025 and 2026)
 - to shape the next Strategic Research Agenda on Plant Health
- To explore the needs and possibilities for future collaboration
- To build trust
- To build the future Network

For Northern Europe, the consultation process began in early 2024 with the identification of stakeholders (e.g. research funders, policy makers, academia, companies, *etc.*) across various countries. During Spring, a stakeholder survey was distributed.

The questions asked in the survey were specifically on:

- Key Plant Health issues or related practical problems that are currently faced by the addressed organizations in Northern Europe
- Research priorities that are important at country, regional or even global level
- Agricultural crops that have needs in research
- Needs in terms of capacity building
- Priority pests that are important for the region/globally
- Research areas to be addressed

The survey also offered stakeholders the opportunity to identify one specific research need to be addressed over the next three years, which could be incorporated into future calls. A total of 105 stakeholders from Northern Europe participated in the survey. The data collected was analyzed by [CEBRA](#) prior to the workshop/consultation, which was designed to align and integrate bottom-up and top-down needs, with a focus on common priorities across the region.

This information, along with data from other regions and disciplines, will be used to identify research priorities and develop Euphresco call topics. By the end of the EUPHRESCO III project in 2026, the collected input will help shaping the next Strategic Research Agenda.

Mr Capieau (SJV, SE) noted that one of the questions referred to ‘agricultural crops’, but the terminology was too narrow and according to him there was the risks to limit inputs from other areas such as forestry, horticultural, and other plant production systems or environments. He suggested that the question should be rephrased in a broader sense. Mr Giovanni (Euphresco, Int.) and Ms Nouwen (FPS, BE) explained that clarifications on the questions were provided in the consultation package, where it was indicated that ‘crop’ includes trees and ‘plant products’ includes ‘tree products’. Mr Giovanni (Euphresco, Int.) and Ms Nouwen (FPS, BE) also added that the survey was sent to organizations that deal with tree and forests issues, thus tree and forest stakeholders were included in the exercise. This is reflected in the CEBRA report, where a national cluster for Norway highlights the importance of trees. However, only transnational clusters were selected for the workshop discussions, to focus on identifying commonalities across the various countries of the region. Finally, a dedicated champion for forest and tree health has been appointed in EUPHRESCO III (NIBIO and UNIBZ) to make sure that the tree and forest issues are identified.

5. Analysis of responses from Northern Europe

Mr. Kneebone (CEBRA, AU) explained the methodology used to analyze the survey data/results gathered from Northern European stakeholders. The process began with cleaning the data and developing an ontology for the survey text to convert it into a machine-readable format. Next, all questions and responses were transformed into graph data using a Graph Database, and then classified according to biosecurity vocabularies. The data was queried using the SPARQL database, and the results were presented in the form of tables, charts, and maps.

Three vocabularies were used to classify the survey responses. The first was a Biosecurity Thesaurus, which includes over 500 concepts organized hierarchically, along with approximately 500 alternative labels (synonyms). This thesaurus is structured using the [Simple Knowledge Organisation System](#) (SKOS) and is licensed under Creative Commons, making it reusable in other systems. A second vocabulary focused on classifying Priority Pests, drawing from multiple lists, including scientific and common names as well as EPPO codes. Like the Biosecurity Thesaurus, this vocabulary also carries a Creative Commons license and is linked to the broader categories in the Biosecurity Thesaurus. The third vocabulary related to Commodities, adapted from the ABARES classification and also linked to EPPO codes and Priority Pests using a ‘threatened by’, allowing for inferences between the vocabularies.

The Biosecurity Thesaurus vocabulary was used to classify:

- ‘Plant Health issues’
- ‘top 5 priorities’
- ‘capacity building’
- ‘research areas’

The Priority Pests and commodities vocabularies were used to classify responses on all columns (survey questions). Known relationships between pests and commodities were also used to make inferences in the survey data.

The key issues arising from the data analysis of CEBRA were:

- Broad concept categories needed to be updated:

- Changes to broad pest and commodity classes
- Grouping Biosecurity Thesaurus top concepts into four main categories
- Survey collection method needs to be revised for the future:
 - Output relied on too much data cleaning to convert it in a machine-readable format
 - Recommendations made for collection application support

Mr. Van Herzele (FPS, BE) inquired whether there is information available on how the responses or contributions to the survey are distributed among different stakeholder groups, such as policymakers, research funders, research organizations, industry, farmers and foresters, expressed as a percentage of the 105 survey responses. Mr. Giovanni (Euphresco, Int.) replied that this information is available in the Excel file shared with participants prior to the meeting, titled '*survey raw data*'. However, he noted that the CEBRA colleagues did not analyze the responses by stakeholder groups, as all answers were considered together. Belgian participants also inquired about how the survey was distributed among the stakeholders identified by each Euphresco/EUPHRESCO III national contact point. Mr. Giovanni (Euphresco, Int.) explained that, as the Euphresco/EUPHRESCO III network office was not familiar with the specific stakeholders in each country, it relied on the information provided by the national contact points, who are responsible for coordinating Euphresco/EUPHRESCO III activities within their countries. The distribution process was discussed individually with each national contact point. In some instances, like in Belgium, the national contact point distributed the survey, while in others, such as Germany, the Euphresco/EUPHRESCO III network office took on the responsibility of distribution. Mr Van Herzele (FPS, BE) asked clarifications on how the stakeholders were contacted. Mr Giovanni (Euphresco, Int.) explained that stakeholders for the survey were identified either by the Euphresco Network Office or by the national contact point.

6. Working Group discussions by country's representatives and reports

The analysis performed by CEBRA identified common priorities based on vocabularies:

- Pest priorities
- Commodity priorities
- Biosecurity activity priorities
- Combination of the previous three vocabularies

Vocabularies were developed in conformance with the Simple Knowledge Organisation System (SKOS). The common interest maps (see figure below) for the different vocabularies show clusters for the top 5 most prevalent concepts reported in the survey responses. Each organization that participated in the national survey is represented by a number on the map. Belgian organizations are represented along the North Sea due to insufficient space to display them inland. Interactive versions of these maps can be requested to the Euphresco Network Office.

Working Groups were formed based on the clusters from the combined vocabularies approach by CEBRA analysis, which are shown below:

Out of 5 clusters identified, only clusters 1, 2 and 3 were considered to organize the discussions. Clusters 4 and 5 were excluded because they are mainly national clusters.

The dendrogram below illustrates how organizations grouped together based on their survey responses:

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The expected outcome of the working group discussions is a list of research topics that will raise an international level of interest in northern Europe and beyond, co-shaped by the working group participants. Achieving this requires prior knowledge:

- From the information available within each organization
- From the research programmes planned/in progress within each organization
- From the information provided within the CEBRA report
- Other

The working group discussions focused on the following questions:

- What are the key issues for each concept within the cluster
- What are the research priorities associated to each issue that you think as a group is of common interest?
- What research topics should be prioritized for the 2025 call?
- Which concrete research need do you want to address in the coming 3 years?

Working Group 1

Cluster 1: Trade Xylella fastidiosa Anoplophora glabripennis Popillia japonica Potatoes	Country	Name	Organization
	Belgium	Kristiaan Van Laecke	ILVO
		Lieven Van Herzele	FPS
		Miryam Benalla	FPS
		Silvia Travella	FAVV-AFSCA
	Estonia	Maarja Malm	REM
	France	Ki-Woong Nam	INRAE
	The Netherlands	Maikel Aveskamp	NVWA
	Slovakia	Jana Hreňová	MPSR
	Sweden	Kristof Capieau	SJV
	Work package 2	Ria Nouwen	FPS
		Lena Vlaminc	FPS

Minutes by Lena Vlaminc (FPS, BE)

Mr Van Herzele (FPS, BE) suggested to make reference and use an already harmonized terminology, such as IPPC ISPM 5 Glossary of phytosanitary terms. Mr. Giovanni (Euphresco, Int.) explained that the IPPC use of IPPC terminology falls outside the scope of Euphresco/EUPHRESKO III. He further noted that there is no universally agreed terminology for research activities, and the ISPM5 is a glossary for phytosanitary terms, not research

terms. Colleagues at Cebra, who have experience in categorizing information, have used several available resources, and adjustments were made when certain terminology appeared unsuitable. Mr. Giovanni (Euphresco, Int.) emphasized that this is the first exercise of its kind and represents the first scientific approach aimed at identifying Plant Health research priorities, marking progress compared to methods that rely on the opinions of individual experts or groups of experts. He also highlighted that the methodologies will be reviewed by regional champions in the coming months to work towards a more unified approach.

For each of the 5 concepts, the following questions were raised:

- What are the key issues?
- What are the research priorities?

Concept 1: Trade

- How to improve quarantine and how to identify and eradicate to prevent invasion?
- Need for information on sea container safety, packaging of materials
- Seed materials: face challenges in import but also exporting materials – mostly risk assessment. How can we convince rest of the world that not everything should be considered as a treat?
- In relation to Plant Health: facilitating save trade! Need for risk assessment. So we can get good justification why we set up restrictions for trade.
- Import controls: the methods to perform import controls – further knowledge, new technology, innovations. Also to reduce time needed for controls. Quicker detection methods
- Trade as a whole also on a global level, we go into a more commodity approach. We address commodities. We need science-based evidence to take measures to prevent diseases coming in together with commodities. And most important is good risk assessment. We miss a lot of knowledge on diagnostics (e.g. fruit flies). Helped by knowledge sharing. How could we involve more new technologies?
- Support availability and accessibility of cost efficient tools for inspectors for import controls. The monitoring, trapping and identification of Scolytinae and Cerambycidae (two very large Q insect groups). In Belgium, a new trap (fan trap) was developed. It would be a good subject to check cost efficiency of the traps with this newly developed fan trap. Elaboration of collection on morphological and especially also on sequencing level.
- Trade is really increasing every year so very important aspect. Find a balance between a good control and a fast possibility of safe trade. Build capacity and knowledge and fast recognition systems

Concept 2: Potatoes

- Can also be linked with trade
- Trade in potatoes is one of the key issues. Wart disease is a key problem. Spread and control of Meloidogyne species. Mainly management of the organisms and also still some issues with diagnostics.
- Important to protect potato against regulated pests. But we need continued monitoring and control in relation to these regulations. What are the best control methods for these potato diseases? For example, potato wart disease remains a significant issue for

Sweden and the Netherlands, and it represents a major challenge for (Northern) Europe.

- Raise awareness – potato can be used to raise awareness. One world one health. Very important crop. How can we involve citizen science in the research? How do we communicate and inform the public?
- Need for a list on resistant crops in our control strategies against a range of potato pests. Also think about crop rotation.
- Potato is very important so also big pressure from industry on agriculture. Less attention to sustainable production of the crops. This can have consequences. Economic pressure for huge production. Also better communication to industry about importance of sustainable production.

Concept 3: *Xylella fastidiosa*

- Big issue in southern Europe but also a lot of touristic exchange. Big risk for nursery stock. Awareness by society.
- A lot of research going-on on Xylella so the key issue is exchange of knowledge on the research that is done.

Concept 4: *Anoplophora glabripennis*

- For insects monitoring and identification, easily transported in woody materials. Morphological but also sequence level – more complete databases are needed.
- More important than Xylella, but if we look at trade we also have the responsibility to protect the other areas in the world.
- For insect pests it is important to know the origin of the insect pests. Is there insect resistance? Risk assessment. Ecological control of pest insects and pathway control. Traps are not really working well. Better traps for this beetle needed.

Concept 5: *Popillia japonica*

- Ecological control of the beetle.
- Molecular techniques are already ongoing.
- Quite some research already ongoing.
- Detection methods
- Knowledge exchange is important
- Really difficult one once you have it in your region. Main concern is control. What are the most effective control measures to eradicate and if not how to contain it? – eradication methods
- Sharing material – Euphresco can contribute here.

Prioritization of the 5 concepts discussed:

1. Trade
2. Potato – Linked to trade as well as effective control methods
3. Pests: are all equally important – is a risky thing to rank them without criteria -> we do risk ranking of pests

Remark: Link to the commodity approach -> it is not a pest approach but a commodity approach

General extra issues:

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- Impact of climate change as driver of emerging pests
- Invasive plants are also important. We also focus on pests and diseases but maybe too little on invasive plants.
- Do not forget about forestry

Working Group 2

Cluster 2: Trade Soil Potatoes Soil protection Pesticides	Country	Name	Organization
	Estonia	Meelis Kõiv	REM
	France	Bernard Quere	FN3PT
	Germany	Bettina Beerbaum	BMEL
	Ireland	Conor McGee	DAFM
	Lithuania	Silvija Pupeliene	VATZUM
	Norway	Ari Hietala	NIBIO
	United Kingdom	Jasmine Burr-Hersey	DEFRA
	-	Giuseppe Stancanelli	EFSA

Minutes by Jasmine Burr-Hersey (DEFRA, GB)

Concept 1: Trade

- Analyses flow of trade for commodities, and the understand risk of pest. Focus on a particular commodity and develop a standard. Pathway analysis. Collect data on a type of trade, trade characteristics and risk assessment.
- Commodity standard- literature review: what type of information is needed to understand on import/ export of potatoes and woodchip.
- Trade issues - introduction of goods from other states .i.e. potatoes, seed potatoes. Exporting seed potatoes. Often, different countries do not follow the same methodology for pest risk analysis and it can be difficult to understand each other phytosanitary schemes/ demands. Ban of seed potatoes between UK and Europe, in favour to remove this ban but would need a lot of research to undertake this.
- Ireland - appropriate measure for bark free wood, woodchip, bark. Agreement that this is a risky commodity and they are often made of poor quality wood, how efficient the phytosanitary methods really are when you have large piles of this material. How can you ensure an entire pile is efficiently sterilized. What kind of wood is being used to make this material. Project in analysing imported woodchips in trade could be a useful,

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type, quality before and after treatment. Risk of bark beetles. Large gaps in information means barriers in trade, to keep protected zone standards.

- General - Developing rapid diagnostic method/ alternative methods for import controls would be very important. Standard methods overlook a lot of insects etc. Mapping of methods that we have in different countries, what new methods could be used? Share methods for testing seed potatoes, many countries do not apply the same methods, need to know exactly what pest / disease different counties have to understand how best to test. Data base sharing would be beneficial, also capacity building exercise, pest risk analysis, then decide standard/ methods.
- Specific High throughput method, DNA pest methods- very powerful, understand if it is alive or not. Preliminary examinations- how can you assess a whole shipment of commodities to ensure it is safe, rather than a subset? Gap in EPPO- methods for quarantine pests but not regulated pests- are there official standards for non-quarantine pests, mapping of diagnostics methods for other commodities would be important.

Concept 2: Soil

- Nematodes in Europe, a way to regulated or deregulate nematodes- further research into this area.
- Exchange of soil between countries.
- Forestry perspective, trade of plants/ nursery grown plants, peat in nursery production, move away/ phase out of peat to use other growth substrates- what understanding do we have with other growth substrates- this could be a big research area. Reduce amount of pesticides in nursery how does this play out in a big picture. Peat is one of Irelands main exports.
- Are there pesticides that can treat soil around larger trees, how can we assess if treatments are successful, how can we prevent insects are present in the soil in the first place, how can we detect the pest in the soil.
- How can we test if pests are in the soil? Especially pathogens.

Concept 3: Potatoes

- Phytoplasma, can make big damages to potato production, not much knowledge about those phytoplasma. Continue work on liberovecta as a vector, need to avoid these pests in Europe. Number of disease in potato are very high, way of diagnosis HTS is key, diagnostics around this area will be key. More development of these would be critical. Need to align research within Euphresco on this area- mapping of works already undertaken in countries, projects in breeding resistance and pesticides etc.
- Work on vectors for disease like leaf hoppers can transmit viruses and phytoplasma- so important to look into these, must rely less on pesticides and learn how to grow without pesticides. Consider costs of research.

Concept 4: Soil protection

- Could be linked to environment research, system for management, beyond the scope of the network?, maybe more forest network/ plantation and climate change. An inventory of activity could be useful as a data sharing exercise.

Concept 5: Pesticides

- Focus on biological pesticides and biological enemies of quarantine pests, chemical pesticides should not be a big topic. Risk associated in not host range for biological agents. When you have a new pest important to do a rapid assessment of control methods. Resistant plants would be the ultimate goal rather than implementing pesticides. Can learn from different countries on natural biological pests from other countries. A follow on project from a previous Euphresco project.

Working Group 3

Cluster 3: Agriculture Trade Viruses Fruit Detection	Country	Name	Organization
	Austria	Elisabeth Jöchlinger	AGES
	Austria	Doris Lucyshyn	FWF
	Finland	Johanna Nykyri	MMM
	France	Philippe Michel	PHYTEIS
	Germany	Silke Steinmoller	JKI
		Christian Hillnhuetter	RPGI
	Sweden	Mattias Norrby	SLF
	Switzerland	Andreas von Felten	FOAG
	United Kingdom	David Kenyon	SASA
	Europe South	Anna Maria D'Onghia	CIHEAM-Bari

Minutes by Anna Maria D'Onghia (CIHEAM-Bari, Int.)

Following CEBRA's analyses for cluster 3 and discussions of research priorities by the organizations represented in the group, a selection of priority crops, pests and plant health activities has been identified. The information will be used by the champion for Northern Europe to identify research priorities, through interactions with the EUPHRESKO III champions of the other regions/disciplines and relevant groups (policy-makers, research funders, scientists, etc.). Research topics will be developed during December 2024 and January 2025, and will be considered for the Euphresco/EUPHRESKO III call for transnational collaboration.

Commodity priorities, covering concepts 1 & 4: Agriculture & Fruit

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Priority plants should include crops, forestry and ornamental species (pest reservoir, important for surveillance). Potato, tomato, vegetables, cereals, apple, grapevine and strawberry were highlighted in the discussion.

Pests priorities, covering concept 3: Viruses

Concerning the priority pests, Tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV) was considered a very important pest, especially because is very difficult to eradicate in soils. Since potato was highlighted as a priority crop, potato diseases as the mop-top virus (PMTV) or *Ralstonia solanacearum* were mentioned. Actually, severe losses in potato crops are found in Southern Germany, due to a complex disease caused by two phytoplasma (*Candidatus Phytoplasma solani/Stolbur* and *Candidatus Arsenophonus phytopathogenicus*) vectored by leaf hopper *Pentastridius leporinus*. The disease complex is as well present in sugar beet and actually spreads into several vegetable crops and moves North. It will become a major threat to agricultural production, as neither resistant nor tolerant varieties are available in any crop nor plant protection products to control the vector. Other important pathogens are *Erwinia amylovora*, *Xylella fastidiosa*, *Diplodia bulgarica*, stolbur phytoplasma and the gamma-3 proteobacterium. However, the following pests were also highlighted: *Popillia japonica*, Flavescence dorée (FD) and Nematodes.

Biosecurity activity priorities, covering concepts 2 & 5: Trade & Detection

The main areas of research were identified in the following order:

- Surveillance & monitoring: new approaches in the field (remote sensing), tools (smart traps for pests), vectors and beneficials, digital platform, sentinel plants/vectors, alternative techniques), citizen science
- Trade: detection (bacteria, viruses); inspection at borders (plant material), passengers control, e-commerce/internet trade
- Diagnostics: validation of new, rapid, easy and cheap methods e.g., NGS, eDNA (reference labs) for NPPOs to be applied at the entry points and in the field monitoring (quarantine pests)
- Pest risk analysis methods, especially for quarantine pests not present yet in Europe
- Modelling for forecasting to help in the searching activities for target pests
- IPM: alternative methods to chemical use in plant protection methods and products (e.g. biocontrol products and agents)
- Bionformatics: digital platform for sharing information for specific pests
- Weed control

Mr. Hillnhuetter (RPGI, DE) and Ms. Steinmoller (JKI, DE) expressed concerns regarding time constraints, noting that a half-day workshop was insufficient for thorough discussions. Additionally, this workshop was perceived as the only opportunity to set the research agenda for the next three years. Mr. Giovanni (Euphresco, Int.) addressed these concerns, explaining that the timing of the workshop was challenging because the organization originally responsible for the event (NWWA, NL) withdrew, leaving the Euphresco/EUPHRESKO III network office to organize it at short notice as an unforeseen, additional activity. He clarified that the workshop outputs will specifically contribute to identify the 2025 research priorities. The work on the research agenda operates somewhat independently, and the exact process for developing the strategic agenda is yet to be defined. He concluded that organizing long in-

person events requires financial and human resources. If there are funds to organize such events under EUPHRESKO III, these funds will no longer be available after 2026, unless Euphresco members decide to increase the annual contribution to Euphresco. He noted the suggestions received and he will prepare in the next months a costing for organizing workshops that will be distributed to Euphresco members.

Ms. D'Onghia (CIHEAM-Bari, Int.) emphasized that conducting the survey is the most challenging part for the champions, and suggested that this exercise could be repeated every 2–3 years. However, she proposed that workshops based on the latest survey results could be organized annually. This would help keep the community engaged, ensure continued interest in Plant Health research coordination, address emerging challenges and facilitate the sharing of new information.

7. Moving forward

Ms. Nouwen (FPS, BE) indicated that following the regional consultation for Northern Europe, all gathered information will be processed. The inputs from the consultations organized in all regions will be reviewed, compared and processed, in order to identify priorities that are transregional and transdisciplinary. This will help to define the research priorities to be implemented in the upcoming Euphresco calls for 2025 and 2026. The input will also play a key role in shaping the Strategic Research Agenda, which is planned to be ready by the end of 2026.

After the event, the following is expected from the workshop organizers:

- Draw up the consultation report, including information from the survey and the workshop discussions. This output will be shared with workshop participants and EUPHRESKO III champions
- Meet with the other regional and discipline champions on 2024-12-02. This meeting will focus on:
 - Sharing experiences on methodologies and outcomes of the consultations
 - Prioritize the research needs identified and transform them into concrete research topics
 - Implement the topics in the 2025 / 2026 call for collaboration
 - Analyze the information gathered in a deeper level to serve as input for the Strategic Research agenda, which will be on a more global scale than the previous one

After the event, the following is expected from the workshop participants:

- To coordinate further on a national level: which topics are interesting to fund further? What are the preferred priorities to work on?
- Find the resources to fund some of these topics that will come out in the next rounds
- Participate in the next Euphresco calls
- Respond to the funding survey, which will be send out in Spring 2025
- Use the Strategic Research Agenda as it is now and the new one once is ready by 2026 to adapt the national agendas

The goals of the funding survey are:

- Collecting information on the processes used by the organizations that fund research:
 - for the identification of research priorities/topics
 - for the prioritization of research activities
 - for the allocation of funds
- Collect suggestions that will help the shaping of processes to increase synergies between the research funding processes of partners of the future network
- Improve the abovementioned processes for EUPHRESKO III and the future network to identify, prioritize and implement research activities that are more impactful for policymaking and innovation.

The funding survey will be reviewed and discussed among champions and this will lead to agree on procedures for future collaboration and give input to the *Modus Operandi* for the future network.

8. End of the meeting

Focusing on the Northern Europe regional championship, led by the Euphresco Network Office, efforts have resulted in the collection of raw data (survey responses) and a report analyzing these responses. The Euphresco Network Office, in consultations with the other regional champions, will use this data to identify commonalities at both regional and transregional levels. However, the 'raw' data will also be made available to all countries and to all Euphresco and EUPHRESKO III members. This allows organizations to make use of the data in other ways, given their role in the national coordination of Plant Health research activities. Additionally, it is recognized that the priorities identified through Euphresco/EUPHRESKO III at the institutional level may not fully align with the specific interests or objectives of individual organizations or countries.

Following the workshop with high level representatives of research funders and policymakers of Northern European countries, the Euphresco network office will convene with the other EUPHRESKO III regional and discipline champions to shortlist the research priorities to be considered for the 2025 Euphresco/EUPHRESKO III call. Prioritization will be based on a number of criteria, the main one being the transregional interest that a topic may arise. For each identified priority, a working group will be established, which will be responsible for preparing a short description of the research idea to be proposed for the 2025 Euphresco/EUPHRESKO III call. To develop these research ideas, the working groups will consider documents produced during the regional consultations and also seek input from external experts such as scientists, funders and policymakers. The goal is to produce research ideas that are sufficiently detailed and compelling to attract the interest of relevant organizations.

Mr. Giovani (Euphresco, Int.) concluded by emphasizing the clear interest in further discussions and increased collaboration among participants arising from the workshop's interactions. The Euphresco Network Office will keep all participants informed about the next steps. In the meantime, if questions arise, participants are encouraged to reach out to the Euphresco Network Office, Mr. Giovani or Ms. Zorrilla, which will ensure that the inquiries are directed to the appropriate individuals and organizations.

3 REPORT OF THE CONSULTATIONS FOR SOUTH-EUROPE AND THE MEDITERRANEAN REGION

Chapter 1

PLANT HEALTH STAKEHOLDERS SURVEY

1.1. Identification of National Contact Points

From February 2024, and as a preliminary step in the implementation of the stakeholder engagement process for the EUPHRESKO III project, CIHEAM Bari (the regional Champion) has identified 19 national contact points (Annex 1), one for each participating country. The selection of these contacts was strategic, targeting individuals affiliated with policymaking bodies, research institutions, or funding organizations with a clear mandate or involvement in phytosanitary research.

The primary role of these national contacts was to act as focal points for their respective countries, facilitating national-level engagement by identifying and connecting with relevant stakeholders. These included policymakers, research funders, research organizations, and representatives from the private sector who could contribute to, or benefit from, international collaboration in plant health research.

Each national contact was formally approached *via* email. The communication provided a concise overview of the EUPHRESKO III project, including its aims, scope, and expected outcomes. Furthermore, the contacts were requested to complete a stakeholder identification exercise using a pre-prepared Excel template (WP 2.2) and an accompanying guidance document for the identification of phytosanitary research stakeholders (Annexes 2, 3). This activity aimed to ensure a comprehensive and harmonized collection of relevant stakeholder data across all participating countries.

1.2. Preparation of the Digital Stakeholder Questionnaire

The stakeholder questionnaire, developed in WP2 in Word format, was adapted into a digital version by CIHEAM Bari to facilitate its distribution and response collection. Google Forms was selected as the preferred platform due to its user-friendly interface, ease of access, and ability to compile responses efficiently.

In May 2024, this link was then shared with the national contact points, who were instructed to disseminate it among the identified national stakeholders within their networks. The aim was to gather input from a broad range of actors involved or interested in phytosanitary research and international cooperation in plant health.

Link to the survey: <https://forms.gle/r1tEZwtfvMJFy7te7> (Annex 4)

1.3. Bilateral Meetings with National Contact Points

In June 2024, CIHEAM Bari convened the first coordination meeting with national contact points through a Zoom videoconference. This meeting served as an introductory session to present the structure and content of the stakeholders' survey, clarify its objectives, and explain its intended outcomes. The purpose was to ensure a common understanding among all national contacts to enable consistent and effective dissemination of the questionnaire within their respective networks.

During the meeting, participants were guided through the survey questions and the rationale behind them. By the end of the session, national contacts were requested to distribute the questionnaire to the list of stakeholders they had previously identified and submitted. An exception was made for the national contact from Egypt, for whom a face-to-face meeting was held in Egypt by the champion coordinator.

Following the survey's initial dissemination, CIHEAM Bari conducted a preliminary analysis of the responses received in September 2024. The objective was to assess the diversity of stakeholder profiles across countries and to ensure adequate representation from different stakeholder categories (e.g., policymakers, research institutions, funders, and private sector actors).

Where gaps or underrepresentation were identified, CIHEAM Bari reached out to the respective national contacts with targeted reminders. These follow-up communications were supported by country-specific summary reports that highlighted preliminary findings and outlined the missing stakeholder categories. This step aimed to maximize inclusiveness and improve the quality of the data collected.

Chapter 2

SURVEY DATA ANALYSIS METHODOLOGY

2.1. National Data Analysis

The analysis of the stakeholder questionnaire data was carried out starting from January 2025 through a structured, multi-phase process to ensure clarity, consistency, and reliability of the results.

The initial step involved exporting the collected responses from the digital survey platform into a structured Excel database. This raw dataset then underwent a comprehensive data cleaning process. Responses submitted in languages other than English such as Spanish or Italian, were translated to ensure linguistic consistency across the dataset. Furthermore, typographical errors, particularly in the names of pests and crops, were corrected. Harmonization was also performed to standardize terminology and formatting, ensuring that the data was ready for detailed analysis.

Following the data cleaning phase, the dataset was disaggregated by country. Each country's data was saved in a dedicated Excel file, enabling a focused and context-specific analysis of the national responses. Stakeholders were identified and categorized based on their

organizational type and role in phytosanitary research such as policy makers, research funders, research institutions, industry, or farmers.

A deeper classification was then conducted for each country's dataset to analyse the references to pests and crops. Pests were categorized into broad biological groups such as pathogens, insects, nematodes, and others, and then overwent a further break down by order for the insects and by classification for pathogens.

Similarly, crops were first grouped by type (e.g., vegetables, fruits, cereals, forest species) and then further broken down into more specific categories such as stone fruits, pome fruits, and citrus fruits under the fruit category and the same was made for vegetables.

In parallel, research priority topics identified in the responses were also organized and classified into the following thematic areas:

- Pest/Disease Management
- Pesticides and Alternatives to Pesticides
- Pest and Disease Focus
- Crop Improvement
- Surveillance, Early Detection, and Risk Prevention of Invasive/Emerging Pests and Diseases
- Climate Change
- Diagnostics and Epidemiology
- Smart Crop Protection
- Food Safety
- Other emerging or cross-cutting themes

Once the classification and harmonization were completed, a statistical analysis was conducted for each country to identify:

- Priority pests and crops
- Key insect orders and species
- Major pathogen groups and specific pathogens of concern
- Capacity building needs
- National research priorities related to plant health
- Research topics for future consideration

The outcomes of this analysis were synthesized into PowerPoint presentations, one per country, to visually present the key findings in a clear and accessible format (Annex 5). These country-specific presentations were then shared in advance with the respective national contacts to allow for their review and input. National contacts were responsible for presenting their country results during the subsequent regional consultation meeting.

2.2. Sub-Regional Data Analysis

To facilitate comparative analysis and enhance the relevance of the findings, the participating countries were grouped into four sub-regional areas based on their geographic and national affiliations. This choice was based on the results obtained in the first study on 'Plant Health Research Priorities in the Mediterranean Region' which was jointly conducted by CIHEAM Bari and Euphresco in 2021 (Compendium <https://drop.euphresco.net/data/4e15edb6-a523-4d4c-8311-be7c0fa70020>) and 2022 (Supplement 1 <https://drop.euphresco.net/data/0d651050->

[3e0b-467b-bf15-d1061110677f](#)) due to similarity in these areas of climatic conditions, crop production and trade routes. This sub-regional division enabled the aggregation and cross-analysis of data at both national and regional levels, thereby offering a broader understanding of phytosanitary research priorities across different parts of the Mediterranean and surrounding regions.

The data analysis for each sub-region was conducted similar to the one per country considering the same questions and by using JMP® Pro 16, an advanced statistical analysis software developed by SAS. JMP Pro offers powerful tools for statistical modelling, data visualization, and predictive analytics, making it particularly well-suited for analysing complex datasets. Its capabilities allowed for the extraction of meaningful patterns and trends, thus supporting evidence-based interpretation of the survey results.

Countries within the same sub-region were analysed collectively to generate regional insights. A major focus of the analysis was the identification of priority pests and crops. These were assessed at both the national and sub-regional levels. Notably, a strong alignment emerged between national-level findings and sub-regional trends, which reinforced the validity of the national data. Consequently, the analysis placed particular emphasis on national responses while still reflecting regional coherence and consistency.

Following the analysis, the results were compiled into dedicated PowerPoint presentations, one for each sub-region. These presentations were used as reference material during the regional consultation meeting and provided the foundation for discussions within the four sub-regional working groups (Annex 6).

The questionnaire was distributed to national contacts across the Mediterranean region and Southern Europe, yielding **147 compiled questionnaires** from **19 Countries** (Fig.1).

The countries were divided into 4 sub-regional areas:

- *North Africa:* **40** compiled questionnaires
- *Near East:* **29** compiled questionnaires
- *South Europe:* **55** compiled questionnaires
- *Balkans:* **23** compiled questionnaires

Figure 1. Map of the countries and number of compiled questionnaires

2.2.1. Stakeholder profiles of survey respondents

The stakeholder composition of the survey respondents reflects a broad and diverse representation of the plant health research ecosystem (Fig. 2). A significant majority 63% of the responses originated from research organizations, underscoring the strong engagement of the scientific community in phytosanitary research and international collaboration.

Policy makers accounted for 15% of the respondents, providing valuable insights into regulatory and policy-related priorities in plant health. Industry representatives constituted 10%, offering perspectives that bridge practical applications, innovation, and market-driven needs. A smaller yet critical portion of respondents were research organizations that also function as funding bodies (5%), which contribute both a scientific and strategic funding perspective. Research funders alone represented 3%, while farmers and foresters also accounted for 3%, bringing forward-grounded, field-level experiences and needs.

This mix of respondents from different sectors ensured a multi-faceted perspective in the survey outcomes, combining scientific, policy, industrial, and practical viewpoints. Such diversity of input is essential for identifying well-rounded priorities and addressing both current and emerging challenges in plant health.

Figure 2. Involved stakeholders in the survey

2.2.2. Capacity building needs

Respondents were asked to identify capacity building needs relevant to their organizations and were allowed to select multiple options (Fig. 3). The results, as illustrated in the graph below, highlight financial resources as the most frequently cited need, selected 121 times (82%), indicating a widespread challenge in securing adequate funding to support phytosanitary research and related activities.

This was followed closely by the need for training, which was selected 102 times (69%), reflecting the importance of continuous skill development and knowledge transfer within the plant health community. Facilities and equipment were identified 98 times (67%), underlining the necessity for modern, well-equipped research infrastructure. Human resources were also

a significant concern, cited 94 times (64%), suggesting limitations in the availability of skilled personnel dedicated to plant health.

Other categories such as methods and processes, specific competences, and commodities were mentioned less frequently, pointing to more specialized or context-specific needs. Overall, the data underscore the pressing demand for both financial and human capital, as well as technical resources, to strengthen phytosanitary research capacities across the region.

Figure 3. Capacity building needs

2.2.3. Research areas to address for future work

As for research areas that should be prioritized to support future work on plant health challenges and related practical issues, respondents were allowed to select multiple areas of interest. The responses revealed a clear consensus on several critical domains that warrant focused attention moving forward (Fig. 4).

Pest management emerged as the top priority, selected 124 times (84%), reflecting the continued need for effective, sustainable strategies to combat plant pests. Phytosanitary research collaboration was the second most cited area, with 113 selections (77%), emphasizing the value stakeholders place on coordinated, cross-border efforts in tackling plant health threats.

Pesticide reduction and development of alternatives followed closely, receiving 101 responses (69%), highlighting a strong demand for environmentally friendly and innovative approaches to crop protection. The impact of climate change on plant health was identified as a priority by 98 respondents (67%), signalling growing concern about how shifting environmental conditions are influencing pest dynamics and disease outbreaks.

Finally, diagnostics selected 92 times (63%) was recognized as essential for early detection, accurate identification, and timely response to plant health threats.

These results collectively point to a need for integrated, multidisciplinary approaches that address both current and emerging issues in plant health, balancing practical application with scientific innovation.

Fig. 4 Research areas to address for future work

2.2.4. Priority crops for all sub-regions

In Figure 5 are reported the statistical analysis of crops classified as group of species (stone fruits, pome fruits, vegetables, cereals) and species (citrus, grapevine, fig, olive, cucurbits, legumes, solanace). The chart illustrates crop prioritization across the four sub-regions. Stone fruits consistently emerge as the top priority in all regions, followed by solanaceous crops and cereals.

South Europe shows the highest frequency for stone fruits, indicating a strong focus on this crop, while the Balkans and Near East reflect a more limited range of crop priorities with lower overall frequencies. North Africa, on the other hand, presents a more balanced distribution, showing interest in a broader variety of crops, including citrus, pome fruits, and grapevine.

Less frequently prioritized crops across all regions include olive, legumes, and cucurbitaceous vegetables. Despite regional variations, the chart clearly highlights a shared focus on a few key crop categories, particularly stone fruits, solanaceous crops, and cereals.

Figure 5. Priority crops for all sub-regions

2.2.5. Priority pests for all sub-regions

Figure 6 presents the frequency of pest types prioritized across the four sub-regions. Pests are classified as pathogens (viruses, phytoplasmas, viroids, bacteria, fungi), nematodes and insects orders.

Fungi and oomycetes are clearly the most frequently cited pest group in all sub-regions, especially in South Europe, where they dominate the pest priorities. Other common pests include bacteria, Hemiptera, Diptera, and viruses/phytoplasmas/viroids, though their relevance varies across regions.

The Near East shows a more evenly distributed concern across several pest types, while North Africa highlights Hemiptera and Coleoptera as major threats. In the Balkans, frequencies are relatively low across the board, but Hemiptera and viruses/phytoplasmas/viroids still lead.

Figure 6. Priority pests for all sub-regions

2.2.6. Priority research thematic areas for all sub-regions

Figure 7 illustrates the key research priority thematic areas in plant health across the four sub-regions. The most prominent priority is pest and disease management, with South Europe and North Africa indicating particularly high frequencies. Followed by pest and disease focus as the second highest frequency and surveillance and early detection in the third place.

Crop improvement and climate change impact appear as mid-level priorities in the Near East and North Africa, while they receive slightly less attention in the Balkans. Meanwhile, smart crop protection, agroecology, and food safety are among the least prioritized topics across all regions.

Figure 7. Research priority thematic areas for all regions

2.2.7. Stakeholders involved per sub-region

In all sub-regions, research organisations are the main contributors to the survey. The Balkans and North Africa show the strongest dominance of research input (74% and 70%, respectively), while the Near East stands out for its high policy maker involvement (38%). South Europe has a more balanced distribution, with notable participation from both policy makers (16%) and industry (13%). Overall, farmers and foresters were underrepresented across all regions (Fig. 8).

Balkans: Research organisations represent the largest group of survey respondents, accounting for a dominant 74%. Following behind are farmers and foresters and industry, each contributing 9% to the responses. Policy makers constitute 4% of the respondents, while 'others' also make up 4%. This distribution suggests that the survey in the Balkans heavily relied on input from the scientific and academic community, with some representation from the primary sector and industry, and less from policy-making bodies.

South Europe: Research organisations continue to be the primary respondent group, though slightly less dominant than in the Balkans (62%). Policy makers show a more substantial involvement here, contributing 16% of the responses. Industry represents 13%, while research funders account for 7%. Farmers and foresters constitute a smaller portion at 2%. This indicates a strong research-driven input, alongside a notable contribution from policy makers and industry, and emerging involvement from funding bodies, but limited engagement from farmers and foresters.

Near East: Research organisations still forming the largest group, but at a reduced 45%. Notably, policy makers play a much more significant role here, accounting for 38% of the responses, indicating a strong governmental or regulatory perspective in the survey. Farmers and foresters contribute 7%, and Research funders represent 4%. Industry makes up 3%, and 'others' account for 3%. This breakdown suggests a collaborative survey effort, with substantial input from both research and policy sectors, alongside some engagement from primary producers and funders, but less from industry.

North Africa: Research organisations again lead the responses, contributing 70% to the total, signifying a strong reliance on academic and research insights. Research funders show a notable presence at 17%, indicating their active involvement. Industry accounts for 10%, while policy makers represent a smaller 3%. This distribution highlights a survey primarily driven by research and funding bodies, with some industry input, but very limited direct engagement from policy makers or primary producers.

Balkans

South Europe

Near East

North Africa

Figure 8. Number of compiled questionnaires and involved stakeholders

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2.2.8. Priority crops per sub-region

Balkans: From the bar chart and the proportionally segmented strip for percentage breakdown (Fig. 9), it's evident that stone fruits are the most grown crops in the Balkans, with the highest frequency recorded (over 45 counts and 21.7% as a percentage), followed by cereals and solanaceae, 17% and 15.6% respectively. Grapevines and pome fruits (12.3% and 8.5%) also show relatively high frequencies.

Figure 9. Priority crop types for Balkans

Overall, the graph underscores the diversity of crop cultivation in the Balkans, with a strong emphasis on fruit production particularly stone fruits alongside cereals and solanaceous crops.

Figure 10. Priority crops for Balkans

While the bar graph (Fig. 10) highlights that grapevine stands out as the most frequently mentioned crop, with 26 instances (making up 13.9% of all crops mentions). This suggests that grape cultivation plays a particularly significant role in the region's agricultural landscape. Cherry, tomato, and wheat are all tied with 14 mentions account for 7.5% each. The mid-range of the graph includes crops such as pepper, plum, peach, and maize, with frequencies ranging from 10 to 12, pepper and plum contribute 6.4% while peach 5.9% and maize 5.3%.

Crops like barley, onion, cucumber, date palm, fig, sunflower, and cabbage show even lower frequencies between 3 and 6, account for less than 3% each. which may reflect their niche cultivation or relevance only in specific microclimates or smaller markets.

South Europe: Figure 11 illustrates that stone fruits are the most dominant crop in the South Europe region, representing 18.7% of total responses, indicating their significant role in agriculture. They are followed by citrus crops (14.4%), which are also prominent due to the region's suitable climate. Solanaceae (13.1%) also show strong representation, highlighting

the importance of vegetable production. Grapevine (9.7%) and cereals (9.0%) follow, confirming the region's mixed agricultural profile. Other frequently cited categories include pome fruits, olives, and figs, further underlining the Mediterranean character of Southern European crop production. Less commonly mentioned but still present are crops like cucurbits, berries, nuts, and legumes.

Figure 11. Priority crop types for South Europe

Figure 12. Priority crop for South Europe

Figure 12 highlights that grapevine stands out as the most frequently mentioned crop, with 38 instances (making up 13.2% of all crops mentions), followed by tomato, orange, peach, and apple representing 9.8%, 9.1%, 8.4%, 5.9%, respectively.

Crops like olive, lemon, fig, cherry, pear, potato, and wheat show even lower frequencies between 15 and 11, account for less than 6% each.

Near East: As shown in Figure 13, stone fruits emerge as the dominant crop category, representing 17.1% of all responses, closely followed by solanaceae at 13.7%. Citrus (1.6%) and cereals (11.0%) also hold significant prominence, collectively underscoring the region's

diverse agricultural landscape that encompasses both fruit and essential crops. Furthermore, the frequent mention of pome fruits, grapevine, figs, legumes, and cucurbits distinctly highlights the Mediterranean influences on Near Eastern crop production. While present, crops such as nuts, olives, and berries are comparatively less cited.

Figure 13. Priority crop types for the Near East

The bar graph below (Fig. 14) highlights that grapevine stands out as the most frequently mentioned crop, with 21 instances (making up 8.4% of all crops mentions) followed by tomato, date palm, fig, and orange. Crops like peach, apple, lemon, wheat, apricot, and potatoes show even lower frequencies between 15 and 12, account for less than 6% each.

Figure 14. Priority crop for the Near East

North Africa: As shown in Figure 15, cereals are the most leading crop in the North Africa region, representing 14 % of total responses, followed by solanaceae (13.7%), stone fruits

(12.2%), and citrus (11.6%). Other frequently cited categories include pome fruits, grapevine, figs, berries, and olive, further underlining the Mediterranean character of crop production. Less commonly mentioned but still present are crops like legumes, cucurbits, and nuts.

Figure 15. Priority crop types for North Africa

The bar graph below (Fig. 16) highlights that grapevine stands out as the most frequently mentioned crop, with 30 instances (making up 10.8% of all crops mentions), followed by fig (10.5%), date palm (10.1%), tomato (8.3%), orange (7.6%), apple (6.9%), peach (4.7%), durum wheat (4.3%), barley (4.0%), mango (3.6%), pear (3.6%), almonds (3.6%), apricot (3.6%), lemon (3.6%), olive (3.6%), pepper (3.6%), bread wheat (3.6%), wheat (3.6%), and all varieties (3.6%).

Figure 16. Priority crop for North Africa

2.2.9. Priority pests per sub-region

Balkans: Figure 17 details pest's prevalence. The bar graph shows Hemiptera (13), viruses/phytoplasmas/ viroids (11), bacteria (10), and fungi/Oomycetes (10) as most frequent. The bottom stacked bar chart reinforces this, showing Hemiptera at 19.1%, viruses/phytoplasmas/viroids at 16.2%, and bacteria and fungi/Oomycetes both at 14.7%. Diptera (13.2%) and Lepidoptera (10.3%) are also significant. This visualization highlights the dominance of these specific pest groups in the surveyed Balkan region.

Figure 17. Priority pests for the Balkans

The graphs in Fig. 18, presenting both frequency and percentage distribution of the top identified insects, show *C. capitata* as the most frequent insect pest, with a frequency of 4 (17.4%); whiteflies follow with a frequency of 3 (13.0%). The remaining eight identified insect pests *Aphids*, *B. oleae*, *C. pyri*, *D. suzukii*, *H. halys*, *N. viridula*, *S. frugiperda*, and *T. absoluta* register a frequency of 2, each contribute 8.7% to the total.

Figure 18. Priority insects for the Balkans

The graphs in Fig. 19, presenting both their frequencies and proportional contributions of the top identified pathogens, highlight *X. fastidiosa* as the most frequently identified pathogen, reaching a frequency of 7 with a substantial 41.2% of the total identified pathogens. Both *P. vitis* and *V. inaequalis* follow, each with a frequency of 3 each account for 17.6%. Lastly, *R. solanacearum* and *Tomato brown rugose fruit virus* are identified with a frequency of 2, each contribute 11.8% to the overall pathogen landscape.

Figure 19. Priority pathogens for the Balkans

Figure 20. Priority pests' names for the Balkans

Figure 20 provides a detailed analysis of the top identified pests in the Balkans. *X. fastidiosa* emerges as the most prominent, detected with a frequency of 7 at 17.5%. Following are *C. capitata* at a frequency of 4 accounts for 10.0%, and a trio of pests *P. vitis*, *V. inaequalis*, and Whiteflies, each at a frequency of 3 each represent a considerable 7.5%. A significant cluster of ten other pests, consistently appear at a frequency of 2 each contribute 5.0% to the total.

This representation provides a clear and comprehensive overview of the most impactful pests in the region.

South Europe: Figure 21 details the prevalence of various Pests in South Europe. Bacteria stand out as the most frequent, with a remarkably high count of 46 (27.7%). Following are Fungi and Oomycete at a frequency of 27 contribute 16.3%, and Diptera at 22 makes up 13.3%. Viruses, Phytoplasmas, and Viroids and Coleoptera both register a frequency of 17 are at 10.2%, while Hemiptera and Lepidoptera are both at 15 contribute 9.6% each. The frequencies then drop significantly for Nematodes (7) account for 4.2%. This graph clearly demonstrates the overwhelming dominance of Bacteria and Fungi/Oomycetes as significant pest concerns in Southern Europe.

Figure 21. Priority pests for South Europe

Figure 22 details top insect pests as follows. *B. oleae* is most frequent at 7 (17.5%). *T. absoluta* is at 5 (12.5%) while *B. dorsalis*, *C. capitata*, *D. suzukii*, *S. frugiperda* are each at 4 (10.0% each) and Bark beetles, *P. cylindrus*, *Pseudococcidae*, *T. parvicornis* are each at 3 (7.5% each).

Figure 22. Priority insects for Southern Europe

Figure 23 shows *X. fastidiosa* as the dominant pathogen (frequency 31, 56.4%). *B. xylophilus* follows at 6 (10.9%), with *Ca. Liberibacter* spp. at 5 (9.1%). *Tomato brown rugose fruit virus* is

at 4 (7.3%), while *Citrus tristeza virus*, *E. amylovora*, and *Phytophthora* spp. are each at 3 (5.5% each).

Figure 23. Priority pathogens for Southern Europe

Figure 24. Priority pests' names for South Europe

In Southern Europe (Fig. 24), *X. fastidiosa* is the dominant pest, with a frequency of 31 and accounting for a commanding 32.6%. *B. oleae* follows at 7 (7.4%), and *B. xylophilus* at 6 (6.3%). *T. absoluta*, *B. dorsalis*, and *C. capitata* are all at 5 (5.3% each). Numerous other pests, including *D. suzukii* and *Tomato brown rugose fruit virus*, are consistently found at a frequency of 3 (4.2% each).

This graph clearly illustrates the significant and pervasive threat posed by *X. fastidiosa*, alongside other notable pest challenges, across Southern Europe.

Near East: Figure 25 effectively illustrates both the frequency of identification and the proportional contribution of pests. Fungi and Oomycete is the most prevalent pest, identified with a frequency of 27 and accounting for 22.9% of the total. Following closely are Coleoptera and Viruses, Phytoplasmas, and Viroids, both identified with a frequency of 16 and each contributing 13.6%. Lepidoptera registers a frequency of 14, making up 11.9%, while Diptera is at 13, contributing 11.0%. Bacteria and Hemiptera show frequencies of 12 and 10, respectively, accounting for 10.2% and 8.5%. Lower frequencies are observed for other pathogens (5.1%), Nematodes (1.7%), and other insects (1.7%). This graph clearly highlights the significant presence of Fungi and Oomycete, alongside various insect orders and other pathogens, as prominent pest concerns in the Near East region.

Figure 25. Priority pests for the Near East

Figure 26 highlights the most frequently identified insect pests in the Near East. *R. ferrugineus* is the most prevalent insect, with a frequency of 13, accounting for a commanding 39.4%. Both *B. oleae* and *T. absoluta* follow with an identical frequency of 5, each contributing 15.2%. *C. capitata* and *S. frugiperda* each show a frequency of 3, representing 9.1% each. Lastly, *E. integriceps* and *H. halys* both register a frequency of 2, each accounting for 6.1% of the total identified insects.

Figure 26. Priority insects for the Near East

Figure 27 details the most frequently identified pathogens. Cereal fungal diseases are the most common, with a frequency of 11, accounting for 34.4%. *X. fastidiosa* follows with a frequency of 5, contributing 15.6%. Both *Banana fusarium wilt* and *P. savastanoi* register a frequency of 4, each representing 12.5%. Three other pathogens *F. oxysporium*, *Tomato brown rugose fruit virus*, and Potatoes viruses each show a frequency of 3, contributing 9.4% each to the total identified pathogens.

Figure 27. Priority pathogens for the Near East

Figure 28. Priority pests' names for the Near East

Figure 28 showcases both the frequencies and proportional contributions of pests. *R. ferrugineus* is the most prevalent pest, identified with a frequency of 13 and accounting for 20.0% of the total. Cereal fungal diseases follow with a frequency of 11, contributing 16.9%. A group of three pests *B. oleae*, *T. absoluta*, and *X. fastidiosa*, each register a frequency of 5, representing 7.7% each. Next, *Banana fusarium wilt* and *P. savastanoi* both show a frequency of 4, each accounting for 6.2%. Finally, a cluster of four pests, including *C. capitata*, *F. oxysporium*, and *Tomato brown rugose fruit virus*, each consistently appear with a frequency of 3, contributing 4.6% each to the total identified pests. The graph highlights the significant impact of *R. ferrugineus* and cereal fungal diseases, alongside other notable insect pests and plant diseases, in the Near East.

North Africa:

Figure 29 presents both the frequencies and proportional contributions of pests. Hemiptera is the most prevalent order, with a frequency of 29, accounting for 23.4% of the total. Following are Coleoptera (14.5%), others pathogens (13.7%), Diptera (11.3%), and Fungi and Oomycete (10.5%). This graph clearly highlights Hemiptera as the dominant pest order in North Africa, followed by Coleoptera and various other pathogens and insect orders.

Figure 29. Priority pests for North Africa

Figure 30 highlights the most frequently identified insect pests in North Africa. *R. ferrugineus* is the most prevalent, with a frequency of 16, accounting for 32.0% of the total. Both *C. capitata* and *D. opuntiae* follow with an identical frequency of 9, each contributing 18.0%. *T. absoluta* is identified with a frequency of 6, representing 12.0%. *D. coccus* registers a frequency of 4, accounting for 8.0%.

Figure 30. Priority insects for North Africa

Figure 31 details the most frequently identified pathogens in North Africa. *X. fastidiosa* is the most common, with a frequency of 6, accounting for 22.2%. Mites follow with a frequency of 5, contributing 18.5%. Both *Citrus tristeza virus* and Weeds register a frequency of 4, each representing 14.8%. *Egmonviruses* and *O. afrasiaticus* each show a frequency of 3, accounting for 11.1% each.

Figure 31. Priority pathogens for North Africa

Figure 32, focusing on the "Top Identified Pests" in North Africa, presents both their frequencies and proportional contributions. *R. ferrugineus* is the most prevalent pest, with a frequency of 16, accounting for 21.3% of the total. Both *C. capitata* and *D. opuntiae* follow with an identical frequency of 9, each contributing 12.0%. *T. absoluta* and *X. fastidiosa* each register a frequency of 6, representing 8.0% each. Mites are identified with a frequency of 5, accounting for 6.7%. A group of three pests *Citrus tristeza virus*, *D. coccus*, and Weeds each show a frequency of 4, contributing 5.3% each. This graph clearly highlights *R. ferrugineus* as a dominant pest in North Africa, alongside several other significant insect pests, pathogens, and even weeds.

Figure 32. Priority pests' names for the Near East

2.2.10. Research priority areas & topics per sub-region:

In addition to the structured questions, the survey included an open-ended section which was classified by research areas based on thematic similarity. This approach enabled the identification of common priorities even when respondents used varying terminology. To complement this qualitative assessment, the open-ended responses were also processed using statistical analysis tools, which facilitated the identification of topic clusters and thematic patterns. This dual-method approach qualitative content review and statistical clustering offered a comprehensive overview of the plant health research landscape across the region.

Balkans: The 3 dominant research areas are represented by Pest & Disease management followed by Pest/Disease focus as shown in Figure 33. Hereafter the list of priority topics grouped per each thematic area:

1. Pest/Disease Management, pesticides and alternatives to pesticides

- IPM
- Biopesticides and biocontrol
- Pesticide reduction
- Improvement of the formulation of chemical pesticides

2. Pest and disease focus

- Virus characterization and detection (potato, wheats)
- Apple diseases

- *Ostrinia nubilalis*
- Wheat and maize diseases
- Apricot apoplexy
- Nematodes

3. Surveillance, early detection, risk prevention and management of invasive/emerging pests and diseases

- Monitoring, management invasive/emerging pests and diseases (*X. fastidiosa*)

4. Crop Improvement

- Breeding, development, and selection of disease-resistant varieties (fruit trees)
- Establishment of olive mother plot with virus-free material
- Implementation of factors to reduce the occurrence of resistance

Figure 33. Research priorities thematic areas for the Balkans

South Europe: Main research thematic areas of this subregion are Pest & Disease Management and Pest and Disease Focus at equal frequency (41 and 40, respectively), followed by Surveillance and Early Detection (frequency 32) as shown in Figure 34. The list of priority titles per each thematic area is hereafter reported:

1. Pest/Disease Management, pesticides and alternatives to pesticides

- Alternative biopesticides (microbiome, mycorrhizal, biostimulants)
- Alternatives to synthetic pesticides (Active natural compounds) NBS (Nature-Based Solutions)
- Precision Integrated Pest Management
- Improvement of the formulation of chemical pesticides (insecticides: coleoptera, lepidoptera, diptera) and herbicides

- Agroecology in pest management

2. Pest and disease focus

- *Xylella fastidiosa* (subspecies, vectors, tolerant cvs)
- *Ca liberibacter* and *Tryoza eritreae*
- Grapevine wood diseases
- Forest trees diseases (*Ceratocystis platani*, Oak diseases, Cork oak plagues and diseases, Pine wilt disease, *Eucalyptus* diseases)
- Potato black ringspot virus; Seed potatoes and ware potatoes health
- *Drosophila suzukii*
- *Tuta absoluta*
- *Tetranychus urticae*

3. Surveillance and early detection

- Digital surveillance methods and tools for early pathogen detection
- Identifying plant pests and pathogens early and understanding their spread and impact.
- Development of reliable and robust early detection methods for quarantine pests (Improvement of sampling methods)
- Transboundary/emerging pests and diseases (Improving knowledge of priority pests in the European Union)

Figure 34. Research priorities thematic areas for Southern Europe

Near East: Main research thematic area is Pest and Disease focus with a frequency of 36, followed by Pest & Disease Management and Pest and Surveillance and Early Detection at equal 14 frequency (Fig. 35). The list of priority titles per each thematic area is hereafter reported:

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1. Pest and disease focus

- Fusarium of stonefruits, avocado and cereals
- Root knot nematode complex
- Red palm weevil and date palm diseases and pests
- New diseases attacking vegetables (ToBRFV)
- Wheat diseases

2. Pest/Disease Management, pesticides and alternatives to pesticides

- Pesticide reduction
- Biocontrol and biopesticides (Plant-parasitic nematodes)
- Finding natural enemies for some economical pests
- Alternatives to synthetic pesticides

3. Surveillance and early detection

- Emerging plant diseases and invasive species
- Strengthening phytosanitary border controls and surveillance
- Forecast and warning models
- Pest Risk Analysis
- Development of methods for detecting and predicting plant pests

Figure 35. Research priorities thematic areas for the Near East

North Africa: Main research thematic area is Pest and Disease focus with a frequency of 50, followed by Pest & Disease Management (29). Pest and Surveillance and Early Detection and Climate Change almost at equal frequency (13 and 12, respectively) as shown in Figure 36. The list of priority titles per each thematic area is hereafter reported:

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-01 under grant agreement No 101130467

1. Pest and disease focus

- *Xylella fastidiosa* and vectors
- Red palm weevil and date palm diseases
- *Dactylopius opuntiae*
- Root-knot nematodes on vegetables and fruits
- *Fusarium spp.*
- *Tuta absoluta*

2. Pest/Disease Management, pesticides and alternatives to pesticides

- Pesticides reduction
- Biocontrol
- Alternatives to synthetic pesticides (olive trees, date palms, citrus pests)
- IPM
- Improvement of the formulation of chemical fungicides (cereals), insecticides, nematicides
- Weed control for cereals

3. Surveillance and early detection

- Early detection and monitoring systems: Developing and implementing advanced technologies for early detection, monitoring, and forecasting of plant diseases and pest outbreaks
- Pest risk analysis

4. Climate Change

- Climate Change Impact on crop diseases, pests, emerging pathogens, and food availability
- Development of climate-resilient crop varieties (drought-tolerant and pest management practices)
- Pesticide use and behavior under climate change

Figure 36. Research priorities thematic areas for North Africa

Chapter 3

17TH INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS OF THE MEDITERRANEAN PHYTOPATHOLOGICAL UNION (MPU)

- **EUPHRESKO III Session:** “Strengthening the plant health research community”
- **Technical field visit** in the *Xylella fastidiosa* outbreak area of Apulia Region

3.1. EUPHRESKO III Session: “Strengthening the plant health research community”

As part of the MPU 2025 Congress, held in CIHEAM Bari, Italy, a dedicated session on July 9th focused on the strategic coordination of plant health research in the Mediterranean region (Annex 7). The session was chaired by Baldissera Giovani, Coordinator of the EUPHRESKO III project. This session served as a platform to raise awareness of EUPHRESKO III's activities to a large audience of different stakeholders participating at the MPU Congress 2025 (about 50 participants in presence and 15 online) and all national contacts to lay the groundwork for the regional consultation meeting held later on July 11th.

The coordinator opened the session outlining the evolution of EUPHRESKO, from a European initiative into a broader, more ambitious global network, emphasizing the project's overarching objectives (Fig. 37):

- *To develop and test governance models and operational structures for a global phytosanitary research coordination network*
- *To establish a Global Strategic Research Agenda (GSRA) for plant health*
- *To organize joint transnational calls for phytosanitary research*
- *To engage key stakeholders in shaping the future of coordinated plant health efforts.*

He also elaborated on the approaches being employed to ensure long-term sustainability of global coordination, including the importance of stakeholder inclusion, regional representation, and evidence-based prioritization.

Figure 37. EUPHRESKO coordinator opening the session EUPHRESKO III

Anna Maria D'Onghia (CIHEAM Bari), the Champion Coordinator for the South Europe / Mediterranean Region, presented a detailed overview of the stakeholder consultation process for regional priority setting. Her presentation, entitled "Consultations for the Mediterranean Region: From National to Global Through Regional Prioritization" highlighted the key role of national contacts in collecting and submitting structured input from diverse plant health stakeholders in their countries (Fig. 38).

Figure 38. The Champion Coordinator for the South Europe / Mediterranean Region during the session EUPHRESKO III

The presentation outlined the structure of the stakeholder questionnaire and its thematic coverage, explaining how responses were collected and analysed at a national and sub-regional level. She presented an executive summary of the survey results, which included:

- *The total number of completed questionnaires*
- *Geographic and sub-regional breakdown (North Africa, South Europe, Balkans, and Near East)*
- *Categories of stakeholders involved*
- *A preliminary identification of plant health research priority areas.*

It was also clarified that these results were analysed in advance of the consultation meeting so that participants could review the data and arrive to the consultation meeting already prepared to engage in in-depth discussions.

To contextualize the regional findings and share concrete national perspectives, four country Ppt presentations were selected (see chapter 2) to be showcased during the Congress session—each representing one of the sub-regions covered in the consultation (Fig. 39): Tunisia (*North Africa*); Albania (*Balkans*); Portugal (*South Europe*); Jordan (*Near East*).

Figure 39. The presentation of the national contact of Albania during the congress session EUPHRESKO III

The selection ensured geographic balance and diversity in the issues and challenges presented. These presentations illustrated how each country interpreted and approached phytosanitary priorities based on stakeholder input and national strategies.

It was also announced that presentations from the remaining participating countries would be showcased during the dedicated Regional Consultation Meeting on July 11th, where deeper discussions and topic prioritization would take place.

The session concluded with a joint intervention, who outlined the participatory methodology that would be applied during the regional consultation. They emphasized the importance of consensus-building and collaborative decision-making to define a robust, regionally endorsed list of plant health research priorities. These priorities are expected to inform future transnational projects and shape the Mediterranean region's contribution to the upcoming Global Strategic Research Agenda.

This session not only strengthened the understanding of EUPHRESKO III's vision but also created an essential link between survey-driven insights and the practical selection of shared research priorities discussed and agreed upon during the regional meeting.

3.2. Technical Field Visit

On 10 July, a technical visit was organised as part of the MPU Congress programme. The EUPHRESKO III consultation group took part in the visit to the area affected by the *Xylella fastidiosa* epidemic in Salento, Puglia. In particular, the visit was organised in the "Parco degli Ulivi Monumentali" (Serranova, Brindisi), where olive trees have been infected by *Xylella fastidiosa* (Fig. 40). The centuries-old olive trees show varying degrees of symptoms typical of leaf scorch and severe branch decline. Some trees have already been eradicated.

Experts from CIHEAM Bari, together with the head of the Apulian Phytosanitary Service, presented the situation regarding *Xylella* infection in Apulia, focusing on phytosanitary measures and the monitoring programme (Annex 8). They also illustrated the type of vectors (leafhoppers) and sampling methods for plant material and insects. The new plantations of the resistant olive variety "Favolosa" were also shown.

The visit represented a concrete example of sharing one of the most serious phytosanitary tragedies affecting certain areas of the Mediterranean, particularly the species most typical of this region, the olive tree.

Figure 40. Various views of the Monumental Olive Tree Park showing different degrees of symptoms caused by *X. fastidiosa* and the new plantations of the resistant olive variety 'Favolosa'.

Chapter 4

REGIONAL CONSULTATION MEETING

4.1. Introduction of the Regional Consultation Meeting

The EUPHRESKO III Regional Consultation Meeting for South Europe and the Mediterranean took place on 11 July 2025 at the CIHEAM Bari Campus. This high-level gathering served as a pivotal moment in the EUPHRESKO III process, bringing together national stakeholders, researchers, institutional representatives, and phytosanitary experts from across the Mediterranean and South European region to collaboratively define and align plant health research priorities.

The primary objective of the meeting was to analyse regional needs, identify shared phytosanitary challenges, and formulate concrete research topics that could be addressed through future EUPHRESKO transnational calls. With a specific focus on pest and disease management, the meeting provided a platform to consolidate the results of national stakeholder consultations conducted in each participating country.

Participants shared country-specific findings, presented proposals for research topics, and discussed opportunities for transnational collaboration on surveillance systems, diagnostics,

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integrated pest management (IPM), smart technologies, and policy support tools. The agenda also included an exchange of ideas on possible funding mechanisms, strategies for research coordination, and the potential to publish the agreed priorities in a special issue of a scientific journal, thereby ensuring wider dissemination and stakeholder engagement.

The meeting gathered the survey results of different countries, represented by the national contact points from 13 countries physically present (Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Egypt, Jordan, Lebanon, Greece, Italy, Spain, Portugal, Bosnia, Serbia, and Albania) and 2 participating remotely via Zoom (Palestine and Cyprus). However, survey's reports from countries unable to participate were also presented (Turkey, Syria, Malta, and North Macedonia) (Annex 9).

4.2. Participants and Represented Institutions

The event welcomed both strategic EUPHRESKO members and national contact points from the broader South Europe and Mediterranean region. Key attendees included:

EUPHRESKO and Institutional members:

- Giovanni Baldissera – Coordinator, EUPHRESKO III, France
- Anna Maria D'Onghia – Regional Champion, EUPHRESKO III, CIHEAM Bari, Italy
- Olga Tikka – Director-General, EPPO (European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization), Paris, France
- Dimitris Tsitsigiannis – President of MPU, Agricultural University of Athens, Greece
- Laura Mugnai – Editor-in-Chief, *Phytopathologia Mediterranea*; University of Florence, Italy
- Nour Al Gndi – CIHEAM Bari, Italy
- Nuray Baser – CIHEAM Bari, Italy
- Franco Valentini – CIHEAM Bari, Italy

National Contact Points (by Country):

- Italy: Alberto Masci – Ministry of Agriculture, Food Sovereignty and Forestry
- Tunisia: Asma Najar – National Institute of Agronomic Research
- Morocco: Fouad Mokriani – National Institute of Agricultural Research
- Portugal: Leonor Cruz – National Institute for Agricultural and Veterinary Research
- Albania: Magdalena Cara – Agricultural University of Tirana
- Jordan: Amani Alawamleh – Plant Protection and Phytosanitary Directorate
- Spain: Pablo Gómez Grande – National Institute for Agricultural and Food Research and Technology (INIA-CSIC)
- Serbia: Dragana Šunjka – University of Novi Sad
- Greece: Emilia Markellou – Benaki Phytopathological Institute
- Egypt: Salah Abdel-Momen – Former Minister of Agriculture and Land Reclamation
- Lebanon: Elia Choueri – Lebanese Agricultural Research Institute
- Palestine (Online): Tariq Abubaker – Ministry of Agriculture
- Algeria: Malika Meziane – University of Chlef
- Bosnia and Herzegovina: Arnela Okić – University of Sarajevo
- Cyprus (Online): Dimitrios Tsaltas – Cyprus University of Technology

Additional participants included:

- Algeria: Samir Ali Arous – University of Chlef
- Turkey: Nihal Buzkhan – Kahramanmaraş Sutcu Imam University
- Turkey: Songül Yalçın-Ateş – Directorate of Agricultural Quarantine, Izmir

- Tunisia: Mounira Drais – University of Tuscia, Italy
- Tunisia: Manel Elair – National Institute of Agricultural Research of Tunisia
- Tunisia: Wafa Rouissi – National Institute of Agricultural Research of Tunisia
- Tunisia: Sabine Nahdi – University of Jendouba
- Egypt: Ahmed EISayed – APHIS/USDA
- Morocco: Ayoub Macchi – National Institute for Agronomic Research

4.3. Opening Session and Methodological Overview

The EUPHRESKO III Coordinator, Baldissera Giovani, opened the event with a plenary session, presenting an overview of the EUPHRESKO III project's objectives, operational structure, and the role of regional consultations in informing collaborative research programming.

The Champion for South Europe and Mediterranean region, Anna Maria D'Onghia, introduced the bottom-up methodology adopted for stakeholder engagement. She emphasized the importance of national inputs in defining shared regional priorities and provided a clear roadmap for the day's proceedings. Her intervention clarified the expected outcomes of the meeting and guided national contacts on how their contributions would feed into the formulation of geographically coordinated research priorities (Fig. 41).

Figure 41. Regional consultation meeting opening session

4.4. Presentation of national survey results

Each national representative delivered the ppt presentation provided by CIHEAM Bari summarizing their country's stakeholder survey results for a more focused and productive discussion during the consultation.

Results covered the followings:

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- Number of completed questionnaires collected
- Profile of stakeholders (e.g., research organizations, policy makers, etc.)
- Priority crops
- Priority pests: insects and pathogens
- Capacity-building needs
- Research priorities topics
- Proposed research lines and thematic areas for future attention

4.5. Working groups consultation

The Champion presented the geographical / sub-regional analysis conducted by CIHEAM Bari. To facilitate targeted dialogue and joint planning, participants were divided into four working groups, equipped with breakout rooms and screens for hybrid interaction. Each working groups discussed data results of each geographical sub-region, with the support of a facilitator and the Ppt presentation provided by CIHEAM Bari (see chapter 2 and annex 6).

- **South Europe: Portugal, Spain, Italy, Greece, Cyprus, Malta**
Facilitator: Laura Mugnai (MPU, University of Florence)
- **North Africa: Egypt, Tunisia, Algeria, Morocco**
Facilitator: Baldissera Giovani (EUPHRESKO Coordinator)
- **Near East: Turkey, Jordan, Palestine, Lebanon, Syria**
Facilitator: Nuray Baser (CIHEAM Bari)
- **Balkans: Serbia, Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia**
Facilitator: Dimitris Tsitsigiannis (MPU, Agricultural University of Athens)

Within their respective groups, participants examined the sub-regional findings and worked together to harmonize and synthesize common research priorities relevant to their geographical context. The discussions focused on identifying mutual threats and potential areas for joint project development. Each group followed a tailored approach, reflecting the diversity of agricultural and phytosanitary contexts across the regions. While some sub-regions prioritized a pest-driven methodology, others relied on stakeholder survey data or crop-based perspectives. The distinct approaches adopted by each sub-region, highlighting the rationale and process behind their selection of research priorities, is hereafter outlined.

The Balkan group grounded their selection of research priorities in a crop-based approach. They first considered the priority crops present in their region, and then they selected the research priority topics. They also integrated prior insights and outcomes from the MPU 2025 congress to finalize their priorities, showing a clear link between regional pest pressure and the thematic focus of their research agenda.

The South Europe group adopted a crop-oriented and integrative approach. The discussion was described as extensive, aiming to bring together various aspects and perspectives. They initially focused on specific crop/pest but later broadened the scope (e.g., tomato into vegetables), suggesting an intention to capture cross-cutting issues across crops and pest types.

The Near East group followed a survey-driven and stakeholder-informed approach. They based the discussion on identified priority crops and pests, ensuring that research priorities reflected the real needs and interests of the region's agricultural sector.

The North Africa group followed a pest-first approach, determining the most pressing pests and identifying the related research activities. This method was strongly focused on pest management and biosecurity concerns, indicating a problem-solving orientation driven by regional phytosanitary threats.

4.6. Identification of regional priorities topics

Main objective of the consultation is the identification of regional research priorities to launch in the future EUPHRESKO transnational calls for research proposals. To this aim, all working groups reconvened in plenary for the presentation of sub-regional results to identify regional commonalities, transboundary issues, and synergistic opportunities. The selection of research priority topics was guided by a set of predefined criteria that had been shared with the participants:

- Topics that have already been addressed in previous or ongoing Euphresco projects or other research projects initiatives, to build on existing knowledge and avoid redundancy.
- Topics of common interest that could be applied across different crops, thereby offering broader impact and flexibility.
- Topics that are relevant to at least two sub-regions, in order to enhance transboundary collaboration and regional synergies.
- Preference was given to topics related to quarantine pests rather than the same topics applied to key pests, due to their higher regulatory and biosecurity importance for Euphresco project.

These criteria were essential to ensure coherence, avoid duplication, and promote collaborative and strategic alignment across the regions. Participants discussed existing project initiatives, regional differences, and the importance of aligning project topics with both scientific innovation and regulatory frameworks, particularly in compliance with international standards (e.g., ISPM 14). These guiding principles allowed for a focused prioritization process that balanced scientific relevance, regional needs, and opportunities for transnational cooperation (Fig. 42).

Figure 42. National contacts presenting their countries results during the regional consultation meeting

4.7. Final Results of the Regional Consultation Meeting

The regional consultation meeting reached a consensus on a final set of 7 priority research topics. These topics reflect both the current phytosanitary challenges in the South Europe and Mediterranean region and the pressing need for innovative, collaborative, and applied research. Each topic was selected based on common

interest across at least two sub-regions, alignment with Euphresco's goals, and the potential for regional or cross-border collaboration.

1. *Xylella fastidiosa*: Early Detection Using Spy Insects in Pathogen-Free Areas

This topic emerged as a high priority due to the devastating impact *Xylella fastidiosa* has had in Southern Europe, particularly in olive-producing areas. Participants emphasized the importance of preventive actions in regions still free of the pathogen using the “spy insects’ approach” for early detection. The topic was supported widely across South Europe and North Africa, where climatic conditions are conducive to potential outbreaks.

2. *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus*: Monitoring via Magnetic Sensors Developed in Egypt

The Red Palm Weevil remains one of the most destructive pests affecting palm trees across the Near East and North Africa. The monitoring technology, based on magnetic sensors for early pest detection, was developed in Egypt and could be scaled up through joint trials and validation studies in different agro-climatic zones.

3. Diseases caused by *Fusarium* spp. on Cereals, Stone Fruits, Banana, and Citrus

Fusarium-related diseases were identified as a cross-cutting concern among all sub-regions. Given their widespread occurrence and economic impact on multiple crops, the group prioritized this topic to encourage shared knowledge, harmonization of diagnostic tools, and development of sustainable management practices.

4. Smart Technologies and Digital Tools for Surveillance and Modelling of Emerging Quarantine Pests
Plant health surveillance was strongly endorsed across all groups due to the increasing pest mobility (global trade and climate change). Therefore, real-time surveillance and predictive modelling based on digital tools are essential. The agreement around this topic was grounded in the potential for transboundary collaboration and the applicability of these technologies to a broad range of pests, including both quarantine and emerging threats.
5. New Technologies for Early Detection and Identification of Citrus Pathogens at Border Laboratory Level
Citrus crops are a key economic asset in several countries represented in the consultation. Reliable and cost-effective diagnostic tools can be deployed at border inspection points to prevent the introduction of regulated pathogens. This topic was selected because of its operational relevance to national phytosanitary authorities and the high demand for improving biosecurity infrastructure across the region.
6. Best Practices for Phytosanitary Measures and Treatments on Exported Commodities to Comply with International Standards
Ensuring that agricultural exports meet international phytosanitary requirements was a shared concern among exporting countries. Participants highlighted the need to compile and validate effective, sustainable treatment methods and to align best practices with IPPC and WTO standards. The topic was selected to strengthen trade facilitation and capacity building, particularly for smallholder-oriented export chains.
7. Breeding Technologies for Developing Resistant Varieties (Beyond Tomato and Potato)
Finally, participants agreed on the strategic importance of genetic resistance as a sustainable solution to pest and disease pressure. While initial discussions focused on tomato and potato, the consensus was to broaden the scope to include other crops of regional significance. This topic reflects a forward-looking research direction aiming to reduce reliance on pesticides and support the development of resilient agroecosystems through advanced breeding tools and knowledge exchange.

Before the closing of the meeting, a presentation was given by Olga Tikka, EPPO Director to highlight the importance of aligning these research priorities with policy support and phytosanitary measures. She emphasized the importance of engaging with the Mediterranean region to better understand its challenges. She considered discussions held during the meeting valuable not only for ongoing projects but also for shaping broader regional strategies. She underscored the role of EPPO in supporting these efforts through its various technical bodies and policy forums, particularly in the areas of plant health and plant protection. She acknowledged the growing need to integrate these two areas and noted that some topics, such as breeding, although currently outside EPPO's direct scope, should still involve plant health experts due to their relevance. She concluded by reaffirming her commitment to bringing these discussions to the EPPO Council and encouraging continued collaboration across the region.

4.8. Closing Session: Funding Mechanisms, Research Dissemination, and Future Actions

In the final session of the consultation, attention turned to ensuring the sustainability and visibility of the EUPHRESKO initiative through the strategic engagement of funders and scientific dissemination platforms.

Funders survey

The team from CIHEAM Bari introduced a draft version of a dedicated funding survey aimed at identifying and mapping national research programs, funding schemes, and priority-setting mechanisms related to plant health across the Mediterranean and South European region. The objective of this initiative is to better understand how research is funded at both governmental and institutional levels, with a view to enhancing coordination, alignment, and communication with potential funders.

The presentation emphasized the importance of:

- Targeting the right institutional stakeholders, particularly ministries of agriculture, national research councils, and major funding agencies.
- Simplifying the questionnaire to ensure clarity, usability, and broad participation.
- Using the collected data to build synergies among countries and better align funding flows with the agreed phytosanitary research priorities.

Special issue *Phytopathologia Mediterranea*

Following this, Laura Mugnai introduced the concept of launching a special issue of *Phytopathologia Mediterranea* dedicated to plant health research in the Mediterranean. This special edition aims to showcase:

- Regional research priorities identified during the EUPHRESKO III consultations.
- Methodological approaches, including the bottom-up process used to engage stakeholders and define research lines.
- Case studies and best practices in plant protection and disease management across the region.

All regional representatives were strongly encouraged to disseminate awareness of EUPHRESKO activities in their respective countries and contribute actively to building a collaborative research community. The intention is to not only publish scientific content, but to foster a long-term network of regional collaboration that extends beyond individual projects.

Agreed Next Steps and Follow-up Actions

To consolidate the outcomes of the meeting and ensure continued momentum, the following next steps were defined and agreed upon by all participants:

- Dr. D'Onghia & Nour Al Gndi will draft and finalize a comprehensive report summarizing the key results, decisions, and research priorities defined during the consultation meeting.

- The EUPHRESKO Coordination Team will work to incorporate the identified research priorities into the broader Strategic Research Agenda for the upcoming year, aligning regional needs with transnational programming efforts.
- All Regional Representatives are tasked to update and submit the list of national funders and relevant authorities who should receive the plant health funding survey.
- Representatives are also asked to connect with their country's official EUPHRESKO National Contact Points, in order to strengthen national-level collaboration and help develop a local EUPHRESKO research community.
- CIHEAM Bari will simplify and circulate the funders survey to ensure it is appropriate for the target audience and fit for purpose.
- All representatives are invited to submit potential article abstracts for consideration in the special issue of *Phytopathologia Mediterranea*, with a submission deadline by December 2025.
- Dr. Mugnai will share the publication guidelines, structure, and timeline for contributions to the journal issue with all regional partners.
- The Egyptian national contact will share details on the magnetic sensor technology for palm pest detection, developed in Egypt, with interested countries in North Africa and the Near East to foster technology transfer and collaboration.
- Finally, all regional stakeholders will be invited to review and provide feedback on the stakeholder questionnaire methodology, ensuring improvements for future rounds of national and regional consultations.

This final session concluded a day marked by fruitful collaboration, open exchange, and strategic alignment, reaffirming the commitment of all participants to strengthen phytosanitary research cooperation in the Mediterranean and South European region through EUPHRESKO III.

Figure 43. Group photo of participants at the regional consultation meeting

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Communication material: During the three days of regional consultation, a video was made showing the highlights of the Euphresco session in the MPU Congress, the technical visit, and the regional consultation meeting. Interviews with some national representatives were also included, who shared their thoughts on the regional consultation approach tested in Euphresco III (<https://www.iamb.ciheam.org/euphresco/>).

ANNEXES

ANNEX 1: List of national contacts selected by CIHEAM Bari

	Organisation	country/region if applicable	contact first name	contact last name	email
NATIONAL CONTACTS EUPHRESKO III	The Agricultural University of Tirana.	ALBANIA	Magdalena	Cara	magdacara@ubt.edu.al
	University of Chlef	ALGERIA	Malika	Meziane	m.meziane@univ-chlef.dz
	MPU BOARD , Cyprus University of Technology	CYPRUS	Dimitris	Tsaltas	dimitris.tsaltas@cut.ac.cy
	Former Minister of Agriculture and Land Reclamation of Egypt; Head Research of the Agricultural Research Center, Giza, Egypt	EGYPT	Salah	Abdel-Momen	salah1993@yahoo.com
	Plant protection and phytosanitary directorate	JORDAN	Amani	Alawamleh	amaniawamleh@yahoo.com
	Lebanese Agricultural Research Institute	LEBANON	Elia	Choueri	echoueiri@lari.gov.lb
	National Institute of Agronomic Research of Tunisia	TUNISIA	Asma	Najar	asmanajara@yahoo.fr
	National Institute of Agriculture Research (INRA-Rabat, Morocco)	MOROCCO	Fouad	Mokrini	fouad.mokrini@inra.ma
	National Agriculture Research Center (NARC), Ministry of Agriculture	PALESTINE	Tariq	Abubaker	Tariq.abubaker@moa.pna.ps
	General Commission for Scientific Agricultural Research (GCSAR)	SYRIA	Nader	Asaad	asaad_nader@yahoo.com
	Faculty of Agricultural Sciences and Food Skopje Makedonia del Nord	Republic of North Macedonia	Stanislava	LAZAREVSKA	stanislavalazarevska@yahoo.com
	General Directorate of Agricultural Research and Policies	TURKIYE	Suat	Kaymak	suatkaymak@tarimorman.gov.tr
	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	GREECE	Emilia	Markellou	e.markellou@bpi.gr
	National Institute of Agricultural and Food Research and Technology (INIA-CSIC)	SPAIN	Pablo Gómez	Grande	pablo.gomez@inia.csic.es
	Ministry for Agriculture, Fisheries and Animal Rights	MALTA	Dennis	Sciberras	dennis.sciberras@gov.mt
	Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e Veterinária, IP (INIAV, IP)	PORTUGAL	Leonor	Cruz	leonor.cruz@iniav.pt
	University of Novi Sad	SERBIA	Dragana	Šunjka	dragana.sunjka@polj.edu.rs
University of Sarajevo Faculty of Agriculture and Food Sciences	Bosnia	Arnela	Okic	a.okic@ppf.unsa.ba	
Ministry of Agriculture, Food Sovereignty and Forestry	ITALY	Alberto	Masci	a.masci@masaf.gov.it	

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ANNEX 2: Template identification of stakeholders

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Category	organisation	country/region if applicable	contact first name	contact last name	email
2						
3	Policy makers					
4	Research funders					
5	Research organisations					
6	Industry					
7	Farmers and foresters					
8	Other					
9						
10						
11						
12						
13						
14						
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16						
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19						
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28						
29						

ANNEX 3: Guidance document identification of phytosanitary research stakeholders

Guidance document for the identification of phytosanitary research stakeholders

In order to help you in identifying phytosanitary research stakeholders, you can find below examples of stakeholders. The stakeholders you identify can be national or international organisations or long-term initiatives with direct or indirect impact on plant health.

Note that not all of the below categories may be relevant for your country or your network. Furthermore, the list is non-exhaustive, meaning that you might identify other categories or examples that are also appropriate.

Which are the phytosanitary research stakeholders?

Category	Example
Policy makers	-National Plant Protection Organisation (NPPO), -Regional Plant Protection Organisation (RPPO), -Ministries, -European Commission / DG SANTE, -Regional policy institutions, ...
Research funders	-Research programme owners (national/regional ministries/authorities responsible for defining, financing or managing research programmes carried out at national or regional level), -Research programme managers (research councils or funding agencies or other national or regional organisations that implement research programmes under the supervision of the programme owner), ...
Research organisations	-Public research organisations, -Private research organisations, -Experimental stations, -Research organizations on specific crops, -Academic research groups, -(technical) federations of research organisations, ...
Industry	-Crop industry (e.g. sugar industry, potato industry), -Federations of industries for primary production or transformation, -Seed industry, -Diagnostic industry, ...
Farmers and foresters	-Farmers associations, -Plant / tree nurseries, -Foresters, Arboreta, ...
Other (if appropriate)	-Waste treatment / biocontrol industry, -(associations of) cities / public bodies, -Environmental associations, -Environmental action groups, -Ethical groups, -Consumer organisations, ...

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Why do we want to survey them?

Role	Category	What for?
Initiator	Policy makers	They provide the policy needs around which research activities are developed
	Research funders Industry	They define the national programmes and provide the resources for the research activities to be undertaken
Research implementer	Research organisations Industry Farmers and foresters Others	They provide the expertise that allow research activities to be implemented, from the lab to the field
End-users of research	Farmers and foresters Industry Policy makers Research funders Others	They use the outputs of the research activities

What information do we want from them?

Category	Information to collect with the survey
Policy makers	Policy questions (current and mid-term)
Research funders	Research programmes (current and mid-term) and processes
Research organisations	Knowledge on the research questions (current and medium term)
Industry	Needs from the industry (current and medium term)
Farmers and foresters	Needs from the field (current and medium term)
Other	Needs from the field (current and medium term)

ANNEX 4: Plant health stakeholders survey

International network for strengthening phytosanitary research programming and collaboration: from European to global phytosanitary research coordination - EUPHRESKO III

Introduction:

WHAT ARE OUR GOALS?

EUPHRESKO III

aims to enhance processes and mechanisms to facilitate international collaboration on common plant health research priorities, and to increase communication on national and regional plant health research activities and their outputs. Increased collaboration and communication will result in better coordinated actions among those that perform research and use research outputs.

For global collaboration and communication, the network builds upon the activities of organizations with a long history of coordinating plant health in their region:

[ACIAR](#), [APAARI](#), [CABI](#), [CIHFAM-Bari](#), [CFIA](#), [Euphresco](#), [KHA](#), [PBRI](#), [INIA-CSIC](#), [PFR](#), [USDA](#)

HOW CAN WE COLLABORATE?

We are launching a rapid survey (estimated time to complete 15-20 minutes) to collect information that will be used to enhance knowledge exchange, capacity building and collaboration on plant health research. We would be very interested to hear your view as representative of a research funder, regulator, policymaker, research organization or as end-user of research. Please complete the survey here. The questions of the survey are listed below.

If you would like to know more about our work and to collaborate on plant health research matters, you can contact Ms. Anna Maria D'Onghia: donghia@iamb.it / Ms. Nour Al Gndi: nour@iamb.it

THE AIM OF THIS SURVEY:

This national stakeholders survey is set up to collect information on plant health research:

- * For the identification of research topics
- * For the identification of research priorities
- * For the identification of potential partnerships between countries from different regions to address issues on a broader scale

Within this survey, "crop" is defined as a plant [including trees] or plant product [including tree products, e.g. palette] that can be grown and harvested extensively for profit or subsistence. "Priority" is defined as the fact or the condition of being regarded or treated as more important than others. Different interests can drive priority: economy, trade, strategy, policy, science ... "Pest" is defined as any species, strain or biotype of plant, animal or pathogenic agent injurious to plants or plant products (IPPC- Glossary of phytosanitary terms 2023).

* Indicates required question

Untitled Section

1. I agree to grant EUPHRESKO III Secretariat right to use and store my personal data (e.g. email, address, name, etc.) collected with this survey during the project's timeframe. This might include the right to use personal data on project activities serving the objectives of the **EUPHRESKO III project** (e.g. for the organization of the consultations with the regional or discipline champion and for the identification of new partners for future collaboration). Personal data will be anonymised whenever possible. In any case, personal data will not be shared outside the project, nor will it occur in the reporting towards the funder. The responder will be contacted to ask for permission in case the Secretariat would like to share the personal data outside of the abovementioned context. The responder holds the right to inquire details on the use of his/her personal data and to withdraw them by contacting the Secretariat.*

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

General information

This section is related to your personal information

2. Name of the institution/organisation *

3. Country *

4. Family name *

5. First name *

Plant Health RESEARCH PRIORITIES in your organization / institution

Identify a maximum of 5 research priorities your organization / institution would like to work on in the next 5-10 years:

13. Priority 1 *

14. Priority 2 *

15. Priority 3

16. Priority 4

17. Priority 5

Which agricultural crops are important to study for your organization / institution?

18. Vegetables:

19. Wheats:

6. Email address *

7. Role in the organization / institution *

Plant Health Research at an Organizational / Institutional level

The answers for the questions of this section are related to your Organization / Institution

Plant Health RESEARCH ISSUES in your organization / institution

Identify a maximum of 5 key plant health issues or related practical problems your organization / institution is currently facing:

8. Issue 1 *

9. Issue 2 *

10. Issue 3

11. Issue 4

12. Issue 5

20. Pome Fruits: (Please specify which species)

21. Stone Fruits: (Please specify which species)

22. Citrus: (Please specify which species)

23. Check all that apply

Check all that apply.

- Grape vine
 Date palm
 Fig
 Mango

24. Others, please specify

25. What are your needs, if any, in terms of capacity building? *

Check all that apply

Check all that apply.

- Competences
 Training
 Methods and processes
 Facilities and equipment
 Commodities
 Human resources
 Financial resources

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26. If others, please specify:

Plant Health Research at a Country level

The answers for the questions of this section are related to your country

Plant Health RESEARCH PRIORITIES at a country level

Identify a maximum of 5 research priorities you think that should be addressed in your country in the next 5-10 years to face plant health issues or related practical problems:

27. Priority 1 *

28. Priority 2 *

29. Priority 3

30. Priority 4

31. Priority 5

PESTS PRIORITIES in your country

Which pests do you consider a priority in your country? (Provide a maximum of 5 pests with their Latin name and the factor that drives the priority (economy, trade, strategy, policy...))

38. Pest 4

39. For which factor?

Check all that apply:

- Economy
 Trade
 Strategy
 Policy

40. Pest 5

41. For which factor?

Check all that apply:

- Economy
 Trade
 Strategy
 Policy

Plant Health Research at a Regional level

The answers for the questions of this section are related to your region

Plant Health RESEARCH PRIORITIES at a regional level

Identify a maximum of 5 research priorities you think that should be addressed in your region in the next 5-10 years

to face plant health issues or related practical problems:

42. Priority 1 *

32. Pest 1 *

33. For which factor? *

Check all that apply:

- Economy
 Trade
 Strategy
 Policy

34. Pest 2 *

35. For which factor? *

Check all that apply:

- Economy
 Trade
 Strategy
 Policy

36. Pest 3

37. For which factor?

Check all that apply:

- Economy
 Trade
 Strategy
 Policy

43. Priority 2 *

44. Priority 3

45. Priority 4

46. Priority 5

PESTS PRIORITIES in your region

Which pests do you consider a priority in your region? (Provide a maximum of 5 pests with their Latin name and the factor that drives the priority (economy, trade, strategy, policy...))

47. Pest 1 *

48. For which factor? *

Check all that apply:

- Economy
 Trade
 Strategy
 Policy

49. Pest 2 *

50. For which factor? *

Check all that apply.

- Economy
- Trade
- Strategy
- Policy

51. Pest 3

52. For which factor?

Check all that apply.

- Economy
- Trade
- Strategy
- Policy

53. Pest 4

54. For which factor?

Check all that apply.

- Economy
- Trade
- Strategy
- Policy

55. Pest 5

PESTS PRIORITIES at a global level

Which pests do you consider a global priority? (Provide a maximum of 5 pests with their Latin name)

62. Pest 1 *

63. Pest 2 *

64. Pest 3

65. Pest 4

66. Pest 5

Research areas to be addressed for future work

56. For which factor?

Check all that apply.

- Economy
- Trade
- Strategy
- Policy

Plant Health Research at a Global level

The answers for the questions of this section are related to global research and pests priorities

Plant Health RESEARCH PRIORITIES at a global level

Identify a maximum of 5 research global priorities you think that should be addressed globally in the next 5-10 years

to face plant health issues or related practical problems:

57. Priority 1 *

58. Priority 2 *

59. Priority 3

60. Priority 4

61. Priority 5

67. Which research areas do you think need to be addressed / developed to support future work on plant health issues or related practical problems. (You can select more than one option) *

Check all that apply.

- Emergency preparedness
- Horizon scanning to identify the next big plant health issue
- Risk assessment
- Pest management (sustainable)
- Diagnostics
- Surveillance & inspection
- Epidemiology
- Minimizing spread of diseases through trade of plant material and travel
- Innovation
- Artificial intelligence
- Climate change impact
- Pesticide reduction and alternatives
- Data and information sharing
- Research infrastructures and collections
- Phytosanitary research collaboration (national, regional, continental) and cooperation (e.g. skill and knowledge transfer)

68. Other, please specify

69. Mention 1 concrete research need you want to address in the next 3 years

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ANNEX 5: Ppt presentations per country (three or more responses): ALBANIA

International Congress of the Mediterranean Phytopathological Union - MPU 2025

Session: EUPHRESKO III: Strengthening the Plant Health Research Community

9 July 2025

Results and data analysis of Plant health stakeholders survey

Magdalena Cara
The Agricultural University of Tirane, Albania

Network for phytosanitary research coordination and funding

www.euphresco.eu

1

Number of compiled questionnaires and involved stakeholders from Albania

N.11 Compiled questionnaires

Classification of stakeholders

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2

Priority crops and pests

Priority crops

RANKING
1. Stone fruits 34%
2. Grapes 27%
3. Tomato 12%
4. Apple, Fig, Maize 9%

Priority pests

RANKING
Almost equal values among Insects and Pathogens

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3

PRIORITY INSECTS: Order and names

Classification by Order

RANKING
1. Hemiptera 37%
2. Diptera 32%
3. Lepidoptera 21%

Priority insects

RANKING
1. Ceratitis Capitata, Whiteflies 16%
2. Bactrocera oleae, Tuta absoluta 11%

EUPHRESKO III

4

PRIORITY PATHOGENS: Classification & names

Pathogen classification

RANKING
1. Fungi 55%
2. Bacteria 23%
3. Viruses, Phytoplasmas, viroids 22%

Priority pathogens

RANKING
1. Xylella fastidiosa 17%
2. Venturia inaequalis, Phytophthora spp., Viruses 11%

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5

Capacity Building needs

FINANCIAL RESOURCES, TRAINING, FACILITIES & EQUIPMENT, AND HUMAN RESOURCES are among the most critically needed components for effective capacity building.

Focus on COLLABORATION AND FARMER TRAINING.

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6

Plant Health research priorities

- Pest/Disease Management, pesticides and alternatives to pesticides**
 - Promote the transfer of new technologies for protection against pests and diseases based on scientific research
 - IPM
 - Soil Health and Sustainable Fertilization Practices
 - Promoting Agroecology and Biodiversity
- Pest and disease focus**
 - Apple diseases
 - Production diseases
 - Onion diseases
 - Nematodes
 - Potatoes viruses
 - Wheat and maize diseases
- Crop Improvement**
 - Breeding and Development of Disease-Resistant Varieties
 - Clonal and sanitary selection on fruit-bearing varieties
 - Establishment of olive mother plot with virus-free material
- Surveillance, early detection, risk prevention and management of invasive/emerging pests and diseases**
 - Management of Emerging Pests and Diseases
 - Monitoring/active growing areas for Xylella fastidiosa
- Climate Change**
 - Advanced Climate Change Impact and Adaptation Strategies for pests and diseases
- Diagnostics and Epidemiology**
 - Diagnostic and Monitoring Systems for Pests and Diseases
- Smart crop protection**
 - Study and increase of scientific research in the field of new technologies in support of agricultural/mechanical crop protection
- Food safety**
 - Pesticide Residue Management

EUPHRESKO III

7

Research topics to be addressed in the future:

- Pesticide reduction and alternatives
- Rapid and early detection of pests
- Influence of gene flow regarding crop protection
- Artificial intelligence

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8

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GREECE

Regional Consultation Meeting
11 July 2025

EUPHRESKO III
International network for Strengthening phytosanitary research programming and collaboration from European to global phytosanitary research coordinations

Network for phytosanitary research coordination and funding

Results and data analysis of **Plant health stakeholders survey**

Emilia Markakou
Benaki Phytopathological Institute, Greece

1

Number of compiled questionnaires and involved stakeholders from Greece

N.8 Compiled questionnaires

Classification of stakeholders

2

Priority crops and pests

Priority crops

Ranking:
1. Vegetables 27%
2. Cereals 23%
3. Stone fruits 19%

Priority pests

Ranking:
1. Insects 55%
2. Pathogens 45%

3

PRIORITY INSECTS: Order and names

Classification by Order

Ranking:
1. Lepidoptera 42%
2. Diptera 35%
3. Hemiptera 18%

Priority insects

Ranking:
1. *Bactrocera oleae* 17%
2. *Spodoptera frugiperda* 12%
3. *Tuta absoluta* 11%

4

PRIORITY PATHOGENS: Classification & names

Pathogen classification

Ranking:
1. Fungi, Bacteria and Viruses 38%
2. Viruses, Phytoplasmas, Viroids 28%
3. Fungi 26%

Priority pathogens

Ranking:
1. *Xylella fastidiosa* 38%
2. ToBRFV 19%

5

Capacity Building needs

HUMAN RESOURCES AND FINANCIAL RESOURCES are among the most critically needed components for effective capacity building.

Focus on (Outreach, training, and adoption of plant health practices)

COMMUNICATION & COLLABORATION

6

Plant Health research priorities

- Pest/Disease Management, pesticides and alternatives to pesticides**
 - Role of microbiome in plant disease development and management
 - Understanding the plant-microbiome interactions for improved plant health
 - Alternatives to synthetic pesticides
 - Development and use of botanicals for the control of pest diseases
 - Identification and development of plant alternative to insecticides for disease prevention
 - Biotechnological approaches to pest control
- Pest and disease focus**
 - Investigation of alternative management options for the insect *Phthorimaea absoluta*
 - Investigation of alternative management options for *Bemisia tabaci*
 - Application of techniques for effective control of *Trialeurodes vaporariorum*
 - Management of *Agrocyba conchyliella* (caused by *Phytophthora minimumii*)
 - Phytoplasma: *Phytoplasma vitifoliae*, *Phytoplasma vitifoliae*, *Phytoplasma vitifoliae*, *Phytoplasma vitifoliae*
 - Identification of *Charitopus platanus* infection foci
- Surveillance, early detection, risk prevention and management of invasive/emerging pests and diseases**
 - Development of methods for immediate and effective management of quarantine pest outbreaks
 - Identification of plant pests and pathogens early and understanding their spread and impact
 - Development of reliable and robust early detection methods for quarantine pests
- Diagnostics and Epidemiology**
 - Epidemiology of pest/diseases
 - Development of RNAi technologies for the control of plant diseases
 - Identifying the role of the host-plant health
- Crop Improvement**
 - Resistance mechanisms and resources
- Smart crop protection**
 - Use of technology and data-driven methods to improve plant health monitoring and response
- Climate change**
 - Identify crop varieties that can adapt and thrive in the Greek climate
- Others**
 - Phytosanitary standards for export crops

7

Research topics to be addressed in the future:

- Synchytrium endobioticum* new resistant Potatoes cultivars to potato virus Y (PVY)
- Methods to identify durable resistance against pests
- Effective biopesticides for plant diseases- Biocontrol agents /identification and production
- Management of *Phytophthora spp*

8

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-01 under grant agreement No 101130467

JORDAN

International Congress of the Mediterranean Phytopathological Union - MPU 2025
 Session: EUPHRESKO III: Strengthening the Plant Health Research Community
 9 July 2025

Results and data analysis of Plant health stakeholders survey

Amari Alawamleh
 Ministry of Agriculture, Jordan

Network for phytosanitary research coordination and funding

1

Number of compiled questionnaires and involved stakeholders from Jordan

N.10 Compiled questionnaires

Classification of stakeholders

2

Priority crops and pests

Priority crops

RANKING
 1. Vegetables 29%
 2. Stone fruits 23%
 3. Citrus fruits 17%

Priority pests

RANKING
 1. Insects 56%
 2. Pathogens 42%

3

PRIORITY INSECTS: Order and names

Classification by Order

RANKING
 1. Coleoptera 44%
 2. Hemiptera 22%
 3. Diptera, Lepidoptera 17%

Priority insects

RANKING
 1. RPW 39%
 2. Bactrocera oleae 17%

4

PRIORITY PATHOGENS: Classification & names

Pathogen classification

RANKING
 1. Fungi and oomycete 50%
 2. Bacteria 33%
 3. Viruses, Phytoplasmas, and viroids 17%

Priority pathogens

RANKING
 1. Pseudomonas savastanoi 27%
 2. Fusarium oxysporum 27%

5

Capacity Building needs

TRAINING, HUMAN AND FINANCIAL RESOURCES, METHODS AND PROCESSES are among the most critically needed components for effective capacity building.

Focus on (Co)laboation projects with industry and academia

6

Plant Health research priorities

- Pest and disease focus**
 - Citrus peelm diseases: Blackfly, Blackwax, Scaleinsects, Dabka bug, and red palm weevil
 - New diseases attacking vegetables (tomato)
 - Fusarium/Root knot nematode complex
 - Cucurbit/waxey viruses
 - Viral diseases
 - Stone fruit viruses
 - Phytoplasma diseases
- Surveillance, early detection, risk prevention and management of invasive/emerging pests, diseases**
 - Strengthening Phytosanitary Border Controls and Surveillance
 - Development of National Pest Risk Analysis (NPRA) Framework
 - Improvement of Phytosanitary Certification and Traceability Systems
- Crop improvement**
 - Resistant varieties to diseases and drought
 - Genetic resistance of wild stock
- Climate change**
 - The relationship of de/back to the impact of climate change
- Smart crop protection**
 - AI and remote sensing for early detection of key pests and diseases
 - Early Detection Systems for Pests and Diseases
- Food safety**
 - Residue monitoring data
- Others**
 - Coordination with customs and harmonization/regulation

7

Research topics to be addressed in the future:

- Genetic Resistance and Breeding: Scan for *Fusarium*/Root knot Nematode resistance gene
- Climate change mitigation for plant health

8

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-01 under grant agreement No 101130467

LEBANON

Regional Consultation Meeting
11 July 2025

Results and data analysis of Plant health stakeholders survey

Ella Choucri
Lebanese Agricultural Research Institute, Lebanon

www.phytosglobal.net

1

Number of compiled questionnaires and involved stakeholders from Lebanon

N.6 Compiled questionnaires

Classification of stakeholders

- Research organizations 50%
- Policy makers 30%
- Research centers 20%

2

Priority crops and pests

Priority crops

- Legumes 19%
- Stone fruits, cereals 17%
- Vegetables 12%
- Forage crops 8%
- Other crops 11%

Priority pests

- Pathogens 61%
- Insects 39%

3

PRIORITY INSECTS: Order and names

Classification by Order

- Leptoptera 50%
- Diptera 37%
- Coloptera 13%

Priority insects

- Tuta absoluta 34%
- Other insects 66%

4

PRIORITY PATHOGENS: Classification & names

Pathogen classification

- Viruses, Phytoplasmas, viroids 50%
- Bacteria 29%
- Fungi 21%

Priority pathogens/diseases

- Xylella fastidiosa 29%
- Potato viruses 15%
- Other pathogens 56%

5

Capacity Building needs

FINANCIAL RESOURCES, TRAINING, FACILITIES, AND EQUIPMENT are among the most critically needed components for effective capacity building.

FINANCIAL RESOURCES	6
TRAINING	6
FACILITIES & EQUIPMENT	6
Methods and processes	3
Human resources	2
Competences	2

Focus on (Technology transfer) — COMMUNICATION & COLLABORATION

6

Plant Health research priorities

- Pest and disease focus**
 - Curtail caplets, *Bectra* olive
 - Graft transmissible diseases of fruit crops
- Pest/Disease Management, pesticides and alternatives to pesticides**
 - IPM
 - Biological control of pests
 - Pesticide use and management
 - Field surveys for yield loss caused by pests
- Climate change**
 - Climate change resilience in agriculture
 - Impact of climate change on pests and diseases
- Surveillance, early detection, risk prevention and management of invasive/emerging pests, diseases**
 - Emerging plant diseases and invasive species
- Diagnostics and Epidemiology**
 - Molecular diagnosis of pests
 - Advanced detection methods
- Crop improvement**
 - Pest resistance breeding
 - Enhancing bee health and phytosanitary measures
- Food Safety**
 - Mycotoxins
- Others**
 - Phytosanitary of agricultural commodities

7

Research topics to be addressed in the future:

- Updated surveys on *Xylella fastidiosa* including vectors
- Regional pest surveillance
- Artificial intelligence: in prediction, detection, monitoring, or decision-making in plant health research.
- Risk management from pest and diseases

8

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MOROCCO

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PORTUGAL

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SERBIA

Regional Consultation Meeting
11 July 2025

EUPHRESKO III
International network for Strengthening phytosanitary research programming and collaboration from European to global phytosanitary research coordination

Results and data analysis of Plant health stakeholders survey

Network for phytosanitary research coordination and funding

Dragana Šunjica
University of Novi Sad, Serbia

1

Number of compiled questionnaires and involved stakeholders from Serbia

N.9 Compiled questionnaires

Classification of stakeholders

2

Priority crops and pests

Priority crops

RANKING
1. Vegetables 30%
2. Cereals, Stone fruits 22%

Priority pests

RANKING
1. Insects 44%
2. Pathogens 40%

3

PRIORITY INSECTS: Order and names

Classification by Order

RANKING
1. Hemiptera 46%
2. Lepidoptera 27%
3. Diptera 18%

Priority insects

RANKING
1. Coleoptera 19%
The others have equal values

4

PRIORITY PATHOGENS: Classification & names

Pathogen classification

RANKING
1. Fungi 40%
2. Bacteria, Virus, Phytoplasmas, Viruses 30%

Priority pathogens

RANKING
1. Botrytis cinerea, Erwinia amylovora 20%

5

Capacity Building needs

FINANCIAL RESOURCES: 8

TRAINING: 8

METHODS & PROCESSES: 7

Facilities and equipment: 6

Competences: 4

Human resources: 2

FINANCIAL RESOURCES, TRAINING, METHODS AND PROCESSES are among the most critically needed components for effective capacity building.

6

Plant Health research priorities

- 1. Pest/Disease Management, pesticides and alternatives to pesticides**
 - Biopesticides
 - Study of biological measures to control pathogens
 - Reduction in pesticide use
 - Improvement of the formulation of chemical pesticides
- 2. Pest and disease focus**
 - *Oryza sativa*
 - Root rot/compaction/agriculture
 - Apicose sporeling
 - Virus/diseases of wheat
- 3. Surveillance, early detection, risk prevention and management of invasive/emerging pests, diseases**
 - Non-invasive pest species
 - Control of invasive pests
- 4. Crop improvement**
 - Implementation of factors to reduce the occurrence of resistance
- 5. Food safety**
 - Mycotoxin mitigation
 - Pesticide residues
- 6. Climate change**
 - Climate change and pest resistance

7

Research topic to be addressed in the future:

- Biopesticide formulation
- The effect of "*Crotalaria juncea*" roots grown in a regenerative agriculture system on soil compaction, nematode reduction and corn wireworm when planted as an intercrop.
- Prevalence and types of brown rat resistance to anticoagulant rodenticides in Serbia
- Alternative sources of bioactive compounds with pesticide activity

8

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SPAIN

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TUNISIA

International Congress of the Mediterranean Phytopathological Union - MPU 2025
 Session: EUPHRESKO III: Strengthening the Plant Health Research Community
 9 July 2025

Results and data analysis of Plant health stakeholders survey

Asma Najjar
 National Institute of Agronomic Research, Tunisia

Network for phytosanitary research coordination and funding

www.euphresco.org

1

Number of compiled questionnaires and involved stakeholders from Tunisia

N.20 Compiled questionnaires

Classification of Stakeholders

- Research organisations: 90%
- Policy makers: 5%
- Industry: 5%

2

Priority crops and pests

Priority crops

- Stone fruits: 18%
- Cereals: 16%
- Vegetables: 13%
- Citrus fruits: 11%
- Others: 2%
- Wheat: 2%
- Legumes: 2%
- Oilseeds: 2%
- Forage: 2%
- Medicinal plants: 2%
- Ornamentals: 2%
- Wild fruits: 2%
- Wild vegetables: 2%
- Wild medicinal plants: 2%
- Wild ornamentals: 2%

Priority pests

- Insects: 65%
- Pathogens: 20%
- Others: 15%

RANKING

- Insects 65%
- Pathogens 20%

3

PRIORITY INSECTS: Order and names

Classification by Order

- Homoptera: 40%
- Coleoptera: 26%
- Diptera: 17%
- Phaneroptera: 8%
- Lepidoptera: 7%
- Orthoptera: 2%
- Psylliida: 2%
- Hemiptera: 2%
- Blattellidae: 2%
- Dermaptera: 2%
- Thysanoptera: 2%
- Collembola: 2%
- Acari: 2%
- Nematoda: 2%
- Protozoa: 2%
- Viruses: 2%
- Bacteria: 2%
- Fungi: 2%
- Pump: 2%

Priority insects

- Rhynchophorus ferrugineus: 50%
- Dactylopusia opuntiae: 20%
- Dactylopusia coccinea: 15%
- Corabitis capitata: 15%

RANKING

- Insects 65%
- Pathogens 20%

4

PRIORITY PATHOGENS: Classification & names

Pathogen classification

- Bacteria: 43%
- Viruses: 29%
- Phytoplasmas, viroids: 29%
- Fungi: 28%
- Pump: 28%

Priority pathogens

- Xylella fastidiosa: 36%
- Citrus tristeza virus: 23%
- Others: 41%

RANKING

- Bacteria 43%
- Viruses, Phytoplasmas, viroids 29%
- Fungi 28%
- Pump 28%

5

Capacity Building needs

TRAINING: 18

FINANCIAL RESOURCES: 15

FACILITIES & EQUIPMENT: 12

Human resource: 10

Connectivity: 8

Competence: 6

COMMUNICATION & COLLABORATION: 4

TRAINING, FINANCIAL RESOURCES, FACILITIES & EQUIPMENT are among the most critically needed components for effective capacity building.

Focus on Transferring research results to Farmers (in collaboration with social science specialists)

6

Plant Health research priorities

- Pest and disease focus**
 - Biological control and containment of *Dactylopusia opuntiae*
 - Pest Management and containment of *Red Palm Weevil*
 - Prevention and control of *Agrotis fabae* and their vectors
 - Management of Mediterranean Rust fly and Carabid beetle in Citrus trees (*Agrotis fabae* and *Carabid beetle*)
 - Management of *Falsaria vitis* in Citrus orchards
 - Strategies to control *Electraea oleae* in citrus groves
- Pest/Disease Management and alternatives to pesticides**
 - Integrated Pest and Disease Management
 - Alternatives to control olive flies, citrus psyllid
 - Reducing pesticide use
 - Promoting Sustainable Agricultural Practices
 - Springing up new and alternative measures
 - Enhancing Soil Health and Fertility
 - Weed control research increases
- Climate change**
 - Study of the impact of climate change on the plant pathogens
 - Development of Climate Resilient Crop Varieties
 - Pesticide use and behavior under climate change
 - Emerging pathogens due to climate change
- Surveillance, early detection, risk prevention and management of invasive/emerging pests, diseases**
 - Management of invasive weeds and pests
 - Advancing Early Detection and Monitoring Technologies
 - Preventing the introduction of exotic pests and surveillance
- Diagnostics and Epidemiology**
 - Setting up new techniques for rapid diagnosis
- Crop improvement**
 - Preserving and enhancing local biodiversity
- Others**
 - Establishing stricter phytosanitary regulations and certification for seeds exchanges

7

Research topics to be addressed in the future:

- Development and implementation of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies for emerging pests
- Reducing pesticide use and promoting IPM
- Alternatives to control pests of main strategic crops
- Inventory of existing pests nationwide with risk assessments for each insect based on the crops they attack
- Citrus tristeza virus
- Cereal soil-borne diseases
- Alternatives for the management of *Elymus repens* in crops
- Polinators conservation
- Integrated pest management in a context of climate change to ensure food security
- Artificial intelligence

8

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EGYPT

Regional Consultation Meeting
11 July 2025

Results and data analysis of Plant health stakeholders survey

Salah M. Abdel-Momen
(Ph.D) Professor Agric. Res. Center 9 Gamaas St. Giza, Egypt

Network for phytosanitary research coordination and funding

www.euphresco.eu

1

Number of compiled questionnaires and involved stakeholders from Egypt

Classification of stakeholders

N.7 Compiled questionnaires

100% Research organizations / Research Funders

2

Priority crops and pests

Priority crops

RANKING
1. Vegetables 23%
2. Citrus fruits 16%
3. Pome fruits, Mango 10%

Priority pests

RANKING
1. Insects 55%
2. Pathogens 40%

3

PRIORITY INSECTS: Order and names

Classification by Order

RANKING
1. Coleoptera 46%
2. Lepidoptera 40%

Priority insects

RANKING
1. Tuta absoluta 27%
2. Rhynchophorus ferrugineus 26%

4

PRIORITY PATHOGENS: Classification & names

Pathogen classification

RANKING
1. Fungi 75%
2. Nematodes 25%

Priority pathogens

RANKING
1. Meloidogyne 25%
2. Postharvest diseases (Rizoctonia solani), Fusarium oxysporum f.sp.melonis 13%

5

Capacity Building needs

FINANCIAL RESOURCES, TRAINING, FACILITIES, AND EQUIPMENT are among the most critically needed components for effective capacity building.

Focus on (increase communication with other countries about plant health and training)

6

Plant Health research priorities

- Pest and disease focus**
 - Spodoptera frugiperda
 - Rook/not nematodes on vegetables and fruits
 - Fusarium spp.
 - Tuta absoluta
- Pest/Disease Management, pesticides and alternatives to pesticides**
 - Safe and effective crop protection materials and techniques
 - IPM
- Smart crop protection**
 - Introduction of advanced technology and related equipment
- Surveillance, early detection, risk prevention and management of invasive/emerging pests, diseases**
 - Plant risk analysis
 - Establishing a Regional Plant Health Information Network
- Climate Change**
 - Studies of climate change effects on plant health and food availability
- Crop Improvement**
 - Production of new resistant strains of economic crops to pathogens and insects

7

Research topics to be addressed in the future:

- Control of Meloidogyne spp. and investigating nematode-fungal disease complex
- Artificial intelligence in early detection of plant pathogens and insect generations predictions

8

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ANNEX 6: Ppt presentations per sub-region: BALKANS

Regional Consultation Meeting
11 July 2025

Results and data analysis of Plant health stakeholders survey

Geographic area: BALKANS
Facilitator: Dimitrios Tsiagiannis

Armelia Oros, University of Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Dragana Surlija, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Miroslava Caci, The Agricultural University of Tirana, Albania
Stanimira Lazarovska, University "Ss. Cyril and Methodius", North Macedonia

International network for Strengthening phytosanitary research programming and collaboration from European to global phytosanitary research coordination

Network for phytosanitary research coordination and funding

www.phytocollab.net

1

Number of compiled questionnaires and involved stakeholders from Balkans

Albania
Bosnia and Herzegovina
North Macedonia
Serbia

N.23 Compiled questionnaires

Classification of stakeholders

- Policy makers: 4%
- Others: 4%
- Farmers and keepers: 9%
- Industry: 9%
- Research institutions: 74%

2

3

4

5

6

Plant Health research priorities

- 1. Pest/Disease Management, pesticides and alternatives to pesticides**
 - IPM
 - Biopesticides and biocontrol
 - Pesticide reduction
 - Improvement of the formulation of chemical pesticides
- 2. Pest and disease focus**
 - Virus characterization and detection (potato, wheat)
 - Apple diseases
 - *Ostryia nubilalis*
 - Wheat and maize diseases
 - Apricot appleey
 - Nematodes
- 3. Surveillance, early detection, risk prevention and management of invasive/emerging pests and diseases**
 - Monitoring, management invasive/emerging pests and diseases (*Xylosta fastidiosa*)
- 4. Crop Improvement**
 - Breeding, development, and selection of disease-resistant varieties (fruit trees)
 - Establishment of olive mother plot with virus-free material
 - Implementation of factors to reduce the occurrence of resistance

7

Thank you

8

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-01 under grant agreement No 101130467

SOUTH EUROPE

Regional Consultation Meeting
11 July 2025

Results and data analysis of Plant health stakeholders survey

Geographic area: SOUTH EUROPE
Facilitator: Laura Mugnai

Denise Scherini, (Pest) Protection Directorate, Malta
Dimitris Tsiflis, Cyprus University of Technology (Spain)
Emilia Marfakidou, Hellenic Phytopathological Institute, Greece
Luisa Ester, National Institute for Agricultural and Veterinary Research, Portugal
Laura Mugnai, University of Florence, Italy
Pablo Gilman, Spanish National Institute of Agricultural and Food Research and Technology, Spain

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Network for phytosanitary research coordination and funding

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1

Number of compiled questionnaires and involved stakeholders from South Europe

Cyprus
Greece
Italy
Malta
Portugal
Spain

N.55 Compiled questionnaires

Classification of stakeholders

Research funders 25%

Research organisations 62%

Industry 13%

Farmers and Growers 0%

2

3

4

5

6

Plant Health research priorities

- Pest/Disease Management, pesticides and alternatives to pesticides**
 - Alternative biopesticides (microbiome, mycorrhizal, bioinsecticides)
 - Alternative bio-synthetic pesticides (acetic acid, compounds, HBC/Neurotoxin/Solubility)
 - Precision Integrated Pest Management
 - Improvement of the formulation of chemical pesticides (insecticides, fungicides, herbicides)
 - Agroecology in pest management
- Pest and disease focus**
 - Wildlife related diseases (wildlife, vectors, tolerant crops)
 - Citrus, olive, citrus and tobacco viruses
 - Citrus and woody diseases
 - Fungal tree diseases (Olive/olive/pistachio), Oak diseases, Cork oak plagues and diseases, Pineweed diseases, Eucalyptus diseases
 - Prunus black stem/young fruit, Seed potatoes and ware potatoes health
 - Drosophila spp/fruit
 - Wine related
 - Cherry/strawberry
- Surveillance and early detection**
 - Digital surveillance methods and tools for early pathogen detection
 - Identify high risk pests and pathogens early and understand their spread and impact
 - Development of reliable and robust early detection methods for quarantine pests (improvement of sampling methods)
 - Transboundary emerging pests and diseases (improving knowledge of priority pests in the European Union)

7

Thank you

8

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-01 under grant agreement No 101130467

NEAR EAST

Regional Consultation Meeting
11 July 2025

Results and data analysis of Plant health stakeholders survey

Geographic area: NEAR EAST
Facilitator: Nuray Baser

Amari Alawneh, Ministry of Agriculture, Jordan
Eliz Chehawi, Lebanese Agricultural Research Institute, Lebanon
Muhammad Alawneh, General Directorate for Scientific Agricultural Research, Syria
Sabah Kaymak, General Directorate of Agricultural Research and Policies, Turkey
Samir Abuhatir, Ministry of Agriculture, Lebanon

International network for Strengthening phytosanitary research programming and collaboration from European to global phytosanitary research coordination

Network for phytosanitary research coordination and funding

www.euphresco3.eu

1

Number of compiled questionnaires and involved stakeholders from Near East

N: 29 Compiled questionnaires

Jordan
Lebanon
Palestine
Syria
Turkey

Classification of stakeholders

- Research organisations: 45%
- Policy-makers: 38%
- Farmers and breeders: 10%
- Industry: 2%
- Others: 3%

2

3

4

5

6

- Plant Health research priorities**
- Pest and disease focus**
 - Fusarium stem blight, antracnose and cereals
 - Root knot nematode complex
 - Red palm weevil and date palm diseases and pests
 - New diseases attacking vegetables (TRPV)
 - Wheat diseases
 - Pest/Disease Management, pesticides and alternatives to pesticides**
 - Pesticide reduction
 - Biocontrol and biopesticides (Parasitoids, nematodes)
 - Finding natural enemies for some economic pests
 - Alternatives to synthetic pesticides
 - surveillance and early detection**
 - Emerging plant diseases and invasive species
 - Strengthening Phytosanitary Border Controls and Surveillance
 - Forecast and early models
 - Plant Risk Analysis
 - Development of methods for detecting and predicting plant pests

7

Thank you

8

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-01 under grant agreement No 101130467

NORTH AFRICA

Regional Consultation Meeting
11 July 2025

Results and data analysis of Plant health stakeholders survey

Geographic area: **NORTH AFRICA**
Facilitator: **Baldissera Giovani**

Asma Najaj, National Institute of Agronomic Research, Tunisia
Fouad Mokriem, National Institute of Agriculture Research, Morocco
Malika Meziane, University of Chlef, Algeria
Salah M. Abdel-Momen, Agriculture Research Center, Egypt

International network for Strengthening phytosanitary research programming and collaboration: from European to global phytosanitary research coordination

Network for phytosanitary research coordination and funding

www.euphresco.net

1

Number of compiled questionnaires and involved stakeholders from North Africa

Algeria
Egypt
Morocco
Tunisia

N.40 Compiled questionnaires

Classification of stakeholders

- Industry: 20%
- Research organizations (Research Leaders): 17%
- Research organizations (Youth): 63%

2

3

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6

Plant Health research priorities

- Pest and disease focus**
 - Xylella fastidiosa and vectors
 - Red palm weevil and date palm diseases
 - Dactylopusia opuntiae
 - Root-knot nematodes on vegetables and fruits
 - Fusarium spp.
 - Tuta absoluta
- Pest/Disease Management, pesticides and alternatives to pesticides**
 - Pesticides reduction
 - Biocontrol
 - Alternatives to synthetic pesticides (olive trees, date palms, citrus pests)
 - IPM
 - Improvement of the formulation of chemical fungicides (cereals), insecticides, nematocides
 - Weed control for cereals
- Surveillance and early detection**
 - Early Detection and Monitoring Systems: Developing and implementing advanced technologies for early detection, monitoring, and forecasting of plant diseases and pest outbreaks
 - Pest risk analysis
- Climate Change**
 - Climate Change impact on crop diseases, pests, emerging pathogens and food availability
 - Development of climate-resilient crop varieties (through tolerance and pest management practices)
 - Pesticide use and behavior under climate change

7

Thank you

8

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-01 under grant agreement No 101130467

ANNEX 7: Agenda EUPHRESKO III Session

9
July

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

CIHEAM Bari | CONFERENCE ROOM

10:00–11:00 CONCURRENT SESSION F3***EUPHRESKO III: strengthening the plant health research community***Chair: *Baldissera Giovani, European Phytosanitary Research Coordination Network (EUPHRESKO)***10:00–10:10 SF3-K1 Strengthening plant health in the Mediterranean region through coordinated research and international collaboration***Baldissera Giovani, Euphresco Secretariat, France***10:10–10:20 Consultations for the Mediterranean region: from national to global through regional prioritization***Anna Maria D'Onghia, CIHEAM Bari***10:20–10:25 EUPHRESKO III consultation: plant health research priorities in Portugal***Leonor Cruz, National Institute for Agricultural and Veterinary Research, Portugal***10:25–10:30 EUPHRESKO III consultation: plant health research priorities in Tunisia***Asma Najar, National Institute of Agronomic Research, Tunisia***10:30–10:35 EUPHRESKO III consultation: plant health research priorities in Albania***Magdalena Cara, The Agricultural University of Tirana, Albania***10:35–10:40 EUPHRESKO III consultation: plant health research priorities in Jordan***Amani Alawamleh, Plant Protection & Phytosanitary Directorate, Jordan***10:40–11:00 CONCLUSIONS***Anna Maria D'Onghia and Baldissera Giovani***11:00–11:15 COFFEE BREAK**

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-01 under grant agreement No 101130467

ANNEX 8: Technical visit program

17th International Congress of the Mediterranean Phytopathological Union

10
July

TECHNICAL VISIT PROGRAM

The EXCURSION: Visit to the ancient olive trees infected with *Xylella fastidiosa* and to Alberobello 'the Trulli's town'

Experts: Khaled Djelouah, *CIHEAM Bari*

Toufic Elbeaino, *CIHEAM Bari*

Donato Boscia, *Italian National Research Council, Bari, Italy*

Giuseppe Cavallo, *CIHEAM Bari*

08:00 DEPARTURE FROM BARI (3 MEETING POINTS)

10:15 Serranova (BR): Visit to *Xylella*-infected olive trees in the "Park of Monumental Olive Trees"

11:30 DEPARTURE

13:30 Lunch at the restaurant "Chiusa di Chietri", Alberobello (BA)

15:15 Visit to Alberobello

17:00 DEPARTURE

18:30 Arrival in Bari

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-01 under grant agreement No 101130467

ANNEX 9: Agenda of the regional consultation meeting

REGIONAL CONSULTATION

Plant Health Research Priorities for South Europe – Mediterranean Region

July 11, 2025

CIHEAM Bari campus, Valenzano: Room: Innovation Hub

Chair: Anna Maria D'Onghia

09:00 - 09:20	EUPHRESKO III overview Baldissera Giovani, Euphresco III coordinator
09:20 - 09:40	Regional surveys and consultations: the bottom-up approach Anna Maria D'Onghia, Euphresco III Regional Champion
09:40 - 10:45	Country reports on national research priorities (5' each presenter) <ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ <i>Italy:</i> Alberto Masci, Ministry of Agriculture, Food Sovereignty and Forestry➤ <i>*Tunisia:</i> Asma Najar, National Institute of Agronomic Research➤ <i>Morocco:</i> Fouad Mokrini, National Institute of Agriculture Research➤ <i>*Portugal:</i> Leonor Cruz, National Institute for Agricultural and Veterinary Research➤ <i>*Albania:</i> Magdalena Cara, The Agricultural University of Tirana➤ <i>*Jordan:</i> Amani Alawamleh, Plant Protection and Phytosanitary Directorate➤ <i>Spain:</i> Pablo Gómez Grande, National Institute of Agricultural and Food Research and Technology➤ <i>Serbia:</i> Dragana Šunjka, University of Novi Sad➤ <i>Greece:</i> Emilia Markellou, Benaki Phytopathological Institute➤ <i>Egypt:</i> Salah Abdel-Momen, Former Minister of Agriculture and Land Reclamation➤ <i>Lebanon:</i> Elia Choueri, Lebanese Agricultural Research Institute➤ <i>Turkey:</i> Nuray Baser, CIHEAM Bari➤ <i>Palestine:</i> Tariq Abubaker, Ministry of Agriculture (online)➤ <i>Algeria:</i> Malika Meziane, University of Chlef➤ <i>Bosnia:</i> Arnela Okić, University of Sarajevo➤ <i>Cyprus:</i> Dimitrios Tsaltas, Cyprus University of Technology (online)➤ <i>Syria & Malta & North Macedonia:</i> Nour Al Gndi, CIHEAM Bari

* Presentations delivered during the EUPHRESKO session at MPU 2025

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10:45 - 11:00	<i>COFFEE BREAK</i>
11:00 - 12:30	Presentation of survey results for each geographical area Anna Maria D'Onghia, Euphresco III Regional Champion Working Group discussions by country's representatives <u>South Europe</u> : Portugal, Spain, Italy, Greece, Cyprus, Malta <i>Facilitator</i> : Laura Mugnai, University of Florence, Italy <u>North Africa</u> : Egypt, Tunisia, Algeria, Morocco <i>Facilitator</i> : Baldissera Giovani, Euphresco <u>Near East</u> : Turkey, Jordan, Palestine, Lebanon, Syria <i>Facilitator</i> : Nuray Baser, CIHEAM Bari <u>Balkans</u> : Serbia, Albania, Bosnia-Herzegovina, North Macedonia <i>Facilitator</i> : Dimitrios Tsitsigiannis, Agricultural University of Athens, Greece
12:30 - 13:45	<i>LUNCH</i>
13:45 - 14:15	Reports presentation and discussion WG Facilitators
14:15 - 15:10	Identification of main research lines All participants
15:10 - 15:30	Research priorities & Policies Olga Tikka, EPPO Director
15:30 - 16:00	Presentation of the EUPHRESKO III Funders Survey Nour Al Gndi, CIHEAM Bari
16:00 - 16:30	Wrap up Baldissera Giovani & Anna Maria D'Onghia
16:30	End of the meeting

4 REPORT OF THE CONSULTATIONS FOR NORTH AMERICA

1. Introduction

The Canadian Food Inspection Agency (CFIA) and United States Department of Agriculture - Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service (USDA-APHIS) are National Plant Protection Organizations (NPPOs) as stipulated under the International Plant Protection Convention (IPPC). Both organizations are responsible for enforcing the respective Acts, Regulations and Standards through science-based programs aimed to protect their plant resources from pests and secure market access.

The identification and prioritization of research needs is a foundational step of annual research planning. Subject matter experts from across disciplines and branches (e.g., Policy and Programs, Operations and Science) identify challenges or gaps that require research to deliver information, tools or methods that support their regulatory mandates at NPPOs.

2. The agricultural crops

The CFIA and USDA-APHIS both monitor and regulate agricultural crops to protect plant health, ensure food safety, and support trade. As NPPOs, they focus on preventing the introduction and spread of regulated or quarantine pests affecting crops grown in their respective countries, including various grains and field crops, potatoes, fruits and vegetables. In addition to agriculture crops, their mandate also includes the protection of the environment and forestry sector.

3. Important pests for the discipline

The specific pests of concern in North America were identified as part of the Euphresco III champions review process to determine research priorities.

Pest	Information
Spotted lanternfly (<i>Lycorma delicatula</i>)	Hosts of concern: grapes, general environment Focus on monitoring and management methods (e.g., traps, lures, pesticides, biocontrol, non-chemical methods) to minimize impact across North America. Use of novel pest surveillance systems for early detection of pests - e.g. AI, remote cameras, robots, citizen science, and eDNA.
Asian long-horned beetle (<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>)	Hosts of concern: Forest and landscape trees, wood packing material Research on spread and climate suitability modeling, monitoring, control, and exclusion methods to minimize damage from this pest by limiting global spread, preventing introduction into Canada, and supporting eradication in the USA. Use of novel pest surveillance systems for early detection of pests - e.g. AI, remote cameras, robots, citizen science, and eDNA.

Box tree moth (<i>Cydalima perspectalis</i>)	Host of concern: Box tree in landscapes and nurseries Early detection and management methods to protect the nursery industry.
European cherry fruit fly (<i>Rhagoletis cerasi</i>)	Host of concern: cherries Development of biocontrol systems to manage the pest in cherry production areas.
Woodboring pests	Host of concern: hard and soft wood and wood products Development and testing of novel MBR alternatives to treat wood and wood products, ensuring continued export and preventing international pest spread.
Snails	Host of concern: multiple commodities Development of identification tools (digital and molecular), and monitoring, control, and eradication methods to improve detection and control of invasive snails. Development and evaluation of alternative phytosanitary treatment options for invasive pests.
Potato wart (<i>Synchytrium endobioticum</i>)	Host of concern: potatoes Assessment of viability and pathotyping, identification of mechanisms for pathogen resistance, and breeding of pathogen-resistant potato varieties to protect production.
Oak wilt (<i>Bretziella fagacearum</i>)	Host of concern: oak trees especially red oak Use of novel pest surveillance systems for early detection of pests - e.g. AI, remote cameras, robots, citizen science, and eDNA.
Spongy moth (<i>Lymantria</i> spp.)	Host of concern: multiple commodities especially in marine ports or land borders Development and evaluation of alternative phytosanitary treatment options for invasive pests.

Table created using M365 Copilot using information from 24-29871_research_priorities_by_region.pptx then edited by a human.

4. Key drivers for collaboration

The major drivers for international plant health research collaboration are harmonizing phytosanitary standards, building capacity through technology and knowledge transfer and strengthening global trade and market access.

1) Harmonizing Phytosanitary Standards

Phytosanitary standards are fundamental to global plant health governance, enabling countries to protect plant resources while promoting safe and equitable trade. Advancing these standards requires robust international and regional collaboration, which facilitates the exchange of methodologies and materials, coordination of validation ring trials, and harmonization of data analysis pipelines.

For example, traditional virus detection methods in plant material are often slow and dependent on prior knowledge of the pathogen. In contrast, high-throughput sequencing (HTS) offers a faster, more sensitive approach capable of identifying both known and novel viruses. Despite its potential, HTS is not yet recognized by the IPPC as an approved method for the international movement of propagative plant material. To support broader adoption of

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HTS, standardized technical criteria and validated workflows are required. This need is being addressed through a collaborative Euphresco project focused on developing best practices for HTS implementation, result interpretation, and the creation of a centralized reference database.

Such initiatives highlight the critical role of cross-border cooperation in testing, validating, and harmonizing diagnostic methods. Ultimately, these efforts strengthen global plant health systems and enhance preparedness for emerging pest and disease threats.

2) Building Capacity through Technology and Knowledge Transfer

Building capacity to address plant health challenges and strengthen plant protection systems is increasingly critical in the face of climate change, expanding global trade, and the spread of invasive species. Cross-border collaboration plays a key role in ensuring that regulatory agencies have access to the latest scientific knowledge and best practices in diagnostics, pest management, and biosecurity.

International partnerships play a crucial role in fostering interdisciplinary knowledge-sharing, which drives innovation and supports the development of standardized frameworks for risk prevention, such as horizon scanning. Collaborative efforts also accelerate advancements in technologies like remote sensing, machine learning, and AI-powered pest identification tools. These innovations significantly enhance early detection and rapid response capabilities by enabling real-time monitoring of pest outbreaks and disease spread. This, in turn, allows for more targeted and efficient interventions. For instance, in the case of the Asian long-horned beetle, such tools can help curb its global spread and support effective prevention and eradication strategies.

3) Strengthening Global Trade and Market Access

Strengthening global trade and market access can directly result from the first two drivers for collaboration. By aligning phytosanitary measures and enhancing technical capabilities, countries can reduce trade barriers, improve compliance with international requirements, and gain access to new markets. For instance, propagative plant material needs to be disease-free to be traded internationally. In North America, coordinated efforts among NAPPO members are essential to harmonize phytosanitary standards, improve surveillance systems, and invest in innovative diagnostic and treatment technologies. By prioritizing plant health, the region can safeguard its agricultural productivity, preserve ecosystems, and ensure compliance with international trade regulations—ultimately fostering more resilient and sustainable trade networks.

5. The research priorities

During the Euphresco III champions review process, the following research priorities for North America were identified:

Pest-specific:

- **Spotted Lanternfly:** Develop monitoring and management methods (e.g., traps, biocontrol, non-chemical methods) to minimize impact across North America.

- **Asian Long Horned Beetle:** Spread and climate suitability modeling, monitoring and control methods to prevent introduction into Canada and eradicate from the USA.
- **Box Tree Moth:** Early detection and management to protect the nursery industry.
- **European Cherry Fruit Fly:** Develop biocontrol systems to manage the pest in cherry production areas.
- **MeBr Alternatives for Wood:** Develop and test novel treatment methods to support wood export and prevent pest spread.
- **Snails:** Develop identification tools (digital and molecular) and monitoring, control, and eradication methods.
- **Potato Wart:** Assess viability, pathotyping, and breed resistant varieties to protect potato production.

Cross-cutting:

- **Novel pest surveillance systems:** Use of AI, remote cameras, robots, citizen science, and eDNA for early detection of pests like Asian long-horned beetle, spotted lanternfly, and oak wilt.
- **Phytosanitary treatments:** Development and evaluation of alternative treatment options for invasive pests (e.g., snails, spongy moths) on cargo and containers, and MeBr alternatives for treatment of wood and wood products.

6. The programs and the funds allocated to plant health research

(optional, if already known or if Funding survey has already been conducted)

Unknown.

7. Coordination and collaboration

(optional, if already known or if Funding survey has already been conducted)

Unknown.

8. Supplementary information or messages originated from the consultation

No supplementary information. All information was summarized in the information above.

5 REPORT OF THE CONSULTATIONS FOR PACIFIC ISLANDS

Executive summary

- As part of the Euphresco III Horizon Europe programme and supported by various New Zealand entities, a one-day consultation workshop was undertaken on 16 August 2024 in Auckland, New Zealand.
- Those in attendance included plant health professionals from six Pacific Islands (n=15) and 30 New Zealanders.
- The objective of the workshop was to promote partnerships and enhance research collaboration/co-ordination and to promote EUPHRESKO, seeking to enhance plant health/biosecurity research in the Pacific Islands.
- The workshop included a range of introductory talks, responses to questions using Mentimeter and group breakout sessions.
- Crops identified having priorities for plant health research include taro, kava, coconut, and various vegetables and fruits.
- Organisms ranked as the greatest priority for research in the Pacific identified by workshop attendees included:
 - Invertebrates: Coconut rhinoceros beetle (CRB), Fruit fly, various species of ants (invasive species incl. white-footed ants, little fire ants, red fire ant), thrips, fall armyworm and the Giant African snail
 - Pathogens: Crop-specific pathogens included kava dieback, taro leaf blight with non-crop-specific pathogens Anthracnose, *Phytophthora* and viruses
 - Weeds: African tulip and *Merremia*.
- When asked to identify the biggest issues facing plant health/biosecurity and activities that could promote capability development, attendees came up with many different options, underpinning the size and complexity of the challenge facing plant health professionals in the Pacific. This was further emphasized by discussion during the breakout groups.
- The workshop emphasized the need to recognise priorities developed within the Pacific, as apposed to priorities developed from elsewhere.
- Pacific Plant Protection Organisation meetings, along with a range of regional meetings, were seen as most important to promote plant health research partnerships in the Pacific. Attendees from New Zealand also ranked the New Zealand Plant Protection Conference highly.

1. Introduction

1.1 A description of the region / the discipline

The Pacific Islands, commonly referred to as the Pacific Island Country and Territories (PICTs), are a vast group of islands scattered across the Pacific Ocean, consisting of three main regions: Melanesia, Micronesia, and Polynesia. They cover a significant proportion of the globe. Despite their remote locations, these islands play a vital role in global biodiversity and are increasingly important in discussions on climate change.

Plant health is of paramount importance in the Pacific Islands, given their unique ecological makeup and reliance on agriculture for sustenance and economy. However, invasive pests, pathogens and weeds pose significant threats to native flora and agricultural productivity. Effective plant protection and biosecurity measures are essential for safeguarding these fragile ecosystems and ensuring food security for local communities. By fostering collaboration between governments, scientists, and farmers, the Pacific Islands can mitigate the risks posed by invasive species, preserving their natural heritage and sustaining livelihoods.

1.2 A description of the regional/discipline champion

The New Zealand Institute for Plant and Food Research Ltd¹¹, who hosted the workshop, is a Crown Research Institute (CRI) advancing knowledge and innovation in horticulture, agriculture and food science. With a focus on sustainability and productivity, Plant & Food Research conducts research to enhance crop yields, improve food quality and develop resilient agricultural practices. Additionally, its expertise extends to bioprotection and biosecurity, therefore working to safeguard New Zealand's unique ecosystem from invasive species. Plant & Food Research hosts the multi-partner research collaboration Better Border Biosecurity (<https://www.b3nz.org.nz/>).

1.3 The reasons underlying the interest for regional and global research coordination

Aotearoa New Zealand is a South Pacific nation with strong cultural, economic and political ties with other Pacific states and territories. New Zealand supports a peaceful, stable, prosperous and resilient Pacific. New Zealand's engagement in the Pacific is guided by the principles of understanding, friendship, mutual benefit, collective impact, and sustainability (MFAT 2025). New Zealand has a long-standing history of supporting PICTs in pest management and plant protection. Over the years, New Zealand has built a strong foundation of collaboration, including foundational studies on pest management and biodiversity through Department of Scientific and Industrial Research (DSIR) and the New Zealand Ministry for Primary Industries (MPI) (formerly the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MAF)), and more recently, through the CRIs and Universities, assisting PICTs to control plant pests having negative impacts on food security, economic development and biodiversity.

New Zealand has also played a critical role in assisting PICTs with biosecurity, through training in pest and disease identification and training essential for securing trade access and safeguarding agricultural economies.

Plant & Food Research considers that their science can create huge benefits for people in developing countries and that, as good global citizens, they should do everything they can to support others in building better lives. Plant & Food Research scientists work with government agencies, regional development agencies, and in-market partners to contribute to the United

¹¹ Plant & Food Research is in the process of merging with three other CRIs: AgResearch (<https://www.agresearch.co.nz/>), Scion (<https://www.scionresearch.com/home>) and Manaaki Whenua Landcare Research (<https://www.landcareresearch.co.nz/>). They will merge on 1 July 2025, to form the New Zealand Institute for Bioeconomy Science Limited (<https://www.bioeconomyscience.co.nz/>).

Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, creating opportunities to reduce poverty and improve lives.

1.4 A summary of the EUPHRESKO III project, the aims of the consultation, and the process used for the consultation

At the beginning of this project in January 2024, most Pacific Islands had little knowledge of Euphresco. This report is part of the activities of year 1 of the Euphresco III project to progress towards engagement and information exchange by the Pacific Islands Champion.

This report details a consultation workshop undertaken on 16 August 2024 in Auckland, New Zealand.

The process of the consultation

- A workshop called Plant Health/Biosecurity Partnerships in the Pacific. 16 August 2024, Mount Albert, Auckland
- Consisting of PowerPoint introductions by the Chair, questions posed to the group and answered on Mentimeter and breakout discussion groups
- Some questions generated a substantial number of responses. In these cases a concise summary of the raw data was generated by Copilot (<https://copilot.microsoft.com/>) and checked for accuracy by the author. Raw text can be found in Appendix 6.
- Held in conjunction with the New Zealand Plant Protection Conference 2024, 13–15 August 2024
- Organised by the Euphresco III Pacific Islands Champion, supported by the Plant Protection in International Development (PPID) (New Zealand) group
- Primary sponsor and funder was Euphresco III (<https://www.phrescoglobal.net/>), with additional support from Plant & Food Research, AgResearch, and PHARMAplus

The aims of the consultation

- Scope: Plant health/biosecurity research in the Pacific Islands
- Objectives: To promote partnerships and enhance research collaboration/co-ordination
 - To promote EUPHRESKO
- Outcomes: Collaborative actions to strengthen plant health/biosecurity research in the Pacific

Workshop attendees

- Pacific Islands: Attendees came from Fiji (n=7), Samoa (4), Tonga (1), Cook Islands (1), Vanuatu (1) and Papua New Guinea (1) (Figure 1). Attendees from Solomon Islands (2) and Niue (1) had to cancel at the last minute owing to logistical problems (Appendix 1).
- New Zealand: Approximately 30 attendees from New Zealand. These were all involved in international development/plant health in the Pacific to a significant degree (Appendix 1).
- Despite targeted invitations (Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade (DFAT), Australian Centre for International Agricultural Research (ACIAR)) there were no attendees from Australia or the USA (Guam, Hawaii). Employees and associates of Secretariat of the Pacific Regional Environment Programme (SPREP) could not attend, as they had their own workshop to attend.

Figure 1. Location of attendees at workshop.

Workshop attendees represented plant health professionals from the research community, government and industry (Table 1).

Table 1. Additional information on workshop attendees (Mentimeter data) (n = number of responses) (raw data).

Attendees	Are you mostly active in?	What organisms do you work on?
Pacific Islands	Research: 5 Government: 3 Education (teaching): 1 Education (student): 3 Other: 0	Invertebrates: 1 Pathogens/diseases: 3 Weeds: 2 More than one of the above: 5 Other: 1
New Zealand	Research: 21 Government: 4 Education (teaching): 0 Education (student): 3 Other: 1	Invertebrates: 9 Pathogens/diseases: 10 Weeds: 0 More than one of the above: 8 Other: 2

2. The agricultural crops

2.1 The list of agricultural crops that are important for the region

The major crops found in the Pacific are listed in Table 2. Those identified as priorities for plant health research include taro, kava, coconut, and various vegetables and fruits (Table 3). Pacific Island and New Zealand attendees were broadly in agreement, with perhaps a greater emphasis on fruit fly hosts and native plants/trees, possibly reflecting New Zealand-specific priorities.

Table 2. Important Plant Systems in the Pacific (from Taylor, McGregor & Dawson 2016)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Staple food crops <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sweet potato, banana, cassava, taro, cocoyam, swamp taro, giant taro, yams, coconuts, breadfruit, <i>Abelmoschus manihot</i> ▪ Export commodities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • copra, coconut oil, coffee, cocoa, palm oil, rubber, tea ▪ High value horticulture <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fruits, vegetables, stimulant, spices ▪ Native and plantation forests <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • tropical lowland rainforest, montane rainforest & cloud forest, tropical dry forest, woodland, swamp & riparian forest, coastal forest, mangrove forest, agroforest and plantation forest ▪ Subsistence agriculture/gardening <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • many plant species
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Table 3. Mentimeter question: Which crops or plants in the Pacific would you prioritise for plant health research (up to 5)? (n = number of responses) (raw data)

Attendees	Crops or plants identified
Pacific Islands	8 – Taro 7 – Kava 6 – Coconut 3 – Vegetables (not specified) Also: 3 – Eggplant, 3 – Yams, 2 – Tomato, 2 – Chilli, 1 – Cabbage, 1 – Solanum, 1 – Cucurbit 3 – Papaya 2 – Banana 1 – <i>Alyxia elliptica</i> , Breadfruit, Coffee, Ginger, Guava, Pineapple, Rice, Vanilla, Watermelon, Fruit fly-affected crops Also invasive weeds 1 – <i>Merremia</i> , <i>Wedelia</i>
New Zealand	7 – Coconut 7 – Taro 5 – Breadfruit 4 – Kava 4 – Banana 4 – Fruit fly-affected crops 3 – Native plants/trees 3 Also: Forests: 1 2 – Papaya 2 – Cocoa 2 – Weeds 1 – Cassava, Coffee, Citrus, Eggplant, Export crops, Fruit (unnamed), Noni, Oil palm, Pawpaw, <i>Sasalapa</i> , Tea

3. Important pests for the region

The invertebrate pests, pathogens/diseases and weeds that are of the greatest priority for research in the Pacific, identified by workshop attendees, included:

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- Invertebrates: Coconut rhinoceros beetle (CRB), fruit fly, various species of ants (invasive species incl. white-footed ants, little fire ants, red fire ant), thrips and fall army worm and the Giant African snail (only New Zealand attendees!)
- Pathogens: Crop-specific pathogens included kava dieback, taro leaf blight with non-crop specific pathogens Anthracnose, *Phytophthora* and viruses scoring highly. New Zealand responses included pathogens seen as priorities there, including *Xylella*, *Ceratocystis*, Kauri dieback, myrtle rust and Rapid 'Ōhi'a Death
- Weeds: African tulip and Merremia were the top-ranked weed priorities.

Attempts to list species of concern have met with limited success, the reason being that there are so many known species of concern. Trying to determine which Invasive Alien Species (IAS) pose the biggest threat to a given location, given incomplete knowledge, is an interesting exercise. When such lists of worst IAS are produced, they should be treated as working lists and not conclusive (USDN 2015).

Table 4. Mentimeter question: Which invertebrate pests, pathogens/diseases and weeds are of the greatest priority for research in the Pacific? (n = number of responses) (raw data)

Attendees	Invertebrates	Pathogens/diseases	Weeds
Pacific Islands	5 – Coconut rhinoceros beetle (CRB) 1 – Coconut pests 1 – Coconut stick insect 5 – Fruit fly 5 – Ants (invasive species incl. white-footed ants, little fire ants, red fire ant) 4 – Thrips 3 – Fall army worm 1 – Asian subterranean termite, Diamond back moth, Leaf miners, Mealybugs, Nematodes, Sap-sucking insects, Whiteflies, Vegetable pests	6 – Anthracnose 4 – Kava dieback 3 – <i>Phytophthora</i> 1 – <i>Phytophthora</i> in forestry 2 – Taro leaf blight 2 – Leaf blight 2 – Viruses 2 – Vegetable viruses 1 – Dieback 1 – Dieback in forestry 1 – Bacterial wilt, <i>Colletotrichum</i> , Bunchy top, <i>Phytoplasmas</i> , <i>Fusarium</i> spp., Mildews, Smuts, Wilt	5 – African tulip 1 – Tulip 4 – Merremia 2 – Mile-a-minute 1 – All weeds, All weeds on farms, <i>C. rotundus</i> , <i>Eleusine indica</i> , Giant reed, Honolulu rose, Nutsedge, Peltata, River weeds, Wedelia
New Zealand	12 – Fruit flies 7 – Coconut rhinoceros beetle (CRB) 4 Giant African snail 1 – Snails 4 – Ants (exotic, tramp ant, fire ant, little fire ants) 1 – Ambrosia beetle, Beetles, Brown marmorated stink bug, Fall army worm, Lepidoptera, Mealybug, Mite, Nematodes, Pod borers, Psyllids, Sap sucking insects, Scale insects, Taro beetle, Thrips, vector species	7 – <i>Phytophthora</i> 5 – <i>Xylella</i> (GWSS) 4 – Viruses 3 – <i>Ceratocystis</i> 2 – Anthracnose 2 – <i>Colletotrichum</i> 2 – Kauri dieback 2 – Myrtle rust 2 – Rapid 'Ōhi'a Death 2 – Forest pathogens 2 – Taro leaf blight 1 – Taro blight, 1 – Taro diseases, 1 – leaf blight 1 – Bacterial blight, Bunchy top, Citrus greening (HLB), Coconut disease, <i>Phytoplasmas</i> ,	6 – African tulip 5 – Merremia 3 – Vines (and crawlers) 3 – Forest weeds 2 – Taro vine and hybrids 2 – Singapore daisy 2 – Agricultural weeds 1 – Chilean needle grass, Fresh water weeds, Glyphosate resistant weeds, Mikania, Moluccan albizzia, Morning glory, Moth plants, Pathogen hosts, Pine, Sedges

	Vanilla pathogens	
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4. Key drivers for collaboration

Table 5. Mentimeter Question: What do you consider is the biggest issue facing plant health/biosecurity in the Pacific? (1 suggestion per person) (raw data)

Pacific Islands attendees

- Transboundary pests / invasive pests / invasive pests
- Diagnostics / diagnostic capabilities / diagnostic capabilities
- Lack of capacity and experience / human resource
- Resources / resources
- Limited understanding / knowledge about pests
- Adoption of technology
- Co-ordination

New Zealand attendees

- Incursions / invasive species / invasive pests / invasive pests / incursions / incursions / emerging diseases / pests
- Co-ordination / collaboration / co-ordination / co-ordination / isolation
- Funding / funding / funding / funding
- People / capability / capability development / education of growers
- Climate change / climate change / climate change
- Trade
- Fruit fly
- Multiple stressors
- Legislation
- Slow to react

Table 6. Mentimeter question: Suggest activities that could promote capability development for plant health research in the Pacific? (Data summarized by Copilot) (raw data can be found in Appendix 6)

Pacific Islands attendees

The responses suggest several key activities to enhance capability development for plant health research in the Pacific:

- **Education & Training** – Student exchange programmes, mentoring fellowships, internships, experiential work placements, and school conferences to provide learning opportunities and skill development.
- **Collaborative Research & Knowledge Sharing** – Establishing research collaborations, workshops, and training sessions to foster knowledge exchange among researchers and practitioners.
- **Institutional & Network Building** – Encouraging each country to establish its own plant health society, with annual conferences to provide a platform for discussion, networking, and engagement.
- **Diagnostics & Biological Control Development** – Advancing tools for diagnostics and reporting, alongside research on biological control methods such as *Trichoderma* to improve sustainable plant health management.
- **Community Engagement & Outreach** – Organizing outreach activities to raise awareness, share knowledge, and involve local communities in plant health initiatives.
- **Funding & Resource Support** – Seeking donations and financial backing for research projects, education programmes, and capacity-building activities.

The emphasis is on sustainable, locally driven initiatives that strengthen expertise, encourage collaboration, and create lasting impact.

New Zealand attendees

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The responses highlight a broad range of activities to support capability development for plant health research in the Pacific, with key themes including:

- **Knowledge Exchange & Collaboration** – Secondments, internships, student exchange programmes, joint research projects, and researcher exchanges between Pacific nations and partners in New Zealand and Australia.
- **Training & Education Initiatives** – Developing in-country training networks, phytosanitary treatment training, risk modelling training, biosecurity response workshops, scholarships for plant protection studies, and capacity-building programmes.
- **Workshops & Conferences** – Regular forums, Pacific-specific conferences, research exchanges, and workshops tailored to biosecurity officers, agricultural extension staff, and farmers.
- **Resource Development & Practical Tools** – Creating flip books, fact sheets, field and laboratory training materials, diagnostics tools, and surveillance programmes to improve knowledge accessibility.
- **Institutional & Community Engagement** – Establishing plant health societies in each country, fostering collaborations between universities and agricultural schools, and organizing outreach efforts such as research weeks and educational talks.
- **Sustainable Funding & Support** – Strengthening links with aid agencies like NZ Aid, MFAT co-investments, and initiatives like VSA and Australian Volunteers, to ensure long-term support for capability development.

The responses emphasize an holistic approach to training, research, and collaboration, ensuring that Pacific-led initiatives align with regional needs while leveraging partnerships for knowledge sharing and sustainable growth.

5. The research priorities

Table 7. Mentimeter question: Which areas are priorities for plant health/biosecurity research in the Pacific? (5 suggestions per person) (Data summarized by Copilot) (raw data can be found in Appendix 6)

Pacific Islands attendees

The responses highlight several key priority areas for plant health and biosecurity research in the Pacific:

- **Diagnostics & Surveillance** – Enhancing disease and pest diagnostics, pest surveys, and detection technologies, particularly at borders, to improve early identification and response.
- **Pest & Disease Management** – Developing pest control strategies, pesticide alternatives, postharvest treatments, and biocontrol solutions, including sterile insect technology and resistant weed management.
- **Capacity Building & Expertise Development** – Strengthening local expertise through training, capacity-building initiatives, and specialist knowledge in areas like *Thrips* management and biosecurity response.
- **Phytosanitary & Risk Assessment Research** – Advancing phytosanitary treatments, pest risk assessments, and economic impact evaluations to support informed decision-making.
- **Emerging Threats & Sustainable Solutions** – Addressing emerging pests, innovating biological control methods, and integrating value-adding approaches for long-term plant health sustainability.
- **Collaborative & Policy-Driven Approaches** – Encouraging integrated research efforts, border biosecurity enhancements, and partnerships to align plant health strategies with Pacific needs.

These priorities emphasize preparedness, innovation, and local capacity-building to strengthen plant health security in the Pacific.

New Zealand attendees

The responses highlight several priority areas for plant health and biosecurity research in the Pacific, emphasizing sustainable, locally driven approaches:

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- **Biocontrol & Pest Management** – Researching and developing biocontrol agents, pest management strategies, and alternatives to synthetic pesticides, including gene silencing (RNAi) methods.
 - **Surveillance & Diagnostics** – Strengthening border and farm-level diagnostics, surveillance systems, field detection technologies, and pest/disease risk assessments.
 - **Capacity Building & Training** – Enhancing training for farmers, biosecurity officers, and researchers through workshops, extension programmes, and specialized skill development.
 - **Phytosanitary & Postharvest Treatments** – Improving phytosanitary treatments for exported crops, postharvest management strategies, and food security initiatives.
 - **Collaborations & Indigenous Knowledge** – Encouraging international and indigenous partnerships to integrate traditional biocontrol practices with modern research methods.
 - **Infrastructure & Policy Support** – Investing in lab facilities, staff development, and legislative frameworks to support plant health and biosecurity efforts.
 - **Integrated Pest Management (IPM) & Systems Approach** – Promoting holistic, agroecological strategies for sustainable pest control across different crops and farming systems.
 - **Grower Engagement & Awareness** – Expanding plant health clinics, seed banking, farmer education, and tools to help locals identify pests and biosecurity risks.
 - **Research Networks & Funding** – Establishing cross-country research collaborations, securing investment for Pacific biosecurity initiatives, and linking efforts to existing aid programmes.
- These priorities emphasize a comprehensive, knowledge-sharing approach that balances scientific innovation with practical, community-driven solutions.

Table 8. Suggest a conference or relevant meeting that could be used to promote plant health research partnerships in the Pacific (n = number of responses) (raw data can be found in Appendix 6)

Pacific Islands attendees

- 5- Pacific Plant Protection Organisation (PPPO) meetings (incl. PPPO regional workshops)
- 4- Regional plant protection/health workshops/conferences
- 3- Regional Meeting of Pacific Heads of Agriculture and Forestry Services (PHOAFS), Regional Meeting of Pacific Ministers of Agriculture and Forestry Services (MOAFS)
- 2- Pacific Week of Agriculture and Forestry (PWOAF)
- 1- Fiji Institute of Agricultural Science (conference or symposium), New Zealand Plant Protection Society, Australasian Plant Pathology Conference, Australian Plant Protection Conference.

New Zealand attendees

- 7- New Zealand Plant Protection Society (NZPPS)
- 7- Pest specific conference / workshop clinics (online) e.g. fruit fly, FAW
- 4- Pacific Plant Protection Organisation (PPPO)
- 3 - International Congress on Biological Invasions (ICBI)
- 2- Regional Meeting of Pacific Heads of Agriculture and Forestry Services (PHOAFS)
- 2 - Pacific Forum regional meeting - side session
- 2- International Congress on Plant Pathology (ICPP) 2028
- 2 - Crawford Fund Conference
- 2- International Plant Protection Convention 2027 (IPPC)
- 2- Australasian Plant Pathology Society (APPS)
- 2- Australian Centre for International Agricultural Research (ACIAR) conference
- 1- New conference/society for pacific plant health, International Union of Forest Research Organizations (Pacific forestry group) (IUFRO), Plant Biosecurity Research Initiative (PBRI), International Plant Protection Convention 2027 (IPPC), Asia Pacific conferences, NZ / Aus conferences, Entomological Society Conference, International Association for the Plant Protection Science, NZ Institute Agriculture and Horticulture Science (NZIAHS), Australian Centre for International Agricultural Research (ACIAR) conference, Council of Australasian Weed Societies (CAWS), Pacific Week of Agriculture and Forestry (PWAf), US conferences, Postharvest 2024, NZ Biosecurity Institute NETS

Table 9. Mentimeter question: If there was one thing you could recommend to promote plant health partnerships in the Pacific, what would it be?

Pacific Islands attendees

Raw data

- Maintain close relationships with attendees at this workshop, and build/expand on these. Contribute knowledge, time and skills to help develop workable, sustainable solutions.
- Undertake specific need analysis for the region and prioritise the key one
- Find expertise needed in country context
- A shared platform to discuss issues.
- Better collaboration between the Pacific Island countries.
- Have networks of plant pathologists, entomologists, etc. that we in the Pacific can contact when we need assistance, technical, student supervisory, etc.
- Build capacity of agriculture ground staff in Pacific Islands
- Capacity and infrastructure development

New Zealand attendees

Copilot generated summary

The responses highlight several key themes for promoting plant health partnerships in the Pacific:

- **Pacific-Led Collaboration** – Emphasizing genuine partnerships driven by Pacific priorities, rather than external influence, ensuring local leadership and community ownership.
- **Strengthening Communication & Networks** – Establishing open dialogue, creating networks of key personnel across countries, and fostering relationships through workshops, conferences, and online platforms.
- **Capacity Building & Research Development** – Investing in training for young researchers, organizing country-specific workshops, conducting pest and disease surveys, and supporting collaborative research efforts.
- **Funding & Resource Allocation** – Securing financial support for biosecurity surveillance, capacity development, and regional initiatives like a Pacific branch of NZPPS or a dedicated committee for plant health coordination.
- **Listening & Cultural Understanding** – Encouraging Pacific voices to be heard, ensuring external partners listen rather than dictate, and taking time to build trust and understanding.
- **On-the-Ground Engagement** – Placing experts in Pacific Island countries for extended periods, involving farmers directly in solutions, and ensuring practical, self-sustaining improvements.

Together, these recommendations reflect a strong push for inclusivity, long-term commitment, and meaningful investment in plant health partnerships in the Pacific.

Table 10. Mentimeter question: What did you know about EUPHRESKO before these meetings? (raw data)

	Nothing	A little	Between a little – a lot	A lot
Pacific Islands	8	3	0	0
New Zealand	13	13	3	1

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Appendix 1. Notes from breakout group 1 collated by Karyn Froud – Biosecurity

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Appendix 2. Notes from breakout group 2 collated by Sulav Palau and Trevor Jackson – Pest Management

Title: Sustainable management of insect pests in the Pacific, integrating climate-sensitive approaches and indigenous knowledge

Gaps

- Lack of alternatives to chemical pesticides
- Lack of coordination within and among local ministries
- Lack of rapid response tools and resources against new invasive pests
- Lack of farmers' involvement in design and implementation of research projects
- Failure to meet UN Sustainable Development Goals by Pacific communities

Objectives

- Improve livelihood and family welfare using sustainable agriculture approaches
- Integrate local knowledge and climate change adaptation agronomic practices
- Develop integrated plant-protection packages with a pathway to adoption through a participatory research approach
- Develop a cohort of farmers (local champion or leader farmers) who are able to adopt sustainable practices and adapt to the variabilities of climate change

Outcomes

- A local team capable of leading the way to adaptation and adoption of sustainable plant protection practices
- A research and development model that can be optimized and replicated based on local conditions
- Outreach materials in local languages, integrating cultures and best practices

Research collaborators

Local extension officers, motivators

Research team

Local universities, research extension offices, ministries, New Zealand/Australian experts

Milestones

- I.D. of local partners/stakeholders
- Development of fact sheets on pests and management practices
- Behavioural change in farmers
- Better income and health
- Local champions

Potential funders

MFAT, DFAT, ACIAR, EU

Appendix 3. Notes from breakout group 3 collated by Lisa Jamieson – Market Access

Title: Improving Market Access (MA) for Pacific Island Nations (IMAPIN)

Reflect in short-term and long-term views

Pacific view might be shorter term

Forward or present

Reactive vs active

Often work in two areas:

1. Want to gain new MA
2. Have MA & want to sustain it

Maintaining sustainability of what the PIs have

Research data to support MA request

Host susceptibility

What pests are present?

Link to quarantine pests of concern

Link to solution to mitigate

Fiji requires additional research for MA to the USA for papaya – a project

Fruit fly heat treatment update for specific species in a country (currently regional). Lead to less severe treatment for most PIs

Samoa HTFA problems, too expensive to fix – dependent on single supplier

Taro – removal + heat treatment – roll out to other PIs

Survey of pests

Residues

Cocoa Samoa – desktop reviews not confined by survey

All MA research needs to have country involved

Much research outdated and/or recommendations without proof. Become a barrier for exports e.g. SROS & MAF were not involved

MPI could fund expanding surveillance for PRA. Every 3–5 years should be survey

Disease ID via AI

Biosecurity AI training

Combine Farmer and Plant Health

Irradiation good option

Mobile X-ray facility

Long term efficacy

Heat treatment – use solar panels

Added value/processing

Funders: PHAMA Plus (DFAT/MFAT), MAF, IAEA, Euphresco, PPPO

Appendix 4. Notes from breakout group 4 – Indigenous Knowledge

No notes taken

Appendix 5. Attendees

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*Unable to attend due to logistical problems

New Zealand

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Appendix 6. Raw text from Mentimeter questions

Table 6. Mentimeter question: Suggest activities that could promote capability development for plant health research in the Pacific?

Pacific Islands attendees

Student exchange programmes, mentoring fellowships, experiential work placements
Research collaborative
Attachments, exchange, internships
School conferences
Mentoring
Conferences and workshops/training sessions
Exchange programmes
Each country to have their own plant health society (similar to NZPPS) and have conferences yearly in cheap sustainable way so that everyone in plant health can attend or present/become members
Diagnostics tools and reporting of results
Development of biological control methods like *Trichoderma*
Community outreach
Exchange programmes
Donations
Projects
More research on the use of biological controls

New Zealand attendees

Exchange secondments (in both directions) to build a sustainable relationship and partnership
Develop in country training networks
Flip books, fact sheets, training workshops both field and laboratory, molecular
Plant Health Surveillance in the region
Phytosanitary treatment development training
Joint research, ECR collaboration throughout the regions, internships
Workshops in each country specific to a need to train/support Biosecurity and Ag Extension officers in their support of farmers
A forum that promotes the knowledge of more mature researchers not exposed to such forums previously
Mentor programmes between researchers. Awareness of what capabilities are needed and where they are available from. Novel capabilities, innovation due to novel problems
Including the biosecurity importance in academic books, organisations of research weeks, and showcase different approaches
Workshops associated with Pacific Ag week
Workshops, research exchanges, Pacific-specific conferences
Short scholarships to New Zealand/Australia. Need to make sure we leave staff behind in-country though!
Surveillance, Field diagnostics
A platform to connect young Pacific researchers with those from New Zealand/Australia
Workshops
Practical training in-country for local extension staff by tropically experienced experts
NZ Aid
Multidisciplinary representatives from New Zealand/Australia meeting with Pacific community colleagues, but in a Pacific location
Collaboration with universities/agricultural schools
Collaboration between the Pacific and New Zealand institute. Short-term exchange, both students and staff
Scholarships for students to specialise in plant protection undergraduate and postgraduate
Students from New Zealand going to Pacific universities
Talks at universities

Mentoring programmes
Researchers exchange
Biosecurity response training that is Pacific-focused
Risk modelling training
Collaborative research
Attachments, secondments
NZ Universities linking with Pacific needs and students: specific scholarships and projects
ACIAR-MFAT co-investments
Secondments both ways
Sandwich scholarship programmes
Student exchange programmes
Pacific Biosecurity conference
Capacity building training
VSA and Australian Volunteers
Linking MFAT Activities to MFAT scholarships

Table 7. Mentimeter question: Which areas are priorities for plant health/biosecurity research in the Pacific? (5 suggestions per person)

Pacific Islands attendees

Preparedness
diagnostics, disease diagnostics, pest diagnosis
Surveillance
Pest management,
Pesticide alternatives,
Biocontrol, biocontrol agents
Phyto research,
Pest risk assessments
Capacity building in these areas, capacity building,
Phytosanitary treatments
Detection technology – border
Biocontrols, biological control
Emerging pests
Resistant weeds (chemical)
More research on PHC and Biosecurity
Postharvest treatments
Capacity building
Biocontrol agents
Pest and disease control options on farms
IRA
Pest risk assessment in terms of potential economical loss
Pest and disease surveys
Expertise e.g., *Thrips* experts
Sterile Insect Technology
Border Biosecurity
Capacity Building
Value-adding
Pesticide advice and expertise
Pesticide alternatives

New Zealand attendees

Biocontrols
Research and development
Phytosanitary treatments

International collaborations
Indigenous collaborations
Food hubs
Staff capacity, infrastructure and equipment to support work, working labs, legislation to support
Capacity building
Training and capability for frontline roles
Biocontrol selection, capacity building, remote assessments
Systems approach
Indigenous knowledge on biocontrol of pests
Alternatives to synthetic chemicals
Systems approaches
Diagnostics at the border and in farm
Training
Systems approach
Exported crops
Decision support
IPM
Training materials, identification building, seed banking, creating awareness and advertisement
surveillance, and pest/disease/weed management
Field detection technology
Pest management using gene silencing/RNAi
Training
Capacity building, training
Training
Tools for helping locals to identify infestations and incursions
Diagnostics/Surveillance
Increase grower knowledge
Pest
Doing more with fewer inputs (water; chemical inputs etc.)
Phytosanitary treatments
Capability and capacity building
Sterile Insect Technology
Train farmers in new technology
Risk assessment
Surveillance
Capability building on molecular pest management
Suitable biocontrols
Preservation of taonga and associated korero
Agroecological management approach
Thrips
Expanding plant health clinics
Extension training
IPM across crops
Research network across countries

Table 8. Mentimeter question: If there was one thing you could recommend to promote plant health partnerships in the Pacific, what would it be?

Pacific Islands attendees

Maintain close relationships with attendees at this workshop, and build/expand on these
Contribute knowledge, time and skills to help develop workable, sustainable solutions
Undertake specific need analysis for the region and prioritise the key one
Find expertise needed in country context

A shared platform to discuss issues
Better collaboration between the Pacific Island countries
Have networks of Plant Pathologists, Entomologists, etc. that we in the Pacific can contact when we need assistance, technical, student supervisory, etc.
Build capacity of agriculture ground staff in Pacific Islands
Capacity and infrastructure development

New Zealand attendees

Hold side session at next NZPPS meeting to advance planning and coordination of one or two regional priorities in plant bioprotection
Build genuine partnerships that are Pacific-led
Open dialogue ... create a network of key personnel of regulators, researchers, etc. from each country and spend time developing relationships
Open communication, but New Zealand/Australia need to listen and not talk to the Pacific people.
Find money to enable key people in the Pacific to increase capacity and capability in key areas for the Pacific
Find money for Regional Biosecurity Surveillance and capacity development
Collaborative research
Survey of pests & diseases
Pacific organiser committee for NZPP forum held in Pacific
Capacity building
Focus on finding solutions at farmer level that create value well above the cost of the solutions, therefore self-funding further future improvements
Invest time in the relationships
Collaboration within the Pacific community
Let the Pacific drive it, based on their priorities, rather than us
Obtain funding to start a Pacific branch of NZPPS
To listen to the people
Things take time. Buy in can't be rushed or tokenistic
Listen to Pacific needs
Take the lead, like ASEAN FAW action plan
Research exchanges
Face-to-face workshops
Chat group to facilitate communication and friendships
Support conference in May next year for the PAAF
Develop capacity of ten young researchers in biosecurity/pest management from every PICTs
Organise in-country workshops to understand needs
Share what you know
Base international tropical experts in PIC countries for extended periods
Ask the growers what's needed and work upwards from there
Understand the culture
Establish a network with appointed leads who will meet regularly online and share information about the state of plant health in our respective regions
Create network for communication and coordination

Appendix 7. Visit to Secretariat of the Pacific Regional Environment Programme (SPREP)

Apia, Samoa. 4–7 June 2024

1. General information

1.1. Organisation/institution

- Secretariat of the Pacific Regional Environment Programme (SPREP)

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-01 under grant agreement No 101130467

- 21 Pacific Island Countries and Territories (PICTs) plus 5 'metros'

1.2. Person completing the survey

- David Teulon (on behalf of David Moverley)
- David.Teulon@plantandfood.co.nz (davidm@sprep.org)
- Euphresco III Pacific Champion (SPREP Invasive Species Advisor)

2. Identify a maximum of 5 key plant health issues or related practical problems your organization/ institution/region is facing

- Tropical islands are also uniquely vulnerable to global threats, such as climate change and invasive species.
- Invasive species are considered the most significant drivers of population declines and species extinctions in island ecosystems.
- Limited human, material, and financial resources
- Interdependence of island communities – thus co-ordination
- Too many targets (esp. weeds), too widespread to be managed
- Climate change is likely to increase the vulnerability of island ecosystems to new invasions and/or increase the chances of existing non-native (or even native) species becoming invasive
- Subsistence farming
- Reliance on donors and expertise from metros (i.e. Australia, NZ, US, UK, France)

3. Identify a maximum of 5 priorities your organisation/institution would like to work on in the next 5–10 years

PRIMSS programmes (priorities are reflected in the main SPREP programmes) (<https://www.sprep.org/invasive-species-management-in-the-pacific/prismss>)

- Border (internal or international) biosecurity (Protect our Islands)
- Eradication of rats (Predator Free Pacific)
- War on weeds – eradication of weeds
- Natural enemies/natural solutions – biocontrol of weeds
- Resilient ecosystems/resilient communities – special sites

4. Identify a maximum of 5 priorities you think that should be addressed in your country/region/ worldwide in the next 5–10 years to face plant health issues or related practical problems

Indicate the scale of each priority (country, region or worldwide)

- Generating Support and Changed Behaviour — Raising awareness of and concern about the impacts of invasive species on biodiversity, the economy, livelihoods, human health, and socio-cultural values, and mobilising support for action to manage and reduce impacts. National/Regional
- Building Capacity — Developing institutions, skills, infrastructure, technical support, information management, linkages, networks, and exchanges required to effectively manage invasive species and biosecurity. National/Regional

- Legislation, Regulation, Policy, and Protocols — Ensuring that appropriate legislation, regulations, policies, protocols, and procedures are in place and operating, to underpin the effective management of invasive species. National/Regional

5. Which agricultural crops are important to study for your organization/institution?

- None as such, but SPREP recognises the importance of whole of system approaches ...
- Invasive plants and animals can completely alter ecosystems and, consequently, the cultural and ecosystem services they provide.

6. What are your needs, if any, in terms of capacity building (e.g. transfer of processes, competences, methods, resources)?

Small island states have limited human, material, and financial resources.

7. Which pests do you consider a regional priority? (Provide a maximum of 5 pests, with their Latin name and the factor that drives the priority (economy, trade, strategy, policy ...))

- *Phellinus noxius*, fungus that causes the disease brown root rot in trees
- Giant African Snail, *Achatina fulica*
- Rats
- Various weeds

8. Which pests do you consider a global priority? (Provide a maximum of 5 pests, with their Latin name)

No opinion (not our focus)

9. Which research areas do you think need to be addressed/developed to support future work on plant health issues or related practical problems (see examples below)

See #3 above

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EUPHRESKO III

Ref: 42209

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June 2025

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6 REPORT OF THE CONSULTATIONS FOR CENTRAL ASIA

1. Introduction

1.1 Description of the region

Central Asia is a large natural geographical region in the central part of the Eurasian continent, stretching from the shores of the Caspian Sea in the west to the border with China in the east, from the West Siberian Plain in the north, to the Nishapur, Safedkoh and Hindu Kush mountains in the south. It is located inland, 4 thousand km from the Atlantic Ocean, 2.5 thousand km from the Arctic Ocean, 5.5 thousand km from the Pacific Ocean and about 1 thousand km from the Indian Ocean, and consists of a closed basin whose waters cannot reach the oceans.

Agriculture in Central Asia provides a brief regional overview of agriculture in the five contiguous states of former Soviet Central Asia – Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan. Two other countries that are sometimes classified as Central Asian – Afghanistan and Mongolia – are not included in this overview because of their substantially different background.

The five Central Asian countries are highly agrarian, with 60% of the population living in rural areas and agriculture accounting for over 45% of total number of employed and nearly 25% of GDP on average. Kazakhstan, with its strong energy sector, is less agrarian than the average Central Asian country, with agriculture accounting for only 8% of GDP (but still 33% of total employment).

Agricultural land in Central Asia is mostly desert and mountain pastures. Arable land suitable for crop production is around 20% of total agricultural land. In Russia, on the other hand, arable land is 60%-80% of agricultural land. As a result, pasture-based livestock production is more prominent in Central Asia than in the core CIS countries.

By far the two most significant crops in Central Asia are cotton and wheat. Only Kazakhstan does not cultivate significant amounts of cotton. Central Asia is largely desert, and cotton production strongly relies on irrigation. More than 80% of arable land in Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan is irrigated, and only Kazakhstan, with its wheat-based crop production, irrigates merely 7% of its arable land. The emphasis on intensive cotton cultivation in the Amudarya and Syrdarya basin countries has played a major role in the drying and polluting of the Aral Sea because of the large amounts of water and fertilizer used in cotton cultivation. Cotton mono-culture during the Soviet period exhausted the soil and led to serious plant diseases, which adversely affect cotton yields to this date.

The cultivation of wheat has also contributed to environmental issues, starting with the Virgin Lands Campaign during the Soviet era. Because the precautionary measures taken to preserve soil quality when the campaign began were insufficient, the soil eroded and its nutrients became degraded by excessive mono-crop cultivation. This history continues to affect grain production today, particularly in Kazakhstan.

Aside from these two primary crops, the region produces a wide variety of products which include barley, corn, flax, grapes, potatoes, rice, sugar beets, sunflowers, tobacco, apricots,

pears, plums, apples, cherries, pomegranates, melons, dates, figs, sesame, pistachios, and nuts.

Animal husbandry constitutes a large part of Central Asian agriculture. Cattle, sheep, and poultry are the main animal species in agriculture, and breeding racehorses is the pride of Turkmenistan. Some famous local breeds include the Karakul sheep and the Akhal-Teke horse. Some regions also cultivate mulberry trees and breed silkworms.

Kazakhstan, jointly with USAID and UNDP, launched a program aimed at introducing digital technologies in weather forecasting. This initiative is especially important for Kazakhstan, the world's seventh-largest exporter of wheat, where farmers depend on reliable weather data for wheat production.

1.2 Description of the regional champion

The Agency of Plant Protection and Quarantine of the Republic of Uzbekistan (KHA) is the champion for Central Asia. It emerges as a pivotal player in safeguarding Uzbekistan's agricultural sector and natural environment. By proactively preventing the introduction and proliferation of pests and diseases, which pose substantial threats to crops, ecosystems and economic well-being, KHA fulfills a vital mandate. Among its primary responsibilities, the agency prioritizes enhancing the forecasting systems within plant quarantine and protection. Additionally, it focuses on identifying and implementing effective methods to combat pests while preventing the introduction and dissemination of harmful organisms that could inflict economic damage within the republic's borders. Furthermore, KHA demonstrates a commitment to fostering international collaboration in plant quarantine and protection, as well as agrochemistry. This includes the adoption of contemporary technologies and methodologies to enhance service delivery and agricultural sustainability.

1.3 Reasons underlying the interest for regional and global research coordination

In central Asia, Phytosanitary policies, regulations and technical recommendations are often determined at a regional level, while the supporting research is predominantly funded and conducted at the national level. Coordinating these national activities is essential to minimizing the impact of plant pests on the economy, the environment, and public health—both within individual countries and on a broader European and international scale.

The success of the Euphresco self-sustained network as a platform for coordinating European phytosanitary research demonstrates the value of such collaborative efforts. This success has paved the way for discussions about developing initiatives to meet the needs of other regions worldwide and to enhance global coordination of phytosanitary research.

1.4 Summary of the EUPHRESKO III project, the aims of the consultation, and the process used for the consultation

The aim of the EUPHRESKO III project is to enhance national and regional phytosanitary research coordination and to set the foundations for global phytosanitary research coordination. This will be achieved by building on the foundations developed by the Euphresco self-sustained network and explore fit-for-purpose activities. The objectives of the project are:

- Develop a global strategic agenda on medium-term (5-10 years) phytosanitary research priorities. The agenda will guide phytosanitary research programming activities of the project partners and support them to address national, regional and global challenges through synergies between regions/continents of the world

- Organize joint calls on common research priorities to support and enhance international collaboration through the commissioning and implementation of research projects which meet the needs of the research funders and policy makers and have significant positive outcomes for Plant Health
- Develop and test models for the governance, the structure and the operations of a global network for phytosanitary research coordination. A roadmap will be established to guide the development of a global network for phytosanitary research coordination
- Engage with stakeholders such as policy makers, research funders, academia, industry (agri-food, biotech, diagnostic, seed industry), farmers and foresters and to foster knowledge exchange, involvement in the project activities, co-development, innovation, dissemination and adoption of outputs

The EUPHRESKO III project is structured across 9 different world regions: Africa, Australia, Caribbean-Central America & South America, Central Asia, Europe-North, Europe-South & Mediterranean, North America, Pacific Islands and South-East Asia. The aim is to implement various activities in the countries within these regions, gradually elevating the knowledge gathered or produced at the national level to a regional scale, and ultimately to a global perspective.

In summary, the EUPHRESKO III consortium will contribute to the coordination of national, regional and global phytosanitary research programmes and will allow a better alignment of the research funding and policy making activities in the participating countries. Key factors for successful alignment of national research programmes include: the combination of (i) bottom-up alignment actions that involve research stakeholders and (ii) top-down alignment actions that involve research funding organizations and building mutual trust and consensus at all levels through regular consultations and dialogue. In line with these recommendations, consultations of stakeholders that operate in Plant Health at national and regional level have been organized in the framework of EUPHRESKO III, following the procedure below:

In Central Asia, the consultation process began in early 2024 with the identification of stakeholders (farmers and foresters, etc.) in different countries. A stakeholder survey was distributed during the spring and approximately 200 stakeholders were invited to provide their views on key issues, needs and priorities in plant health. Approximately 80 responses were

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-01 under grant agreement No 101130467

received. Approximately 80 proposals were received from Uzbekistan, Russia, Kazakhstan, and Kyrgyzstan.

The collected data were then analyzed for the biological protection of plants. Three dictionaries were used to classify the survey responses: (1) Biosecurity Thesaurus, (2) Priority Pest Dictionary, and (3) Commodity Dictionary. The results from this analysis are presented in approx.

2 The agricultural crops

9. List of agricultural crops that are important for the region and the reasons (propose to limit to 10)

The following agricultural crops were identified as important for Central Asia:

- Cotton (*Gossypium*)
 - It is the most widely grown crop
 - It produces export-oriented products such as clothing, oil, and soap.
 - It forms the main part of the economy in some countries
- Potatoes (*Solanum tuberosum*)
 - Cultivated as a staple food crop throughout Asia
 - High yields per hectare make it a major food source for rural and urban populations
 - Used in a variety of ways, from fresh consumption to industrial processing (e.g. starch, chips, fries)
- Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*)
 - A cornerstone of Central Asian diets, used for bread, pasta and other staples
 - Central Asia is a leading global exporter of wheat, supporting international trade
 - Provides feed for livestock and raw material for beer and whiskey industries
 - Adaptable to varied climates, making it a primary crop across much of Central Asia
- Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*)
 - Essential for Central Asia diets, fresh and processed (sauces, canned products)
 - High economic value, grown intensively in countries like other country, Kazakhstan and the Uzbekistan.
 - Supports greenhouse agriculture and advanced farming techniques, such as hydroponics
- Maize (*Zea mays*)
 - Critical as a feed crop for Central Asia's extensive livestock industry
 - A growing bioenergy source for ethanol and biogas, supporting renewable energy goals
 - Provides food products like cornmeal and corn oil
 - Fits well into crop rotation systems, enhancing soil health
- Vegetables
 - Includes a wide array of crops (e.g., carrots, cabbage, onions) essential for nutrition and health
 - Contributes to regional economies and employment in greenhouse and open-field agriculture
 - Meets the increasing consumer demand for fresh, locally produced foods

- Berries
 - Includes crops like strawberries, raspberries and blueberries, which are popular for fresh and processed products
 - High market demand due to increasing awareness of their health benefits
 - Supports rural development and agri-tourism, especially in small-scale farming systems
- **Important pests for the region**
 1. List of pests for which collaboration within the region is sought, including some information on this pest like geographical distribution / host range / impact

Based on the survey responses and the Common Pest Priority Clusters map analysis the following pests have been identified as priority for Central Asia:

Insects

- *Helicoverpa armigera* (Cotton bollworm)
 - Geographical Distribution: Asia, southern Europe and Africa.
 - Host range: wide, including cotton, tomato and maize
 - Impact: Damages plants at various stages, This pest is considered o
 - mnivorous and causes significant crop losses
- *Agrotis segetum*
 - o Geographic distribution: Asia, Southern Europe and Africa.
 - o Host range: Wide, including cotton, tomato and maize
 - o Impact: Damages plants at the seedling stage, This pest
 - causes significant yield losses
- *Tuta absoluta* (Tomato leaf miner)
 - Geographical Distribution: South America, Europe, Africa, and Asia
 - Host Range: tomato and related solanaceous crops
 - Impact: causes severe losses in tomato production; difficult to control due to rapid reproduction and resistance development

Bacteria

- *Clavibacter sepedonicus*
 - Geographical Distribution: temperate regions worldwide
 - Host Range: potatoes
 - Impact: causes ring rot, leading to severe economic losses in potato production
- *Erwinia amylovora* (Fire blight)
 - Geographical Distribution: North America, Europe, the Middle East, and parts of Asia
 - Host Range: pome fruits like apples, pears, and quince
 - Impact: destroys blossoms, shoots, and branches, severely impacting orchard productivity and profitability
- *Xylella fastidiosa*
 - Geographical Distribution: Americas, Europe, and Asia
 - Host Range: wide host range including olives, grapevines, citrus, and almonds

- Impact: causes diseases like olive quick decline and Pierce's disease in grapevines, leading to significant crop losses

Fungi

- *Fusarium oxisporium*
 - Geographical Distribution: Central Asia
 - Host Range: over 200 plant species, including avocado, sycamore, and castor bean
 - Impact: causes *Fusarium oxisporium* damage to cotton crops and vegetables plants.
- *Fusarium* spp.
 - Geographical Distribution: worldwide
 - Host Range: broad host range including cereals, vegetables, and ornamentals
 - Impact: causes wilt, root rot, and blight, resulting in yield and quality losses in many crops

At this stage, it is premature to complete this section, as the specific pests to be addressed in the topics proposed by the Network Office after the consultation for Central Asia will be determined later in the Euphresco call process.

4. Key drivers for collaboration

4.1 Main Plant Health issues or related practical problems of the farmers and foresters in the region

Country	Plant Health issues or related practical problems
Uzbekistan	Issue 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Organisms that are QP or RNQP and therefore have major consequences if found on the farm Issue 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Organisms problematic for export to third countries Issue 3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Phytophthora ivfestans</i>, <i>Erwinia amylovora</i>, <i>Bemisia tabaci</i>, (Asian) longhorn beetle, etc.
Russia	Issue 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Biological warfare agents Issue 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Environmental conditions and plant stress
Khazakistan	Issue 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Diseases and pests Issue 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Biological diversity Issue 3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Soil quality Issue 4 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Economic consequences of plant health problems
Khirgizistan	Issue 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mainly sucking pests ▪ aphids ▪ thrips Issue 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Predators include the tomato moth (<i>Tuta absoluta</i>), the cherry slime fly (<i>Caliroa cerasi</i>)

- cherry fruit fly (*Rhagoletis cerasi*)

4.2 The needs in terms of capacity building

Country	Needs in terms of capacity building
Uzbekistan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increased resources ▪ Methods ▪ Processes ▪ Biological control & resistance breeding ▪ Comparable guidelines for the use of PPPs
Russia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increased resources ▪ People, formation, resumed information in the mother tongue, photos and information on the spread stat of new pathogens ▪ Independent advisory services, inclusion of non-chemical solutions in the curriculum of farming schools ▪ Centralization of knowledge in the sector that can also be deployed in a guided manner ▪ Resources that allow field work ▪ Fast determination & detection methods ▪ Increase in potato production to meet need for the potato industry ▪ Talent ▪ Knowledge (competences) ▪ Sufficient employees (labor) ▪ Specific funding for research projects and the possibility of hiring researchers in these areas ▪ Expansion of resources and personnel to implement and expand the monitoring programme, training and equipment (in particular appropriate IT tools) ▪ Increased standardization of methods certifying plant reproductive material ▪ Training for researchers on how to search for practical applications of research results
Khazakistan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increased resources ▪ Raising awareness of travelling and international trade ▪ Sharing experience between member states regarding pests that are not yet present in Estonia ▪ Ensuring sustainable resources for research ▪ Better rooms for growing plants and stability in the acquisition of funds for researchers and technicians ▪ Stay up to date with the latest research, methods and solutions in plant health. ▪ Collaboration with other experts and practitioners to share knowledge and experience and best practices in solving problems
Khirgizistan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Increased resources ▪ Bioinformatics skills, data science and artificial intelligence ▪ Access to biological reference material ▪ Maintaining skills in traditional taxonomy over the long term ▪ Access to quick barcoding methods ▪ How to manage the epidemiology (including vectorization) of a new emerging or reemerging pest ▪ Experimentation, evaluation of alternative phytosanitary products, phytodiagnostic, supporting innovation, supporting competitiveness of agricultural branches

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Exchanges with other countries on technical issues ▪ High needs for research and development of alternatives plus regulatory harmonization of PPP uses ▪ Improve EU and worldwide collaborations ▪ Information and data sharing to develop alternatives faster in minor crops ▪ Information and shared knowledge on major and emerging pests ▪ Data science and modelling for risk assessment and impacts of climatic change ▪ Innovative detection tools, including metagenomics and characterization of microbial diversity ▪ Indicators for plant health and soil fertility ▪ Transfer of processes, methods, and resources from abroad ▪ Harmonization on definition and naming of uses ▪ Promote public & private research projects ▪ Funding to perform research with other research institutes in the world ▪ Collaboration with research institutes to test protocols/methods with growers
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4.3 The medium-term research (5-10 years) priorities identified through the top-down approach (stakeholders' survey input from decision makers/policy makers/research funders)

Country	Medium-term (5-10 years) research priorities
Uzbekistan	Institutional priorities
	Priority 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Coordination on main issues ▪ Soil protection ▪ Healthy propagating material for plant production in professional horticulture
	Priority 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Development of appropriate legal framework ▪ Plant protection systems ▪ Safe testing methods for scions and rootstocks in nurseries and other propagating material in plant production
	Priority 3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Funding of research activities ▪ Resistance management ▪ Information for inspectors and professional operators about pests and possible confusion with other causes
	Priority 4 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Detecting diseases, pests and competitors through "Agrokumakchi" programm ▪ Combination of traps for different pests on the same locations to optimize working hours
	Priority 5 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Information about good practice for eradication and containment of pests ▪ Research and exchange of experience on specific pests among Central Asian member states
Russia	Institutional priorities
	Priority 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <input type="checkbox"/> Strengthening phytosanitary risk analysis control, more training on identifying new diseases and pests

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <input type="checkbox"/> Preventing the introduction of pests through qualitative testing of plant samples ▪ <input type="checkbox"/> Climate-soil water relationship ▪ <input type="checkbox"/> Biodiversity and climate ▪ <input type="checkbox"/> Development of a One Health concept (biodiversity part) ▪ <input type="checkbox"/> Availability of detailed information on the location of risk areas for each quarantine pest ▪ <input type="checkbox"/> Awareness-visibility Plant Health (e.g. within a single health framework) ▪ <input type="checkbox"/> Diagnostics <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <input type="checkbox"/> Retraining of phytosanitary specialists ▪ <input type="checkbox"/> Training in rapid pest detection and identification methods ▪ <input type="checkbox"/> Methodology for assessing the health status of horticultural and vegetable crops ▪ <input type="checkbox"/> Decision-making on criteria/regulation (emission horizon scanning, risk assessment) ▪ <input type="checkbox"/> Plant health (emerging) issues in supporting the sector
Khazakistan	<p>Institutional priorities</p> <p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Maintaining high levels of control in the face of reduced joint funding <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Strengthening phytosanitary border control methods and processes; raising awareness of travel and international trade <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Improving the effectiveness of integrated pest management, especially in cereals, potatoes and oilseed rape; better control measures for clubroot disease <p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Innovations: development of new diagnostic tools and control measures for selected pests
Khirgizistan	<p>Institutional priorities</p> <p>Priority 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Development of biocontrol <input type="checkbox"/> Impact of climate change <input type="checkbox"/> Combined strategy for plant protection instead of relying solely on chemical products. This strategy is based on four pillars: Bio-solutions (Biopesticides + Bio-stimulants) - Biotechnologies - Digital agriculture and plant protection products <p>Priority 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Surveillance and prevention of harmful pests, including innovative monitoring, to maintain the health of seed plots and farms <p>Priority 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Epidemiology and risk assessment for major pests (pathogen development conditions, identification of reservoirs, etc.). <input type="checkbox"/> Use/management of plant immunity <p>Priority 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Innovative, reliable and cost-effective tools for the diagnosis, detection or quantification of pests, in particular for certification (viruses, bacteria, nematodes, etc.). <input type="checkbox"/> Developing agroecology

4.4 Outcome of the consultation: common research priorities for the region (agreed upon after having confronted and harmonized bottom-up and top down priorities)

The report on the international workshop 'Plant Health Research Priorities for Central Asia' contains the minutes from the three working group discussions held during the event. These discussions led to the identification of the following common research priorities for the region:

Advancing diagnostics for phytosanitary import controls

With the increasing globalization of trade and the rise of e-commerce, effective diagnostic methods at entry points are critical for preventing the introduction of quarantine pests through plant material and passenger-carried items. This research priority focuses on developing, validating and implementing rapid, cost-effective and easy-to-use diagnostic tools to enhance phytosanitary inspections at borders.

Strengthening phytosanitary measures for trade in wood and related commodities

The global trade of wood and wood-derived materials, such as woodchips and bark, presents significant phytosanitary risks due to the potential for pest and pathogen introduction. This research priority focuses on improving risk assessment, treatment efficiency, and safety protocols for these high-risk commodities.

Key objectives include:

- Gather detailed data on trade characteristics, including the types and quality of wood materials (e.g., bark-free wood, woodchips, bark) and their associated risks
- Evaluate current phytosanitary measures and their effectiveness in mitigating risks for these materials
- Assess the efficiency of sterilization methods for large volumes of wood-derived materials, such as woodchip piles
- Investigate the type and quality of wood used to produce these materials and analyze how treatments affect pest and pathogen eradication
- Conduct studies on imported woodchips to evaluate their condition before and after treatment, ensuring compliance with phytosanitary standards
- Develop protocols for assessing entire shipments of wood and wood-derived commodities rather than relying on sample subsets, to ensure they are fully safe for trade
- Examine the safety of sea containers and the packaging materials used in transporting these commodities to identify additional risks
- Identify and test innovative technologies and methods to improve the reliability and efficiency of phytosanitary treatments for large-scale materials
- Explore alternative approaches to ensure consistent sterilization of entire shipments

Addressing potato diseases and vector management

Potato production faces significant challenges from a wide range of diseases and pests, many of which pose threats to both yield and trade. Key issues include managing diseases such as potato wart, mop-top virus (PMTV), *Ralstonia solanacearum*, phytoplasmas, and emerging threats like *Harsenphonus* and zebra chip. With limited knowledge about certain pathogens, such as phytoplasmas, and their vectors, focused research is essential to protect potato crops globally.

Key objectives:

- Investigate insect vectors like leafhoppers, which are known to transmit viruses and phytoplasmas
- Study the biology, lifecycle and transmission mechanisms of these vectors to develop targeted management strategies
- Focus on regulated quarantine organisms, including the vector of *Liberibacter solanacearum* haplotype Solanaceae, to prevent their spread within Europe and beyond
- Develop and refine high-throughput sequencing (HTS) and other advanced diagnostic tools to rapidly and accurately detect potato diseases
- Strengthen epidemiological surveillance to track the spread of diseases and their vectors, especially under the pressures of climate change and reduced chemical control options
- Promote the sharing and standardization of testing methods for seed potatoes across countries to ensure consistency and reliability
- Address trade-related issues by improving phytosanitary protocols for the import and export of potatoes and seed potatoes
- Assess how global trade and the movement of potatoes and seed potatoes contribute to the spread of diseases and pests
- Consider climate change as a driving factor that increases the prevalence and impact of pests and pathogens in potato production

Advancing pest monitoring and detection systems

Effective pest monitoring and early detection are critical components in Plant Health protection, especially for high-risk pests in both agronomic and forestry contexts. This research priority focuses on the development and validation of innovative tools and techniques for monitoring and trapping pests, with an emphasis on improving the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of inspection processes.

Key objectives:

- Explore new approaches to pest surveillance, such as remote sensing technologies and digital platforms for real-time data collection and analysis
- Investigate the use of smart traps for detecting pests, including those targeting Scolytinae and Cerambycidae—two significant insect groups of quarantine concern
- Develop and test novel trapping systems, such as the newly developed fan trap in Belgium, assessing their cost efficiency compared to existing methods
- Enhance pest detection capabilities using automatic image recognition technologies, enabling rapid and accurate identification of pests, such as *Anoplophora glabripennis* (Asian longhorned beetle)
- Improve trapping techniques for pests like *Agrilus* and *Epitrix* (on potatoes), focusing on trap color, shape, placement and lure effectiveness
- Incorporate citizen science to expand monitoring efforts and enhance data collection, particularly in areas where traditional surveillance might be limited
- Test and validate alternative pest monitoring techniques, including sentinel plants and vectors, for a broader understanding of pest presence and movement
- Establish an international network for validating trapping systems and methodologies, allowing participating countries to test and compare different trapping systems

- Support the validation of pest detection techniques and traps across multiple countries, ensuring that methods are universally applicable and effective in different regions

Advancing Integrated Pest Management (IPM) and sustainable plant protection

The future of Plant Health relies on reducing dependency on chemical pesticides and exploring alternative, sustainable methods for pest control. This research priority focuses on advancing IPM strategies, with an emphasis on biological control, resistance breeding, and ecological alternatives to chemical treatments.

Key Objectives:

- Explore the use of biological pesticides and biocontrol agents (BCAs) to target quarantine pests, with a focus on developing environmentally friendly and sustainable plant protection products
- Investigate the role of natural predators and beneficial organisms in managing pest populations, reducing reliance on chemical control
- Continue projects focused on breeding potatoes with resistance to key pests and diseases, aiming to reduce the need for chemical interventions
- Foster collaboration between countries to share knowledge about natural biological pest control methods that have been successful in other regions, enabling the transfer of effective strategies across borders
- Build on previous Euphresco projects to expand research on IPM and biocontrol, learning from international experiences and adapting them to local contexts
- Research alternatives to peat in nursery production, moving towards more sustainable growth substrates
- Investigate the ecological implications of different growth substrates and their potential to support healthy plant growth while maintaining pest control efficacy
- Explore specific strategies for controlling pests like *Anoplophora glabripennis* through ecological methods, emphasizing sustainable, long-term solutions for pest management

Raising awareness and engaging public participation in Plant Health

Raising awareness about Plant Health is critical, especially for key crops like potatoes, which are vital to global food security. As one of the most important crops worldwide, potatoes play a central role in food systems and offer a unique opportunity to engage the public in Plant Health initiatives.

Key Objectives:

- Use the importance of potatoes as a central theme to raise awareness about Plant Health and its impact on global food systems. By emphasizing their role in food security, this initiative aims to engage a broad audience in understanding the need for plant protection
- Promote the concept of "One World, One Health," highlighting the interconnectedness between Plant Health, human health and environmental health, reinforcing the idea that protecting crops is essential for the well-being of all living systems
- Encourage public participation in Plant Health research through citizen science initiatives, such as pest monitoring, data collection, and reporting of plant diseases. This approach can increase the scale of monitoring efforts and contribute valuable data to research

- Identify and implement effective communication strategies to inform and engage the public on Plant Health issues. Use diverse channels such as social media, educational campaigns and community outreach to reach different audiences, from farmers to consumers

4.5 The suggested research topics for 2025 and 2026

Research topic 1 – Trade: Cotton bollworm control through biopreparations and beneficial insects

- Meeting rate
- Damage rate
- Identification of natural entomophages
- Breeding and application of biological control agents against them

This research topic is being developed by a special working group consisting of experts from the following regions and disciplines: It is proposed for the upcoming 2025 call.

Research topic 2 – Restoration of entomofauna in agrobiocenosis of areas affected by natural disasters

- Species composition of pests in flooded areas.
- Determination of the degree of harmfulness of pests
- Study and formation of entomofauna
- Monitoring of pest development stages

This research topic is being developed by a special working group consisting of experts from the following regions and disciplines: It is proposed for the upcoming 2025 call.

Research topic 3 – Trade: Risk assessment and measures for wood material

- Various pests
- Bark free wood, woodchip, bark
- Validate phytosanitary methods for large volumes, collect data on trade (type of wood, quality before and after treatment)
- Better knowledge on trade, safer trade

Research topic 4 – Vegetable and technical crops biological protection systems: evaluation, development and practices in Central Asia in open field and crop protected areas.

- Biological control agents are used against harmful organisms of vegetable and technical crops
- Entomophages are used against pests
- Devices for high-quality propagation and distribution of entomophages are developed

5 The programmes and the funds allocated to Plant Health research *(optional, if already known or if Funding survey has already been conducted)*

The funding survey has not been conducted yet.

6 Coordination and collaboration *(optional, if already known or if Funding survey has already been conducted)*

The funding survey has not been conducted yet.

7 Supplementary information or messages originated from the consultation

International seminar has not yet been held

3 REPORT OF THE CONSULTATIONS FOR SOUTH EAST ASIA

1. Introduction

The Asia-Pacific, encompassing South Asia and Southeast Asia, is a diverse region with unique agricultural challenges, particularly in pest and disease management across varying climates and crop systems. APAARI, a regional leader in agricultural research, champions initiatives to address these challenges through coordinated research efforts. With growing interest in harmonizing research priorities, the EUPHRESKO III project aims to foster regional and global collaboration. Through consultations with country partners, the project identifies key research topics that align with regional priorities, strengthening Asia-Pacific's plant health and biosecurity research efforts.

2. The agricultural crops

The important agricultural crops for the Asia-Pacific region, selected based on export value, include staple and high-demand commodities such as rice from countries like Indonesia, Thailand, and Vietnam, which hold substantial commercial importance. Other significant crops include maize, sugarcane, cassava, and tropical fruits such as durian and pineapple, especially from Malaysia and the Philippines. India's notable contributions include basmati rice, spices, and cotton. This crop selection reflects each crop's economic impact, with export values influencing the prioritization of these commodities for regional agricultural focus and trade.

Region	Countries	Crops
South Asia	India	Rice, Basmati Rice, Wheat, Cotton, Spices, Pulses
	Pakistan	Wheat, Cotton, Rice, Sugarcane, Maize
	Bangladesh	Rice, Wheat, Jute
	Nepal	Rice, Wheat, Maize
Southeast Asia	Indonesia	Rice, Maize, Cassava, Cocoa, Mango, Sweet Potato
	Thailand	Rice, Maize, Sugarcane, Cassava, Black Pepper, Cocoa, Rubber, Mango
	Vietnam	Rice, Pepper, Sugarcane, Maize
	Malaysia	Oil Palm, Cocoa, Tropical Fruits (Durian, Papaya, Pineapple, etc.)
	Philippines	Rice, Maize, Tropical Fruits (Durian, Pineapple, Papaya)

Based on the survey results, the following crops were identified as their country's important crops.

Region	Country	Crops
South Asia	Bangladesh	Rice, wheat, vegetables, oil crops, fruits; pulses and oilseeds; sugarcane.
	India	Rice, wheat, maize, pulses (pigeonpea, blackgram, greengram, chickpea); vegetables (onion, potato, solanaceous crops, cucurbits, crucifers); barley; banana; millets; groundnut; soybean; spices (chillies).
	Nepal	Not specified.
	Pakistan	Wheat, rice, maize.
	Sri Lanka	Rice, maize, chilli, pulses, coconut, banana, mango.
Southeast Asia	Malaysia	Rice, palm oil, vegetables, fruits.
	Philippines	Rice, corn, banana, pineapple, high-value crops (e.g., mango, banana), upland and lowland vegetables, coffee, cacao, dragon fruit.
	Thailand	Not specified.
	Vietnam	Rice.

3. Important pests for the region

Survey results have revealed significant pest and disease challenges affecting agriculture across South Asia and Southeast Asia. Key pests, such as the fall armyworm and invasive species like water hyacinth and *Parthenium*, pose threats to critical crops, including rice, maize, and wheat. Several countries in the regions also report emerging issues with specific pathogens and insect pests that impact productivity and ecological balance. These findings, summarized in the table below, highlight the urgent need for regional collaboration and coordinated management strategies to mitigate agricultural losses and ensure sustainable crop production.

Region	Country	Pest(s)
South Asia	Bangladesh	Wheat blast, Fall armyworm, etc.; not well-known.
	India	UG99 and blast in wheat; new races/pathotypes of BLB and blast in rice; new strains of tomato leaf curl virus; Fall armyworm; Rugose spiraling whitefly; Cotton mealybug; Subabul psyllid; All invasive weeds (Eichhornia, Parthenium, Lantana); Tomato pinworm; Phytophthora infestans; Potato Golden cyst nematode; Black thrips of chilies; mealybug in plantations; rugose spiraling whiteflies in coconut; mites in plantations; Heterodera glycine; Heterodera schachtii; Bursaphelenchus xylophilus.
	Nepal	Parthenium, Water Hyacinth, Mikania: Rapid spread and severe impact on agriculture and ecology.
	Pakistan	Not specified.
	Sri Lanka	Coconut whitefly, Papaya mealybug, Parthenium, Fall armyworm.
Southeast Asia	Malaysia	Not specified.
	Philippines	Khapra beetle; Fall armyworm; Fusarium wilt; Water hyacinth; Golden apple snail; Devil's weed.
	Thailand	Black chin tilapia (animal pest); Weedy rice.
	Vietnam	Fall armyworm; South American tomato leafminer.

4. Key drivers for collaboration

The major crop health challenges identified through surveys across South Asia and Southeast Asia encompass a wide range of pests, diseases, and weeds affecting key crops such as rice, maize, tomato, and others. In Bangladesh, issues like rice blast, Tungro diseases, and the brown plant hopper insect have been noted, while in India, rice blast, bacterial blight, and maize stem borers cause significant yield losses. In Nepal, fall armyworm, bacterial leaf blight, and rust diseases in wheat are major concerns, and in Sri Lanka, pests and diseases have been exacerbated by climate change. Southeast Asia faces similar challenges, with pests like the fall armyworm, rice tungro virus, and fungal diseases impacting crops in the Philippines, while Thailand and Vietnam report significant pest issues such as rice planthoppers and cassava insect vectors. Additionally, Malaysia and the Philippines report growing concerns related to climate change and the lack of resistant germplasms, alongside post-harvest losses and pest outbreaks. These challenges are being addressed through various research efforts, and the findings will be further refined through an international conference and surveys involving policymakers, farmers, and foresters in the second phase.

Another critical issue identified is mycotoxin contamination, particularly in cereal grains, chilies, maize, and groundnut. This poses a significant risk to food safety, affecting both human and animal health, as well as market acceptance. Mycotoxins can severely compromise the

quality and safety of agricultural products, leading to both health hazards and economic losses. Furthermore, post-harvest losses, driven by pests, diseases, and the absence of resistant germplasms, continue to disrupt the agricultural value chain. These issues contribute to economic instability, reduce food availability, and threaten food security in the region.

The main plant health issues or related practical problems faced by policymakers and farmers in the region will be collected in the next phase of the survey. This phase will focus on understanding the ground-level challenges experienced by these key stakeholders in managing pests, diseases, and weeds that affect crop health. In addition, data from research funders will be gathered to gain insights into the critical areas of funding and support needed for addressing these plant health challenges. For the industry sector, relevant data will be collected through the upcoming international conference, scheduled for December 17-18, 2024, in AP, India. This conference will specifically address plant health priorities in Asia and will provide a platform for stakeholders from the agriculture, and industry to exchange knowledge and collaborate on solutions.

5. The research priorities

Based on the survey results, we have identified the following research priorities categorized into mid-term and long-term goals. The mid-term priorities focus on practical, scalable solutions such as sustainable pest management practices, rapid detection technologies, and field validation of biocontrol agents. These initiatives are designed to deliver measurable outcomes within 3–5 years. On the other hand, the long-term priorities emphasize the development of regional frameworks, early warning systems, and advanced digital tools, which require extensive collaboration, technological innovation, and infrastructure development over a 5+ year horizon. This alignment ensures that the research agenda addresses both immediate challenges and strategic needs for sustainable agricultural growth.

Mid-Term Areas (3 - 5 long years)

Rugose Spiraling Whitefly in Coconut

- Sustainable management practices using botanicals and biopesticides.
- Long-term effects of neem-based formulations on whitefly populations.

Mycotoxin Detection and Management

- Development of rapid, cost-effective detection methods for Trade and food safety.
- Pilot technologies like solar dryers and hermetic storage for contamination-free commodities.
- Strengthening regional standards and protocols for mycotoxin management.

Maize Fall Armyworm Management

- Field validation of biocontrol agents against fall armyworm.
- Evaluation of *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt) and entomopathogenic fungi.

Fruit Fly Management

- Development and application of semiochemical-based attractants for mass trapping.
- Biopesticide evaluation for fruit fly management in organic systems.

Other Areas

- Training programs for farmers on safe pesticide use.
- Strengthening phytosanitary protocols to reduce post-harvest contamination.

Long-Term Areas (>5 years)

- Establishment of early warning systems using digital technologies for Fallarmy and Whiteflies.
- Development of regional frameworks for effective phytosanitary certification (ePhyto in Asia).
- Application of digital and AI tools for real-time monitoring in value chains for major export crops - Mycotoxins.

6. The programmes and the funds allocated to plant health research *(optional, if already known or if Funding survey has already been conducted)*

South Asia

- **Government Funding:** Many responses indicate that national governments, such as the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR), state governments, and others in South Asia, are pivotal in supporting plant health projects.
- **National and International Funding:** A number of responses highlight that both national and international agencies support these projects, showcasing the collaborative effort across borders in advancing plant health.
- **International Funding:** Some responses emphasize international sources, including global organizations and international bodies that play a significant role in providing essential resources.
- **Private Sector Funding:** The private sector is also recognized as a potential contributor to plant health initiatives, though accessing these funds may require formal applications to national and private entities.
- **Institutional In-House Funding:** Key institutions, notably ICAR, provide in-house funding for select projects, demonstrating their internal commitment to plant health research.
- **Limited or No Funding:** A few respondents noted an absence of funding or support, which highlights gaps in funding for certain projects and presents opportunities to enhance capacity in this critical area and some respondents weren't aware of the fundings available..

South East Asia

- **National Governments:** Several responses mentioned funding from national governments, such as the Malaysian government, the Philippine government, and specific departments like the Ministry of Higher Education and the Department of Science and Technology. This indicates a strong commitment at the national level to support plant health initiatives.
- **International Funding Sources:** Many organizations seek funding from international entities such as UNDP, GCF, CGIAR, and USDA, showcasing the importance of global partnerships in financing research.
- **Private Sector Contributions:** Responses indicated that the private sector is also involved in funding, either independently or through joint funding arrangements with other sources.
- **Academic Institutions:** Universities contribute funding through annual budgets, contracted research, and internal grants, highlighting their role in supporting plant health research.

- **NGOs:** Some responses indicated funding from non-governmental organizations, further diversifying the funding landscape.
- **Joint Funding Mechanisms:** The presence of joint funding arrangements with multiple sources, including government, academic, and international organizations, underscores a collaborative strategy to enhance resources for plant health projects.
- Overall, the responses indicate a complex funding environment that encompasses government, national and international organizations, and private sector contributions, highlighting the potential for increased collaboration to secure more resources for plant health projects.

7. Coordination and collaboration

(optional, if already known or if Funding survey has already been conducted)

The survey results revealed that participants expressed strong agreement regarding their interest in collaboration, emphasizing their willingness to join a global network and engage in coordination

8. Supplementary information or messages originated from the consultation

The excessive use of chemical fertilizers, pesticides, and herbicides across these regions has profound environmental implications, including soil degradation, water contamination, and the emergence of pest resistance. Agrochemical residues in soil and water, along with mycotoxin contamination in crops like maize and groundnut, compromise food safety and long-term agricultural sustainability.

Both regions (South Asia and Southeast Asia) face challenges in addressing these environmental and trade-related issues, underscoring the need for sustainable farming practices, including Integrated Pest Management (IPM), natural farming, and regenerative agriculture.

9. Report of the 2025 country consultations on plant health research priorities for South-East Asia

Introduction

This report summarises the outcomes of 2025 country consultations on Plant Health Priorities for the EUPHRESKO III 2026 call.

In a previous call (2024) of EUPHRESKO III collaborative research project development, APAARI undertook a survey of 450 selected researchers in crop health across institutions in 15 countries in the South and Southeast Asia regions to identify priority plant health issues in each country. From the 35 responses from 9 countries, five preliminary research topics were developed with only three project topics eventually being accepted by the EUPHRESKO committee to be developed into full project proposals, each being led by a Research coordinator with multiple partner institutes. The projects involving APAARI are:

- 2025-C-500 Risk assessment of anthracnose of fruit trees, tropical yams and chili plants, being led by Dr MLN Nandini, Vignan University, India.
- 2025-C-501 Bio-rational management of invasive rugose spiralling whitefly in coconut and banana, being led by Dr N K Dutta, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute.

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-01 under grant agreement No 101130467

- 2025-C-504 Eco-friendly mitigation of *Phytophthora* root rot in vegetables using biostimulants and biopesticides, being led by Dr MLN Nandini, Vignan University, India.

In addition, APAARI is also involved in a project from the 2024 call:

- 2024-G-466 Enhancing knowledge and management of risks to reduce pest introduction and spread through the sea container pathway, being led by Dr W Asbil, Canadian Food Inspection Agency.

Letters of commitment have been requested from EUPHRESKO from partner institutes nominated for each proposal which will be developed into full project proposals in 2026.

This report summarises the country consultations with the national plant health representatives to identify the key plant health priority pests, diseases and weeds affecting the South and southeast Asia regions.

Methodology

Between June to October 2025, in response to the EUPHRESKO III 2026 call, on-line country consultation meetings were undertaken with five countries that were not effectively involved in previous surveys – Bhutan, Cambodia, Philippines, Sri Lanka and Vietnam.

The consultations engaged respective national representatives from their leading government research institutions. Each country representative was asked to submit a report outlining the current challenges, research directions, and collaboration needs; as well as prepare a presentation for on-line discussions.

Results

Table 1. List of pests, diseases, weeds affecting Plant health in Bhutan, Cambodia, Sri Lanka, Vietnam, Philippines nominated by country plant health officers.

Country	Commodity	Pest	Disease/ pathogen	Weed
Bhutan	Rice	White-backed planthopper	Blast	<i>Potamogeton distincus</i>
	Maize	Fall armyworm	Turicum leaf blight	<i>Galinsoga parviflora</i>
	Potato	Tuber moth	Gray leaf spot	<i>Persicaria runcinate</i>
	Chili	Pod borer	Late blight	<i>Galium aparine</i>
	Oranges	Chinese citrus fruit fly	Blight	<i>Persicaria nepalensis</i>
Cambodia	Rice	White fly – <i>A. indicus</i>	Citrus Greening (HLB)	<i>Galinsoga quadriradiata</i>
		<i>Armyworm Spodoptera</i> sp		<i>Bidens Pilosa</i>
		Brown plant hopper		<i>Scurrula parasitica</i>
		Yellow stem borer		
		Fall armyworm		
	Maize	Asian corn borer	Fusarium stalk/ear rot	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>
		Corn aphid	Maize lethal necrosis disease	<i>Cyperus difformis</i>
			Common rust	<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>
	Cassava	Mealybug	Southern corn rust	
		Mite	Cassava mosaic virus	<i>Echinochloa colona</i>
Cashew	Whitefly (<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>)	Witches' Broom		
	Tea mosquito bug	Anthracnose (<i>Colletotrichum</i> sp)		
	Leaf and flower thrips			
	Shoot tip caterpillar			

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	Mango	Oriental fruit fly Mango leaf hopper Mealy bug	Shoot rot and leaf fall (<i>Phytophthora nicotianae</i>) Leaf and nut blight (<i>Cryptosporiopsis</i> sp) Mango malformation (<i>Fusarium mangiferae</i>) Anthracnose (<i>Colletotrichum</i> sp) Powdery mildew (<i>Oidium mangiferae</i>)	
Sri Lanka	Rice Maize Rubber Coconut Tea Sugarcane	Brown plant hopper Thrips Yellow stem borer Fall armyworm Rhinoceros beetle Red palm weevil Coconut mite Mites Thrips Tea mosquito bug Shoot borer Internode borer Fall armyworm Pyrrilla	Rice blast Bacterial leaf spot Sheath rot/ blight Circular Leaf spot Colletotrichum leaf disease Powdery mildew Weligama coconut leaf wilt Ganoderma root and bole rot leaf blight Blister blight Grey blight Anthracnose White leaf disease Smut Leaf scald	<i>Echinochloa colona</i> , <i>E. crus-galli</i> <i>Panicum repens</i> <i>Cyperus iria</i> , <i>C. difformis</i> <i>Weddellia trilobata</i> <i>Clidemia hirta</i> <i>Dillenia suffruticosa</i> <i>Tephrosia purpurea</i> <i>Acanthospermum hispidum</i> <i>Ocimum sanctum</i> <i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> <i>Borreria latifolia</i> <i>Panicum maximum</i> <i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i> <i>Cyperus rotundus</i>
Vietnam	Rice Maize Coffee Banana Citrus	Brown plant hopper (<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>) White-backed plant hopper (<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>) Rice leaf folder (<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i>) Fall armyworm (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>) Cotton bollworm (<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>) Asia corn stem borer (<i>Ostrinia furnacalis</i>) Maize aphid (<i>Rhopalosiphum maidis</i>) Japanese mealybug (<i>Planococcus kraunthiae</i>) Nematodes (<i>Meloidogyne incognita</i> ; <i>Pratylenchus coffeae</i>) Coffee berry borer (<i>Stephanoderes hampei</i>) Coffee green scale (<i>Coccus viridis</i>) Banana borer (<i>Cosmopolites sordidus</i>) Citrus Red mites (<i>Panonychus citri</i>) Citrus leafminer (<i>Phyllocnistis citrella</i>) Fruit flies (<i>Bactrocera</i> spp.)	Blast disease (<i>Magnaporthe oryzae</i>) Bacterial leaf blight (<i>X. oryzae</i> pv. <i>oryzae</i>) Rice Grassy Stunt – RGSV Sheath blight (<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>) Fusarium stalk rot (<i>Fusarium solani</i>) Coffee rust fungus (<i>Hemileia vastatrix</i>) Brown blight of coffee (<i>Colletotrichum coffeanum</i>) <i>Fusarium</i> spp <i>Phytophthora</i> spp Panama disease (<i>Fusarium wilt</i>) Sigatoka disease of banana (<i>Mycosphaerella musicola</i>) Bunchytop Banana Bunchy Top Virus Greening diseases (<i>Candidatus Liberibacter asiaticus</i>) HLB Virus Citrus tristeza <i>Fusarium</i> spp	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> <i>Oryza sativa</i> f. <i>spontanea</i> <i>Echinochloa colonum</i> <i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> <i>Bidens pilosa</i> <i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> <i>Synedrella nodiflora</i> <i>Commelina communis</i> <i>Bidens pilosa</i> <i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> <i>Synedrella nodiflora</i> <i>Commelina communis</i> <i>Bidens pilosa</i> <i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> <i>Synedrella nodiflora</i> <i>Commelina communis</i>

			<i>Phytophthora</i> spp Citrus canker (<i>X. axonopodis citri</i>)	
Philippines	Rice	Planthoppers Stem borers	Blast Blight	
	Maize	Fall armyworm		
	Coconut	Scale	Lethal Yellowing	
	Rubber		Pestalotiopsis leaf fall disease	
	Mango	Cecid fly	Anthracnose (<i>Colletotrichum</i> spp)	
	Banana		Fusarium wilt TR4	
	Onion	Onion armyworm	Anthracnose (<i>Colletotrichum</i> spp) Bulb rot	
	Dragon fruit		Stem canker Anthracnose (<i>Colletotrichum</i> spp)	
	Chili		Anthracnose (<i>Colletotrichum</i> spp)	
	Tomato		Anthracnose (<i>Colletotrichum</i> spp)	
	Sugarcane	Red-striped soft scale	Anthracnose (<i>Colletotrichum</i> spp) Anthracnose (<i>Colletotrichum</i> spp)	

Table 2. Summary of the priority pests, pathogens, weeds affecting plant health in Bhutan, Cambodia, Sri Lanka, Vietnam, Philippines

Commodity	Pest	Disease/pathogen	Weed
Rice	Brown plant hopper (<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>)	Rice blast disease (<i>Magnaporthe oryzae</i>) Rice bacterial leaf blight (<i>X. oryzae</i> pv. <i>oryzae</i>)	Barnyard grass (<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>)
Maize	Fall armyworm (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>)	Fusarium stalk rot (<i>Fusarium solani</i>)	Awnless barnyard grass (<i>Echinochloa colonum</i>)
Citrus	Chinese citrus fruit fly (<i>Bactrocera minax</i>)	Greening disease (<i>Candidatus Liberibacter asiaticus</i>) Citrus canker (<i>X. axonopodis citri</i>)	
Banana	Banana borer (<i>Cosmopolites sordidus</i>)	Panama disease (Fusarium wilt)	
Tropical fruit	Fruit fly	Anthracnose (<i>Colletotrichum</i> spp)	
Cashew		Anthracnose (<i>Colletotrichum</i> spp)	

Discussion

Many of the priority pests, pathogens and weeds affecting agriculture in Bhutan, Cambodia, Sri Lanka, Vietnam, Philippines were similar to those identified in the 2024 survey of countries in the South and Southeast Asia regions.

The country consultations were mostly with national representatives from leading government research institutions who had good knowledge of priority pests affecting the production and trade of important commodities in their respective countries. However, the consultations did

not identify specific research projects currently being undertaken or planned for the near future.

Research projects and key researchers in national research institutes and Universities need to be identified and invited to participate in transnational (Regional and Global) research projects supported by EUPHRESKO III. To this extent, the national representatives of the five consultative countries will be sent the list of the eight EUPHRESKO III plant health priority topics, common across global regions, identified by the EUPHRESKO III regional champions, which are listed below:

- *Xylella fastidiosa* detection, surveillance, and preparedness
- *Fusarium* spp. (including TR4) management and diagnostics
- Fruit fly (*Tephritidae*) management and trade compliance
- Digital tools, AI, and smart technologies for surveillance and diagnostics
- Climate change impacts on pest dynamics and surveillance
- Integrated Pest Management (IPM) and biological control
- Vector-borne pathogens and insect vector management
- Public engagement and knowledge exchange for biosecurity

Working groups from the regional champions will be identified to liaise with research institutions in their respective regions and develop collaborative, transnational research projects that can be submitted to EUPHRESKO III 2026 call. APAARI has been proposed to prepare the description for Topic 3 on Fruit fly (*Tephritidae*) management and trade compliance. The Pacific islands region is interested in joining this activity.

There may be opportunities to focus on specific research projects in plant health at a planned APAARI-EUPHRESKO workshop/symposium to be held in March 2026 in which researchers from regional institutes will be invited to present their research aligning with the eight plant health priority topics.

Appendix 1. Bhutan plant health report

National Consultation on Plant Health Champion
EUPHRESKO III Initiative
APAARI

Yeshey Dema
Program Director
National Plant Protection Centre
June 2025

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Five key crops and associated pests, diseases, or weeds impacting production, environment, and trade

Key crops	Insect pests	Diseases	Weeds
Paddy	White-backed planthopper	Blast	Potamogeton distinctus
Maize	Fall armyworm	Turicum Leaf Blight, Gray Leaf Spot	Galinsoga parviflora, Persicaria runcinata
Potato	Potato tuber moth	Late blight	Galium aparine, Persicaria nepalensis
Chilli	Pod borer	Chilli blight	Galinsoga quadriradiata, Bidens pilosa
Oranges	Chinese citrus fruit fly	HLB	Scutulla parasitica

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National Plant Health Research Programmes

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Stakeholder involvement in setting plant health priorities

Stakeholder	Role in Plant Health Priority Setting	Level of Involvement
Department of Agriculture (DoA)	Sets national agricultural policy; oversees plant protection programs	High
National Plant Protection Centre (NPPC)	Leads pest surveillance, IPM, internal quarantine measures; coordinates national planning and research	Very High
Agriculture Research and Development Centre (ARDCs) Dzongkhag/Gewog Agriculture Offices	Conduct field research, trials, and pest monitoring Collect field data, respond to farmer complaints, participate in planning	High Medium to High
BFDA (Regulatory Authority)	Input on quarantine pests, phytosanitary risks, and trade-related concerns	High
Academia (CNR, RUB)	Research on pests/diseases; student theses and field trials	Low to Medium

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Barriers to International or Regional Collaboration in Plant Health in Bhutan

Barrier Type	Description
Technical Capacity Constraints	Limited number of trained plant health professionals and diagnostic experts to engage in collaborative programs
Infrastructure Limitations	Inadequate lab facilities, pest diagnostic tools, and data systems for pest identification and reporting
Funding and Resource Gaps	Lack of dedicated budget for international participation, project co-financing
Weak Regional Coordination Mechanisms	Limited platforms for sustained engagement with neighboring countries (e.g., India, Bangladesh, Nepal)
Regulatory and Policy Differences	Varying plant quarantine rules, pesticide regulations, and pest reporting protocols across countries
Data Sharing Limitations	Limited digital infrastructure and systems for real-time pest surveillance data exchange
Limited Involvement in Regional Bodies	Bhutan is not a full member of or has low engagement in some regional technical bodies (e.g., APPPC sub-groups)

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Key crop health challenges and related economic impact			
Pest/Disease/Weed	Affected Crop(s)	Key Challenge	Economic/Trade Impact
Fall Armyworm (FAW)	Maize	Rapid spread, high larval feeding damage, resistance to pesticides	Yield loss, food security concerns
Fruit Flies	Citrus, Peach, Guava, Apple	Infestation during fruiting stage, difficult to manage organically	Export rejection, market losses, high cost of monitoring and control
Citrus HLB (Greening)	Citrus (mainly mandarin)	No cure, tree decline, spread by citrus psyllid	Long-term orchard productivity loss, reduced fruit quality, trade restrictions
Shoohum (<i>Potamogeton distinctus</i>)	Paddy rice	Aquatic weed, difficult to control, thrives in poorly drained fields	Reduces rice yield and increases labor and weeding costs

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Major Phytosanitary Trade Barriers in Bhutan		
Barrier Type	Description	Remarks
Strict Import Regulations by Trading Partners	Many importing countries have stringent phytosanitary requirements and certifications.	India often requires stringent pest-free certificates, causing delays.
Limited National Laboratory Accreditation	Bhutanese labs often lack international accreditation for pest diagnostics.	Creates doubts about test validity by importing countries.
Inadequate Pest Surveillance and Reporting	Insufficient systematic pest monitoring can delay the identification of quarantine pests.	Delay in setting up internal quarantine to prevent spread.
Lack of Capacity for Pest Risk Analysis	Limited expertise and resources to conduct rigorous pest risk assessments.	Hinders negotiation of market access and recognition of pest-free status.
Limited Awareness and Training	Exporters and farmers sometimes lack knowledge of phytosanitary requirements.	Risk of importing invasive pests through agricultural imports without proper assessment.

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Priority invasive and alien species	
Pests	Impact
Fall Armyworm (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>)	Major pest of maize. Rapid spread since its first detection in Bhutan in 2019. Causes significant yield loss.
Fruit Flies (<i>Bactrocera</i> species)	Serious threat to mango, guava, citrus, and other fruits. Reduces marketable yield, affects export quality, and leads to trade restrictions.
Polka Dot Plant (<i>Hypoestes phytolachya</i>)	Competing with crops and posing a risk to native biodiversity.

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Appendix 2. Cambodia plant health report

National Consultation for the EUPHRESKO III initiative

Plant Health Research

POL Chantry
Cambodian Agricultural Research and Development Institute (CARDI)
Date: 19 June 2025

1

Crop	Area (ha)	%	Crop	Area (ha)	%
1. Rice	3,856,326	64.38	3. Industrial Crops	1,770,173	30.02
2. Horticultural Crops	335,303	5.60	Cassava	808,548	13.50
Mango	154,908	2.59	Cashewnut	633,342	10.57
Vegetables	76,117	1.27	Maize	213,533	3.56
Banana	56,894	0.95	Sugarcane	41,038	0.69
Longan	14,272	0.24	Coconut+Coconut oil	40,987	0.68
Orange	9,806	0.16	Mungbean	15,484	0.26
Watermelon	5,681	0.09	Soybean	11,436	0.19
Jackfruit	3,684	0.06	Sesame	8,426	0.14
Duren	2,956	0.05	Black pepper	7,120	0.12
Sapodilla (Lamut)	2,128	0.04	Sweet potato	4,382	0.07
Pineapple	1,672	0.03	Others (7 crops)	13,877	0.23
Others (11 crops)	7,183	0.12	Total Area (1+2+3)	5,989,802	100

The most important crops are:

1. Rice
2. Cassava
3. Cashewnut
4. Maize
5. Mango

2

Table 1. The production of top 5 crops

Crops	2023				2024			
	Cultivated Areas (ha)	Harvested Areas (ha)	Average Yield (t/ha)	Production (tons)	Cultivated Areas (ha)	Harvested Areas (ha)	Average Yield (t/ha)	Production (tons)
Rice	3,549,353	3,512,918	3.56	12,497,232	3,856,326	3,814,333	3.64	13,887,986
Cassava	713,168	707,546	20.15	14,255,401	808,548	759,082	20.53	15,688,230
Cashewnut	472,946	357,887	1.38	494,953	633,342	580,117	1.53	885,565
Maize	293,244	285,376	5.60	1,597,048	213,533	208,367	5.16	1,076,053
Mango	142,825	117,218	19.19	2,250,145	154,908	119,274	18.46	2,201,566

3

Major pests, diseases and weeds affecting crops

Crop	Insect pests	Diseases	Weeds
Rice	Brown planthopper (<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>)	Rice Blast (<i>Pyricularia oryzae</i>)	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.)
	Army worm (<i>Spodoptera</i> spp.)	Bacterial Leaf Blight (<i>Xanthomonas oryzae</i>)	<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.
	Yellow stem borer (<i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i>)	Sheath Blight (<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>)	<i>Pennisetum polystachyon</i> (L.)
Cassava	Cassava mealybug (<i>Phenacoccus manihoti</i>)	Cassava Mosaic Virus Disease (CMVD)	
	Cassava mite (<i>Tetranychus</i> spp., especially <i>T. bimaculatus</i>)	Cassava Witches Broom Disease (CWBD)	
Cashew	Tea Mosquito Bug (<i>Helopeltis theivora</i>)	Anthraxnose (<i>Colletotrichum gloeosporioides</i>)	
	Leaf and flower thrips (Order: Thysanoptera)	Shoot rot and leaf fall (<i>Phytophthora nicotianae</i>)	
	Shoot tip caterpillar (Family: Gelechiidae, Order: Lepidoptera)	Leaf and nut blight (Genus <i>Cryptosporopsis</i>)	
Maize	Fall Armyworm (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>)	Fusarium stalk/ear rot	<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.)
	Asian Corn Borer (<i>Ostrinia furnacalis</i>)	Maize Lethal Necrosis Disease (MLND)	
	Corn Aphid (<i>Rhopalosiphum maidis</i>)	Common rust, and Southern corn rust	
Mango	Oriental fruit fly (<i>Bactrocera dorsalis</i>)	Mango Malformation (<i>Fusarium mangiferae</i>)	
	Mango Leafhoppers (<i>Amrilodius atkinsoni</i>) and others	Anthraxnose (<i>Colletotrichum gloeosporioides</i>)	
	Mango Mealybugs (mangiferae)	Powdery Mildew (<i>Oidium mangiferae</i>)	

4

Major Crop Health Challenges and Economic Impact

- In the last five years (2020-2024), rice production in Cambodia faced to drought and flood very often. But the most serious problem was flood.
- The highest of the total rice crop lost due to biotic and abiotic stress occurred in 2020 (149,871 ha) and followed 127,967 ha in 2022.
- In 2024, a total of 13,191 ha were affected/damaged by AW, RLF, and Whitefly in 22 provinces (GDA annual report, 2024)

5

Exportation of Agricultural Products, 2020-2024

- Cambodia exported agricultural products with certification=12,002,301 with 122 types of Agr. Products to 87 directions/counties.
- It increased 3,552,887t (=42%) compared to exportation in 2023.
- Paddy rice = 4,608, 574 tons (> 4.6 M tons)
- Milled rice = 645, 872 tons
- other products rather than rice = 6,747,855 tons such as
 - Dry chopped cassava
 - Fresh cassava
 - Raw Cashew nut
 - Banana Fruit
 - Maize/corn (grain)
 - Fresh mango fruit
- Exporting of Agr. products to
 - EU (24 countries),
 - China,
 - Asian Countries (7 countries) and Other countries

6

Plant Health Research Program

- Crop resistance to Biotic: Rice Varietal Screening for BPH, Rice Blast and BLB resistance
- Insect Pest Management in leafy vegetable
- Rice Weed Management options (by stale seedbed, water management, and pre- and post-herbicide application)
- Fall Armyworm Management in Maize (Biological Control of FAW in Maize)

8

Priority Invasive and Alien Species

- Fall Armyworm (FAW)- *Spodoptera frugiperda* - The presence of this type of worm was founded in Cambodia in May 2019 on a total area of 11,142 ha of corn crops in the provinces of Pailin, Battambang, Banteay Meanchey, and Tbong Khmum provinces (CARDI Annual Report, 2022).

- White fly (*Aleurocybotus indicus*)- A new insect pest damaged on rice.

In Cambodia: Whiteflies were not previously reported as pests of rice crops and they were rarely found and caused damage on rice, only common on vegetables such as peppers, eggplants, melons, cucurbits, etc.

In late June to July 2024, a large-scale insect pest, White fly was recorded in Prey Veng, Svay Rieng, Takeo and Tbong Khmum provinces, with 23,000 ha of rice land were affected (<https://www.phnompenpost.com/national/whitefly-outbreak-affects-over-20-000-hectares-of-rice-in-cambodia>).

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Appendix 3. Philippines plant health report

Crop Health and Plant Protection in the Philippines

Joan-May R. Tolentino
 Chief, National Plant Quarantine Services Division
 Bureau of Plant Industry

Major Crop Health Challenges

Key Crops & Threats:

- Onion – Onion armyworm
- Corn & Sugarcane – Fall armyworm, Red-striped soft scale
- Banana – *Fusarium* wilt TR4
- Mango – Cecid fly
- Rubber – *Pestalotiopsis* leaf fall disease
- Rice – Planthoppers, stem borer, blast, blight
- Coconut – Scale insect, lethal yellowing disease

Other factors: climate change, inadequate surveillance systems, fragmented stakeholder coordination, and regulatory constraints

Impacts: yield reductions, increased production costs, compromised product quality, lower farmer incomes, higher consumer prices, reduced export competitiveness, threats to rural livelihoods and national food security

National Plant Health Research Priorities

BPI Research and Development Agenda 2025–2030: 7 Flagship Programs

- 1 Crop Diversity Improvement
- 2 Sustainable Pest Management
- 3 Climate Change Adaptation
- 4 Crop Production Tools and Mechanisms
- 5 SMART Digital Agriculture
- 6 Improved & Efficient Regulations
- 7 Establishment of Innovation Networks

Goal: Develop the Philippine plant industry into a strong-food producing and economically viable industry based on scientific research-informed technology and a technology-driven foundation for dynamic and productive agriculture

Trade & Collaboration Challenges

- Stringent quarantine & complex certification requirements
- Mismatched standards & differing pest risk assessments with trading partners
- Limited diagnostic capacity, infrastructure and resource constraints
- Inconsistent enforcement and lack of transparency
- Regional and international collaboration challenges
 - national policies, funding and administrative constraints
 - Inconsistencies in pest reporting and data sharing

Way Forward

- Coordinated response encompassing science-based research, stakeholder-driven planning, and strengthened international collaboration.
- By advancing the Bureau of Plant Industry's research and development agenda, aligning it with other national plant health initiatives, investing in sustainable pest management strategies, and addressing trade and regulatory barriers, the Philippines can foster a more resilient agricultural sector.

Appendix 4. Sri Lanka plant health report

Initiative on Enhancing Global Coordination in Phytosanitary Research

ANW Sumedha Thushari
Senior Scientist
Sri Lanka Council for Agricultural Research Policy
Colombo 07
Sri Lanka

1

SRI LANKA

2

Major Agricultural crops

The Sri Lankan Department of Agriculture has designated

Paddy	Big onions	Gingelly
Maize	Green beans	Kurakkan
Chillies	Cowpea	Black gram
Potatoes	Soybeans	Groundnuts
Red onions		

3

Plantation Crops:

Tea, Rubber, Coconut, Spices (cinnamon, pepper, cardamom) sugarcane

Livestock & Fisheries:

Dairy, poultry, inland and marine fisheries

4

Key crops

Tea, Paddy, Rubber, Sugarcane, Coconut

5

Common disease, pests and weeds in Paddy in SL

Common Diseases	Common Pests	Common weeds
01 Rice Blast	01 Brown Plant Hopper	01 <i>Echinochloa colona</i>
02 Sheath blight	02 Thrips	02 <i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>
03 Brown Spot	03 Yellow Stem Borer	03 <i>Panicum repens</i>
04 False smut	04 Rice Leaf folders	04 <i>Cyperus iria</i>
05 Leaf scald	05 Rice sheath mite	05 <i>Cyperus difformis</i>
06 Bacterial Leaf Blight		06 <i>Commelina diffusa</i>
07 Sheath Rot		07 <i>Eclipta alba</i>

6

Common disease, pests and weeds in Tea in SL

Common Diseases	Common Pests	Common weeds
01 Blister blight	01 Mites	01 <i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>
02 Grey blight	02 Thrips	02 <i>Borreria latifolia</i>
03 Brown blight and Anthracnose	03 Tea Mosquito Bug	03 <i>Leuotheranthera ruderalis</i>
04 Red rust	04 Shot Hole Borer	04 <i>Mikania scandens</i>
05 Bacterial shoot blight	05 Tea Tortrix	
06 Cankers	06 Termites	
07 Red root rot	07	

7

Common disease, pests and weeds in Rubber in SL

Common Diseases	Common Pests	Common weeds
01 Circular Leaf Spot Disease	01 Wild boar	01 <i>Weddellia trilobata</i>
02 Powdery Mildew	02 Porcupine	02 <i>Clidemia hirta</i>
03 Colletotrichum Leaf Disease -		03 <i>Dillenia suffruticosa</i>
04 White Root Disease		04 <i>Pueraria</i>
05 Brown Root Disease		
06 Black Root Disease		

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Common disease, pests and weeds in Coconut in SL

Common Diseases	Common Pests	Common weeds
01 Welligama Coconut Leaf Wilt Disease (WCLWD)	01 Rhinoceros Beetle	01 <i>Tephrosia purpurea</i> (Pila)
02 Ganoderma Roots and Bole Rot Disease	02 Red Palm Weevil	02 <i>Acanthospermum hispidum</i> (NerENCHI)
03 Coconut Leaf Blight	03 Coconut Mite	03 <i>Ocimum sanctum</i> (Madurutala)
04 Bud Rot	04 Black-headed Caterpillar	04 <i>Hyptis suaveolens</i>

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Disease, pests and weeds in Sugarcane in SL

Common Diseases	Common Pests	Common weeds
01 White leaf disease	01 Shoot borer	01 <i>Panicum maximum</i>
02 Smut disease	02 Internode Borer	02 <i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>
03 Leaf scald disease	03 Pyrrilla	03 <i>Imperata cylindrica</i>
04 Poklah boeng	04 Sugarcane Woolly Aphid (SWA)	04 <i>Cyperus rotundus</i>
05 Yellow leaf syndrome	05 Termites	05 <i>Mitracarpus hirtus</i>
06	06 Fall Armyworm	06 <i>Euphorbia hirta</i>
	07 Sugarcane spider mite	07 <i>Cyperus iria</i>

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Overview of National Plant Health Research Programs in Sri Lanka

Key Research Institutions Involved

- Department of Agriculture (DoA)** – Under the Ministry of Agriculture
 - Institutes: National Plant Quarantine Services (NPQS)
 - Plant Protection Service (PPS)
 - Field Crops Research and Development Institute (FCRDI)
 - Horticultural Crops Research and Development Institute (HORDI)
 - Rice Research and Development Institute (RRDI)
 - Fruit Research and Development Institute (FRDI)
- Tea Research Institute (TRI)
- Rubber Research Institute (RRI)
- Sugarcane Research Institute (SRI)
- Coconut Research Institute (CRI)
- Department of Export Agriculture
- Department of Animal Production and Health
- National Institute of Post-harvest Management

Focus: Pest and disease management in major food and horticultural crops

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Overview of National Plant Health Research Programs in Sri Lanka

- National Aquatic Resources Research & Development Agency
- National Aquaculture Development Authority of Sri Lanka
- Sri Lanka Cashew Corporation
- Hector Kobbekaduwa Agrarian Research and Development Institute
- Palmyrah Development Board / Palmyra Research Institute
- Sri Lanka Council for Agricultural Research Policy (SLCARP)
 - Coordinates, funds, and sets national research priorities in plant health under thematic programs

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Overview of National Plant Health Research Programs in Sri Lanka

Major Research Themes and Areas

- Integrated Pest and Disease Management (IPM)
- Biological control and eco-friendly alternatives
- Phytoplasma, viral, fungal, and bacterial disease diagnostics
- Vector biology and control
- Pesticide resistance monitoring and safe use
- Development of resistant crop varieties (in collaboration with breeders)
- Disease surveillance, early warning systems, and GIS mapping
- Use of molecular tools (PCR/qPCR) for pathogen identification
- Plant quarantine and invasive species research

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Stakeholder involvement in setting Plant Health Priorities in Sri Lanka

Key Stakeholders Involved

*Multiple stakeholders contribute to identifying and prioritizing plant health issues. These include

- Government research institutes such as the Department of Agriculture (DoA), TRI, CRI, RRI, and SRI
- SLCARP – which plays a central role in coordinating stakeholder consultations and setting national agendas
- Provincial agriculture departments and extension officers, who provide ground-level feedback
- Universities and academia, who contribute technical expertise
- Private sector agribusinesses and exporters, especially for high-value crops
- Farmer organizations and cooperative societies, who highlight pressing field problems

Identification of priorities

- Field-level feedback from extension services and farmers
- Workshops and consultations coordinated by SLCARP and research institutions
- Multi-stakeholder platforms for crops like rice, tea, coconut, sugarcane
- Review of pest and disease surveillance data and emerging threats
- National and regional climate change vulnerability assessments
- Compliance needs for phytosanitary export standards

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Barriers to International or Regional Collaboration

- Limited funding and resources**
 - Inadequate national budget allocation for collaborative research, travel, or joint projects.
 - Difficulties in participating in regional networks, attending international conferences, or initiating joint studies
- Lack of coordinated research platforms**
 - Absence of formal mechanisms or regional consortia specifically dedicated to plant health
 - Missed opportunities for collaborative surveillance, data sharing, and joint diagnostics.
- Bureaucratic and administrative hurdles**
 - Lengthy government approval processes for MOUs, foreign-funded projects, and data sharing agreements.
 - Delays in launching joint initiatives or responding quickly to cross-border pest and disease threats.
- Limited access to global databases and technology**
 - Restrictions in accessing paid or subscription-based molecular databases, remote sensing platforms, and proprietary diagnostic tools.
 - Reduced competitiveness and dependence on foreign collaborators for cutting-edge diagnostics or modeling.

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Key crop health challenges and related economic impact

- Climate Change**- More frequent and intense droughts and floods negatively impact crop yields
 - Paddy cultivation, which feeds millions and supports rural livelihoods, faces reduced yields due to water stress and flood-related crop loss, leading to increased rice imports and price instability
 - Coconut production declines during prolonged droughts, while floods damage palms and reduce nut yield—impacting both domestic consumption and export-based industries such as coconut oil and desiccated coconut
 - Tea, a major export crop, suffers from unpredictable rainfall, with droughts reducing leaf quality and plucking cycles, and heavy rains causing soil erosion and bush damage
 - These effects collectively result in declining farmer incomes, increased production costs, reduced export earnings, and heightened pressure on national food security and the economy
 - Climate change is also effect on vulnerability for diseases and pest as well

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Key crop health challenges and related economic impact

2. Pests and Diseases

The fall armyworm has become a major threat to maize and other crops
Fall Armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*) – MaizeChallenge: Rapid spread since its first appearance in 2018; affects over 60% of maize-growing areas. Impact: Up to 30–50% crop loss reported in some regions. Economic Loss: Millions of rupees in damage annually; higher costs for chemical control
Circular Leaf Spot Disease
 The disease is contributing to a decline in rubber production, potentially impacting the country's rubber industry, which is a significant export earner. Sri Lanka is already importing rubber to meet local demand
Weligama Coconut Leaf Wilt Disease (WCLWD) Significant yield loss, leading to economic hardship for coconut farmers.
 The combined effects of leaf yellowing, premature leaf drop, and sooty mold can lead to a significant decrease in coconut production.
Paddy Blast and Bacterial Leaf Blight – RiceChallenge: Frequent outbreaks during wet seasons; varieties often lack durable resistance. Impact: Yield losses up to 40%, particularly in rain-fed areas. Economic Loss: Direct reduction in national rice production and food security

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3. **Economic Crisis and Policy Changes:** The recent economic crisis led to shortages of essential inputs like fertilizers and pesticides, affecting crop production.
4. **Low Agricultural Productivity:** Traditional farming methods and the slow adoption of modern technology contribute to low productivity.
5. **Inefficient Resource Use:** Inefficient water and fertilizer management further reduces yields.
6. **Post-Harvest Losses:** Significant losses occur due to inadequate storage and processing facilities.
7. **Market Access Issues:** Limited access to markets hinders farmers' ability to sell their produce effectively

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Major Phytosanitary Trade Barriers

1. Inadequate Testing Facilities:

Sri Lanka lacks sufficient testing facilities to meet the requirements of some importing countries, particularly for specific products like shrimp

2. Delays in Certification:

Exporters report delays in obtaining phytosanitary certificates and in the testing process due to capacity limitations at regulatory bodies and the prevalence of manual processes

3. Non-GMO Certification:

All agricultural imports must be accompanied by certification stating they are not genetically modified organisms (GMOs) or living modified organisms (LMOs).

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Priority invasive and alien species

1. Water Hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*)
2. Giant Salvinia (*Salvinia molesta*)
3. Guinea Grass (*Panicum maximum*)
4. Prickly Pear (*Opuntia dillenii*)
5. Lantana (*Lantana camara*)
6. Autograph Tree (*Clusia rosea*)

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Thank You

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Appendix 5. Vietnam plant health report

National Consultation from Vietnam (05 June 2025)
Brief note on present Vietnam's priorities on crop health, pest management, and phytosanitary trade issues

Prepared by Nguyen Van Liem from PPRI

1. Major Crops and Pests Affecting Trade, Production, and Environment
Top five economically important crop commodities in Vietnam

No	Key crop	Major pests, diseases, and weeds	Affecting
1	Rice (7,200 thousands ha)	+ Brown plant hopper (<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>) + White-backed plant hopper (<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>) + Rice leaf folder (<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i>) + Rice blast disease (<i>Magnaporthe oryzae</i>) + Rice bacterial leaf blight (<i>Xanthomonas oryzae pv. oryzae</i>); + Rice virus diseases (<i>Rice Grassy Stunt</i> – RGSV; <i>Southern Rice Black-Streaked Dwarf Virus</i> – SRBSDV; <i>Rice Grassy Stunt Virus</i> – RGSV; <i>Rice Ragged Stunt Virus</i> – RRSV; <i>Rice Transitory Yellowing Virus</i> - RTYV; <i>Rice Tungro Bacilliform & Rice Tungro Spherical Virus</i> - RTBV + RTSV); + Barnyard grass (<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>) + Weedy rice (<i>Oryza sativa f. spontanea</i>)	- Domestic production; - Environmental sustainability
2	Maize (1,100 thousands ha)	+ Fall armyworm (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>) + Cotton bollworm (<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>) + Asia corn stem borer (<i>Ostrinia furnacalis</i>) + Maize aphid (<i>Rhopalosiphum maidis</i>) + Sheath blight (<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>) + Fusarium stalk rot disease (<i>Fusarium solani</i>) + Awnless barnyard grass (<i>Echinochloa colonum</i>) + Billygoat-weed (<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>) + Beggarticks (<i>Bidens pilosa</i>)	- Domestic production; - Environmental sustainability
3	Coffee (710 thousands ha)	+ Japanese mealybug (<i>Planococcus kraunhiae</i>) + Nematodes (<i>Meloidogyne incognita</i> ; <i>Pratylenchus coffeae</i> and others) + Coffee berry borer (<i>Stephanoderes hampei</i>) + Coffee green scale (<i>Coccus viridis</i>) + Coffee rust fungus (<i>Hemileia vastatrix</i>) + Brown blight of coffee (<i>Colletotrichum coffeanum</i>) + Yellow leaves and root rot caused by nematodes and fungi (<i>Fusarium</i> sp., <i>Phytophthora</i> sp., <i>Rhizoctonia</i> sp.) + Billygoat-weed (<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>) + Cinderella Weed (<i>Synedrella nodiflora</i>) + Asiatic dayflower (<i>Commelina communis</i>)	- Domestic production; - Environmental sustainability - International trade (phytosanitary concerns - MRL)

4	Banana (154 thousands ha)	+ Panama disease (Fusarium wilt) <i>Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. cubense</i> Tropical Race 4 (<i>Foc TR4</i>) + Sigatoka disease of banana (<i>Mycosphaerella musicola</i>) + Bunchytop <i>Banana Bunchy Top Virus</i> + Banana borer (<i>Cosmopolites sordidus</i>) + Beggarticks (<i>Bidens pilosa</i>) + Billygoat-weed (<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>) + Cinderella Weed (<i>Synedrella nodiflora</i>) + Asiatic dayflower (<i>Commelina communis</i>)	- Domestic production; - Environmental sustainability - International trade (phytosanitary concerns - MRL)
5	Citrus (260 thousands ha)	+ Greening diseases (<i>Candidatus Liberibacter asiaticus</i>) + <i>Virus Citrus tristeza</i> (CTV) + Yellowing leaves and root rot diseases caused by soilborne agents (<i>Phytophthora</i> spp., <i>Fusarium</i> spp., <i>Rhizoctonia</i> sp., nematodes, mealybug...) + Citrus canker (<i>Xanthomonas axonopodis citri</i>) + Citrus Red mites (<i>Panonychus citri</i>) + Citrus leafminer (<i>Phyllocnistis citrella</i>) + Fruit flies (<i>Bactrocera</i> spp.) + Beggarticks (<i>Bidens pilosa</i>) + Billygoat-weed (<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>) + Cinderella Weed (<i>Synedrella nodiflora</i>) + Asiatic dayflower (<i>Commelina communis</i>)	- Domestic production; - Environmental sustainability - Domestic production; - Environmental sustainability - International trade (phytosanitary concerns - MRL)

● **Top five trade blocks or export destinations for these crops**

- + ASEAN
- + Comprehensive and Progressive Agreement for Trans-Pacific Partnership (CPTPP)
- + EU
- + China
- + America

2. Plant Health Research Programme

● **An active plant health research programme by PPRI, Vietnam.**

The Plant Protection Research Institute (PPRI), a member institute of the Vietnam Academy of Agricultural Sciences (VAAS), is a leading national research organization with over 55 years of experience in the fields of plant protection, integrated pest management (IPM), biological control, development of environmentally friendly plant protection products, and promotion of sustainable agricultural production systems. PPRI has consistently played a key role in addressing plant health issues, supporting food security, and advancing environmentally sound farming practices in Vietnam.

Over the past two decades, PPRI has developed more than 20 biopesticide products derived from beneficial microbes such as *Trichoderma*, *Bacillus*, *Streptomyces*, *Metarhizium*, and *entomopathogenic nematodes*. Examples include: (1) SH-Lifu: multifunctional products for controlling various fungal pathogens and insects; (2) Bio-VAAS.1: effective against *Phytophthora* spp. in citrus and durian; (3) BIOCAM: controls soil-borne diseases using *Trichoderma* and *Streptomyces*; (4) EntoNema-33: nematode-based bioproduct targeting vegetable and food crop pests.

● **A brief overview of its scope, thematic areas, and current projects.**

Scope, thematic areas

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- Development of research methods on detection, identification of plant pests and diseases, natural enemies, and their biological and ecological characteristics;
- Development and application of biopesticides and biofertilizers based on beneficial microorganisms such as *Trichoderma* spp., *Bacillus* spp., and *Pseudomonas fluorescens*; botanical pesticides, predatory mites, predatory lady-beetles, predatory bugs,...
- Development and application of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) and Integrated Plant Health Management (IPHM) strategies tailored to different agroecological zones on major crop (rice, maize, cassava, citrus, litchi, dragon fruit, citrus, durian, passion fruit, banana, coffee, black pepper, tea, rubber tree, sugarcane ...);
- Research and deployment of nature-based solutions (NbS) for enhancing crop resilience under climate stress conditions;
- Monitoring and surveillance of Invasive and Alien Species; pest and disease outbreaks under climate change scenarios;
- Capacity building for agricultural technicians, local extension staff, and farmer groups on sustainable crop protection technologies.

Current projects:

- + (2024–2026). Research applying nano-biological formulations to control fungal diseases caused by Phytophthora on durian and avocado in Dak Lak province;
- + (2023–2024). Apply Botanical and biological preparations to control pests and diseases in kohlrabi production to ensure food safety in Thai Binh province
- + 2023–2026). Implement intensive vegetable and fruit farming models under organic standards, replacing chemical pesticides with herbal nano-biological formulations.
- + (2020–2022). Research applying bio-polymer to develop biological plant protection products serving organic agriculture production;
- + 2020–2022. Research on the production development of herbal biological formulations for controlling rats damaging rice in Ha Tinh province;
- + 2018-2021). Research on the effects of several natural bioactive compounds derived from antagonistic and endophytic bacteria for producing highly effective biological formulations to control diseases on coffee and pepper plants in Vietnam;
- + 2018–2020. Research on production technology and the application of biological formulations to control flea beetles damaging vegetables;
- + 2019–2022. Research and development of extraction technology for bioactive compounds to produce pesticides for safe agriculture

PPRI is actively to propose and to carry out studies related to the following national programs:

- (1) Project on the Development of the Production and Use of Biological Plant Protection Products (Bio-pesticides) by 2030, with a Vision to 2050 (Decision No. 5415/QĐ-BNN- BVTV dated December 18, 2023, issued by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development)
- (2) Project on the Development of the Production and Use of Organic Fertilizers by 2030, with a Vision to 2050 (Decision No. 5190/QĐ-BNN-BVTV dated December 7, 2023, issued by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development)
- (3) Project on the Development of Integrated Plant Health Management by 2030 (Decision No. 5416/QĐ-BNN-BVTV dated December 18, 2023, issued by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development).
- (4) Project on Enhancing Soil Health and Plant Nutrition Management by 2030, with a vision to 2050 (Decision No. 3458/QĐ-BNN-BVTV dated October 11, 2024,

issued by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development):

- a) Increase the number of commercial bio-pesticides up to 30% in total number of commercial pesticides permitted to use in Vietnam.
- b) Increase the amount of bio-pesticides used up to 30% in total amount of pesticides used annually
- d) At least 70% of communes will be trained for safe and efficient of using bio-pesticides
- đ) Increase the percentage of bio-pesticide manufacture enterprises/companies up to 90% of pesticide manufacture enterprises/companies.
- e) Develop efficient use bio-pesticide demonstration for 9 major crops (rice, coffee, rubber tree, cashew nut, black pepper, tea, fruit trees, vegetables, cassava)

3. Priority Setting and Stakeholder Involvement

- **Explain if and how the process of identifying research and development priorities is open to external stakeholders (e.g., farmers, private sector, academia, NGOs).**

+ Eventually, advanced technologies, good farming practice will be adopted and applied by farmers and private sector. Farmer participatory research (FPR) approach is very important to the success of a research program because by doing this the farmers will learn and understanding more clearly about the new technologies and apply these technologies properly and effectively. Identify farmers' need is essential to the development of a research project, its objectives, deliveries and outcomes.

+ A research and development program are comprehensive issue, and cover many areas and multidisciplinary. Therefore, it requires the involvement and contribution from many external stakeholders (including farmers, private sector, academia, NGOs)

+ Usually, a research and development program will related directly to the value chain of a crop industry/agricultural commodity international trading. Therefore, all related stakeholders involve in the value chain should join the program, including private sector, academia and NGOs).

- **Examples of how external inputs have influenced my organization's plant health initiatives.**

+ Provide and update information on Invasive and Alien Species (Pink cassava mealybug, Sri Lanka cassava mosaic virus, Fall army worm, South American tomato leafminer).

+ Sharing new/advanced technologies on detect, surveillance and management of Invasive and Alien Species (Using parasitoid *Anagyrus lopezi* for biological control of pink cassava mealybug *Phenacoccus manihoti*; tolerant/ressitant varieties to control Sri Lankan Cassava Mosaic Virus; Control Coconut leaf beetle *Brontispa longissima* (Gestro, 1885) by imported exotic parasitoid *Asecodes hispinarum* Boucek *A. hispinarum* was introduced from Western Samoa; Bioproducts and Pheromone to control of fall army worm *Spodoptera frugiperda*)

+ Enhance our research capacity on plan health research (including research facilities, expertise and human resource training)

4. Barriers to Transnational Collaboration

- **Main barriers that limit your organization's participation in:**

- ***Cross-border collaboration***

- + Differences in priorities in research and development; in professional qualification and in depth of research; and differences in research capacities;
- + Differences in objectives of research plan;
- + Administration procedure for approval of research proposal is complicated and time consuming (approved by a number of Ministries involvement: Ministry of Agriculture and Environment, Foreign Affairs, Ministry of Planning and Investment; Ministry of Finance,...);

- ***Regional or international project partnerships***

- + Limited available Funding for joining Regional or international workshop in common interests;
- + Limited funding contribution to Regional or international research programmes
- + Differences in priorities in research and development;
- + Member fee contribution

- ***Access to or exchange of funding***

- + Funding constraints;
- + Policy barriers;
- + May not meet requirements from the donor;
- + Complicated procedures for receiving funding

5. Major Crop Health Challenges and Economic Impact

- **Top three crop health challenges across the production and value chain.**

- + Increasing damage caused by pests and diseases due to climate change and trading;
- + Requirements of phytosanitary standards are more strict, especially MRL from importing countries;
- + Degrading of soil health.

- **Economic losses or impact estimates related to pests, diseases, or weeds.**

+ Economic losses or impact estimates related to pests, diseases, or weeds is significant. Yield losses from pest and disease outbreaks have reached up to 30–40%, even up to 100% if no measure control is applied; However, estimated data is not always available and documented. Only Data of infestation area reported by Plant Production and Protection Department (PPPD) (under Ministry of Agriculture and Environment – MAE) monthly.

+ Some examples: In 2019 fall armyworm infested 76,538 ha of maize (7.8% in total growing area); In 2013: Pink cassava mealybug infested 1,350 ha in 10 provinces; In 2021: *Sri Lanka Cassava Mosaic Virus* infested 70,456 ha in 23 provinces; In 10/2022: Coconut black headed caterpillar *Opisina arenosella* infested 1,128 ha in 05 provinces.

6. Phytosanitary Trade Challenges

- Highlight the **main phytosanitary barriers to trade** for the prioritized crops and products:

- + Quarantine pests;
- + RML requirement;

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- + Compliance with importing country standards (Growing area code, Postharvest treatment)
- Provide specific examples (e.g., market access issues, quarantine pests, compliance with importing country standards).
- + Negotiate on Pest Risk Analysis took very long time (Export mango to Australia took 15 years);
- + Irradiation treatment for commodities to export to America; Hot steam treatment for commodities to export to Japan,...)

7. Priority Invasive and Alien Species

- **The most important invasive or alien species** currently threatening national crop production, ranked in order of priority.
 - + Coconut Black-headed Caterpillar *Opisina arenosella*
 - + South America tomato leaf miner (*Tuta absoluta*)
 - + Sri Lanka Cassava Mosaic Virus (SLCMV)
 - + Fall armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*)
- Include species that pose an **emerging threat or risk of introduction**.
 - + Nematodes on Rice (*Meloidogyne graminicola*)
 - + Hindu mite on Citrus (*Schizotetranychus* sp. maybe *Schizotetranychus hindustanicus*?)
 - + Sweet potato foot rot disease caused by *Diaporthe destruens*
 - + Pestalotiopsis leaf fall disease on rubber (*Hevea brasiliensis*)

4 REPORT OF THE CONSULTATIONS FOR THE BIOTECH INDUSTRY

1. Introduction

Plant biotechnology holds tremendous potential to significantly enhance plant health and productivity through multiple avenues. For example, it enables the development of advanced diagnostic tools for the rapid and precise detection of emerging plant diseases. It also facilitates the creation and implementation of innovative biocontrol products that effectively combat pests and pathogens. Furthermore, by partnering with the seed industry, biotechnology can help identify and integrate new traits essential for strengthening plant pathogen resistance. As such, the biotechnology sector is well-positioned to play a pivotal role in global phytosanitary research and in promoting overall plant health. By fostering collaboration among diagnostic companies, seed producers, researchers, regulators, and governments, progress in safeguarding plant health can be accelerated.

Abiopep is a technology-driven company dedicated to advancing agricultural innovation. The company focuses on developing and commercializing solutions that enhance the quality and productivity of vegetable crops. Through intensive research and the application of cutting-edge biotechnology, particularly in plant virology, Abiopep designs effective crop protection strategies. Its diverse portfolio includes biocontrol products, diagnostic technologies for virus detection and characterization, and tools for identifying novel breeding traits—all aimed at improving plant health and sustainable agricultural practices.

In the context of EUPHRESKOIII, Abiopep's role is to represent the perspective of the biotechnology industry and contribute to achieving the project's objectives by enhancing the involvement of this sector.

The EUPHRESKO III project aims to strengthen the coordination of national and regional phytosanitary research, while laying the groundwork for a globally coordinated phytosanitary research framework. Building on the foundation established by the self-sustained Euphresco network, the project will explore fit-for-purpose activities to support this goal.

The main objectives of EUPHRESKO III are:

- Develop a global strategic agenda outlining medium-term (5–10 years) phytosanitary research priorities. This agenda will guide the research programming efforts of project partners and enable them to tackle national, regional, and global challenges through collaboration across regions and continents.
- Launch joint calls for research projects addressing common priorities, thereby fostering international collaboration. These projects will be tailored to meet the needs of research funders and policymakers and are expected to deliver significant positive outcomes for plant health.
- Design and pilot models for the governance, structure, and operation of a global phytosanitary research coordination network. A roadmap will be created to guide

the development of this future global network.

- Engage a broad range of stakeholders—including policymakers, research funders, academia, industry (agri-food, biotech, diagnostics, seed), as well as farmers and foresters—to promote knowledge exchange, encourage participation in project activities, and drive co-development, innovation, dissemination, and adoption of results.

EUPHRESKO III is structured across several world regions: Africa; Australia; Caribbean, Central & South America; Central Asia; Northern Europe; Southern Europe & the Mediterranean; North America; Pacific Islands; and Southeast Asia. The project also actively involves stakeholders from seed, plant diagnostics, biotechnology, and tree and forest health industries.

The aim is to implement various activities in the countries within these regions, gradually elevating the knowledge gathered or produced at the national level to a regional scale, and ultimately to a global perspective.

In summary, the EUPHRESKO III consortium will contribute to the coordination of national, regional and global phytosanitary research programmes promoting better alignment between research funding and policymaking activities across participating countries. Successful alignment of national research programmes relies on a combination of two key approaches:

- Bottom-up actions, which actively involve research stakeholders in identifying needs and priorities, and
- Top-down actions, which engage research funding bodies and policy institutions. Building mutual trust and achieving consensus at all levels is essential, and this is fostered through regular consultation and open dialogue.

2. The biotechnology industry consultation

Efforts were made to engage key stakeholders from the plant biotechnology sector in the project and related consultations. However, a structured consultation could not be carried out, as the plant biotechnology industry showed limited interest in identifying pests, crops, or other phytosanitary drivers. Their primary concerns lie in addressing regulatory challenges related to the development and commercialization of biocontrol products and new breeding technologies, rather than in participating in phytosanitary research initiatives.

3. Agricultural crops

The list of agricultural crops that are important for discipline could not be provided as explained above.

4. Important pests for the region

Neither the list of pests for which collaboration within the discipline, nor the list of pests for which collaboration at global level is sought, could be provided as explained above.

5. Key drivers for collaboration

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Not available.

6. The research priorities

Not available.

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5 REPORT OF THE CONSULTATIONS FOR THE DIAGNOSTIC INDUSTRY

1. Introduction

The discipline Plant Diagnostic Industry involves all manufacturers of diagnostic reagents and assays used for the detection and diagnosis for any plant pathogen in any crop or plant. Moreover, this discipline is not only involving the manufacturer but also its various distinct customers who are facing the diverse range of agricultural challenges, particularly in risk, pest and disease management across all over the world. Agdia Inc. and BIOREBA AG are two of the leading providers of plant pathogen diagnostics for more than 40 years. Both companies are working closely with people coming from different industries, public and private laboratories and research institutions. This network is used for the identification of the regional and global needs for diagnostic solutions and to better understand where and on what topics regional and global research coordination should be established. With growing interest in harmonizing research priorities, the EUPHRESKO III project aims to foster regional and global collaboration. Within EUPHRESKO III, Agdia and BIOREBA identify through consultations with other plant diagnostic industry stakeholders (manufacturers and customers) key research topics, that align with the identified topics from the other regional and discipline champions. Most of the consultations were done on a one-to-one basis and summarized in this report. Because of the confidentiality of private industry, no customer information nor any company names are used in this report.

2. The agricultural crops

Since Plant Diagnostic Industry is a global discipline and countless agricultural crops are important for its stakeholders, a list of 10 crops was selected based on the survey results and the common feedback from the consultations:

1. Potato
2. Grapevine
3. Tomato
4. Cucurbits
5. Berries
6. Maize
7. Citrus
8. Sweet Potato
9. Wheat
10. Beans

3. Important pests for the discipline

Like the agricultural crops, the Plant diagnostic Industry has a global picture of important pests and countless pests are important for its various stakeholders. The variations in identified important pests were even higher. Therefore, a list of only 6 pathogens/pests was selected based on the survey results and the common feedback from the consultations. This list of pests could be important for global research collaboration:

Pests	Information
Phytoplasma	Multiple distinct phytoplasma were reported. Host range: Stone fruits, potato, sugar beet, grapevine, and many more. Global distribution. Reason for many, different diseases.
<i>Phytophthora</i> spp.	Multiple distinct species were reported. Various host plants.
<i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i> species complex (RSSC)	Big impact on Potato Other important crops and hosts: Pepper, Banana, Tobacco, Tomato, Ginger, Curcuma, Pelargonium, roses and many more...
<i>Xylella Fastidiosa</i>	Olives (<i>Olea europaea</i>), Grapevine (<i>Vitis vinifera</i> , Pierce's disease), Coffee (<i>Coffea</i>), citrus and many more...
Tobamoviruses	Very high impact vegetables and ornamentals. Seed transmitted.
Begomoviruses	Broad global impact on various crops and host plants

As for the agricultural crop list, the above list is not exhaustive and there is a great variability in pest/pathogen priorities according to the geographic regions and type of activity of the stakeholders.

4. Key drivers for collaboration

Besides pests and diseases, the major plant health challenges identified through surveys with Plant Diagnostic Industry stakeholders were related to rapid diagnostics and monitoring, pathogen pressure and pathogen regulation.

On-site diagnostics and monitoring:

Based on the consultations and survey results, there is a general lack of early and rapid detection methods that could be applied on-site (field, greenhouses, border control). Robust, reliable, sensitive and specific rapid tests can help growers and farmers to detect pathogens fast and early which allows them to make decisions and take actions. Moreover, the results showed that even if tests for on-site diagnostics are available, very few of them are used routinely by official laboratories and certification / control schemes. In addition, the improvement of monitoring systems, especially of early warning systems, proved to be an important factor. Therefore, a strong need for collaboration between various stakeholders in plant health was identified on that topic.

Pathogen pressure and pathogen regulation:

The consultations and survey results showed that there is a major and common challenge within Plant Diagnostic Industry stakeholders about pathogen regulation. On one hand, the pathogen pressure by new outbreaks is challenging for everyone and there is a strong need for collaboration in such situations. On the other hand, stakeholders reported that it is very difficult to deal with the current situation of global plant pathogen regulation. Difficulties identified are:

- More than 900 regulated organisms
- Availability of protocols for regulated organisms

- Availability of diagnostic tests and/or validation data
- Availability and lack of access to infected reference material to develop diagnostic protocols
- Lists of regulated pathogens that are not up to date
- Difficulties with land border controls
- Different regulations globally, within regions but also country by country

5. The research priorities

Based on the consultations and the survey results, we have identified the following top 3 research priorities for Plant Diagnostic Industry:

- Improvement of on-site diagnostics and make it available for regulations and certification schemes
- Establishment of new monitoring and early warning systems
- Collaboration between growers, research institutions, plant diagnostic industry and regulatory bodies to establish strategies for common global (or regional) actions in cases of new outbreaks.

6. The programs and the funds allocated to plant health research

(optional, if already known or if Funding survey has already been conducted)

No funding survey has been conducted so far for the Plant Diagnostic Industry.

7. Coordination and collaboration

(optional, if already known or if Funding survey has already been conducted)

No funding survey has been conducted so far for the Plant Diagnostic Industry.

8. Supplementary information or messages originated from the consultation

No supplementary information. All information was summarized in the information above.

6 REPORT OF THE CONSULTATIONS FOR THE SEED INDUSTRY

1. Introduction

The seed sector is a highly internationalized industry that underpins global agriculture and food security. Seed production and trade take place across multiple regions to ensure year-round supply, access to genetic diversity, and the deployment of innovation to farmers. Because seed is both a critical agricultural input and a potential pathway for pests and diseases, the sector is closely linked with phytosanitary regulation and international trade frameworks. This makes research and innovation in phytosanitary measures a cornerstone of the sector's work to guarantee safe and efficient seed movement.

The International Seed Federation (ISF) serves as the global champion of the private seed sector. Representing members from more than 70 countries—including National Seed Associations and seed companies—ISF's mission is to create the best environment for the international movement of quality seed. ISF plays an active role in shaping science-based and harmonized approaches in collaboration with international organizations such as the International Plant Protection Convention (IPPC), OECD, UPOV, and FAO. Acting as a bridge between industry, governments, and policymakers, ISF drives cooperation and practical solutions to ensure that seed can move safely and sustainably across borders.

The interest of ISF in regional and global research coordination stems from the inherently transboundary nature of phytosanitary risks. Pests and diseases do not respect borders, and therefore solutions require shared surveillance, harmonized diagnostic methods, and coordinated responses. Coordinated research reduces duplication, optimizes scarce resources, and builds capacity, particularly in regions where laboratory infrastructure or technical expertise is limited. It also supports trust between National Plant Protection Organizations (NPPOs) and industry by promoting science-based regulation, proportionate measures, and mutual recognition of results. This is vital for resilient seed supply chains that secure global food production.

EUPHRESKO III is a timely and important initiative that builds on earlier efforts to strengthen cooperation in phytosanitary research. Its aim is to align national and regional agendas, identify shared priorities, and create opportunities for collaboration that directly inform and support evidence-based regulation. As part of the consultation process, ISF carried out a survey among its diverse membership. This included both National Seed Associations, which represent collective trade interests, and seed companies, which bring practical, operational perspectives from global seed production and movement.

The survey results highlight the key challenges, opportunities, and innovation needs for the seed sector. These insights provide a valuable contribution to EUPHRESKO III's goal of defining a coordinated research agenda that reflects the realities of international trade while safeguarding plant health. By ensuring that the seed sector's voice is included in this process, ISF helps to advance a globally aligned research framework that benefits not only the industry but also farmers, regulators, and consumers who rely on the safe and timely movement of seed.

2. The agricultural crops

Across the responses, the following main crop groups were identified as priorities for phytosanitary focus due to their international trade relevance and vulnerability to seed-borne pests and diseases:

Priority Crops for Research and Regulatory Alignment:

- Vegetables: Tomato, pepper, cucurbits, brassicas, lettuce, carrot, onion.
- Field Crops: Maize, soybean, wheat, barley, sorghum, sunflower, rapeseed.
- Legumes: Beans (*Phaseolus*, *Vigna*), chickpea, groundnut, faba bean, cowpea.
- Forages & Pastures: Ryegrass, clover.

3. Important pests for the sector

The responses converge on several high-risk seed-borne or seed-associated pathogens that significantly affect international trade and phytosanitary regulation. They can be grouped into major categories:

Global Priority Pests:

- Viruses: Tobamoviruses (ToBRFV, TMV, CGMMV, PMMoV), Maize chlorotic mottle virus, Wheat streak mosaic virus, PepMV, PVY, TSWV, CMV, ToLCNDV, LMV.
- Bacteria: *Clavibacter michiganensis*, *Acidovorax citrulli*, *Curtobacterium flaccumfaciens*, *Xanthomonas* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp.
- Fungi: *Tilletia* spp., *Fusarium* spp., *Stenocarpella* spp., *Colletotrichum* spp., *Phytophthora infestans*.
- Insects: *Spodoptera frugiperda*, *Bruchus* spp., *Trogoderma granarium*.
- Others: Pospiviroids, nematodes.

4. Key drivers for collaboration

The international seed sector faces a complex set of phytosanitary challenges that cannot be addressed in isolation. Divergent and fragmented national regulations, including inconsistent testing requirements, pest lists, and documentation, continue to create uncertainty and delays in the movement of seed. In some cases, import requirements are introduced without notification to the WTO, or countries apply precautionary measures for non-pathogens, leading to unnecessary barriers. Collaboration at regional and global levels is therefore essential to promote harmonized, science-based approaches, foster the use of internationally recognized standards such as ISHI-Veg and ISTA protocols, and scale up digital solutions like ePhyto to streamline compliance and reduce duplication.

Diagnostics present another key driver for collaboration. The widespread use of highly sensitive molecular methods, such as PCR, raises concerns about the biological meaning of low-level signals and the detection of non-pathogens. At the same time, reliable diagnostic solutions are still lacking for certain seed-transmitted pathogens, creating risks of over-testing or restrictions on trade. Joint research and validation efforts are needed to develop innovative tools—including high-throughput sequencing (HTS), portable PCR, and multiplex assays—and to ensure that regulatory frameworks integrate biological relevance and plant resistance

data alongside laboratory testing.

Emerging pests and climate-driven risks further underscore the need for collaboration. Global warming, evolving trade routes, and the circulation of counterfeit seed all heighten the risk of new pest incursions, including seed-borne diseases. These transboundary threats demand shared solutions, such as pest modelling tools, horizon scanning, regional surveillance networks, and early warning systems to anticipate and mitigate risks proactively.

Collaboration is equally critical in addressing capacity gaps. In many countries, limited laboratory infrastructure and inspection resources result in inconsistent outcomes, bottlenecks, and mistrust in certificates. By working together, NPPOs, seed trade associations, and industry can strengthen capacity-building, training, and proficiency testing, supported by the digital exchange of pest and diagnostic data. This builds trust and creates more reliable, harmonized systems.

Finally, effective collaboration supports science-based risk analysis and prioritization. Too often, phytosanitary regulations are driven by precaution rather than evidence, resulting in disproportionate measures such as expanded quarantine pest lists or unnecessary re-testing of seed. Collaborative research and data sharing on pest prevalence, epidemiology, and host resistance can ensure that decisions are proportionate, targeted to the most relevant threats, and support both plant health protection and the efficient movement of seed.

In summary, the key drivers for collaboration in the seed sector are the need to harmonize regulations, improve diagnostic tools, anticipate emerging risks, build global capacity, and ensure science-based decision-making. These efforts safeguard plant health while enabling the resilient and efficient international movement of seed, which is essential for global agriculture and food security.

The aims of EUPHRESKO III align closely with these drivers for collaboration. By coordinating phytosanitary research across borders, EUPHRESKO provides a platform to identify shared priorities, develop innovative diagnostic solutions, strengthen capacity, and promote harmonized, science-based approaches. For the seed sector, engagement in EUPHRESKO III ensures that global research agendas are connected to the practical realities of seed production and trade, creating solutions that are both scientifically robust and operationally relevant.

5. The research priorities

Strategic Priorities for the Next 5–10 Years:

- Harmonization of Standards – Align pest lists, protocols, and acceptance of equivalent test results.
- Next-Generation Diagnostics – Develop and validate HTS, multiplex PCR/LAMP, and AI-driven tools.
- Surveillance & Early Warning – Establish predictive modelling and global pest intelligence platforms.
- Capacity & Cooperation – Build diagnostic capacity and enable consistent application of measures worldwide.
- Risk-Proportionate Regulation – Ensure biological relevance, use PRA for

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proportionate, science-based rules.

Global-Level Priorities:

- Broader adoption of ISPMs, harmonized standards, and ePhyto.
- Establishment of global pest intelligence and surveillance networks.
- Strengthened transparency, trust, and cooperation among NPPOs.
- Support for low-resource countries to achieve global consistency.
- Integration of NBTs, novel seed treatments, and digital inspection tools into regulatory frameworks.

6. Supplementary information or messages originated from the consultation

Key Current Challenges and Opportunities:

Survey respondents identified several pressing issues affecting seed production and international seed movement:

- 1. Fragmented and Inconsistent Regulations**
 - Divergent national requirements, unreported changes, stacking of measures, and repeated re-testing of seed lots.
 - Opportunity: Adoption of ISPM 38, harmonization of diagnostic protocols, acceptance of equivalent measures, and digitalization (ePhyto).
- 2. Emerging Pests and Climate-Driven Risks**
 - Spread of new/re-emerging pests (e.g., ToBRFV, FAW) and climate-related distribution shifts.
 - Opportunity: Horizon scanning, pest modelling, early-warning surveillance, and collaborative response systems.
- 3. Seed-Transmitted Pathogens and Diagnostic Gaps**
 - Challenges in differentiating viable vs. non-viable pathogens, false positives, and reliance on indirect PCR-based tests.
 - Opportunity: Advanced diagnostics (HTS, multiplex PCR/LAMP, portable devices) and validated devitalization methods.
- 4. Capacity Gaps**
 - Unequal diagnostic infrastructure, counterfeit seed risks, inconsistent testing quality.
 - Opportunity: Proficiency testing, capacity-building, reference labs, and stronger public-private partnerships.
- 5. Need for Science-Based Risk Analysis**
 - Regulations often precautionary rather than risk-based.
 - Opportunity: Evidence-driven pest risk analysis, biological relevance of results, and data sharing on epidemiology and seed transmission.

Technical and Research Needs:

1. **Diagnostics:** Reliable, rapid tools; methods to distinguish viable from non-viable pathogens.
2. **Epidemiology:** Seed transmission data and biological relevance to underpin PRA.
3. **Seed Treatments:** Devitalization, alternatives to hot water treatment and methyl bromide, efficacy of biologicals.
4. **Systems Approach & Digitalization:** Hygiene-based systems, traceability, mutual recognition of results.
5. **Capacity & Knowledge Transfer:** Shared reference labs, training, and global proficiency testing.

Proposed Research Projects (Next 3 Years):

- Transmission and diagnostic thresholds for ToBRFV and other major seed-borne pathogens.
- Development of effective devitalization treatments for viruses on/in seed.
- Research on *Spiroplasma kunkelii* and other “difficult” pathogens.
- Asymptomatic tissue testing and threshold setting.
- Positioning studies on acceptable soil contamination levels in seed trade.

7 REPORT OF THE CONSULTATIONS FOR FOREST AND TREE HEALTH

1. Introduction

Europe is a climatically diverse continent, with distinct regional variations shaping its forests. The boreal climate of northern Europe is characterized by long, cold winters and short summers, while the temperate climate of central Europe features moderate rainfall, cold winters, and warm summers. In contrast, the Mediterranean climate of southern Europe experiences hot, dry summers and mild, wet winters.

Forests play a multifunctional role beyond timber production, offering crucial ecological and societal benefits. The economic importance of forestry for timber production varies across Europe, with northern Europe being the leading timber producer due to its vast, commercially managed forests. In central Europe, forests are essential for protecting against landslides, avalanches, and soil erosion, particularly in mountainous areas such as the Alps and Carpathians. They also play a key role in regulating water cycles, reducing flood risks, and maintaining water quality. In southern Europe, forests contribute significantly to soil stabilization, desertification prevention, and fire risk reduction, which are increasingly important in the face of rising temperatures and prolonged droughts. Additionally, forests across all regions serve as carbon sinks, biodiversity hotspots, and recreational spaces, contributing to climate mitigation, ecosystem health, and human well-being.

Forest health and productivity are increasingly threatened by pest outbreaks and climate change-driven disturbances. It is noteworthy that most tree pests exhibit high host specificity, meaning that the pests of concern in a given region largely depend on the dominant tree species. Additionally, pest-host-climate interactions play a crucial role in determining the severity of outbreaks. In many cases, tree species at the southern or central edge of their natural distribution have suffered severe damage from abiotic stressors (such as drought and heatwaves) and biotic threats (such as invasive pests and pathogens), which have been exacerbated by climate change.

In a stakeholder survey, we identified key research priorities that align with both regional and continental needs, this to foster scientific cooperation to enhance forest resilience and ensure the sustainable management of Europe's diverse forest ecosystems.

2. Forest tree species

The respondents from **northern Europe** represented Denmark, Finland, Lithuania, Norway, Sweden and UK. They identified the following tree species as important: conifers *Picea abies* and *Pinus sylvestris*; deciduous trees *Acer platanoides*, *Alnus glutinosa*, *Alnus incana*, *Betula pendula*, *Fraxinus excelsior*, *Quercus robur*, and *Tilia cordata*. Unnamed species in the genera *Abies*, *Larix* and *Ulmus* were mentioned as important. *Fagus sylvatica*, *Pinus contorta*, and *Quercus petraea* are mentioned as alternatives to *P. abies* when combating climate change. No general pattern of relative importance of different tree species emerges from the responses; it is obvious there are region, country and respondent -specific differences.

The respondents from **central Europe** represented Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Netherlands, Poland and Slovakia. They identified the following tree species as important: conifers *Picea abies*, *Pinus sylvestris*, *Pinus mugo*, *Pseudotsuga menziesii*, and the deciduous *Fagus sylvatica*. Unnamed species in the genera *Abies*, *Acer*, *Cedrus*, *Fagus* and *Fraxinus* were also mentioned as important. No general pattern of relative importance of different tree species emerges from the responses; it is obvious there are region, country and respondent -specific differences.

The respondents from **southern Europe** represented Italy and Spain. They identified the following tree species as important: conifers *Pinus pinaster*, *Pinus pinea*, *Pinus sylvestris*, *Pinus strobus*, and *Pseudotsuga menziesii*; deciduous *Acer pseudoplatanus*, *Alnus glutinosa*, *Castanea sativa*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Ostrya carpinifolia*, *Prunus padus*, *Quercus pubescens*, *Quercus ilex*, and *Quercus suber*. Unnamed species in the genera *Abies*, *Cedrus*, *Larix*, *Betula*, *Populus*, *Sorbus* and *Ulmus* were also mentioned as important. No general pattern of relative importance of different tree species emerges from the responses; it is obvious there are region, country and respondent -specific differences.

3. Important pests for the region

North European responders identified the following insect pests as important: *Agrilus anxius*, *Agrilus planipennis*, *Anoplophora glabripennis*, *Anoplophora chinensis*, *Dendrolimus sibiricus*, *Diprion pini*, *Hylobius abietis*, *Ips acuminatus*, *Ips typographus*, *Leptinotarsa decemlineata*, *Neodiprion sertifer*, and *Thaumetopoea processionea*. The following fungal pests were considered as important: *Diplodia sapinea*, *Heterobasidion* spp., *Hymenoscyphus fraxineus*, *Neofusicoccum laricinum*, *Ophiostoma ulmi*, *Ophiostoma novo-ulmi*, *Phytophthora ramorum*. The bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa*, nematode *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* and deer *Capreolus capreolus* are also considered as important. Drought is considered a major challenge in relation to bark beetle damages in general. It is noteworthy that many of the pests listed above are invasive alien species not native to Europe.

Central European responders identified the following insect pests as important: *Agrilus anxius*, *Agrilus planipennis*, *Anoplophora glabripennis*, *Corythucha arcuata*, *Hylobius abietis*, *Ips typographus*, *Lymantria monacha*, *Popillia japonica*, *Saperda candida*, *Thaumetopoea pityocampa*, *Xylosandrus germanus*, and *Xylotrechus chinensis*. The following fungal pests were considered as important: *Ceratocystis platani*, *Diplodia sapinea*, *Hymenoscyphus fraxineus*, *Phytophthora kernoviae*, and *Phytophthora ramorum*. The bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa*, nematode *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* and deer *Capreolus capreolus* are also considered as important.

Southern European responders identified the following insect pests as important: *Dryocosmus kuriphilus*, *Ips typographus*, *Leptoglossus occidentalis*, and *Thaumetopoea pityocampa*. The following fungal pests were considered as important: *Fusarium circinatum*, *Gnoniopsis smithogilvyi*, and *Phytophthora xalni*. The nematode *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* was also considered of importance. The relatively short list of pests perceived as important in southern Europe probably reflects a low number of respondents in comparison to central and northern Europe.

As a reference, we also received responses from one very knowledgeable stakeholder in the **Republic of South Africa**, where planted forests (*Pinus*, *Eucalyptus*, *Acacia*) are important

from a commercial perspective, whereas native trees in Southern Hemisphere countries (Myrtaceae, Proteaceae, Leguminosae etc) are ignored and at a great threat. Fungi in the genus *Ceratocystis* and in the Botryosphaeriaceae family are a major challenge due to climate change issues, as are wood -boring and bark beetles, such as *Euwallacea fornicates*, and their fungal associates, e.g. *Harringtonia lauricola*.

4. Key drivers for collaboration

It is noteworthy that the majority of pests considered as important by European stakeholders are **not native** to Europe. Alien **insect species** include *Agilus anxius*, *Agilus planipennis*, *Anoplophora glabripennis*, *Anoplophora chinensis*, *Dendrolimus sibiricus*, *Leptinotarsa decemlineata*, *Neodiprion sertifer*, *Corythucha arcuate*, *Lymantria monacha*, *Popillia japonica*, *Saperda candida*, *Xylosandrus germanus*, *Xylotrechus chinensis*. Alien **fungi** include *Hymenoscyphus fraxineus*, *Ophiostoma ulmi*, *Ophiostoma novo-ulmi*, *Phytophthora ramorum*, *Phytophthora kernoviae*, *Fusarium circinatum*. The **bacterium** *Xylella fastidiosa* and **nematode** *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* are not native to Europe either. An understanding of factors that facilitate local introduction, establishment and spread of these pests into the wider environment is of common interest, as are diagnostic methods and phytosanitary methods and inspections of commodities that can serve as fast-track vehicles for country-to-country spread of the organisms. Climate change related increased drought conditions are already a major precursor of vast bark beetle damages on Norway spruce in central Europe. As an example, Climate change related extreme events like the Vaia storm devastated northern Italy's forests, creating ideal conditions for bark beetle outbreaks (*Ips typographus*), which further damaged surviving spruce stands. Such damages are currently still of rather minor importance in northern Europe, but they are predicted to increase significantly also in this region along with climate change.

5. The research priorities

Northern Europe has relatively few invasive alien tree pests today, and the threat from climate change or native tree pests exacerbated by climate change is not yet acute. Stakeholders prioritize long-term pest management strategies, focusing on resilience, sustainable practices, and predictive modeling. Their approach to climate change emphasizes mitigation through forest diversification. Emergency preparedness is integrated into broader sustainable management practices, while capacity building, particularly in diagnostic services, enhances stakeholder coordination. Northern stakeholders also show a strong interest in mapping and predictive modeling to track pest spread and environmental stressors. Trade-related pest spread is considered within a wider sustainability framework.

In contrast, **Central and Southern Europe** are already dealing with numerous invasive alien tree pests. Compared to Northern Europe, the region experiences more frequent abiotic damage and native tree pest outbreaks driven by climate change. Stakeholders emphasize rapid response, invasive pest control, and contingency planning. Their climate change strategy prioritizes risk assessments and horizon scanning due to acute threats in Central Europe and the Mediterranean region. Emergency preparedness focuses on securing public support for research into emerging forestry diseases. Infrastructure development is geared toward long-term research, such as pest collections and improved data management systems

for risk assessment. Regarding trade, Southern Europe prioritizes inspection systems and monitoring trade routes to prevent further introductions of non-native pests.

Based on the survey results, the following two research priorities are of urgent priority:

a) Diagnostics, Surveillance, and Early Warning Systems

- Efficient monitoring and early detection of pests and diseases
- Improved diagnostic methods for faster, reliable results
- Surveillance and inspection of new outbreaks (linked to climate change)
- Enhanced sampling techniques at borders and in trade (*a related call text has already been drafted: 2025-G-491 RAMWOOD: Risk Assessment and Mitigation in Wood Chip and Fuelwood International Trade*)

b) Climate Change Impact & Forest Resilience

- Effects of climate change on forestry and plant health
- Identifying resilient tree species and forest management practices
- Emergency preparedness for extreme climate events
- Establishing seed banks for alternative species that can thrive in warmer, drier conditions

Additional topics of wide common interest among European forest associated stakeholders include:

Pest and Pathogen Management

- Sustainable and innovative pest control methods
- Reduction of pesticide use and alternatives (nature-based solutions, biological control)
- Management in nurseries and forests
- Data Collection, Sharing, and AI Integration
- Mapping and modelling pest spread and host prevalence
- Use of artificial intelligence for risk assessment and surveillance
- Greater collaboration between government, research institutions, and industry
- Platforms for knowledge sharing and contingency planning

Risk Assessment and Preparedness

- Horizon scanning for emerging plant health threats
- Development of contingency plans for pest outbreaks
- Evaluating and improving national plant health response strategies
- Understanding plant health-related behaviors and public awareness

Global Collaboration & Policy Development

- Strengthened international cooperation on phytosanitary measures
- Better networking across disciplines (genetics, physiology, pathology, molecular biology)
- Peer review mechanisms for national contingency plans
- More effective regulatory and policy frameworks to mitigate disease spread through trade and travel

6. The programmes and the funds allocated to plant health research
(optional, if already known or if Funding survey has already been conducted)

Funding survey has not yet been carried out.

7. Coordination and collaboration
(optional, if already known or if Funding survey has already been conducted)

Funding survey has not yet been carried out.

8. Supplementary information or messages originated from the consultation

The responses indicate a strong focus on early detection, innovation, and international cooperation to mitigate the growing risks of pests and diseases in a changing climate.

8 CONCLUSIONS

The methodology for the identification of research priorities based on national surveys and regional consultations, developed within EUPHRESKO III, is innovative. It has a number of advantages:

- National surveys allow to gather data from a large number and type of sources
- The methodology is modular and priorities are explicitly available at the level of: i) the organization, ii) the type of stakeholder, iii) national level, iv) regional level, v) global level
- The data collected can be statistically analyzed, providing an accurate and unbiased picture of phytosanitary priorities
- The information collected can be used for different purposes and by different end-users at national and international level
- Once established, the consultation method will be easy to adopt routinely and will allow the number and type of stakeholders interviewed to be expanded

The priorities identified with the methodology have been considered in the framework of the 2025 call¹² for translational collaboration of Euphresco and EUPHRESKO III and will also be considered for the 2026 call. Work on the strategic research agenda is currently in progress and a document will be published by the end of the EUPHRESKO III project in December 2026.

¹² https://www.phrescoglobal.net/call_topics

